

**Stakeholders' Perceptions and Attitudes Towards
Learners with Speech Disorders in Algerian Middle
Schools: A case study of stuttering**

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Declaration

I confirm that this thesis has been authored solely by me and represents my original work, except where explicitly indicated otherwise. Additionally, I affirm that it has not been previously submitted for any other academic degree or professional certification.

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28th of August 2024

Abstract

In middle schools, where students undergo pivotal stages of social and academic development, the impact of stuttering can be profound. Despite the acknowledged influence of the social environment, schools, given the extensive time students spend there, carry significant influence over children who stutter. Recognising this, it becomes imperative to investigate stakeholders' knowledge regarding stuttering and its associated stigma. The research aims to delve into the comprehension of stuttering among stakeholders—speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers—within the Algerian context. By probing into their insights, this study seeks to elucidate prevailing stigmas and identify interventions to lessen them. Semi-structured interviews served as the basis of this research, facilitating nuanced exploration of stakeholders' perceptions. The study recruited three different participant groups—speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers, a total of 28 participants. Employing the stigma theory as a conceptual framework, the research adopted a qualitative approach, employing case study methodology complemented by thematic analysis to discern patterns and extract meaningful insights from the data. The findings underscored differences in knowledge levels among stakeholders, with speech-language therapists exhibiting superior comprehension. While the majority of mothers and teachers tend to base their knowledge on pragmatic understanding, they consider speech-language therapists as their primary sources of knowledge. Despite familiarity with the nature of stuttering, all participant groups held some stereotypes regarding its aetiology. The medical model view of stuttering dominated the participants' understanding of the nature and causes of the disorder. Although there was data indicating social stigmatizing attitudes, the treatment and efforts to overcome stuttering were primarily focused on the child. Notably, the prevalent treatment approach in Algeria was only characterized by the François Le Huche treatment method, focusing on abdominal breathing exercises. Furthermore, stakeholders acknowledged the adverse impact of stuttering on children, who face many forms of negative attitudes, including discrimination and bullying. However, during these challenges, stakeholders exhibited an apparent awareness of potential interventions to mitigate stigma, tailored to the Algerian cultural environment. These interventions advocate fostering positive relationships between students who stutter and their peers and teachers, improving self-esteem, promoting awareness about stuttering, and destigmatizing it within societal norms. In conclusion, this study explains the background of stakeholders' knowledge regarding stuttering and the associated stigma within Algerian middle schools. The findings emphasise the critical need for targeted interventions to ameliorate the challenges faced by students who stutter. By presenting culturally appropriate strategies to combat stigma, this research contributes to promoting inclusive environments conducive to the holistic development of all students. Ultimately, this study underlines

the imperative of collaborative efforts among stakeholders to foster understanding, empathy, and support for students who stutter, thereby promoting their well-being and academic success within the Algerian educational context.

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1. Chapter One: General Introduction

This introduction establishes a framework for this PhD research project by providing a contextual background of stuttering and studies that address this speech disorder highlighting the challenges faced by individuals who stutter within this specific social and cultural environment. Furthermore, the introduction outlines the research questions that will guide this PhD research. These questions aim to understand the stakeholders' experiences with children who stutter in Algeria, including their perceptions of this speech disorder and their attitudes towards them. By delving into these experiences, the study seeks to contribute valuable insights that could inform support structures and interventions tailored to the Algerian context. The next section will also provide a more detailed overview of the research aims and objectives, outlining the specific goals of the study and its potential contributions to the field. Finally, the introduction concludes with an outline of the following chapters, briefly summarizing the content of one.

1.1. Background, Aim and Focus of this Research

Children spend a significant amount of time at school (Abdalla and St. Louis, 2012). Consequently, teachers can have a considerable impact on a child's life during this formative period (Abrahams et al., 2016). Therefore, it is crucial for children who stutter to be supported in a positive school environment (Arnold and Goltl, 2015). Teachers bear responsibility for the educational development of children, which can present considerable challenges, especially when teaching children with disabilities (Safwat and Sheikhan, 2014). Stuttering is one form of disability, characterized by a communicative disorder at the oral level. It is a complex speech disorder, also referred to as stuttering (Onslow and O'Brian, 2013; Baxter et al., 2015; Johnson, 2016), which will be further explained in the literature review chapter. Stuttering often leads to negative stereotypes and stigma (Zeigler-Hill, 2019), potentially impacting a child's self-esteem, educational attainment, and peer relationships (Al-Qaisi et al., 2020). Therefore, educators must acquire knowledge to interact effectively with children who stutter, ultimately contributing to their educational and social development (Arnold and Goltl, 2015). The personality of preschool-age children should also be considered (Bratha et al., 2019). Children who stutter encounter significant stigmatization, posing a major challenge for them (St. Louis, 2015), and their families.

Teachers play a pivotal role in the educational development of children who stutter, and their attitudes may significantly impact students' academic performance, particularly among primary and middle-school-age students (Al-Qaisi et al., 2020). A significant knowledge gap exists regarding the experiences of children who stutter within Algerian middle schools. Specifically, there is a lack of understanding of how stuttering is perceived and how Algerian society reacts to this speech disorder,

while there are numerous research studies have investigated teachers' attitudes towards children who stutter (Abrahams, 2015; Irani et al., 2012; Abdalla and St. Louis, 2012; Adriaensens and Struyf, 2016; Al-Qaisi and Ali, 2020; Hearne et al., 2021), as well as their knowledge about stuttering (Al-Qaisi et al., 2020; Katebe, 2020). This study focuses on children aged 10 to 16 who stutter and are in middle school in Algeria. This age group is particularly crucial because adolescence is a critical period for social and emotional development. During this time, children who stutter may be especially vulnerable to negative peer reactions and the development of speech anxiety. Plexico et al. (2013) highlighted the significant influence of bullying on the well-being of children who stutter and emphasized that teachers play a crucial role in preventing these negative experiences. In their research, Hearne et al. (2021) shared experiences and stories of adults who used to stutter. Some adults who stutter expressed challenges in participating in activities that require speaking aloud in front of peers to avoid bullying, which complicates their school experiences (Hearne et al., 2021).

To gain a comprehensive understanding of existing research on stuttering interventions for children in middle school, a narrative review was conducted. This review revealed a significant knowledge gap regarding stuttering education practices within the Algerian context. No research specifically addressing the experiences and perspectives of Algerian stakeholders working with children who stutter was identified. In response to this gap, the current study aims to investigate the attitudes, perceptions, and experiences of Algerian middle school teachers towards children who stutter. While research has extensively investigated teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards learners with speech production problems, including stuttering, in various parts of the world (e.g., Hearne et al., 2021; Abdalla and St. Louis, 2012; Abdalla and St. Louis, 2014; Plexico et al., 2013; Adriaensens and Struyf, 2016), there is a notable absence of studies focusing specifically on knowledge and perceptions regarding stuttering and its associated stigma toward children who stutter in Algeria.

Stuttering could have a serious impact on the overall quality of life of individuals who stutter during their schooling years (Hearne et al., 2021). Therefore, children who stutter require a supportive environment facilitated by teachers, particularly during activities involving group interaction and speaking (Katebe, 2020). Hence, this research delves into the experiences of children who stutter within Algerian middle schools aiming to understand their schooling experiences, the way they are treated by peers and teachers, and the way stuttering is perceived and managed within the Algerian sociocultural context but mainly in middle schools, which may represent other stages of the school system.

Furthermore, this study focuses specifically on middle schools located in the western region of Algeria to explore attitudes towards children who stutter within this under-researched context. By addressing

this knowledge gap, the study seeks to provide valuable insights that can inform support structures and interventions tailored to the needs of children who stutter in Algerian middle schools. While a variety of speech disorders exist, this research focuses specifically on stuttering. This decision is based on several key factors. Firstly, stuttering is the most common speech disorder encountered by children (Al Araifi et al., 2020). Secondly, the limited word count inherent in a PhD thesis necessitates a focused approach to ensure in-depth exploration. Investigating all speech disorders within this scope would likely result in findings that lack sufficient detail and credibility. Furthermore, the impact of different speech disorders can vary significantly, making a comprehensive study potentially less reliable due to the heterogeneity of the data. Finally, stuttering shares some characteristics with other speech disorders, suggesting that the insights gained from this research may have broader applicability and the findings resonate within Algeria and outside its borders too.

Furthermore, this study utilised a qualitative methodology, namely semi-structured interviews with speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter and middle school language teachers to gather the data and explore the perspectives of these three key stakeholder groups. Investigating these diverse viewpoints shed light on the challenges faced by children who stutter in Algeria and identify potential strategies for creating more supportive learning environments. Besides, they enrich the analysis and capture a broader perspective on the experiences of children who stutter in Algerian middle schools. Speech-language therapists possess valuable expertise in stuttering interventions, and their insights can inform the development of more effective support structures within schools. Mothers, on the other hand, offer a unique perspective on the challenges their children face and the support they receive both at home and in the classroom. Furthermore, since the focus is on middle school learners, teachers are key participants in revealing their experience with students who stutter inside the classroom.

By these diverse perspectives, speech-language therapists, mothers, and teachers, the research aims to identify patterns regarding the strengths and challenges of teaching children who stutter in this under-researched context. In investigating the experience of students who stutter in middle schools, teachers' attitudes and practices will be explored in this study highlighting the extent of their awareness of the academic and social challenges faced by children who stutter in Algeria. This information will provide valuable context for interpreting teachers' perspectives and identifying potential areas where their support can be strengthened. Additionally, the research will delve into the strategies that teachers currently employ to create an inclusive learning environment for students who stutter. Examining these existing practices can reveal potential strengths that can be built upon and areas where additional training or resources might be beneficial. Accordingly, the findings can add professional development programmes.

Hence, this study aims to address the following research questions,

- 1- What is the depth and scope of the Algerian stakeholders' knowledge of stuttering?
- 2- What is the depth and scope of stakeholders' knowledge of the stigma associated with stuttering in Algerian middle schools?
- 3- What are the stakeholders' perspectives on the strategies for mitigating stigma-related stuttering in Algerian middle schools?

1.2. The Importance of this Research Study

Adolescence is the period where the development of both physical and cognitive maturity occurs (Adriaensens, Beyers and Struyf, 2015). A speech disorder like stuttering, similar to other disabilities, can profoundly affect the experiences of these adolescents creating an even more challenging period (Chun, Mendes, Yaruss and Quesal, 2010; Erickson and Block, 2013). Hence, adolescents who stutter are likely at a higher risk for developing low self-esteem (Adriaensens, Beyers and Struyf, 2015). This could have influenced the development of their personalities and the way they interact with others, potentially restricting their aspirations and hindering their ability to pursue their full potential. As the severity of stuttering increases, children may experience a range of negative emotions, such as embarrassment, shame, isolation, and anxiety (Boyle et al., 2016; Eggers et al., 2021). According to Briley, Gerlach and Jacobs (2021), this speech disorder is associated with increased depressive symptoms in both genders, reporting a significantly higher likelihood of suicidal thoughts among males who stutter. Furthermore, stuttering is associated with a social anxiety disorder in adulthood that could likely develop gradually during the school years and adolescence (Messenger et al., 2015). Hence, investigating the experiences of children who stutter within the Algerian context can yield valuable insights that can inform interventions and support structures, ultimately improving their lives.

Beyond the challenges of stuttering itself, the social stigma that follows it, particularly the experience of being devalued in social interactions, likely plays a role in the higher rates of depression observed among adolescents who stutter (Briley, Gerlach and Jacobs, 2021). Bullying and negative attitudes towards children who stutter are unfortunately universal issues (De Luca et al., 2019). According to Baryshevtsev et al. (2020) individuals who stutter are perceived as experiencing more stigma compared to those with other speech disorders. Although this perception could be linked to the frequency of stuttering, it is important to recognise that stuttering can be accompanied by negative attitudes that can create significant obstacles to the educational achievement of many children who stutter (Panico et al., 2018). Children who stutter often face challenges in their interactions with peers, starting as early as kindergarten (Macallister, 2016). These challenges can lead to negative social

consequences throughout their school years, as documented in research on stuttering in school-aged children (Osborn, 2013). By understanding teacher perspectives on stigma management in the classroom, this study can provide valuable insights into how to reduce stigma and promote better social and emotional development for children who stutter in Algerian schools.

Teachers play a crucial role in creating a supportive learning environment, especially for children who stutter. Research by Abrahams et al. (2016) highlights their central role in managing stuttering within the classroom. Furthermore, the way teachers treat children who stutter significantly influences how their peers view and interact with them (Boberg and Calder, 2012; Jenkins, 2010). Beyond classroom management, teachers' attitudes significantly influence student performance and progress across all subjects (Jenkins, 2010; Silva et al., 2016). This emphasizes the importance of understanding teacher perspectives on stuttering. In addition to investigating teacher awareness and attitudes, this study will explore the potential presence of classroom stigma associated with stuttering and how teachers manage these situations. For instance, presenting and speaking in front of peers can be particularly difficult for children who stutter (Tammemäe and Söggel, 2021). Investigating how teachers navigate these difficulties and foster a supportive environment for students who stutter is thus crucial. Limited knowledge about stuttering and how to support children who stutter can lead teachers to accidentally adopt negative attitudes. This, in turn, can negatively impact children's experiences through interactions and perceptions (Abdalla and St. Louis, 2012). By delving into these topics, this study offers a unique and valuable contribution to our understanding of stuttering education in Algeria. Accordingly, this research has the potential to fill critical knowledge gaps by providing valuable insights that can inform educational interventions. These interventions can support teacher training and educational policy, ultimately improving teachers' roles in managing stuttering and the associated stigma in Algerian classrooms.

Understanding the classroom experience is crucial, however, stuttering can have a significant impact on children beyond academics, potentially affecting their social lives and emotional well-being (McAllister, 2016). To gain a comprehensive understanding, the study employs a multifaceted approach to the field-work, interviewing speech-language therapists, mothers, and teachers. This approach goes beyond the classroom experience and delves into the broader cultural perspectives on stuttering in Algeria. Therefore, this study is crucial as it examines these diverse viewpoints, aiming to provide a stronger foundation for understanding how stuttering impacts the educational experiences of children in this specific context.

In conclusion, this study into stuttering among children in Algeria has the potential to make significant contributions to their educational experiences and overall well-being. By investigating the social,

emotional, and behavioural challenges faced by these children, alongside teacher attitudes, knowledge, and classroom management strategies, the research offers valuable insights into the Algerian context. This multifaceted approach, encompassing perspectives from teachers, speech and language therapists, and mothers, can provide a stronger foundation for understanding the root causes of these challenges. Ultimately, the goal is to develop effective educational interventions and practices that empower teachers to create a more positive and inclusive learning environment for children who stutter in Algeria. The results of this study will significantly contribute to research on stuttering and stigma among children who stutter in middle schools in Algeria, addressing a notable research gap in this area. Additionally, this study will add valuable data to the global understanding of stuttering and the associated stigma, particularly in the context of Algeria.

1.3. Overview of Chapters

This thesis is divided into nine chapters designed to build a comprehensive foundation for this PhD research. The current chapter (Chapter One) served as the general introduction, providing an overview of the study and its focus and aims. It highlights the existing research gap and the importance of conducting this research. Furthermore, it sets the stage for the subsequent chapters. Given the interdisciplinary nature of this PhD research, Chapters two, three, and four provide background knowledge on key aspects, the Algerian educational system, communication disorders and stuttering, and the associated stigma with stuttering, respectively. Chapter five presents the methodology, followed by the presentation and discussion of the findings in chapters six, seven, and eight. Finally, chapter nine of the thesis provides a general discussion and conclusion for this study.

Chapter **Two** establishes the context by providing an overview of the Algerian educational system. Understanding this system is crucial as it shapes the environment where children who stutter might face communicative challenges. Furthermore, it helps to understand the academic policies regarding inclusive education, including those related to communication disorder, and how these were affected by reforms implemented after independence to improve the educational system. The primary focus of this chapter will be on primary and middle schools, which are informative and critical stages within the Algerian educational system.

Chapter **Three** delves deeper into communication disorders, with a specific focus on stuttering. The chapter is divided into two parts. The first part begins by explaining communication disorders to establish the context for where stuttering is classified. The second part focuses primarily on stuttering, aiming to provide an overall theoretical and scientific foundation for understanding the nature of stuttering and how it is perceived by stakeholders, particularly teachers and mothers. This serves as a

good starting point, setting the stage for the next chapter that discusses the stigma associated with stuttering.

Chapter **four** equips the reader with relevant conceptual frameworks. The chapter focuses on the stigma theory introduced by Ervin Goffman (1963), as it helps analyse the social and emotional challenges faced by children who stutter. Through a comprehensive examination of stigma theory, this chapter aims to provide insights that can inform targeted strategies to mitigate stigma and enhance the well-being and educational experiences of children who stutter. Additionally, this chapter will focus on the stigma associated with stuttering, providing an in-depth exploration of existing research on this topic. Through a comprehensive review of the literature, this chapter seeks to deepen understanding of the complex dynamics surrounding stuttering-related stigma and its implications for individuals, families, educators, and society at large.

Chapter **Five** details the methodological choices that guided this research. It begins by explaining the research philosophy and its underlying paradigm, which helps to make sense of the overall research process. The chapter then outlines the methods used for data collection, which is the sampling strategies and semi-structured interviews. Furthermore, it provides a detailed presentation of the process of analysing the data using thematic analysis. The transparency of explaining the methodological choices for this study ensures the reliability of this research. Finally, the chapter discusses the ethical considerations that govern the research practices. This ensures that the chosen methods were used responsibly, the participants were protected and felt safe throughout the study, and the resulting findings are reliable and trustworthy.

Chapters **Six, Seven, and Eight** form the core of this research, presenting and discussing the study's findings. Each chapter focuses on a specific research question and follows a similar structure. Hence, chapter **six** addresses the question: What is the depth and scope of the Algerian stakeholders' knowledge of stuttering? It delves into the participants' knowledge about stuttering. It explores themes related to the nature of stuttering, its causes and treatment options, and their perception of its impact on the children who stutter. The analysis provides an in-depth understanding of how different stakeholder groups in Algeria perceive and understand stuttering. This provides a strong basis for the following chapter **seven** which addresses the question: What is the depth and scope of stakeholders' knowledge of the stigma associated with stuttering in Algerian middle schools? It explores participants' perceptions and understanding of the stigma associated with stuttering, using the knowledge base established in Chapter Six. Similarly, this finding of this chapter helps provide a comprehensive understanding of the findings of the following chapter. Hence, Chapter **Eight** addresses the question: What are the stakeholders' perspectives on the strategies for mitigating stigma-related

stuttering in Algerian middle schools? It explores participant knowledge regarding interventions that could reduce stigmatizing attitudes in Algerian middle schools. The chapter also discusses recommended teaching practices that could address the potential interventions to promote a more inclusive learning environment. By addressing these interconnected chapter themes, a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of stuttering and stigma in the Algerian context. This integrated approach helps to minimize potential ambiguities in the results and strengthens the overall findings.

Finally, Chapter **nine** concludes the thesis. It summarizes the key findings from each section answering the research questions. Furthermore, it highlights their significance and potential contributions to the research in the field of inclusive education and social studies that are related to stuttering and social stigma. The chapter also discusses the broader implications of the research and identifies potential areas for future investigation, paving the way for further exploration of this important and impactful topic.

The following chapter will discuss the educational system in Algeria and the concept of communication disorders.

2. Chapter Two: Background of The Study

This chapter aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the education system in Algeria. This chapter aims to equip the reader with basic knowledge of the nature of education in Algeria and the amendments that have shaped the current schooling system. Additionally, this chapter outlines the Algerian educational profile from primary to university levels. Moreover, the chapter delves into inclusive education, which is pertinent to this study's focus on learners with disabilities, particularly those with speech disorders. I have structured four sections to explore the concept of inclusive education in Algeria. The first section will clarify the concept of inclusion as recognised and adopted by educational institutions worldwide, following a definition of disability. The second section will discuss inclusive education within the Algerian educational field. The following section will review the inclusive laws and regulations in Algeria. The final section will discuss the challenges of implementing inclusion in schools.

The following section will describe the educational system of Algeria.

2.1. Educational development and reforms in Algeria

Education currently plays a critical role in a country's prosperity (Mekdad et al., 2014), encouraging a large number of individuals to pursue learning without exclusion or restriction, as it is an essential aspect of life (Johan and Harlan, 2014). Education has always been a significant indicator of progress in any community (Boudersa, 2016) and is widely regarded as an essential tool for fostering genuine development across various domains of life (Boudersa, 2016). Therefore, countries should prioritise quality schooling over mere enrolment percentages (Gran, 2017). In 2006, Algeria reported a literacy rate of 72.6% among the general population, with youth literacy at 91.8% (Rose, 2015). Additionally, UNICEF (2015) highlighted shortcomings in the Algerian educational system in addressing the needs of children with disabilities. While there were some specialised institutions, efforts to integrate them into regular classrooms were limited (UNICEF, 2015), potentially contributing to the significant proportion of out-of-school children with disabilities (Rose, 2015). Consequently, several reforms were implemented, aiming to establish and implement inclusive education (UNICEF, 2015). Legislators and educational stakeholders have taken steps to address educational inequalities (Touitou et al., 2020).

Algeria has consistently prioritised the education and development of its youth since gaining independence in 1962 (UNICEF, 2015). The effort to establish an integrated and public national educational system began with the founding of the Ministry of Education in 1963 (Clark, 2006). An estimated 890,000 children aged 6 to 16 were out of school, comprising 443,000 boys and 447,000 girls (UNICEF, 2015). However, between 2006 and 2013, the number of out-of-school children in this

age group was reduced by approximately 50% (UNICEF, 2015). This section discusses the Algerian educational reforms adopted after independence, focusing on language policies and the education system.

It is important to note that the Algerian government underwent three main phases during these reforms, as summarised by Benrabah (2007). The first phase occurred during the colonial period when the French language and colonial legacies predominated. The second phase was characterised by a nationalist transition, during which the Arabic language was enforced. The third phase began in the early 2000s when the government started to loosen Arabization policies.

The first phase commenced during the colonial period, when the French colonisers sought to eradicate Algerian identity, culture, language, and religion by imposing their educational system and language in Algerian schools (Rahoui, 2011). Consequently, the French language was extensively utilised in Algeria before 1962 (Baghoussi and El Ouchdi, 2019). Following the country's independence in 1962, Algeria's education system was built on the French colonial model and was not designed from scratch (Clark, 2006). A year later, the Algerian government embarked on the official reconstruction of the country and its educational system (National Report, 2019)

The second phase began during the early 1960s, with Arabic replacing French as the primary language of instruction in the lower levels of schooling (Clark, 2006; Baghoussi and El Ouchdi, 2019). By the end of this decade, Arabic had been standardised as the language of instruction even at higher levels (Clark, 2006; Baghoussi and El Ouchdi, 2019). Officials were entrusted with formulating an educational system encompassing various objectives (Clark, 2006). According to Lewis et al. (2004), the Arabization of the curriculum and faculty was a pivotal objective, strengthening post-1962 with the aim of eradicating all vestiges of French influence over Algeria (Rezig, 2011), because Arabic is the foundation of the Algerian identity and culture. The focus also extended to teaching skills at all levels and cultivating proficient cohorts of employees and specialists by emphasising technical and vocational education (Clark, 2006). Moreover, in 1976, a new educational system was introduced in Algeria, comprising nine years of primary and middle school combined, known as the fundamental school (Rezig, 2011). Starting from the late 1970s until the early 1990s, French became a compulsory foreign language course from Grade 4 of the primary cycle onwards (Benrabah, 2007).

The final phase saw the Algerian government reconsider the elimination of the French language and permit its use in certain subjects. The Arabic language served as the primary language of instruction for all subjects except foreign languages (Rezig, 2011). However, minister Mostepha Lacheraf reintroduced French into teacher training, and subjects like mathematics and biology were taught in French (Rezig, 2011). Consequently, the use of the Arabic language significantly dropped in scientific

and technical fields such as medicine, natural sciences, and architecture (Le Roux, 2017). According to Benrabah (2007), Arabization, the language policy aimed at replacing French entirely, was not successful. Furthermore, in 2003, new educational reforms were implemented, leading to significant changes in the education system. This included restructuring educational frameworks, revising teaching methods, and modifying educational programmes to enhance learning quality (UNICEF, 2015). To put it into perspective, Algeria has constantly prioritised improving schooling and teaching skills since after independence. The reform occurs as a result of several failures and complaints about the absence of efficiency and effectiveness in educational policies.

The next section will provide an overview of the Algerian education profile.

2.2. The Algerian Educational System

The Algerian educational system is rooted in both the French colonial legacy and post-independence reforms aimed at Arabization (Rose, 2015; Rose, 2014). The educational institutions in Algeria are organised into several levels: primary, middle, secondary, and vocational/higher education (National Report, 2019). Compulsory education mandates that all children starting at the age of six enrol in school at no cost (UK NARIC, 2012), which is five years of primary education to pass to middle school (Nuffic, 2019; Rose, 2014). In the fourth year of middle school, the students sit for the national exam aiming to pass to Secondary school (BEM).

Generally, in secondary education, students study a range of subjects and specialisations for three years. In their third year, they sit for the baccalaureate exam (Rose, 2015) to earn the baccalaureate certificate (Baccalauréate). After passing the baccalaureate exam, students can choose to attend vocational school, which involves three years of practical study to obtain a vocational certificate in a specific profession. Alternatively, they can pursue a higher educational certificate at the university, which requires three years for a bachelor's degree. They can also pursue further studies for a master's degree, which takes an additional two years, and a doctorate, which requires three to five years.

The following Figure 1 demonstrates these stages of the Algerian educational system for better understanding.

Figure 1 The Algerian Educational System Adapted from (Nuffic, 2019)

The previous figure illustrates the Algerian educational structure and the different stages the students proceed through in the school system. The current study, however, focuses specifically on middle school students, typically between the ages of 10 and 14. Some students in this age range may fail a grade and have to repeat a year, extending their middle school experience to age 16. This age range

is considered a critical period as it marks the beginning of adolescence. Furthermore, the middle school educational system differs significantly from the primary school system.

Since the study focused on students who stutter in middle school, the following section delves further into the concept of inclusive education and discusses its implementation within the Algerian educational system. However, before discussing this, the following section defines the concept of disability and its models.

2.3. Inclusive Education

While a growing body of literature and evolving policy frameworks address inclusion, a universally accepted definition remains vague (Layachi, Douglas, and Reraki, 2024). This lack of agreement could be attributed to the different educational systems, cultural perspectives, and institutional policies that vary worldwide (Forlin et al., 2013). As such, it is important to consider the theory of inclusion that governs both schools and society, not just its practical implications (Amor et al., 2017). Still, despite some misunderstandings, the concept of inclusion became internationally recognised during the 1990s as a global shift toward educational equity (Graham, 2020).

According to Osborne (2002, p. 301), inclusion is a paradigm in which children with disabilities are taught together with children without disabilities in general education classrooms. This understanding goes beyond the physical placement of children with disabilities as it emphasises classroom participation for all students, equitable access, and enhanced learning experiences (Hunter-Johnson, Newton, and Cambridge-Johnson, 2014). This demonstrates a critical difference between the concept of integration and inclusion in the discourse of disability and education. As integration consists of integrating students with disabilities in mainstream school without any modification to the teaching pedagogy, the school environment (UNESCO, 2022). Such an approach would not fulfil the educational attainment of students with disabilities despite their presence in the classroom (UNESCO, 2022). In contrast to educational inclusion Accordingly, it ensures the fundamental right to an education system that requires ongoing reform to remove any obstacles for all students that hinder their participation and engagement in learning alongside their peers of the same age (Graham, 2020; Hunter-Johnson, Newton, and Cambridge-Johnson, 2014; Jury et al., 2021).

To this end, inclusive education includes a socio-ecological perspective that emphasises students' abilities during interactions emphasising that the system should be accommodating not expecting students to conform to the system (Walker et al. 2014). In doing so, it challenges the traditional approach that considers disability as deficit oriented (Shogren, Wehmeyer, and Shing 2017). This cultivates an inclusive school setting that addresses any discrimination and promotes a welcoming environment for all learners (Hasan, Halder and Debnath, 2018; Aladini, 2020; Bhatia, 2021). The

central idea of inclusive education is that the education system must adapt to meet the needs of people with disabilities, not the other way around (Gordo, 2013). Hence, supporting inclusion and social equity in various educational contexts requires a commitment to examining and modifying institutional systems, as well as a willingness to take risks to improve learners' performance (Pantić and Florian, 2015).

Subsequently, inclusive education requires a rethinking of education policies, teachers' perceptions regarding inclusion to ensure that it is not merely a theoretical concept but a genuine experience for all learners. As such, the role of teachers and school culture is highly significant when implementing inclusion in schools. According to Ainscow, Booth and Dyson (2006, p. 300) the teachers' main concern is to strike a balance between the 'standard agenda' and 'inclusion', ensuring that one does not undermine the other. As they put it, the standard agenda focused on performance, productivity and outcomes, while inclusive education focused on equity in learning. Indeed, implementing inclusive education could be challenging for many teachers who aim to successfully meet the needs of their students as inclusive educators (Hunter-Johnson, Newton, and Cambridge-Johnson, 2014). Therefore, teachers' training for inclusion in school is deemed important for many teachers. As such, research has reported that educators with no training regarding disabilities demonstrated a lack of understanding of inclusion of students with disabilities (Rosado-Castellano et al., 2022). Besides the training, Rosado-Castellano et al., (2022) also argued that experience can enhance the teachers' attitudes and perceptions positively.

The development of inclusive education has been notably influenced by a series of key events and documents, as outlined by Opertti et al. (2014). The 1990 World Conference on Education for All suggested the notion that everyone should have access to education and paved the way for future efforts in inclusive education (UNICEF, 2015). Three years later, Standard Rules for the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities went a step further and stressed the need for equal opportunities within education itself by removing any barriers (UN, 2004). In 1994 the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education was a pivotal declaration that promoted inclusive education by advising schools to accommodate all children, including those with disabilities, thereby influencing global education policies (UNICEF, 1994). Developing further from this framework, the 2006 United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), particularly Article 24, contributed to the implementation of inclusive rights for persons with disabilities within the education system (UN, 2006). This ensured their rights to education without discrimination at all levels accommodating their needs to help them to fully participate in schools. Moreover, the 2009 Follow-up Conference to the Salamanca Statement reviewed the CRPD progress and reinforced its commitments (Opertti et al., 2014).

In conclusion, the implementation of inclusive education varies widely due to over the last sixty to seventy years, inclusive education has undergone a remarkable transformation (Opertti et al., 2014) to become a notion that can be applied around the world with different levels of implementation and success (Boyle and Sharma, 2015). To date, inclusion has been implemented in many schools across the world, becoming not only an aspect of education or a policy or set of policies for education but a principled way of viewing the development of education and society (Ainscow et al. 2006).

2.4. Disability

Constantino, Campbell, and Simpson (2022) defined disability as the experience of encountering barriers that hinder an individual's participation in social activities. Additionally, a disability can be related to any impairment that causes a disorder, dissimilarity, or malady in disabled people, such as multiple sclerosis, a spinal cord injury, a facial deformity, or verbal disfluency (Bailey et al., 2015). Hence, the current study focuses on stuttering as a disability that is classified as a verbal disfluency. As disability conveys the inadequate and restricted opportunities, as well as the difficulties, that persons with disabilities confront in relation to the general community (Bailey et al., 2015).

It is important to note that disability can be viewed differently based on theoretical background. Oliver provides an example of "someone with polio" as defined by medicine, being viewed by society as a "victim of witchcraft" (1990, p. 22). Accordingly, the concept of disability has been explored using several models within scientific studies since the 1960s (Degener, 2016). These models are frameworks that aid in understanding disability by outlining assumptions about its causes and nature, thereby facilitating more effective approaches to addressing it (Bogart et al., 2022). The main models are the medical model, social model, biopsychosocial model, and human rights model (Graham, 2021, p. 30). This study, however, focuses on how stakeholders construct their social knowledge regarding stuttering and how this affects their attitudes toward children who stutter. This will determine which lens or model stakeholders are using to view stuttering. Accordingly, the study focuses on two models: the medical model and, more extensively, the social model.

2.4.1. Medical Model of Disability

The medical model of disability emerged from biomedical sciences and considers impairment as the primary cause of disability (Graham, 2020, p. 30). This impairment is viewed as a sign or a physical condition within the individual's body that is addressed by medical intervention (Berghs et al., 2016). Starting from the mid-1800s, the medical model gradually replaced earlier models such as moral or religious models (Retief and Letšosa, 2018). Traditionally, disability was perceived solely through the medical model, viewing the individual's disability as the primary barrier (Constantino, Campbell, and Simpson, 2022). According to this model, disability is seen as residing within the individual as a defect

or illness (Bogart et al., 2022; Olkin, 1999). Individuals with disabilities are often regarded as patients seeking treatments to mitigate their condition as much as possible (Olkin, 1999). based on that, the following figure demonstrates the medical model of disability assumptions.

Figure 2 The Medical Model of Disability, Adapted from Inclusive London, 2015

The above Figure 2 depicts the perspective of the medical model regarding disability, illustrating barriers as internal to individuals with disabilities. The arrows extending from each disability towards the individual signify the model's premise that disability is inherent to the person. When applying this model to stuttering, the focus is more on the defect that resides within the person to understand the nature and cause of stuttering, ultimately contributing to its treatment (Constantino, Campbell, and Simpson, 2022).

2.4.2. Social Model of Disability

Oliver (1990) introduced the social model, which posits that disability is actually the barrier society creates, rather than being inherent to the individual. The social model of disability emerged in response to criticisms of the medical model (Shakespeare, 2018). In the field of education, the social model of disability serves as a foundation for developing inclusive practices (Graham, 2020). Therefore, the social model argues that eliminating societal barriers will eliminate disability (Mackie, 2012). An example of a barrier in education often manifests as teachers' attitudes and knowledge regarding teaching learners with disabilities, which can impede the flow of instruction (Graham, 2020). Moreover, addressing biased behaviours to enhance the accessibility of learning for all students is a key objective of the concept of inclusion (Adewumi and Mosito, 2019).

Figure 3 The Social Model of Disability, Adapted from Inclusive London, 2015

The figure 3 above illustrates the perspective of the social model regarding disability, depicting barriers within society that contribute to disability. Applying this model to stuttering could have significant implications, particularly within the school environment, as it aids in understanding the stuttering experience and reducing negative attitudes towards it (Constantino, Campbell, and Simpson, 2022).

2.4.3. Critiques of medical and social model of disability

The medical and social models were deemed suitable for this research for several reasons discussed in the previous section. In the context of stuttering, many studies have used these models, which allow me to gain an insight into how this could be applied to the current study (Bailey, Harris, and Simpson, 2015; Banerjee, 2021; Constantino, Campbell, and Simpson, 2022). However, it is important to note that after an in-depth reading, some limitations were highlighted. These limitations were taken into consideration throughout this research to strengthen the reliability of their application. Furthermore, there were other theoretical frameworks such as the identity model, the human rights model, and the charity model that also appeared to be applicable to my research at first glance. However, the biopsychosocial and ecological models were mostly compelling alternatives, yet they did not align with

the sample or the objectives of my study. Therefore, the aim of this section is to critically highlight the limitations of the models used and argue their relevance in comparison to other models.

Despite the useful insights provided by the medical model, some limitations were identified. This model focuses more on the individual level and overlooks the effect of the social environment (Graham, 2020). Furthermore, it can reinforce the stigma because it classifies the disability as a deficit (Haegele and Hodge, 2016). This model was essential for this study as it provides a lens to examine how the participants of this study perceive stuttering, which ultimately helps in understanding the attitudes of the society towards individuals who stutter. Moreover, it is important to highlight that one of the participant groups was speech language therapists, who are expected to treat stuttering. This group is regarded as the main source of knowledge for those who seek their help, such as parents and teachers. As such, it is likely that they would have a strong influence on their knowledge and perception of stuttering. Accordingly, despite its limitations, the medical model significantly contributes to this research, particularly given the main objective is to investigate the stigma that follows this speech disorder.

While this study was not mainly related to social studies, it also related to inclusive education. Therefore, the social model was considered as a second model. This model challenges the stigma by focusing on how society constructs and manages the disability (Oliver, 2013; Manago, Davis, and Goar, 2017), which was deemed to be relevant to this study. The social model shifts the focus from the disability itself to the social attitudes that surround it, including the environmental barriers and the institutional practices (Graham, 2020). However, the model also has some limitations, such as neglecting the medical aspects of the disability (Shakespeare, 2006), stuttering in this study. Stuttering, for example, could be accompanied by some psychological and emotional challenges that should not be disregarded (see Jones, et al., 2021). Although the social model is considered to be an important one to highlight the attitudes of the stakeholders (teachers, parents, and speech therapists) towards children who stutter, the medical perspective should also be considered.

Another model that was considered was the biopsychosocial model, which integrates the biological, psychological and social aspects (Roberts, 2023). This model was developed by George Engel in 1977 as a response to the limitation of the biomedical model that focuses on the biological aspects only. Therefore, it was mostly used in medical studies (Bolton, and Gillett 2019). Although it could combine more than the social and medical factors, it did not align with the aim and the focus of this research. Upon initial review, this model sounds theoretically holistic, yet the current study does not aim to explore the psychological aspects of children who stutter. Instead, the primary focus was on the

participants' perspectives regarding stuttering and their attitudes towards children who stutter. Therefore, using this model could divert the focus from the main objective of this study.

Another model that was considered during the first stage of the study was the ecological model. This model has been widely used in studies related to both social science and inclusive education. Urie Bronfenbrenner developed this model within the context of human development (1979). Thus, the ecological model argues that the individual is embedded within a system of connected layers such as family, school, and culture (Bronfenbrenner, 1994). Hence, the individual's development is a result of multiple aspects during their interaction with society and their environment. Although the ecological model could have provided valuable insight for the study, the first aim of the study was to investigate the stakeholders' knowledge regarding stuttering. Given that stuttering has received a significant attention on its treatment and neurological understanding (e.g., Maguire, Yeh, and Ito 2012; Prins and Ingham, 2009; Chow and Chang, 2017; Jossinger et al., 2021), the medical model was necessary to explore the stakeholder' understanding regarding its nature, cause, treatment. Hence, the current research does not only investigate the social attitudes that the ecological system could help to understand, but also the participants' knowledge regarding the stuttering. This knowledge could eventually explain their attitudes towards children who stutter. Therefore, I have chosen two different models taking into account models considering their limitations to make them complementary to each other after. This would ultimately help identify the stigmatising attitudes and correct them (Banerjee, 2021).

In conclusion, all the alternatives' models offer a valuable insight into this research, however the medical and social model provided the most appropriate grounding covering both the knowledge regarding stuttering and attitudes towards children who stutter. Furthermore, it is crucial to recognise that all models have limitations, but they do not necessarily affect their value (Samaha, 2007).

2.5. Inclusive Education in Algeria

Around the world, the need for inclusive education and efforts to improve systems in this area have been recognized to varying degrees. Some countries have been more effective in adopting the concept of inclusion than others (Boyle and Sharma, 2015). A significant effort has been made to establish inclusion in schools across the world over the last couple of decades (Crispela and Kasperski, 2021); however, this effort has become a source of concern for educational policymakers (Karellou, 2019). Data on disability prevalence and the implementation of inclusive practices within the Algerian education system are limited (Layachi, Douglas, and Reraki, 2024). According to Boutebal and Yahi (2018), children with disabilities are welcomed into schools without discrimination in teaching techniques and curriculum. Furthermore, a study conducted by Hoadjli and Latrache reported that the

majority of teachers (68.92%) support the right to inclusive education for learners regardless of their disability (2020, p. 133).

According to Benssai (2018), inclusive education in Algeria refers to an educational system that focuses on providing equal educational opportunities for all learners, including those with disabilities. Disabilities, as described by Boutebal and Yahi (2018), are permanently fixed conditions caused by maladies, injuries, or genetic problems, categorising them as physical and mental. Despite arguments both for and against the inclusion of individuals with disabilities in mainstream education, educational institutions must embrace creativity and diversity for inclusive education to be effective (Karellou, 2019). Many countries, including Algeria, have recently aimed to promote education for children with disabilities to enable their engagement in their social environment (Boutebal and Yahi, 2018). Francis et al. (2021) argued that inclusive education is widely acknowledged as a key component in ensuring equitable and high-quality education for all learners.

Like many countries, Algeria has also endeavoured to implement inclusive education in its schools. From its independence in 1962 until the 1980s, the socialist single-party system struggled to ensure equal educational opportunities for all children (Tiliouine, 2014). Mitchell et al. (2008) reported that many aspects hinder the implementation of inclusive education in Asia and South Africa, including the lack of teacher training and knowledge about inclusion in schools, as well as the absence of pedagogical, material, and parental support (Mitchell et al., 2008). Therefore, Algeria's educational system reform (Education Act, 2008) aimed primarily to provide better education (Tiliouine, 2014).

Many teachers strongly advocate for eliminating the separation between general and inclusive education, instead favouring the integration of learners with disabilities alongside those without into a single educational system that meets the needs of all learners (Karellou, 2019). Consequently, the disability rights movement worldwide has opposed judgmental, racist, and stereotyped representations of disabled people (Karellou, 2019). Hoadjli and Latrache (2020) conducted a qualitative study to investigate teachers' preparation to adjust teaching to meet learners' needs and reduce difficulties associated with impaired pupils in Algeria. Overall, the results revealed that middle school educators could incorporate inclusive education into their classrooms as a beneficial contribution to fulfilling the diverse requirements of their learners.

Inclusive education for children with disabilities aims to provide education for all children, regardless of their disability, within the sectors or educational institutions in the child's local community (Boutebal and Yahi, 2018). Mainstream schools or general settings may not always be equipped to accommodate individuals with disabilities. Therefore, when implementing an inclusive approach, the environment must be carefully considered. In other words, settings for individuals with disabilities

could be general, and children with disabilities, in particular, may encounter challenges that extend to social environments or academic settings (Boutebal and Yahi, 2018).

In an inclusive classroom framework, full-service institutions are specifically equipped to accommodate a wide range of learning difficulties (Adewumi and Mosito, 2019). In Algeria, on the other hand, local diagnosis has been primarily focused on children with disabilities who are enrolled in regular schools but lack the inclusive environment necessary for stable and organised learning (Bouabdallah, 2013). Therefore, promoting social inclusion in Algeria, both physically and emotionally, as well as meeting the needs of individuals with disabilities, has become the main objective (Almeras, 2016). Efforts are being made to improve the rights of individuals with disabilities to enhance their quality of life and address their situations (Almeras, 2016). In 2010, the establishment of local facilitators and the identification of obstacles to the education of disabled children were initiated under a project entitled "Education for All: Towards the Inclusion of Children with Disabilities in the Algerian Educational System" (Bouabdallah, 2013, p. 51). However, specialised training programs focus only on learning difficulties or physical disabilities (UK NARIC, 2012).

Algeria has shifted some attention to children in their second decade of life to ensure that their specific needs are met, and their rights are upheld (UNICEF, 2016). Notwithstanding the evidence that suggests a comprehensive range of attitudes and behaviours is extremely important to students' long-term performance, studies have mostly concentrated on how teachers influence student attainment on standardised tests (Blazar and Kraft, 2017). Algeria's early childhood development is successful in certain domains, however, not in others, exposing children to the danger of not reaching their full developmental potential (El-Kogali, 2015). Emotional and personal characteristics, for instance, determine an individual's quality of life and cognitive functioning (Chernyshenko et al., 2018), as well as the amount of knowledge children acquire in the classroom, according to psychologists (Duckworth et al., 2012).

"The number of special departments open for this school year 2015-2016 has reached 414 in 41 provinces and 282 departments during the 2014-2015 academic year, including 250 special sections for children with minor mental disabilities. The level of these special sections is 3246 disabled children among them (1326 girls)" (Boutebal and Yahi, 2018, p. 28).

This quote explains that there are a large number of legal provisions in Algeria aimed at ensuring the right to education of all children without discrimination within the national legal framework and at the international level. Hence, in mainstream divisions, particularly at the middle and secondary levels, the general participation of children with disabilities is also encouraged. However, national and local

organisations are not sufficiently equipped and structured to meet the challenges of inclusive education by implementing the existing legal framework (Handicap International, Algeria, 2012). On the other hand, according to Boutebal and Yahy (2018), inclusive education is well established in Algerian schools, both in terms of policies and pedagogical practices.

The inclusive pedagogical concept emerged from conceptions of inclusive classrooms that initially focused solely on children with disabilities (Pantić and Florian, 2015). Furthermore, it takes into account individual differences among students while actively trying to avoid the stigmatisation of some students and/or the ongoing marginalisation of certain groups (Pantić and Florian, 2015). For instance, ethnic minority learners, learners from different cultures, learners who are not native speakers, learners with disabilities, and learners from poorer backgrounds may be marginalised by poverty.

Educational politics have an impact on the implementation of inclusive education. Hence, the following section reviews the education politics of inclusive education in Algeria.

2.6. The Challenges of Implementing Inclusive Education

The reform of the Algerian educational system emphasises the need for effective educational programmes and an appropriate academic environment for all children in society (Boutebal and Yahy, 2018). Furthermore, educational policies and legislation were also considered. In the field of education, amendments were made at the level of Algerian schools in Tizi Ouzou and Setif by improving the competencies of local educators, implementing local social action programmes, coordinating local legislation, and enhancing regional discussion structures (Almeras, 2016). However, further efforts are required to develop adequate strategies and policies for competent education, necessitating collaboration from relevant ministries (Boutebal and Yahy, 2018).

Internationally, there is inconsistency between policies and their implementation that needs to be recognised and addressed (Florian, 2014). Nevertheless, policy proposals, legislative changes, and related regulations for educational institutions contribute to an ongoing debate regarding neo-liberalism, wherein parents have the opportunity to choose the educational setting for their children. This ostensible right was formulated in the Children and Families Act (Department for Education, 2014). Parents are allowed to choose between specialised schools and general schools as the best setting for their children (Done, 2019). Additionally, the role of parents has been recognised in expanding inclusive educational practices worldwide. According to Srivastava et al. (2015), parents should be acknowledged as the fourth factor in scaling up inclusion in schools. The official Journal of the Algerian Republic N33 (2017) outlines policies aimed at preventing disabilities by addressing factors that cause or worsen them. Chapter 1, Article 3 (2017, p.3) specifies that disability prevention

involves implementing measures to prevent the occurrence of physical, mental, or sensory impairments or to ensure they do not lead to permanent functional limitations. This policy highlights the Algerian educational system's commitment to reducing struggles and difficulties for individuals with disabilities and protecting against factors that might cause disability. However, practicing inclusion presents numerous challenges (Crispela and Kasperski, 2021).

Implementing inclusive education is a challenging approach across many countries, not only in Algeria. Deeply entrenched ideas, behaviours, and actions that reject or ignore the concept of social inclusion are the most disruptive barriers to inclusion (Opertti et al., 2014). These attitudes oppose the diversity that comes with a more inclusive and integrated society and do not consider addressing social and educational needs a major concern (Opertti et al., 2014). The concept of disabling describes a community that tends to discriminate against individuals with disabilities (Gordo, 2013). For example, the absence of lifts for wheelchair users to enter public buildings or use public transportation is considered disabling. Hence, according to the social model, it is not the disabled person who needs to be adjusted, but society (Gordo, 2013).

When public institutions struggle or refuse to support young people with disabilities, parents and caregivers often seek assistance from specialised institutions. However, children with disabilities in local areas are unlikely to be able to access these places, or their requirements are not adequately met locally (House of Commons, 2006).

Another challenge emerged concerning the competency of teachers in promoting inclusive education. The perspectives of educators towards inclusion, coupled with a thorough understanding of inclusive education principles, largely influence the effectiveness of inclusive classrooms (Sokal and Sharma, 2017). This underscores the need for teachers to communicate adeptly, requiring a deep understanding of how inclusive practices can be applied in diverse contexts (Pantić and Florian, 2015). Teachers must be prepared to respond appropriately in instances where children with disabilities face bullying or stigma. The emphasis on including children's experiences of bullying has advanced research on social relationships and psychological well-being (Goswami, 2012, p. 576). This elucidates parental concerns regarding their children's support within mainstream schools (Allan, 2008). Teachers must dedicate significant time and effort to support children with disabilities in inclusive classrooms (Crispela and Kasperski, 2021).

While there is some consensus on the understanding, expertise, and principles that teachers should possess to effectively engage with diverse learners in research, there remains a dearth of understanding on how these are formulated, implemented, sustained, and demonstrated across various school settings where educators operate (Pantić and Florian, 2015). The level of teachers' self-

efficacy determines their resilience in addressing challenges, obstacles, and adverse experiences associated with adopting inclusion (Crispela and Kasperski, 2021). Mainstream teachers often encounter significant challenges in aligning their teaching approaches with the needs of their students while also attaining high academic standards (Mieghem et al., 2018; Abegglen and Hessels, 2018). Hence, fostering multidisciplinary teamwork and equitable responsibilities among school staff is imperative for effectively educating learners with disabilities in inclusive classrooms (Crispela and Kasperski, 2021).

In conclusion, the researcher endeavoured to review inclusive practices in Algeria and the pertinent policies concerning inclusive education. However, the available sources discussing the issue were limited. The researcher consulted several articles and journals detailing the promotion of inclusion in Algeria, as well as official international documents outlining the rights to education for all. Since the study focuses on Algerian schools, this section does not solely address inclusive education in a general sense but rather delves specifically into inclusive educational practices within Algerian schools.

Inclusive education, much like in many other countries, aims to facilitate the participation of learners with special needs alongside their peers without discrimination, while simultaneously catering to the diverse needs of all students. Within the context of inclusive education, the concept of inclusion in schools advocates for the schooling of all learners in regular educational settings (Florian, 2014). Individuals with disabilities may exhibit impairments that manifest as disorders, differences, or illnesses, such as multiple sclerosis, spinal cord injuries, facial deformities, or speech disfluencies (Bailey et al., 2015).

To summarise, inclusive education in Algeria has been the subject of extensive research, with scholars seeking to comprehend and implement inclusive practices within Algerian schools. According to Karellou (2019), specialised schooling in Africa, including Algeria, has made significant strides in recent years, with the provision of additional educational opportunities. In the present study, the researcher has placed particular emphasis on learners with stuttering. As previously mentioned, stuttering is recognised as a disability that warrants attention in terms of inclusive practices. Before delving into the concept of stuttering as a communicative disorder and its impact on the learning process of affected children, the following section will elucidate communication and developmental language disorders.

3. Chapter Three: Literature Review

This chapter delves into communication disorders, with a particular emphasis on stuttering. It highlights how stuttering is classified within the broader category of communication disorders, exploring its unique characteristics and differentiating it from other speech-related issues. The chapter clarifies the process of communication as an introduction to the concept of communication disorders. Furthermore, it examines the types of communication disorders, namely language and speech disorders. Since stuttering falls under speech disorders, the chapter places greater focus on this area. It provides a comprehensive understanding of stuttering, discussing its nature, causes, and impacts on children who stutter. The aim of this chapter is to offer a thorough analysis of the literature to foster a deeper understanding of speech disorders, and the specific challenges associated with stuttering.

The following section explains the process of communication and the nature of communication disorders.

3.1. Communication and Language Development

Communication is a process that we take for granted every day, without considering what it entails or how vital it is to us (Thompson, 2018). The term "communication" is derived from the Latin word "communicare," meaning "to share" or "to make common" (Pearson et al., 2017, p. 10; Manojlovich et al., 2015). It involves the ability to transmit and receive knowledge and thoughts between individuals (Morris, 2013). This process is essential for individuals' social well-being and emotional states because it facilitates the transfer of information (Konadath et al., 2020).

Thompson (2018) claimed that having the correct speech at the right moment is critical to achieving cohesion, better accuracy, and satisfaction. Consequently, communication occurs in various forms, such as lexical, nonverbal, and semantic processes, which affect individuals' ability to interact with others (Zebron et al., 2015). Through meaningful interaction, individuals understand and learn more (Haverkamp, 2017). This process reduces negative thoughts and gestures caused by fear, self-blame, and other negative emotions, ultimately helping to alleviate nervousness and depression (Haverkamp, 2017).

Before comprehending and assisting children with speech impairment, it is significant to study the nature of language acquisition under typical conditions. Language and speech development commence from childbirth and continue to evolve during the early years of life. Language is a crucial method for individuals to communicate; difficulties in language acquisition negatively affect educational and societal development (Paul and Gilbert, 2011). Researchers have explained the way

our brain processes language and how we utilise it for communication purposes. Three main theories have been developed for this reason: the innate theory (Chomsky, 1957), the behaviourist theory (Skinner, 1957), and the interactionist approach, which comprises the developmental cognitive theory associated with Piaget (1971).

First, Noam Chomsky's theory has been widely known and implemented in linguistic contexts (Çakıroğlu, 2018). According to the innate theory, also known as the nativism theory, language is innate (Saxton, 2017). Pinker (1994) also referred to it as an instinct; however, the word instinct here is used metaphorically rather than literally. In other words, unlike the unchanging automatic responses of individuals, language is a learned skill that undergoes constant improvements to reach the final stage of acquisition (Dékány, 2019). Language is believed to be biologically based in the human brain (Çakıroğlu, 2018). This makes it an innate ability for humans to be ready and competent in learning and acquiring language (Çakıroğlu, 2018; Saxton, 2017). Chomsky suggested that children are ready to acquire language because it is hard-wired in their brains (Matthews, 2003). He referred to this as a language acquisition device.

Nevertheless, another theory that stands in contrast to the previously mentioned theory is the behaviourist approach, developed by Skinner (1957). This approach explains that language acquisition is based on environmental factors. Therefore, the social environment affects language performance and usage, which in turn influences the cognitive aspects of individuals and their interactions with society (Kidd, 2018). In light of these beliefs, the child acquires language from the surrounding environment. Consequently, the amount of language and speech the child receives greatly influences their language acquisition (Weisleder and Fernald, 2013). Skinner believes that humans do not possess language innately, as Chomsky claimed; rather, language is learned (Skinner, 1957). Children at this stage are passive, but with time, they start to develop their ability to speak based on the surrounding environment (Mavis, 2007; Greene and Petty, 1975). Therefore, behaviourists believe that individuals learn language in the same way animals form habits (Mehrpour and Forutan, 2015). That is to say, spoken language is a skill that does not differ from other human behavioural skills (Dastpak et al., 2017). Accordingly, the beliefs of behaviourists on language acquisition can be summarised in three points: imitation, reinforcement, and reward (Mehrpour and Forutan, 2015).

In addition to the above theories, usage-based Language theories (Lieven, 2016) that argues how the language is developed based on the frequency of human interaction and their experience. These theories argue that language is actually shaped by the amount of linguistic input and context that children receive during their daily communication (Lieven, 2016; Bybee, 2009). In this sense, the development of language is gradual, as the children start acquiring the spoken language by noticing

its patterns and memorising it through their daily use (Tomasello, 2001). As an example, the construction of sentences and common phrases only get rich over time, where the child builds more complex linguistic expressions (Goldberg, 2006).

All the aforementioned theories have strengths and weaknesses, despite being opposed to each other (Çakıroğlu, 2018). Unlike Chomsky, Piaget's beliefs on language structure do not align with the theory of innateness (1972). However, this also does not agree with the theory that language is purely acquired; rather, this process is based on continuous interactions related to cognitive function and environmental communication (Piaget and Inhelder, 1969). Even nativists recognise the importance of interaction with the environment (Shore, 1995). Hence, a theory named the interactionist approach encompasses many other theories, such as the developmental cognitive theory associated with Piaget (1971), information processing theory, competitive model, and other theories related to the socio-cultural views of Vygotsky (1978), all of which are significant for language acquisition (Çakıroğlu, 2018). This theory tends to relate language acquisition to many factors such as societal, linguistic, cognitive, and biological features that influence each other (Çakıroğlu, 2018).

However, communication can be affected by various factors that hinder and influence the speech process, leading to communication disorders. Therefore, the following section discusses these factors to lay the groundwork for understanding stuttering.

3.2. Communication Disorders

Communication disorders are described as a lack of ability to transmit, receive, understand, and distinguish between verbal and nonverbal behaviours (Gupta, 2015). The American Speech-Language-Hearing Association (ASHA) defines a communication disorder as 'an impairment in the ability to receive, send, process and comprehend concepts or verbal, non-verbal and graphic symbol system'. This definition encompasses struggles in speaking, the use of language, and/or the perception of speech (Konadath et al., 2020). According to Gupta (2015), "In clinical populations, such as individuals with aphasia, autism, cleft lip and palate, expressive and receptive language disorders, hearing impairment, intellectual disability, specific learning disorders, stuttering, etc., show one or the other kind of problems in speech and language" (p. 82). Hence, the following figure demonstrated a summary of the types of communication disorders.

Figure 4 Diagram Illustrating the types of communication disorders

As illustrated in the above Figure 4, it is also significant to distinguish between language and speech disorders as types of communication disorders. A study conducted in Jordan reported that language disorders are the most common type of communication disorder found among children, followed by articulation disorders (Al Araifi et al., 2020). The word "language" refers to a basic systematic way that helps an individual apply or interpret a signifier, which could be a term, symbol, or other linguistic labels, to describe the message being transmitted or comprehended, along with applying a proper grammatical form to organise or interpret words and phrases (Dronkers et al., 2017). A person with language disorders has problems with utilising proper forms of language such as phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics, as well as using the meanings of the language, which is to say pragmatics (Miller, 2016).

Approaches such as aetiology, linguistics, and language development have made significant contributions to understanding types of language and speech disorders, as well as language development impairment (Paul and Gilbert, 2011). Developmental language impairments are related to other disorders such as syndromes, autism, hearing impairments, fetal alcohol syndrome, as well as trauma resulting from environmental factors such as stigma and mistreatment (Paul and Gilbert, 2011). In 2015, the Delphi method was used in a project named CATALISE (Criteria and Terminology Applied to Language Impairments: Synthesising the Evidence to discuss and agree on terminologies used to refer to children with language impairment (Bishop et al., 2016, 2017). A board of 57 professionals approved the use of the term Developmental Language Disorder for children with inexplicable language impairments (Bishop, 2017). This term refers to children who have not met the

expected level of language competence for their age, with the cause being unknown (Bishop, 2017; Paul and Gilbert, 2011). The two most common disabilities affecting children's academic progress are reading and language impairments (Adolf et al., 2017). All panel members documented that some children struggle to acquire their mother tongue, which can severely affect their social and academic environments (Bishop, 2017).

Bishop (2014) highlighted the fact that there is no agreement on a specific term for children whose language impairment is not categorised or known, unlike children with developmental impairments. He illustrated this with terms such as dyslexia, which refers to reading difficulties, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, which refers to attention disorders, and autistic spectrum disorder, which refers to social cognition disorders (Bishop et al., 2014). In his article "Ten Questions About Terminology for Children with Unexplained Language Problems," Bishop discussed ten questions related to labelling individuals with language disorders (Bishop, 2014). The following section explains speech disorders.

On the other hand, the term speech refers to the method by which information is vocally produced and how the speech is eventually articulated (Dronkers et al., 2017). The vocal organs and vocal cords create sounds during speech production (Price et al., 2011). More specifically, the phases involve word processing, a suitable choice of the form of morphology, syllable, part of speech, and term structuring, the decoding of the phonological articulation strategies, initiation, and integration of patterns of the articulators' movements such as the tongue, teeth, lips, and vocal cords, and the management of respiration for syllable speech production (Price et al., 2011). Lee et al. (2021) explain further speech disorders as follows:

"Here, the notion of speech disorders is interpreted widely, including, but not limited to, protracted phonological development, articulatory and phonological disorders in children, childhood apraxia of speech (or developmental verbal dyspraxia), motor speech disorders and speech disorders from other neurogenic conditions, and speech disorders resultant from physiological impairments, or various genetic conditions" (p. 2).

According to the quote, speech disorders appear when the act of speaking is affected or disrupted. Sometimes people suffer from a motor speech deficiency that creates difficulties in uttering words (e.g., dysarthria) or in coordinating the complex movements required for pronunciation (apraxia of speech) (Dronkers et al., 2017, p. 742). In other words, a speech disorder results from difficulty articulating sounds when uttering words, struggling with controlling sounds that affect the voice, and issues with speech rhythm that impact the speaker's fluency.

The American Speech-Language-Hearing Association (ASHA) is a national professional, scientific, and credentialing association for audiologists; speech-language pathologists; speech, language, and hearing scientists; audiology and speech-language pathology support personnel; and students. According to ASHA (2021), speech disorders are categorised into three types: articulation disorders, voice disorders, and fluency disorders, which are the focus of this research. Articulation disorders are characterised by abnormalities in the generation of particular speech sounds, resulting from issues in the areas responsible for speech articulation, such as the tongue, larynx, teeth, and so on (ASHA, 2021a). Voice disorders may be organic or functional and manifest in inappropriate voice, sound, pitch, or loudness for the speaker's age, gender, culture, or geographical area (ASHA, 2021b). Finally, fluency disorders are defined as disruptions affecting speech fluency at the level of speech rhythm and may be accompanied by secondary behaviours such as stress and hesitation in speech (ASHA, 2021c). Thus, fluency disorders might manifest as syllable repetition, such as stuttering, progressing to complete blocks in articulating sounds and, eventually, an inability to use language to communicate (Jacob, 2015). Moreover, the disorder might be classified in terms of severity, ranging from slight to intense (Jacob, 2015).

In conclusion, a communication disorder is an impairment that affects an individual's ability to comprehend and transmit speech and language, either verbally or nonverbally. In this research, however, more focus will be given to stuttering in particular. Accordingly, the section will explain this speech disorder. The term stuttering is used in most articles describing this disorder, and it is also described as dysfluency, disfluency, and non-fluency (Onslow, 2020).

3.3. Stuttering

Stuttering and stammering are two terms often confused as different; however, they are mostly used interchangeably (Mongia et al., 2019). Some scholars argue that stammering is frequently used in the United Kingdom and Ireland (Onslow, 2020; Kelman and Whyte, 2012). Hence, it is significant to highlight that the term "stuttering" will be primarily used in this study, although other terms such as stammering and cluttering can also be used. This section elaborates more on the nature of speech disorders, the different theories, and the causal factors proposed by some scholars to explain the reasons behind these speech disorders, including stuttering onset, developmental stuttering, and severe stuttering.

3.3.1. Nature of Stuttering

Many scholars have agreed on definition regarding the nature of stuttering arguing that is a speech disorder that is characterised by blocks or repetitions of sounds, syllables, and monosyllabic words, as well as involuntary prolongations (Chang et al., 2019; Etchell et al., 2018; Chang et al., 2015; Chow and

Chang, 2017; Mongia et al., 2019; Büchel and Sommer, 2004). Accordingly, stuttering is one of the fluency disorders that are described as breaks throughout the rhythmic flow of speech (Khabri et al., 2019). It is related to the involvement of oral speech disruptions that affect the process of normal communication (O’Brian et al., 2011; Chang et al., 2019). Some syllable repetitions, prolongation, and blocks disrupt the speech fluency frequently and without the intention of the speaker to his normal flow of the speech (Chow and Chang, 2017).

Guitar (2016) used the expression "core behaviours," stating that he adopted it from Van Riper (1971), to refer to the prolongation, blocks, or repetitions that arise from stuttering. Smith and Weber (2017) defined stuttering as a neurodevelopmental disorder, which manifests as disfluency and involuntary disruptions of the speech fluency flow. In addition to this, facial grimacing and superfluous behaviours may accompany the behavioural speech characteristics of stuttering (Meredith et al., 2012). Severe stuttering can produce more secondary behaviours, including eye blinks and looking away (Perez and Stoeckle, 2016). It is difficult to define fluency; consequently, there has been more focus on dysfluency (Guitar, 2016), and among all these disfluencies, stuttering is considered the most common speech disorder (Cummins, 2010). Commonly, people who stutter are referred to as stutters (Guitar, 2019). The following figure demonstrates and explains more the above.

Figure 5 Primary and secondary characteristics of stuttering

Many stutters develop involuntary physical behaviours that do not align with normal speech behaviours, such as eye blinking, and head, jaw, or body nodding (ALBdour et al., 2020). These secondary behaviours are reactions to escape from the primary behaviours of stuttering, which might be repetitions, blocks, or prolongations (Guitar, 2016; ALBdour et al., 2020). The severity of stuttering

varies from day to day, week to week, and even month to month (Kelman and Whyte, 2012). Measuring the severity of stuttering is categorised as normal, mild, or severe stuttering (Mongia et al., 2019). Distinguishing the severity of stuttering helps to determine the therapy's evaluation as well as the amount and type of counselling that should be offered (Mongia et al., 2019).

The severity of stuttering is presumably measured according to the frequency of speech disruption and the behavioural struggles that occur during moments of stuttering in the flow of speech (Packman et al., 2007). Some studies have found that the length of uttered words could have a direct relationship with the severity of stuttering in preschool children who stutter (Khabri, 2019). Nevertheless, the severity of stuttering can be affected by the number of strategies individuals who stutter use to avoid this disfluency disorder (Packman et al., 2007). It is also related to the amount of enthusiasm of the individual who stutters in the context of communication (Packman et al., 2007). ALBdour et al. (2020) illustrated that stuttering may cause psychological issues such as feeling anxious, worried, confused, shy, and socially isolated, which might affect the confidence of the person who stutters in educational settings or social interactions.

Stuttering typically begins at a young age, around three to four years old, when a child starts to utter short connected words as sentences (Packman et al., 2007). It affects 5% of all preschool-aged children and 1% of the general population (Chang et al., 2019). Yairi and Ambrose (2013) stated that men are generally more likely to have developmental stuttering compared to women. This topic will be discussed further in the section on the impact of stuttering according to gender. Stuttering might disappear for weeks or even months, giving the impression that it has resolved, only to start again without any obvious reason (Kelman and Whyte, 2012). Therefore, recovery can sometimes be spontaneous and occur without any intervention; however, in some cases, it requires the help of a speech therapist, who plays an important role in the therapy of stuttering (Cruz et al., 2018). The following section explores the types of stuttering: developmental and acquired stuttering.

Stuttering can be classified as either developmental or acquired. Developmental stuttering is the most common type (Ward, 2017). It occurs at the early stages of language acquisition in children and is also called childhood-onset fluency disorder (Chang et al., 2019; Perez and Stoeckle, 2016). Developmental stuttering is the most recognised type of disfluency, generally starting between the ages of 2 and 5 years (Anderson, 2011). In contrast, Ward (2017) explained that acquired stuttering results from trauma and can manifest as neurogenic stuttering when brain damage occurs due to an accident, or psychogenic stuttering as a result of psychological trauma. However, Büchel and Sommer (2004) consider neurogenic stuttering merely an alternative term for acquired stuttering. It is agreed that neurogenic stuttering may result from brain damage or injury where the brain regions responsible for

speech are disrupted, causing speech problems and disfluency (Theys et al., 2013). Jokel et al. (2007) added that it is an acquired speech disorder in adulthood, generally resulting from brain injury, stroke, neurological disease, or insult (Theys et al., 2011). Traumatic brain injury generates a brain function deficit at the level of the injured brain tissue due to external physical force, such as blood loss, contusion, or diffuse axonal injury (Strasberg et al., 2016). Early studies of acquired stuttering were case reports that lacked imaging data and were unable to determine the location and extent of brain lesions (Ludlow, 2003). Stuttering in adults can also be a neurological condition arising from developmental speech disfluency that appears suddenly or gradually (De Nil, 2018).

We distinguish between acquired stuttering and developmental stuttering according to the age at which disfluency starts, with developmental stuttering mainly occurring in childhood, whereas adult stuttering is considered neurogenic stuttering (Theys et al., 2011). Notwithstanding that neurogenic stuttering has particular features, identifying it from psychogenic stuttering or developmental stuttering based solely on speech characteristics can be challenging (Cruz et al., 2018). Some neurologically based language and speech impairments may coincide, making it difficult to draw clear distinctions among different entities (Cruz et al., 2018).

3.3.2. Conceptualisations of Stuttering

While this section focused on the biomedical view of stuttering, which frames it as a speech deficit, it is important to note that stuttering can also be understood from a neurodiversity perspective. From this standpoint, stuttering is not regarded as a defect but as a natural human variation in speech (Constantino, 2018). This perspective goes beyond the social model of disability, emphasising that the act of stuttering itself is not inherently problematic; rather, the difficulties arise from the social barriers and negative attitudes that people who stutter encounter (Bailey, Harris and Simpson, 2015). The concept of neurodiversity is commonly attributed to Judy Singer (1998), who highlighted neurological differences as part of human diversity. Applied to stuttering, this framework provides an alternative understanding that directly challenges the biomedical model by normalising stuttering and recognising it as a form of human diversity. At its core, this perspective promotes the idea of embracing disability as a difference rather than a deficit (Lewis, 2014). Accordingly, instead of prioritising remediation or fluency-oriented interventions, stuttering is reframed as a valid and acceptable way of speaking that should be respected within society (Constantino, 2018).

In this regard, the work of Constantino, Campbell, and Simpson (2022), alongside Bailey, Harris, and Simpson (2015), provides a significant orientation toward the conceptualisation of stuttering. Their work reported important implications, uncovering both the experiences of individuals who stutter and the ways in which stuttering is perceived by society. Bailey, Harris, and Simpson (2015) emphasised

the acceptance and normalisation of stuttering, arguing that the burden of producing fluent speech is notably reduced. Accordingly, this reinforces the neurodiversity view of disability, where the public is encouraged to embrace and accept dysfluency as a valid form of communication, thereby reducing the stigma associated with stuttering. Furthermore, they extended their argument by highlighting that negative attitudes toward disability not only create external barriers but also provoke the internalisation of stigma. These stereotypes could eventually develop into a negative self-concept, leading individuals to believe the identities society has created for them and to belittle themselves (Constantino, Campbell and Simpson, 2022). Therefore, the acceptance of disability shifts the focus from fixing the impairment to placing responsibility on society to accommodate and respect differences. In doing so, it is important to highlight that understanding stuttering is as difficult as understanding the barriers that individuals who stutter face in society (Constantino, Campbell and Simpson, 2022). These barriers can be characterised as stressful situations for individuals who stutter, which could in turn increase the severity of the stutter.

Applying these insights in schools aligns with the principles of inclusive education. Florian and Black-Hawkins (2011) advocate inclusive pedagogical principles, such as designing a learning environment that embraces and values diversity. Florian and Black-Hawkins (2011) highlighted the importance of differentiating between the educational concepts associated with inclusion, such as pedagogy, education, and practice. In doing so, the aim is to avoid problems and stigmatising attitudes, such as labelling students as “different” (Florian and Black-Hawkins, 2011, p. 822). Interestingly, their findings concluded that teachers’ knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs regarding learning and the processes of learning determine their inclusive pedagogical practices (Florian and Black-Hawkins, 2011). From this perspective, teachers are expected to meet the required standards for inclusive pedagogy, while also recognising that they will face certain challenges and dilemmas in practice.

Norwich (2007) addressed the concept of the “dilemmas of difference,” arguing that these can be understood as progressive dilemmas arising from the ways in which disability is perceived and experienced. Education policies and practices are central to addressing such dilemmas; nevertheless, they may remain unstable, often generating new challenges while attempting to resolve the original tensions (Norwich, 2007). Educators are therefore required to adopt a natural variation perspective, fostering a classroom environment that reflects inclusive practice through the normalisation of dysfluency and the promotion of flexible participation grounded in respect and collaboration (Norwich, 2007).

The following section will discuss the theories of stuttering.

3.3.3. Theories of Stuttering

A theory is a framework that synthesises knowledge about a specific area or concept to enhance understanding (Guitar, 2006). In other words, theories systematically integrate previous findings to clarify and make predictions about future outcomes (Guitar, 2006). Understanding stuttering and its contributing factors, including onset, development, and prevalence, helps establish therapeutic approaches (Khebri et al., 2019). Theories encompass various aspects such as brain functioning theories like the system control theory and speech motor control, and theories involving external factors such as the anticipatory struggle theory and the multifactorial struggle.

Historically, stuttering has been observed across many cultures, although its precise causes were not initially understood (Maguire et al., 2020; Chang et al., 2019; Chang et al., 2015; Packman and Attanasio, 2017). Numerous theories have emerged over time to explain stuttering (Guitar, 2006; Büchel and Sommer, 2004). Guitar (2006) categorised these theories in his book "Stuttering: An integrated approach to its nature and treatment", identifying them as constitutional, developmental, and environmental factors. Constitutional factors include the Orton-Travis theory (Orton and Travis, 1931), male-related factors (Geschwind and Galaburda, 1985), anomalous cerebral organisation (Webster, 1993), temporal programming (Kent, 1984), tracking abilities (Megan and Neilson, 1987), covert repair (Lolk and Postma, 1997), dyssynchrony (Perkins, Kent, and Curlee, 1991), and psychological tremor (Smith, 1989). The constitutional theories emphasise biological or neurological vulnerabilities, viewing stuttering as a structural abnormality at the level of the brain (Guitar, 2006). Developmental and environmental factors encompass the diagenetic theory (Johnson et al., 1942), communication failure and anticipatory struggle (Bloodstein, 1987, 1997), and capacities and demands (Andrews et al., 1983). The developmental theories suggest that stuttering is situated within the broader process of language acquisition, particularly in relation to linguistic capacities and communicative demands (Guitar, 2006). Furthermore, the environmental theories highlight the impact of external circumstances, arguing that negative reactions towards children or stressful environments could contribute to the onset of stuttering (Guitar, 2006).

Smith and Weber (2017) clarify that a theory of stuttering is deemed integrative and comprehensive when it encompasses the subsystems of "motor control, auditory integration, language processing, and emotional aspects," along with an understanding of their complexity and temporal fluctuations, including a developmental perspective (p. 2485). Despite the fact that some theories were developed in the early years, some of them continue to be cited and expounded upon in recent literature (e.g., Packman, 2012). Currently, multifactorial models dominate the characterisation of stuttering causes (Packman, 2012). Packman and Attanasio (2017) introduce the P and A theory, which focuses on causal

conditions underlying stuttering. They argue that stuttering may arise from both proximal and other distal causes (Packman and Attanasio, 2017).

The term "proximal" in this context refers to the final connection of the related causes, for instance (Packman et al., 2007), and it is used to describe the triggering conditions (Packman and Attanasio, 2017). For example, the situation the speaker is in may trigger stuttering, as speaking to a child will not trigger stuttering as speaking to someone with authority might. Conversely, the distal cause could be a certain genotype (Packman et al., 2007). It is often used in human disorders to describe the primary condition behind the disorder, such as a biological condition or hereditary bias (Packman and Attanasio, 2017). It is commonly held that neurological disorders related to speech processing are responsible for creating the stutter. Additionally, the language used and the speaker's environment can affect speech fluency (Lieshout et al., 2004).

The produced language might be affected if there are physical anomalies in the parts responsible for speech, such as the larynx and tongue, as they are considered secondary causes of stuttering (Max et al., 2004a). Consequently, in the early years, treatments for stuttering focused on these physical anomalies until Orton and Travis classified stuttering as a brain abnormality in the early 20th century (Maguire et al., 2020).

Before exploring the neurological causes of stuttering, this section will first examine how the brain processes language. Understanding these typical language processing pathways will be crucial when discussing the theories related to potential neurological impairments linked to stuttering.

As many studies have demonstrated, according to Guitar (2006), the left hemisphere is dominant for language in most people, including both normal speakers and brain-damaged patients. Abbott (2016) described this process, stating that regions in the frontal lobe of the brain, particularly Broca's area, are responsible for formulating sentences to convey messages or ideas. Additionally, the motor cortex, located in the frontal lobe, facilitates spoken speech by using the lungs, vocal cords, and mouth to generate sounds (Fedorenko, Ivanova and Regev, 2023). Wernicke's area, located in the posterior part of the superior temporal gyrus, is primarily responsible for language comprehension (Friederici, 2011). It is connected to Broca's area via the arcuate fasciculus, which facilitates the integration of language comprehension and production (Le, Liu, and Liu, 2024). The debate over which hemisphere is primarily responsible for language continues (Abbott, 2016). While language is more likely to occur in the left side of the brain, some people might use both hemispheres, and infrequently, the right side of the brain may have predominant control over language (Abbott, 2016).

The speech act is a motor control task executed in a rapid flow; actions must occur within a few milliseconds for the receiver to understand the communicated message correctly (Ludlow, 2003). Nevertheless, speech disorders can occur for various reasons, such as aphasia, which results from damage to language-processing regions of the brain. In the same vein, recent studies have suggested that cerebellar disorders are associated with a range of motor impairments that can ultimately affect verbal communication (Ackermann and Brendel, 2016). Consequently, some theories that attempt to explain stuttering are related to the functioning of the brain's motor and sensory areas responsible for language production. Unlike some other motor disorders, stuttering is considered a reflection of an intrinsic barrier within the motor speech control system, involving complex motor performance actions accompanied by intellectual, psychological, and speech motor stimuli (Namasivayam and Lieshout, 2011).

Speech motor control theories attempt to account for differences in sensory and sensory-motor skills, hypothesising that stuttering behaviours result from a disturbance between motor speech function and brain hemisphere activation (Forster and Webster, 2001). Packman (2007) explains that the repetition of syllables during the onset of stuttering enables the youngster to control the disruption in speech motor control. More specifically, it is related to anomalies in interhemispheric relations and the speech motor control system, particularly those involving the supplementary motor area (Forster and Webster, 2001).

In the same vein, the system control theory also relates the cause of stuttering to a disorder in brain organisation, specifically one associated with unconscious self-regulating speech motor control (Onslow et al., 2008). This theory suggests that system control modelling affects speech performance when stuttering occurs (Packman and Attanasio, 2004). Studies have identified distinct differences in the brain areas of people who stutter compared to those who do not, particularly in the cortical and subcortical areas. These regions are crucial for motor functions and sensory support functions, significantly affecting the timing and motor control of speech behaviours (Chang et al., 2015).

It is worth noting that limitations in the speech motor control system may become evident when the complexity of activity increases or when there are high demands for correct behaviours and speed. In such situations, the system lacks the capacity to utilise other basic control strategies or maintain the balance of speed and accuracy (Namasivayam et al., 2011).

In contrast to theories that link stuttering to brain abnormalities, the anticipatory struggle theory was developed, describing the cause of stuttering as a learned behaviour (Packman and Attanasio, 2004). The term "anticipatory struggle" is most often associated with Bloodstein, who introduced it in the 1950s (Brocklehurst et al., 2013). This theory posits that the anticipation of the struggle to

communicate impedes the fluency of speech (Brocklehurst et al., 2013). Guitar (2006) explained that Oliver Bloodstein (1987, 1997) developed this theory, suggesting that the anticipation of future speech difficulties, particularly after repeated failures and struggles in childhood, can lead to the onset of stuttering (Guitar, 2006). As a result, individuals who stuttered in childhood often anticipate which words they will stutter on before speaking, which then leads to actual stuttering (Jackson et al., 2015).

The multifactorial struggle theory explains stuttering as a complex developmental disorder, with various studies highlighting a range of individual characteristics and interrelationships among multiple factors such as cognitive, behavioural, and psychological aspects (Smith and Weber, 2017; Walsh et al., 2018). Packman (2012) argued that the multifactorial struggle is most likely the cause of stuttering. He explained this theory from a holistic perspective, suggesting that stuttering onset occurs due to an imbalance between the child's capacities and the demands placed on them. Thus, the demands and capacities models represent two facets of the multifactorial theory (Packman, 2012). According to this theory, when the demand for fluency exceeds the child's capacity to provide it, stuttering results from a combination of innate and external forces (Packman, 2012).

In summary, several theoretical perspectives have been developed to address the underlying issues of stuttering, yet the exact cause remains elusive (Cruz et al., 2018). Stuttering is a fluency disorder characterised by repetitions of syllables and sounds, complete blocks, and involuntary prolongations (Etchell et al., 2018). Although the aetiology of stuttering is not fully understood, emerging data suggest that speech production fluency is influenced by the interplay of epigenetics, genetics, and other environmental factors affecting brain development (Chang et al., 2018). Stuttering is linked to a sensorimotor coordination impairment, affecting speech output fluency (Sares et al., 2019). Therefore, understanding the role of sensory data in the sensory-motor processing of speech is crucial for comprehending speech motor performance and sensorimotor learning in both fluent and dysfluent speakers (Parrell and Houde, 2019).

The neurological basis of stuttering involves abnormalities in cerebellar interactions and speech-motor control brain networks, particularly those involving the supplementary motor area (Forster and Webster, 2001). Stuttering may also result from the anticipatory struggle, as proposed by Bloodstein (1987; 1997), which suggests that individuals anticipate stuttering based on their past experiences with stuttered words. Additionally, it may be a multifactorial struggle, encompassing the demands and capacities model developed by Packman (2012). In essence, a deeper understanding of stuttering behaviours can help us better comprehend long-standing observations and address perplexing issues related to stuttering (Tichenor and Yaruss, 2018).

The following section will review teachers' perceptions and attitudes toward stuttering.

3.3.4. The Impact of Stuttering

A high rate of anxiety, typical stuttering severity, and speech frustration are all common effects of stuttering (Iverach et al., 2017). Stuttering can cause a variety of physical, psychological, and mental reactions, which vary from person to person (Samson et al., 2021). Traumatic interactions related to stuttering are believed to lead to distrust in others' reactions and behaviours, potentially contributing to feelings of low self-esteem over time (Nang et al., 2018). Individuals who experience lower levels of daily anxiety have reported behaviours indicative of improved emotional regulation strategies, as evidenced by parasympathetic nervous system activity (Bauerly and Jones, 2021). Accordingly, this section aims to review the impact of stuttering in general, with specific attention to the severity of the stutter and gender differences. Additionally, this section will explore the impact of stuttering on school-aged children.

Stuttering can impact various aspects of life for those who stutter (Samson et al., 2021). Consequently, several qualitative studies have aimed to explore the experiences of individuals who stutter (e.g., Bricker-Katz et al., 2013; Jackson et al., 2015; Plexico et al., 2010; Tichenor and Yaruss, 2018). Similar studies have focused on the experiences of learners who stutter within educational settings (e.g., Cobb et al., 2019; Tichenor and Yaruss, 2019; Tichenor and Yaruss, 2018; Zamprogno et al., 2020; Ellis and Hartel, 2017). These studies have reported challenges faced by adolescents who stammer, particularly regarding their teachers' and classmates' perceptions and attitudes towards stuttering, which are considered part of their school experiences (Cobb et al., 2019).

In light of these findings, Al-Qaisi et al. (2020) proposed a stuttering training course for primary school teachers to help them better understand stuttering in the classroom. Despite the lack of assessment of the effectiveness of teachers' methods in improving stutterers' self-reactions to their stutter, speech-language therapists can guide teachers with their expertise and knowledge about factors that affect stuttering (Li and Arnold, 2015). Over time, the emotional reactions of many stutterers towards their stutter change, significantly impacting their mental health, social development, and overall life (Samson et al., 2021).

Many studies have attempted to cover the overall effect of stuttering, as this speech impairment is linked to certain psychological factors (e.g., Manning and Beck, 2017; Samson et al., 2021; Nang et al., 2018; Iverach et al., 2017; Boyle, 2013; Beilby, Byrnes, and Yaruss, 2012; Bauerly and Jones, 2021; Manning and Beck, 2013; Brileya et al., 2020; Messenger et al., 2015). These studies were conducted in different countries such as Sweden (Samson et al., 2021) and Western Australia (Beilby, Byrnes, and Yaruss, 2012; Brileya et al., 2020). Additionally, research was carried out at institutions such as the Australian Stuttering Research Centre, the University of Sydney, the School of Human Communication

Sciences at La Trobe University, Melbourne, and the Department of Linguistics at Macquarie University, Sydney (Iverach et al., 2017).

The study by Boyle (2013), for instance, included various nationalities such as African Americans, Asian Americans, Hispanic Americans, white non-Hispanics, and participants who specified "other" for ethnicity (p. 372). Research related to stuttering that investigates the impact of stuttering generally is based on a self-assessment tool called the Overall Assessment of the Speaker's Experience of Stuttering (OASES) (Yaruss and Quesal, 2006). However, the mentioned studies have adopted both qualitative and quantitative approaches to investigate the experiences of individuals who stutter.

Manning and Beck (2017) reported that connections between psychological problems, such as anxiety, social anxiety, depressed mood, and personal traits, are significant indicators in individuals who stutter. Their study found that social and trait anxiety were the only predictive factors of stuttering severity. Moreover, the severity of speech and the frequency of stuttering vary among individuals. Anxiety levels, therefore, have been found to be substantially higher among adolescents who stutter compared to those who do not stutter (Iverach et al., 2017). One aspect of stuttering is its severity; it is presumed that the more severe an individual's stuttering is, the more negative attitudes towards communication they might have (Samson et al., 2021). It is significant to note that the rate of articulation and rhythm of speech are two different aspects of the temporal structure of speech (Bóna and Kohári, 2021).

A study conducted by Constantino et al. (2016) aimed to assess the everyday variability of disfluency percentages among stutterers and non-stutterers during various situations. The study reported that the severity of stuttering varies from day to day in the same person. This inconsistency was not related to any stuttering intensity tests but was related to life effects as calculated by the Overall Assessment of the Speaker's Experience of Stuttering. Among or within the participant group, there was no discernible trend in inconsistency from one day to another. During everyday speaking, there were substantially more instances of non-stuttering disfluency than during reading activities (Constantino et al., 2016).

On the other hand, various factors such as pressure, standards, culture, and beliefs have drawn variations between women and men (Samson et al., 2021). Therefore, the impact of stuttering could vary depending on gender. As reported by Iverach et al. (2017), adolescents who stutter exhibit different mental and behavioural characteristics when comparing females to males; this includes anxiety, depression, introversion, and complaining behaviours. Women tend to share a detailed description of how stuttering has affected their relationships and emotions, and their sense of

belonging to families, peers, significant others, co-workers, and wider cultural groups (Nang et al., 2018).

Samsona et al. (2021) compared the communicative experiences of male and female teenagers who stutter with those who do not in a quantitative study. They reported that teenage females are more likely to be negatively affected by their stuttering than males. Similarly, Byrd et al. (2017) found that the stigma associated with stuttering could affect females more than males, as the women in their study placed a strong emphasis on their social lives. Aligned with this, Byrd et al. (2017) argued that women who stutter tend to experience more negative attitudes from the public than men who stutter. Furthermore, in a report on the relationship between stuttering and anxiety in children and adolescents, young males ranked better on social attraction scales, suggesting that males, unlike females, may mask their true anxiety levels regarding their stuttering (Messenger et al., 2015). However, Samsona et al. (2021) noted that inconsistencies between men's and women's performance, perceptions, demands, and norms might have a cultural basis.

Nang et al. (2018) conducted a qualitative study to explore the issues experienced by women who stutter. They interviewed nine women who stutter, aged between 35 and 80. Participants Patricia, Steffi, and Mabelle reported that they "fear, so much fear every time I talked"; "is impacting me, talking to people in certain situations when I go like 'I better not talk now'"; and "as soon as I would start stuttering they would look down on me, 'uh! Not her' and then turn around and talk to someone else," respectively (Nang et al., 2018, p. 1249). The study concluded that stuttering affects the entire lives of women who stutter and negatively changes the way they see themselves, impacting their relationships, employment, and societal perceptions (Nang et al., 2018). Furthermore, other studies have shown a slight difference in stuttering behaviours, with females generally having more positive responses to their stuttering compared to males (Arnold and Li, 2016; Arnold et al., 2015; Li and Arnold, 2015).

The age of individuals who stutter is one of the aspects that affects how stuttering is viewed and experienced. It is worth mentioning that developmental stuttering occurs during the child's development period, which can lead to emotional and psychological issues related to speech communication (Ludlow, 2003). Teenage adolescence represents a sensitive period for social interaction (Blakemore and Mills, 2014). Previous research has attempted to evaluate at what age children who stutter become aware of their disfluency and begin to experience negative reactions and feelings (Samsona et al., 2021; Clark et al., 2012). Therefore, the age of stutterers can influence their experience of stuttering. Generally, the views of school-aged children and teenagers tend to be

somewhat similar to those of adults; nevertheless, some studies indicate that young children and adults may have conflicting views (Weidner et al., 2016; Weidner et al., 2015; Weidner et al., 2015a).

Butler (2013) conducted a study to highlight the possibility of social exclusion of individuals who stutter, particularly their right to inclusive education. In summary, the terms "tension" and "worry" often occurred as participants discussed their educational life (Butler, 2013, p. 60). These terms were frequently linked with their fear of being asked to talk, and their anxiety interfered with their learning capability (Butler, 2013). Only one of the participants in this study indicated that teachers refused to react to their requests for assistance, and this behaviour created feelings of disappointment and/or irritation (Butler, 2013). These activities had a clear and negative effect on the participants' learning outcomes, academic success, and eventual "ability" to pursue higher education (Butler, 2013).

As compared to nonstuttering adolescents and children, those who stutter showed significantly lower awareness and understanding of their speaking ability, along with more pronounced behavioural and psychological responses to their communicative abilities. They also exhibited a greater impact of the environment on their speech capability and lower overall life quality (Beilby, Byrnes, and Yaruss, 2012). In contrast to their fluent-speaking peers, children tended to develop a negative affective, behavioural, and cognitive response to their stuttering (Beilby, Byrnes, and Yaruss, 2012).

Zamprogno et al. (2020) conducted a study aimed at describing school-aged patients with chronic stuttering and their reported experiences of violence at school. They found that nearly 50% of the stuttering patients had been subjected to bullying, which included incidents such as being given nicknames, being defamed, blamed, physically assaulted, and mocked. The classroom was identified as the most common place where bullying occurred. Reactions to the violence included feelings of sadness, a desire to change schools, and efforts to seek support from friends, teachers/principals, and relatives. Participants in middle school reported experiences of teasing, bullying, and feelings of shame, whereas high school students indicated that their teachers, staff, and peers were more accepting of them and their stuttering. Notably, all participants noted that speech therapy had improved their ability to participate in class (Cobb et al., 2019).

Ellis and Hartlep (2017) conducted a study focusing on African American adult males who stutter in educational settings. The study aimed to capture the voices, stories, and experiences of these men. According to their findings, stuttering had a profound impact on the development of African American males, particularly within educational contexts. It significantly affected their self-identity and career options (Ellis and Hartlep, 2017).

In conclusion, the impact of stuttering was discussed based on the age, gender, and severity of the stutter among individuals. To comprehend stuttering and its variations among individuals, it is essential to appreciate the diversity of their experiences with the condition (Tichenor and Yaruss, 2019). Therefore, understanding the relationship between teachers and children who stutter is crucial. The teacher-student relationship can be positive when the child experiences less victimization (Berchiatti et al., 2021). Besides managing classroom social dynamics effectively, teachers should also serve as attachment figures, which is significant for the child's developmental process (Schwab and Rossmann, 2020). Thus, this research aims to investigate how teachers in Algeria respond to children who stutter and their understanding of this speech disorder. Sharing concerns about stuttering with others can help both children who stutter and their peers to reduce the social stigma associated with the condition. Input from parents, teachers, and collaborating speech-language therapists is crucial in this regard.

The following chapter delves deeper into the impact of stuttering on children from the theoretical standpoint of stigma introduced by Erving Goffman (1963). This perspective also examines the attitudes of teachers and mothers towards stuttering and children who stutter, highlighting both positive and negative attitudes as documented in the literature and interpreted through Goffman's framework of stigma.

4. Chapter Four: Stigma and Stuttering

The previous chapter reviewed the concept of communication and communication disorders, laying the groundwork for a deeper understanding of stuttering. However, since this study primarily focuses on children who stutter and their interactions with stakeholders, it explores stakeholders' knowledge and perceptions guided by the theory of stigma proposed by Erving Goffman (1963).

The theory of stigma is linked to the potential for individuals to face severe rejection or even social exclusion, resulting in what Goffman (1963) defined as "The everyday presentation of a discredited self". In this context, 'discredited' refers to a visible or known stigma, much like stuttering becomes evident when individuals who stutter speak. Despite the negative experiences associated with stuttering (Boyle, 2017), it is crucial to examine how individuals who stutter are perceived in Algeria by the group of participants selected for this study. Individuals' behaviour is influenced by their self-concept (Herbert, 1986), highlighting the importance of societal support for children who stutter. Therefore, the theory of stigma employed in this study provides a robust conceptual framework aligned with the research questions and objectives. Before delving into the theory of stigma, it is essential to introduce in this chapter Erving Goffman, the American sociologist who pioneered this theory, and to review how other scholars have engaged with his work on stigma. Furthermore, this chapter explores the theory of stigma in depth, clarifying the literal meaning of the term 'stigma' as well. Subsequently, the chapter reviews the relationship between stigma and stuttering, and how this connection is applied within the context of this study. Finally, the chapter will discuss the mothers and teacher perceptions regarding stuttering.

4.1. Erving Goffman

Erving Goffman, born in Mannville, Alberta, Canada, in 1922, was the son of Ukrainian Jewish immigrants (Henry, 2016). He held the Benjamin Franklin Professorship of Anthropology and Sociology at the University of Pennsylvania (Goffman, 1967). Goffman is widely revered as one of the most influential American sociologists of the 20th century (Fine and Manning, 2018), prominent for his groundbreaking theories on social interaction and symbolic interactionism (Manning, 1992). His academic journey began at the University of Toronto, where he earned his Bachelor's degree, followed by advanced studies at the University of Chicago, culminating in his Masters and doctoral degrees (Goffman, 1967).

Critical to Goffman's intellectual legacy was his preference for anonymity, a stance that reflected his deep focus on observing social behaviour without personal interference (Shalin, 2013). His theoretical framework drew from a diverse array of sociological thinkers such as Simmel, Durkheim, and Blumer,

synthesizing their ideas into his own unique perspective (Fine and Manning, 2018). Moreover, his works profoundly influenced a generation of scholars who could be considered his disciples, including Harvey Sacks, John Lofland, Emmanuel Schegloff, Eviatar Zerubavel, Carol Brooks Gardner, Marjorie Goodwin, Charles Goodwin, David Sudnow, and Gary Marx (Fine and Manning, 2018).

Goffman's contributions are characterised by his examination of key social themes, often challenging conventional approaches (Fine and Manning, 2018). The Goffman Archives represent a significant investigation that blurs the lines between subject and object in sociological study, offering a fresh perspective in the field (Shalin, 2013). Among his notable works are *'The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life'*, *'Asylums'* and *'Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity'* (Goffman, 1967). Goffman employed three metaphors (drama, ritual, and game) to elucidate the dynamics of community and interaction (Henry, 2016). In his book "The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life," Goffman explores how individuals present themselves in social interactions, using the metaphor of a theatrical performance to visualize his ideas (Goffman, 1959). *'Asylums'* was an analysis work published first in 1961 and conducted by Erving Goffman at St. Elizabeths Hospital in Washington, D.C. in 1955-56. The work was divided into four essays focusing on the social environment of individuals with mental illness and their subjective experiences within the hospital setting. Goffman employed three metaphors (drama, ritual, and game) to elucidate the dynamics of community and interaction (Henry, 2016). Moreover, *'Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity'* is a concise and important book published in 1963, particularly noteworthy for its exploration of the author's personal concerns regarding stigma. This book focuses on the significant social and psychological impacts of stigma, highlighting how societal reactions influence the experiences and self-perception of those who are stigmatised.

Erving Goffman remains a seminal figure in sociology whose insights into face-to-face interaction have a profound impact on modern sociology (Manning, 1992). A critical examination of his work, *Stigma* for instance, prompts ongoing discussions about the scope and boundaries of sociological inquiry (Hannem and Bruckert, 2012). This has been reflected in current research, where the ideas he introduced regarding stigma have served as valuable conceptual tools for understanding the attitudes of Algerian stakeholders towards children who stutter. Hence, the following section discusses Goffman's theory of stigma in-depth and explains how it is associated with social attitudes towards individuals who stutter.

4.2. Understanding Stigma

Before delving into the theory of stigma, it is essential to define the meaning of the word 'stigma'. The Greeks, renowned for their visual symbolism, originally coined the term 'stigma' to describe bodily

signs that revealed something unusual and undesirable about the moral status of the bearer (Goffman, 1968). The word 'stigma' originates from the practice of tattooing with a pointed instrument called a 'Stig', which eventually evolved to connote a mark or badge of disgrace (Link and Stuart, 2017). Before Erving Goffman's seminal work 'Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity', the term 'stigma' was used in the social sciences with a similar meaning to its contemporary usage, and it was less prevalent than today (Link and Stuart, 2017). On the other hand, in sociology dictionaries, the term 'stigma' aligns with sociologists' definition. It refers to a social phenomenon where individuals who are seen as different face rejection from society because of that difference (Goffman 1963). The theory of stigma describes how individuals are perceived as deficient, risky, or deserving of hostility based on certain attributes (Davis, 2016).

Stigma is defined as a negative attribute, a discrediting characteristic that can lead to discrimination. Goffman (1963) defined social stigma as a '*mark*' that identifies a person's status within a particular category or set of perceived attributes that are socially stigmatized (p. 5). Individuals generally dislike being labelled in ways perceived as hindering or unpleasant. They prefer to highlight their similarities to others rather than their differences, and their abilities rather than their limitations (Shakespeare, 2018). In the context of mental disorders for instance, stigma engenders fear of an uncertain future, social isolation, and misconceptions arising from inadequate understanding of mental illnesses (Santos et al., 2016). Accordingly, numerous studies have applied Goffman's theories (e.g., Manning, 2011; Ritzer, 2008; Rampton and Eley, 2018; Freidson, 1983; Henry, 2016; Shalin, 2013), including doctoral theses (e.g. Lockenvitz, 2016). Goffman argued in his seminal work on stigma that it is "an attribute that is deeply discrediting," which diminishes an individual in the eyes of others "from a whole and usual person to a tainted, discounted one" (1963, p. 3). In essence, an attribute that stigmatizes one person may affirm the normality of another, thus stigma is not inherently truthful or false but rather socially constructed (Goffman, 1968).

Goffman's theory of stigma revolves around attributes that fundamentally devalue individuals, although he stressed the importance of linguistic interactions over fixed attributes (Goffman, 1968). His interest in individuals subjected to stigma, initially explored in his 1952 paper "On Cooling the Mark Out: Some Aspects of Failure," drew insights from professionals who managed deceptive situations to help victims reclaim their reputation (Shalin, 2013). Goffman astutely observed, "Cooling the mark out is one aspect of a much larger social process," (1952, p. 453). He noted that excessive hostility from the 'marks' (those deceived) could be detrimental to business interests, prompting efforts to manage their reactions and "cool them out" (1952, p. 452).

According to Goffman (1968), typical responses towards individuals with stigmas, as well as the behaviours engaged in as a result, are widely recognised. These responses constitute sympathetic public actions aimed at smoothing over and ameliorating the stigma (Goffman, 1968). When a new person joins a group, initial impressions enable the group to infer their social standing and characteristics of their '*social identity*', a term encompassing individual traits like '*integrity*' alongside organizational ones such as '*occupation*' (Goffman, 1968, p. 2). Stigmatized individuals may indirectly attempt to improve their situation by dedicating extra effort to excel in areas typically perceived as hindered by their perceived deficiencies, both unintended and structural (Goffman, 1968). This could be translated as a number of attitudes, such as a plastic surgery that aim to correct a physical deformity.

Many researchers have explored Goffman's work on stigma, particularly within psychology and social psychology, where the study of prejudice and stigma overlap significantly since Goffman's delineation of different types of stigmas (Arjan et al., 2013; Corrigan, 2004; Link and Phelan, 2001). Stigma, as commonly understood today, extends beyond a physical marker (Arjan et al., 2013), to encompass a spoiled social identity as referred to by Goffman (1963). Individuals may experience stigma intentionally or inadvertently through the actions or remarks of authorities such as judges, law enforcement officers, colleagues at work, family members, acquaintances, neighbours, or strangers (Page, 1984). Consequently, the threat to social identity arises from the fear of being stigmatized, which can have detrimental effects even in the absence of objective discrimination or prejudice from others (Major et al., 2017).

Moreover, individuals with greater authority may stigmatize those with less authority to maintain social inequalities (Arjan et al., 2013). Additionally, reinforcing social norms plays a role, as the prospect of stigma encourages individuals to conform to societal expectations, thereby preventing deviance (Arjan et al., 2013). 'Imposters', 'wannabes', and individuals who navigate life with challenging experiences are particularly concerned with concealing any stigmatizing information that could result in a loss of social status and profound embarrassment (Shalin, 2013, p. 12). However, as noted by Shalin (2013), Goffman's approach to understanding stigma remains distinctive and influential in its depth and insight.

Non-stigmatized and stigmatized individuals exhibit markedly different behaviours in similar circumstances, largely influenced by cultural perceptions (Major and O'Brien, 2005). Conditions such as being overweight, facial deformities, mental disorders, or addiction are not universally identified as stigmatized markers, but efforts by organisations like the National Association to Advance Fat Acceptance and the National Alliance on Mental Illness seek to challenge such perceptions (Major et

al., 2017). According to Major et al. (2017), one of the most prevalent findings in stigma and well-being research is the negative impact on both social exclusion and health outcomes; individuals frequently report experiences of prejudice that worsen their physical and emotional health. Social exclusion profoundly affects the identity, mental health, and overall well-being of stigmatized individuals by limiting their access to essential life domains (Major and O'Brien, 2005). In summary, it is essential to acknowledge that stigma is articulated through individual interactions and is also entrenched in the cultural norms, practices, and institutional frameworks of society (Hannem and Bruckert, 2012).

The following section explores the concepts of stigma and its various types as outlined by Goffman in his book.

4.3. Types of Stigmas

In the first chapter of Goffman's work on stigma, entitled 'Stigma and Social Identity', discusses the social construction of stigma, which will be a primary focus of this research. While the other chapters will not be neglected, the first chapter introduces key concepts that explain how society forms assumptions about individuals during social interactions, particularly during initial meetings. Goffman presents a number of ideas that shed light on how these assumptions are constructed and the impact they have on individuals' social identities.

In the first chapter, Goffman introduced the concept of 'preliminary conception' (pp. 11-31) discussing the types of stigmas, we consider both the types of attributes that can be stigmatized and the corresponding stigmatizing attitudes. In his work on stigma, Goffman highlights three fundamental types of stigmas related to attributes and four types of stigmatizing attitudes. Goffman categorises them based on attributes such as bodily deformities, character flaws, and ethnic stigma (1963). Firstly, there are bodily deformities or abnormalities that visibly mark the person as different (Goffman, 1963). Secondly, there are character flaws such as perceived undesirable traits, abnormal emotions, rigid beliefs, or dishonesty, which historically have been associated with conditions like mental illness, incarceration, addiction, homosexuality, unemployment, attempted suicide, or extreme political views (Goffman, 1963). Lastly, there is ethnic stigma based on factors like culture, nationality, or religion, which can persist across generations and affect other family members similarly (Goffman, 1963).

Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that some of these attributes can be visible, while others may not be, which can directly affect the individual's social identity and social interaction, leading to stigmatizing attitudes. Goffman introduced the concepts of '*Virtual Social Identity*' and '*Actual Social Identity*' to explain how society categorizes individuals (1963, p. 12). Goffman argued that during initial social encounters, we tend to develop certain assumptions about individuals (1963). The virtual social

identity refers to the expectations and stereotypes associated with an individual based on their perceived attributes. On the other hand, the actual social identity is the individual's true identity, which may clash with societal expectations, leading to stigma.

Figure 6 Construction of the Stigma and Social Identity by Society

The above Figure 6 demonstrates the social construction of stigma, highlighting the preliminary conceptions that determine and explain how stigma and social identity are formed. These preliminary conceptions are divided into virtual social identity and actual social identity, which often clash, creating discrepancies during and after social interactions. Identities are built based on individual attributes or stigmas, which can be either visible (discredited) or not immediately visible (discreditable). These attributes can be either observable stigmas or hidden stigmas, depending on their characteristics.

Furthermore, Goffman's work of stigma (1963) discusses broader concepts that introduce the four types of stigmas that reflect the social interaction and individual's social management of spoiled identity. Some researchers have classified these types as public stigma, structural, courtesy stigma, and self-stigma (Pryor and Reeder, 2011). These are discussed by Goffman as Stigma and Social Interaction, Public Perception and Reaction, courtesy stigma, Internalization of Stigma, respectively (1963).

Figure 7 The four types of stigma and the relationship between them (Adapted from Pryor and Reeder 2011)

As demonstrated in Figure 7 there are types of stigmas that some of them affect or create other types of stigmas. However, the public stigma has a central effect on other types (Gaebel, Rössler, and Sartorius, 2017). Social or public stigma refers to the perception of injustice by others (Gray, 2002). It occurs when society harbours prejudice and engages in discrimination against individuals diagnosed with a particular illness (Major et al., 2017). Goffman has argued how this type of stigma arises in society, as explained in the first chapter discussing the preliminary conceptions (1963). This type originates from people's assumptions of those associated with stigmatized conditions (Arjan et al., 2013). It pertains to the attitudes and behaviours of community members towards stigmatized individuals (Boyle, 2018). Accordingly, this research focuses more on public stigma investigating the public attitudes towards stuttering and individuals who stutter in Algeria. This type of stigma could significantly influence the policies and practices of institutions in the society creating another type of stigma known as Structural stigma. Hence, it occurs when regulations and practices in public and private sector institutions intentionally or inadvertently restrict opportunities for individuals with disabilities (Angermeyer et al., 2014; Corrigan and Miller, 2004). Policies implemented by these sectors can unintentionally constrain opportunities for marginalized groups (Link and Stuart, 2017), which could be translated as a reaction to the public stigma.

Furthermore, courtesy stigma, also known as stigma by association, affects individuals who are closely associated with stigmatized communities (such as mental health care workers, acquaintances, and relatives) (Link and Stuart, 2017). Goffman explained how the stigma affects both the stigmatized and the 'normal' (1963, p 44). It extends beyond individuals with disabilities to include their relatives, who also experience stigma (Ostman and Kjellin, 2002; Corrigan and Miller, 2004). Goffman introduced the term courtesy stigma to describe the discrimination and prejudice faced by people associated with

stigmatized individuals (1963). Understanding how this stigma impacts relatives is crucial for comprehending their role in supporting the mental well-being and psychiatric treatment of individuals with disabilities (Ostman and Kjellin, 2002).

Moreover, self-stigma, also known as internalised stigma, occurs when individuals with mental illnesses internalise societal prejudices; they recognise public stigma and incorporate these stigmas into their own subconscious (Muñoz et al., 2011). In other words, it represents the internalised emotional response to public stigma, where individuals adopt and reflect societal stigmatising attitudes towards themselves (Bathje and Pryor, 2011). This provokes psychological impact due to the possession of a stigmatising attribute which individuals internalise (Bathje and Pryor, 2011). Accordingly, self-stigma involves integrating negative stereotypes within oneself, which individuals experiencing stigma may internalise over time. Research has shown that self-stigma is associated with a diminished quality of life (Rüsch et al., 2014) and tends to persist over extended periods (Lysaker et al., 2012).

It is important to note that self-stigma differs from felt stigma, which involves anticipating future stigmatising situations (Boyle, 2018). According to Major and O'Brien (2005), individuals vary in their susceptibility to experiencing stigma persistently. Self-stigma can develop as individuals with stigmatized conditions become deeply aware of societal devaluation associated with their condition (Major and O'Brien, 2005). Felt stigma can be as detrimental as enacted stigma, leading individuals to withdraw and limit seeking help (Gray, 2002).

Among various stigmatized conditions, mental disorders have received significant attention and study (Link and Stuart, 2017). Despite numerous efforts to reduce stigma and discrimination against people with mental disorders, the issue persists as a serious challenge (Jacobsson et al., 2017). The understanding of mental disorder stigma has advanced considerably since Goffman's initial categorisation (Link and Stuart, 2017). It involves the stigmatization and rejection of individuals with mental illnesses based on misconceptions and stereotypes, rather than their actual personal characteristics and experiences (Santos et al., 2016). Over time, conditions in mental health facilities have evolved (Shalin, 2013), yet as Goffman noted, 'the mental patient status still carries a significant stigma' (1957, p. 172). Santos et al. (2016) illustrated how analysis of respondents' discourse reveals culturally constructed stigma ingrained in societal attitudes towards mental illness (Shalin, 2013). That being said, numerous studies on stuttering and communication disorders have utilized stigma theory to illustrate the challenges individuals who stutter face, as well as the social attitudes towards them and their stuttering. Therefore, the next section will explore the relationship between stigma and stuttering.

4.4. A Critical perspective of the theory of stigma

Goffman's work served as a conceptual framework in this study, although it is often referred to as a theory in academic literature. It serves as a valuable source of inspiration, particularly within the context of sociology; thus, could help in understanding the attitudes of Algerian stakeholders toward children who stutter. In his book, Goffman introduces key concepts and ideas that explain how stigma is experienced by individuals within society, shaping their self-identity. Further, Goffman's work has influenced not only sociology but also other fields, such as psychology. Although it has been a guiding framework for many researchers, it is also important to recognise the limitations it presents. In this regard researchers argued that the traditional stigma primarily focused on the micro level of interactions of individuals as this was driven from a symbolic interactionism perspective (Tyler, 2018). Hence, it focuses more on individual-level approaches grounded in social cognition (Parker and Aggleton, 2003). It is important to note that many criticisms of stigma theory come from mental health research (see Kleinman and Hall-Clifford, 2009), which often points out its limitations in dealing with structural inequality, institutional stigma, and the influence of medical systems. Many scholars have criticised its overemphasis on the individual management of the spoiled identity, neglecting the social factors (Tyler and Slater, 2018). Alongside this, the theory has been criticised for its limited attention to intersectionality and multiples stigma, as well as its inadequate social resistance against stigma. Although these critiques are important to be considered, they may not fully apply to the educational and communication setting of stuttering. Goffman's focus on social interaction is still very useful to the current study, however, some of these concerns did appear during the data analysis and were highlighted in the general discussion section. Accordingly, this section critically discusses the limitation of stigma theory and assesses its relevance to this research.

To begin with, many researchers argued that the traditional stigma has focused on the micro level of stigma (Link and Phelan, 2001; Major and O'Brien, 2012; Phelan, Link and Dovidio, 2013; Aranda et al., 2023). Meaning that the focus was mainly on how the individual cope and manage their interactions with society, while the aspect of social and cultural conditions was neglected (Parker and Aggleton, 2003). Given, Goffman's argument on how individuals should cope was reported in many ideas such as passing, covering or information control (1963) this reflected negatively on stigma theory as the focus was too much on individual "management" of stigma. This could put a lot of pressure on individuals with disability to overcome the stigma and put a huge burden on them mainly. In the context of the present study this limitation could be reflected on the way Algerian society views stuttering and individuals who stutter. Goffman's theory could reflect the student's adaptation of the stigma, and their management of the social behaviour of their surroundings, which plays a significant

role in either reinforcing or resisting the stigma. To put it differently, it is seen as an individual responsibility to overcome the stutter and the stigma that follows it.

Knowing that many researchers have reported that the social environment might not fully accommodate the need of children who stutter, Campbell and Deacon (2006), argued further that stigma is more than an internalised feeling of stigma yet it is an act that is socially shaped and persisted because of social structures, therefore the individual efforts are not enough to overcome the stigma. While early stigma theory has been critiqued for its individualist orientation, this study draws on more sociologically grounded developments of the theory that emphasize the relational, structural, and cultural dimensions of stigma. Thus, despite this limitation, the theory plays an important role examining the perspectives of parents, teachers, and speech therapists, as it helps understand the stigma within the broader social context that shapes students' everyday experiences. To this end, Kleinman and Hall-Clifford (2009) did not criticise the theory itself, but rather how scholars have applied it, sometimes overlooking the cultural and structural contexts in which the stigma occurs, by focusing more on individual experience.

It is also essential to recognise that stigma is not always disempowering as discussed in Goffman's work. In some cases, it can become a source of resistance and encouragement, particularly when individuals and communities have access to external resources and social support. The stigmatised individuals could be a source of strength, standing together to raise sensitivity among people and develop a sense of solidarity with them, helping them challenge negative representations. According to Tylet and Slater (2018) reducing stigma could be achieved by educating the public and schools about the stigmatising condition, yet systems and policies that provoke the stigma should not be ignored. In the same vein, an emphasis was directed toward Goffman's insufficient focus on addressing how society and political institutions reinforce exclusion (Parker and Aggleton, 2003). In the context of this study, children who stutter are not viewed as passive individuals who are socially silenced of stigma; rather, they may actively resist negative labelling and manage social interaction in ways that reshape the attitudes of their social environment. Similarly, Link and Phelan (2001) argued that the stigma is not about individual interactions, yet it involves a larger system of power, discrimination and inequality.

Although Goffman's (1963) work primarily focuses on the individual management of stigma in social interactions, it has been criticised for overlooking the broader structural, social, and political dimensions that persist stigma (Parker and Aggleton, 2003). Nevertheless, his theory remains highly influential and continues to provide a useful framework for investigating social stigma. It helps identify public attitudes, institutional barriers, and the mechanisms through which marginalised groups are

excluded. As a result, many researchers have built on Goffman's foundation to explore stigma at both individual and social levels and to reduce and mitigate stigma (Hatzenbuehler and Link, 2014; Scambler, 2004).

In conclusion, while Goffman's work remains a foundational contribution to stigma studies, its limitations must be acknowledged, particularly in light of contemporary concerns around structural inequality, intersectionality, cultural specificity, resistance, and power. Such critical perspectives are essential.

4.5. Labelling theory

Children with disabilities are identified primarily by their impairments (Demetriou, 2022; Boyle 2013), even within inclusive educational environments (Lauchlan and Boyle; 2020). The categorisation of people has been known for decades due to the bureaucratic system and continued to become labels assigned to individuals based on certain attributes (Boyle, 2013). Therefore, the concept of labelling was deemed relevant and considered within the framework of this study. Labelling individuals who are stigmatised can have a significant impact on their lives (Goffman, 1963), which could be either beneficial or harmful. Yet, before delving into the impact of labels on children with disabilities, it is important to provide first a brief overview of labelling theory.

The theory of labelling was shaped by the scholar Howard Becker in 1963 in his work *Outsiders* (Becker, 1963). In common with Goffman, Becker was also a prominent American sociologist and a key figure in symbolic interactionism (Blumer, 1969). In his work "*Outsiders*", Becker illustrates how labelling can lead individuals to being perceived as deviant (Becker, 1963). His theory explains how society uses labels to shape individuals' identities and behaviours. Such labels can influence not only individuals' self-concept but also how others interact with them (Goffman, 1963).

Prior to this, a key contribution to what is known as labelling theory was discussed by the scholar Lemert in 1951, in which he identified two main concepts, which are primary and secondary deviance, that describe the development of labelling. The Primary deviance is associated with the initial act that led the individual to being labelled, which could be overlooked or dismissed over time.

Nevertheless, internalising the labels can lead to a secondary deviance, where it becomes a part of the individual's identity and starts to affect their behaviours (Becker, 1963). This idea led to the concept of self-fulfilling prophecy that describes how social perceptions and labelling could unintentionally shape the behaviours of the stigmatised individuals (Rosenthal and Jacobson, 1968). Accordingly, individuals may start to act based on the labels they have been assigned to, believing that these labels represent their identity (Rosenthal and Jacobson, 1968).

The latter demonstrates how stigma can affect the individual's sense of self and how society perceives them (Goffman, 1963). Ultimately, labelling could have a serious consequence not only on their psychological well-being, yet it could affect their integration with society, limiting individuals' opportunities to fully participate in society (Goffman, 1963; Becker, 1963). This is not a result of the stigmatisation per se, yet the social categorisation based on certain traits and attributes, and the way others react to this categorisation.

In the context of this research, such labelling may affect teachers' knowledge and attitudes towards students with disabilities, potentially leading to further stigmatisation (Caslin, 2021). This idea is reinforced by a number of studies that investigate the effect of labelling on individuals with disabilities. The medical model uses categories and labels to individuals with disabilities; however, some researchers and specialists have questioned its benefits (Florian et al., 2006), because of the stigma that may follow this categorisation (Tomlinson, 2012). This could occur when the focus is on the disability itself and its limitations, rather than shifting attention to the individual's needs (Demetriou, 2022).

Nevertheless, Graham (2020) pointed out that in inclusive education, labels are used to develop a shared understanding. Furthermore, Lauchlan and Boyle argued that labelling can be used to provide a better understanding of the needs of children with disabilities, avoiding stigmatisation (2020). The educational legislation in some countries requires labelling students with disabilities to protect them from being excluded or marginalised and to ensure their right to access different support services (Demetriou, 2022).

This is to be investigated in the current research, the data could provide an understanding of how labelling is perceived in Algerian society and whether it is used in schools and how this could affect the student and help the teachers. According to Boyle (2014) the act of labelling from a sociological perspective could be harmful to individuals with disabilities. However, in educational settings, the use of labelling can be beneficial to students, as it enables them to access additional support services (Boyle, 2014). Still, the idea of labelling seems to be helpful in the educational setting, however, many critiques have been addressed to it proposing other alternatives such as Universal Design Learning (UDL) that allows students with different needs to be integrated without the need to be labelled or categorised. This could be done by offering multiple learning methods during the lecture allowing everyone to engage with it and reach the targeted understanding (See Al-Azawei, Serenelli, and Lundqvist, 2016). Accordingly, the use of labels in Algerian educational settings will be discussed in the following chapters.

4.6. Stigma and Stuttering

Goffman's seminal work on stigma (1963) is widely regarded as a foundational source for understanding stigma (Boyle, 2018). The expanding body of research on stigma encompasses various aspects of language proficiency, communication disorders, and sensory processing disorders (Lockenvitz, 2016). Stuttering, as a fluency disorder, can lead to stigmatisation among children who stutter (Boyle, 2015). This stigma may cause individuals with a stutter, for example, to anticipate negative reactions from society (i.e., felt stigma), resulting in fear, anxiety, and social isolation (Boyle, 2018). Therefore, the theory of stigma provides a suitable framework for addressing the objectives of the current study.

Numerous qualitative research studies have demonstrated that individuals who stutter often anticipate and worry about being harshly judged by others due to their stutter (Boyle, 2018). Similarly, children who stutter anticipate judgment in school environments (Butler, 2013), which will be explored in the research based on the participants' data. Therefore, the knowledge of individuals constructs a social world of close relationships, engaging in direct or indirect interactions, whether in person or through media (Goffman, 1969). It is important to note that despite the common social practice of exchanging language and gestures between individuals, the intricacies of these communications can be challenging to discern (Goffman, 1963).

Bessai argued that despite numerous legal requirements ensuring the right to education for all children without segregation in Algeria (2018), there appears to be a significant gap in the provision of services for children with disabilities (Bessai, 2018). This study aims to investigate whether children who stutter experience segregation and stigma in Algerian schools. The extent of stigma experienced can vary depending on the visibility of the stigmatized attributes (Goffman, 1963).

Once children who stutter struggle to speak, their stuttering becomes noticeable. Hence, the stigmatisation of stuttering happens throughout their speech (Van Riper, 1987). Alongside, people who stutter think that they will be seen as '*mentally defective*,' '*weird*,' '*not good enough*,' '*a fool*,' '*incompetent*,' '*freak of nature*,' '*not a full person*,' '*mentally retarded*,' '*inferior*,' '*socially crippled*,' '*not normal*,' '*an imbecile*,' '*an idiot*,' or '*crazy*' by somebody else (Boyle, 2012). This issue has not only been discussed in studies but also illustrated in movies based on real stories, which demonstrate the struggles individuals who stutter face, regardless of their position of power. A notable example is the movie '*The King's Speech*.' Being worried about negative judgement may encourage individuals who stutter to minimize talking or avoiding social events (Boyle, 2018).

Many individuals who stutter have reported experiencing bullying during their school years and adolescence (Erickson and Block, 2013). These experiences can have lasting effects that persist into

adulthood (Blood and Blood, 2016; Daniels et al., 2012). While most adults who stutter are aware of the societal stigma associated with stuttering, the Self-Stigma of Stuttering Scale used in this research did not specifically assess their apprehension, stress, or fear of potential stigmatizing situations such as rejection or devaluation (Boyle, 2013; Boyle, 2015). This suggests that future research on discrimination and bullying faced by people who stutter needs to consider enacted stigma as a significant outcome (Boyle, 2018).

Many studies have been conducted to explore attitudes towards stuttering and people who stutter (e.g., Girli et al., 2016; Healey, 2010; Valente et al., 2017; St Louis et al., 2011; St. Louis and Lass, 1981; St. Louis et al., 2009; St. Louis et al., 2016; El-Adawy et al., 2020; Al-Shdifat et al., 2018; Al-Shdifat et al., 2013; Özdemir et al., 2011). These studies have contributed significantly to understanding public attitudes towards individuals who stutter, facilitating the analysis of stigmatisation through observable attitudes, behaviours, and reactions. Similarly, in this study, the theory of stigma guides the analysis of interview responses concerning the perceptions and attitudes of speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers in Algeria.

Arnolda and Lib (2016) conducted a study to investigate whether attitudes towards individuals who stutter influence intentional reactions and emotional responses across a diverse group of people. This study accounted for experience with individuals who stutter as well as demographic characteristics such as age, education, and gender. The results illustrated that the accuracy of individuals' perceptions regarding people who stutter strongly predicted their planned behaviours and emotional responses towards them, even when considering demographic factors, knowledge, and understanding. Additionally, gender and experience with people who stutter were significant factors influencing individuals' responses.

Boyle (2017) conducted a pioneering study that collected both statistical and descriptive data on individual perceptions and social attitudes towards stuttering. The study aimed to identify themes related to the conception of anti-stigma programmes for stuttering. Numerous respondents showed optimistic personal opinions of people who stutter, recognising their cleverness, competence, and ability to achieve. However, societal perceptions were more negative, with a significant proportion of respondents indicating hesitation to engage in conversation with people who stutter. The community also tended to advise stutterers to avoid tasks requiring extensive speaking or public speaking. The findings highlighted that people who stutter are often perceived as less competent or emotionally stable by others, according to a small number of study participants. These results offer valuable insights for speech therapists aiming to shift societal perceptions of individuals with speech disorders. Similar studies on stigmatised conditions provide additional data that speech therapists can use to

develop strategies for reducing stigma and improving the social integration of people with speech disorders (Boyle, 2017).

Another study by Boyle (2013) aimed at comparing individuals who stutter with and without support group experience, focusing on differences in confidence, quality of life, anticipated severity of stuttering, self-stigma, perceived cause and expected course of stuttering, as well as the significance of fluency. The results showed that individuals involved in support groups experienced a reduced internal feeling of stigmatisation compared to those not involved in such groups. They were more likely to believe that they would stutter throughout their lives and were less inclined to consider speaking fluency as extremely or highly significant in their interactions with others. Moreover, those who participated in support groups reported higher levels of confidence, overall happiness, and reduced internal stigmatisation and perceived stuttering severity compared to those who had never participated in such services. Interestingly, when comparing the average of standardised criteria to individuals who do not stutter, those who attended support groups exhibited similar levels of confidence, higher self-efficacy, and lower levels of depression. This study underscores the positive impact of support groups on individuals who stutter, suggesting that such groups can significantly enhance their quality of life, reduce self-stigma, and improve their overall mental health and social interactions (Boyle, 2013).

In conclusion, public perceptions of stuttering vary significantly across different countries and cultures (El-Adawy et al., 2020). It is undeniable that stigmatised individuals suffer disruptions in social identity and face constraints in achieving their life goals due to limited opportunities in social, intellectual, and professional spheres (Boyle, 2017). Regarding speech disorders, increased tension, despair, and a lower quality of life, confidence, and efficiency have been linked to individuals who stutter due to their awareness and internalisation of negative reactions towards stuttering (Boyle, 2015). For speech-language therapists, academics, and counsellors, a thorough understanding of societal perceptions around stuttering is crucial. This knowledge can be used to develop targeted anti-stigma strategies aimed at altering social perceptions (Boyle, 2017). Therefore, the current research will involve interviews with speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter and teachers, to investigate their perceptions regarding stuttering and their attitudes towards children who stutter. Therefore, the following two sections provide an overview of the literature that focused on teachers' and parents' perceptions regarding stuttering separately.

4.7. Teachers' Perceptions and Attitudes Toward Stuttering

Stuttering is a widespread speech disorder characterised by involuntary interruptions to the speaking process, significantly impacting communication and social participation throughout life (Iverach et al.,

2018). Most stuttering cases are not directly associated with brain damage or any discernible deficits affecting cognitive, linguistic, or psychiatric functions (Chang et al., 2018). However, genetic factors can play a role in the onset of stuttering (Domingues and Drayna, 2017). While most children learn to speak effortlessly, about 5% begin to stutter between the ages of 2 and 6 for reasons that are not entirely understood (Jiang et al., 2012). This age range is crucial for a child's developmental learning. Consequently, teachers hold a significant responsibility to ensure a positive school experience and successful educational attainment for these children. Therefore, this section reviews studies that investigate teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards children who stutter.

Studies have shown that teachers are not always confident in supporting their students' needs (Adriaensens and Struyf, 2016). Aghaz et al. (2021) conducted a study indicating that teachers who have previously taught children who stutter or have substantial knowledge about stuttering are more likely to develop positive attitudes towards it. Before experiencing difficulties with speech, children often anticipate being judged on their errors and expect to encounter negative attitudes from their teachers (Silva et al., 2016). Children who stutter endure negative experiences due to their stuttering during both childhood and adolescence (Davidow et al., 2016). These emotional and social consequences of stuttering can significantly impact their educational attainment (Davidow et al., 2016).

In this regard, numerous studies have been conducted internationally to investigate teachers' attitudes and knowledge towards stuttering. Research in various countries includes Irani et al. (2012), Abdalla and St. Louis (2012, 2014) in Kuwait, Arnold and Goltl (2015) and Li and Arnold (2015) in the United States, Abrahams et al. (2016) in South African schools, Adriaensens and Struyf (2016) in Flanders, Belgium, Aghaz et al. (2021) in Tehran, Iran, Al-Qaisi and Ali (2020) and Al-Qaisi et al. (2020) in Baghdad, Hearne et al. (2021) in New Zealand, Katebe (2020) in Zambia, and St. Louis et al. (2018) in Poland. These studies have reviewed and discussed teachers' attitudes and perceptions of stuttering and its effects on learners' educational attainment.

The selection of these studies was based on their focus on investigating teachers' attitudes and knowledge towards stuttering in various parts of the world, considering the date of publication to ensure the inclusion of recent research (2015-2021). However, recent studies specifically from Arab countries are scarce, with only three notable exceptions: Irani et al. (2012), Abdalla and St. Louis (2012), and Abdalla and St. Louis (2014). Many of the aforementioned studies employed the Public Opinion Survey of Human Attributes–Stuttering (POSHA-S) database to assess reactions, attitudes, and knowledge regarding stuttering. For example, studies such as those by Al-Qaisi and Ali (2020) and Abdalla and St. Louis (2014) utilised this tool. The POSHA-S survey comprises subsections including

demographic variables, self-rated health, ability, priority item ratings of stuttering relative to other human attributes, and detailed items about stuttering (St. Louis et al., 2018). It aims to collect quantitative data on public beliefs and attitudes towards stuttering and people who stutter (Katebe, 2020).

A quantitative study conducted by Abrahams et al. (2016) aimed to investigate primary school teachers' attitudes in South Africa towards stuttering and compare these with attitudes from a pooled group of respondents. In this study, the POSHA-S survey was used to collect data from the pooled group of respondents from various countries during the years 2009–2014 (Abrahams et al., 2016). The research was conducted in two urban education districts in South Africa. The findings indicate that the teachers generally hold positive attitudes towards children who stutter (Abrahams et al., 2016). These results are consistent with the study by Irani et al. (2012), which reported neutral to positive attitudes among Kuwaiti teachers towards their students who stutter. However, the teachers in Abrahams et al.'s study appeared to be uncertain about their knowledge of the causes of stuttering (Abrahams et al., 2016).

In the same vein, a study conducted by O'Brian et al. (2011) highlighted several concerns after observing children who stutter in schools. These concerns included difficulties in participating in group discussions, leading peers in play, resolving game problems, and giving explanations (O'Brian et al., 2011). The study results also revealed that while teachers tend to have positive perceptions about certain aspects of stuttering, they often have limited knowledge about the disorder (O'Brian et al., 2011; Al-Qaisi et al., 2020). Similarly, Hearne et al. (2021) reported that teachers in New Zealand lacked knowledge about the causes of stuttering. When comparing the results from the POSHA-S database and the South African sample, it was found that the assembled group's attitudes were somewhat less positive (Abrahams et al., 2016).

Another study conducted in Zambia aimed to compare the attitudes of pre-service and in-service teachers, investigating whether these attitudes could be influenced by factors such as age, region, gender, or level of education (Katebe et al., 2020). Using a quantitative approach with the POSHA-S survey, the study surveyed a random sample of 324 participants across Copperbelt, Luapula, Lusaka, and Muchinga provinces in Zambia. The findings indicated that special education teachers generally held more positive attitudes toward students who stutter compared to regular and student teachers. Interestingly, the study also found that gender differences, geographic locations, and educational levels did not significantly impact teachers' attitudes towards stuttering students. Similarly, Panico et al. (2018) conducted a study to explore the knowledge of student teachers and regular education

teachers regarding students who stutter. Their study yielded results consistent with Katebe's findings (2020), showing similar perceptions among the different samples regarding stuttering.

Li and Arnold (2015) conducted a quantitative study using the POSHA-S survey to assess teachers' reactions towards stuttering and compared them with non-teachers in the United States. Their sample included 263 teachers and 1336 non-teachers. The study found that teachers generally had more knowledge about stuttering compared to the general public sample. It was also noted that male teachers tended to conduct more research on stuttering than female teachers. However, female teachers showed more positive reactions than male teachers in terms of flexibility with stuttering learners and providing assistance. Similarly, Al-Qaisi and Ali (2020) used the POSHA-S survey to assess the attitudes of teachers in 370 primary schools in Baghdad towards children who stutter. The results indicated that a majority of the teachers held neutral attitudes towards children who stutter in the classroom.

Adriaensens and Struyf (2016) conducted a qualitative study aiming to explore teachers' perceptions and reactions towards stuttering in secondary schools in Flanders, Belgium. The study utilized semi-structured interviews with secondary school teachers to gather data on their perspectives and experiences related to stuttering. The findings from the study revealed that many teachers expressed uncertainty about their ability to effectively support students who stutter. They often felt inadequate in addressing the needs of these students within the classroom setting. Teachers highlighted those disruptions in lectures sometimes occurred due to peers' reactions to stuttering rather than the stuttering itself. This perspective suggested that social dynamics and peer interactions played a significant role in how stuttering was perceived and managed in the classroom. Moreover, the study noted that students who stutter tended to avoid discussing their stuttering openly, possibly to minimize negative reactions from their peers. This avoidance behavior was perceived by teachers as a strategy employed by students to cope with the challenges associated with stuttering. In summary, Adriaensens and Struyf (2016) provided insights into the challenges faced by teachers in supporting students who stutter, highlighting issues related to teacher confidence, peer interactions, and student coping strategies. The qualitative approach allowed for a deeper exploration of teachers' attitudes and perceptions towards stuttering in educational settings.

Studies like Abdalla and St. Louis (2014), Silva et al. (2016), and Hearne et al. (2021) have explored changes in teachers' attitudes and perceptions towards stuttering after they were provided with educational materials on the topic. These studies aimed to assess the effectiveness of interventions in enhancing teachers' understanding and support for students who stutter. Abdalla and St. Louis (2014) focused on the impact of documentary videos that illustrate stuttering on teachers' attitudes.

They found that such materials contributed positively to improving teachers' knowledge about stuttering and fostering more supportive attitudes towards students who stutter. Similarly, Silva et al. (2016) and Hearne et al. (2021) also reported positive shifts in teachers' attitudes after receiving educational interventions. These interventions likely included information sessions, workshops, or educational resources aimed at increasing awareness and understanding of stuttering among teachers. Overall, these studies underscore the importance of educational interventions in improving teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards stuttering. By providing teachers with accurate information and insights into stuttering, these interventions can help create more inclusive and supportive classroom environments for students who stutter.

In summary, the studies reviewed highlight the critical role of teachers in shaping the experiences of children who stutter in educational settings. Teachers' understanding and knowledge about stuttering are pivotal factors that can either mitigate or exacerbate negative experiences for these children (Li and Arnold, 2015; Panico et al., 2018). This can create more inclusive and supportive classroom environments, reducing the stigma and anxiety associated with stuttering, thus significantly improving students' overall educational experiences. Accordingly, teacher education programs should include comprehensive training on stuttering, equipping educators with the skills needed to support these students effectively as shown in studies such as (Boyle, Dioguardi, and Pate, 2017). Conversely, when teachers lack sufficient knowledge about stuttering. They may inadvertently contribute to negative experiences among students who stutter by misinterpreting stuttering as a lack of knowledge or nervousness, leading to inappropriate responses or disciplinary actions. Moreover, knowledgeable teachers can foster positive peer interactions, reduce bullying or teasing and promoting a more empathetic environment. Understanding stuttering also enables teachers to implement strategies that accommodate these students' needs, encouraging their academic success and participation.

Despite numerous studies conducted worldwide, generalising their findings is challenging due to variations in educational systems and cultural contexts across different countries. Most studies have employed quantitative methods to assess teachers' attitudes towards stuttering, providing valuable insights into broad trends but sometimes lacking depth (Abdalla and St. Louis, 2012; Irani et al., 2012; Abrahams et al., 2016; Aghaz et al., 2021; Al-Qaisi et al., 2020). Abrahams et al. (2016) advocate for future qualitative research to offer a deeper understanding of teachers' knowledge and perceptions related to stuttering and their approaches to teaching children who stutter. Thus, this study employs a qualitative constructivist approach to investigate the understanding of stuttering among teachers, mothers, and speech therapists. By including these perspectives, the study aims to strengthen its findings, enhance support and educational experiences for children who stutter, and foster more inclusive and supportive classroom environments.

The next section will explore parents' perceptions regarding stuttering, providing further insights into the broader societal attitudes towards this speech disorder.

4.8. Parents' Perceptions of Stuttering

It is noteworthy that stuttering emotionally affects both children who stutter and their parents (Millard and Davis, 2016). Therefore, prior studies have investigated how school-age children perceive their stuttering; however, there is limited knowledge regarding their parents' perceptions (Rocha et al., 2020). Furthermore, Studies have indicated that parents often develop negative thought patterns that lead to negative emotions when they struggle to respond appropriately to their children's stuttering (Beilby et al., 2014; Plexico and Burrus, 2012). Nonetheless, parents recognise that stuttering affects their children in various ways and understand their pivotal role in supporting them against bullying and stereotyping (Erickson and Block, 2013). Parents play a crucial role in their children's stutter therapy (Yaruss and Reardon-Reeves, 2017), providing valuable insights to language and speech therapists about their child's fluency across different contexts (Tumanova et al., 2018). Furthermore, the information parents provide to clinicians about both the child and themselves aids in understanding the impact of this speech disorder on the lives of children who stutter (Rocha et al., 2020).

Rocha et al. (2020) conducted a study in Portugal to examine parental perceptions of the impact of stuttering, which aligned with the perceptions of their children. The study involved 50 children who stutter, aged between 7 and 12, along with their parents. The findings indicated that the impact of stuttering was generally rated as mild to moderate. However, the study also highlighted the necessity of enhancing knowledge about stuttering. In a similar context, El-Adawy et al. (2021) conducted a quantitative study in Egypt to assess parental attitudes towards stuttering. The study employed a translated version of the Public Opinion Survey of Human Attributes–Stuttering (POSHA–S) (St. Louis, 2011), administered to one hundred Egyptian families with children who stutter, with eighty percent of the participants being parents. In contrast to global databases of POSHA-S, Egyptian parents exhibited less favourable attitudes towards stuttering and stutterers. This disparity was attributed in the study to cultural differences between Egypt and other countries.

The impact of parents' reactions to stuttering and their interactions with children who stutter is significant (Millard et al., 2018; Humeniuk and Tarkowski, 2016). Salehpoor, Latifi, and Tohidast (2020) utilised a Persian version of the Reaction to Speech Disfluency Scale (RSDS) to investigate parental attitudes towards their children's stuttering. Their findings indicate differences in reactions between fathers and mothers, as well as variations in reactions between parents of boys who stutter compared

to parents of girls who stutter. These reactions were categorised into emotions such as anger, tension, shame, guilt, apprehension, and embarrassment.

In contrast to studies involving Polish parents who reported experiencing these emotions (Humeniuk and Tarkowski, 2016), Salehpoor et al. (2020) found that such reactions were less frequent among their sample. However, on a cognitive level, parents tended to correct their children's speech during instances of disfluency or impatiently completed their child's speech (Salehpoor et al., 2020). To address these reactions, other studies have suggested strategies to guide parents in supporting their children who stutter. These strategies include advising children to speak slowly (Plexico and Burrus, 2012; Safwat and Sheikhy, 2014), encouraging them to breathe, relax, and think before speaking (Plexico and Burrus, 2012), and avoiding rushing the child while they are speaking (Costelloe et al., 2015; Safwat and Sheikhy, 2014). Other studies have documented reactions such as avoiding eye contact, reducing tension, and filling word gaps during conversations with individuals who stutter (Safwat and Sheikhy, 2014; Glover et al., 2019).

In contrast, Guttormsen, Yaruss, and Næss (2020) conducted a study exploring teachers' perceptions of children who stutter. The research aimed to compare these perceptions with those of parents and to examine the impact of stuttering on children who stutter. The findings indicated that teachers generally perceived a mild to moderate impact of stuttering on the lives of children who stutter. Furthermore, the study revealed similarities in perceptions of stuttering and its impact between mothers and fathers, as well as between parents and teachers. The study employed the Overall Assessment of the Speaker's Experience of Stuttering–Caregivers (OASES-C) instruments, which assesses the overall impact of stuttering on various aspects of the stuturer's life. However, it is worth noting that the study had limitations due to its small sample size, which restricted the exploration of factors contributing to these agreements.

Building on the insights from the aforementioned studies, valuable information could enrich the investigations of speech therapists and academics in this field (Salehpoor et al., 2020). Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat (2022) underscored the importance for speech therapists to explore parental knowledge and perceptions of stuttering, given its significant impact on the lives of those who stutter. It is widely acknowledged worldwide that parents play a crucial role in managing stuttering (Donaghy and Smith, 2016). However, studies have indicated a limitation in parents' understanding of this speech disorder and varying attitudes towards it (Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat, 2022). Parents often adopt a wait-and-see approach, hoping their child will naturally outgrow stuttering, which can hinder their preference to seek assistance from speech therapists (Kefalianos et al., 2017; Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat, 2022).

The following chapter will discuss the methodological choices that has been selected to achieve the aim of this research and address the research questions.

5. Chapter Five: Research Design

The previous chapter discussed the conceptual framework guiding this study, specifically the theory of stigma, and illustrated how stigma can be associated with stuttering, both within and beyond school environments. Building upon this foundation, this chapter delves into the methodological approach of the research. This employs a qualitative case study design adopting a constructivist paradigm, and utilising semi-structured interviews to collect data. For a more comprehensive understanding of the methodological choices of this, the chapter is organized into three key sections: methodology, research methods, and the data analysis process. At the end of the chapter, a discussion of the challenges encountered during the research process and the strategies used to overcome them will be provided.

5.1. Methodology

Research is a systematic investigation that utilises a defined methodology to obtain new data and contribute to the existing body of knowledge (Kumar, 2017; Lopes, 2015). This knowledge could be explored using different methodological approaches, such as qualitative, quantitative, or mixed research designs (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). The choice of the methodological approach should be discussed explicitly as it demonstrates the researcher's awareness of how these choices shape the research findings (Creswell 2007). Hence, this section discusses the Research approach and Paradigm that shaped the methods chosen for this study. Furthermore, it discusses the researcher's positionality and reflexivity, acknowledging how the researcher's background and perspectives may influence the research process.

5.1.1. Ontological and Epistemological Foundations

Before delving into the methodological design of this study, it's important to establish the underlying philosophical assumptions, as they guide the research design and methodology, acknowledging the various ways of understanding and interpreting social reality (Cohen, Manion and Morrison 2018). It is worth noting that paradigms demonstrate meanings that are constructed from the gathered data, depending on the individual's experience (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017), and each paradigm has its own ontological and epistemological assumptions (Scotland, 2012). This section involves a discussion of the research paradigm, and its ontological and epistemological stances, which justify the choice of qualitative research methods (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Hence, researchers should utilise these paradigms carefully, because of their complexity, for a better understanding of the study (Elshafie, 2013). By explicating these stances, we can better understand the research paradigm guiding this study.

The current research focuses more on constructing knowledge and reporting stakeholders' knowledge and perceptions about stuttering. Besides, investigating all sorts of stigma in Algerian middle schools towards students who stutter and provide an in-depth understanding of how stuttering and teaching children who stutter is perceived in Algerian society. Thus, I have adopted a constructive paradigm for this study (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017; Edwards, 2015). This paradigm seeks to bring out awareness about implicit social power and structures (Scotland, 2012). Besides it aims at comprehending the researched problem from the participants' viewpoints and allows several interpretations, double hermeneutic (Elshafie, 2013). In addition, the research aim of the constructivist paradigm is to relate the participants' points of view of a given phenomenon as much as possible (Creswell, 2014). In the same vein, the current research is based on this paradigm as the knowledge of this study is constructed on the participants' perceptions and views about stuttering and the stigma that follows this speech disorder in Algerian middle school settings. Through the participants' responses and views, the researcher will interpret and construct these findings (Cohen, Manion and Morrison 2018). Consequently, the constructivists paradigm is thought to be the suitable approach for this study.

In essence, ontology explores the nature of reality, while epistemology delves into the ways we acquire knowledge (Flick, 2014). In the constructivist paradigm, ontology primarily concerns individuals' beliefs and worldviews regarding the nature and description of reality and the social world (Leavy, 2017). It refers to the individual's conception of reality (Mertens, 2020). Accordingly, my ontological stance posits that worldviews are constructed by individuals' perceptions and interpretations of meaning based on their experiences. Additionally, within the same society, multiple truths and realities exist, shaped by individuals' experiences. As Killam (2013) notes, ontology in research reflects the researcher's beliefs about the nature of reality (p.7). This is exemplified by my belief that perceptions of stuttering may vary between Algeria and other countries, potentially influencing their attitudes toward children who stutter. Accordingly, the findings of the current may differ compared to previous studies. Moreover, attitudes toward stutterers are not universally shared behaviours; they can vary from person to person. Therefore, I believe that knowledge, culture, and other factors that are not commonly shared about stuttering may affect these attitudes.

On the other hand, epistemology refers to how knowledge is understood. The researcher's epistemological stance is crucial as it influences decisions regarding the selection and justification of knowledge, laying the foundation for the study (Lukenchuk, 2017). Unlike ontology, which focuses on the nature of reality, epistemology seeks to answer the question, 'What is the nature of the relationship between the knower or would-be knower and what can be known?' (Guba and Lincoln, 1989, p. 108). This question relates to the researcher's relationship with the participants and whether the researcher adopts an objective or subjective stance toward the research topic (Killam, 2018). The

researcher's epistemological stance is subjective for several reasons. In this study, I conducted the literature review before data collection which provided a foundational understanding of stuttering. While my prior knowledge could influence the research process (Guba and Lincoln, 1989), I ensured to mitigate any potential bias. Hence, I did not disclose my background and research interests related to stuttering with my participants before or during the interviews as it could also be leading. It was important to prioritise creating a space for participants to share their unique experiences and interpretations without influencing their responses. Epistemology also addresses how knowledge is acquired, as described by Crotty (1998) as 'how we know what we know?' (p. 8). Furthermore, epistemology serves as a philosophical framework that guides the selection and validation of information (Crotty, 1998). According to Hughes (2018), epistemology seeks to answer questions such as 'How certain are we that we have accumulated knowledge' and 'How can we distinguish this knowledge from belief' (n.p.). The data collection involved direct interaction with participants through interviews. My position as an Algerian researcher interviewing Algerian participants aligns with a constructionist epistemology. While my familiarity with Algerian social culture can offer valuable insights during data analysis, it is important to acknowledge the potential for bias resulting from my prior knowledge. These inquiries concern the validation and trustworthiness of knowledge.

5.1.2. Qualitative Research

While research on stuttering experiences using qualitative studies is vast, (e.g., Bricker-Katz et al., 2013; Jackson et al., 2015; Plexico et al., 2010; Tichenor and Yaruss, 2018). Previous research suggests that adolescents who stutter face challenges beyond just teacher perceptions as they also face negative reactions and a lack of understanding from their peers regarding their stuttering. Consequently, these factors impact the overall school experiences of children who stutter (Cobb et al., 2019). However, there is a lack of qualitative research in the Algerian context that explores the experiences of children who stutter in middle schools. This gap in knowledge hinders our understanding of how stuttering is perceived in Algeria and how it impacts their lives within the Algerian educational system.

Moreover, most of the studies that address the areas of teachers' attitudes and perceptions adopted a quantitative approach. These studies aimed to assess the teachers' attitudes using a survey called The Public Opinion Survey of Human Attributes-Stuttering (POSHA-S) (e.g. Abrahams, et al., 2016; Irani et al., 2012; Arnold, and Goltl, 2015). POSHA-S is designed to be a useful, consistent, effective, and valid survey to measure human attitudes towards stuttering (St. Louis, 2011). As it can be translated into any language to accommodate the standards of all societies around the world (St. Louis, 2011). However, this study seeks to gain an in-depth understanding of the stakeholders' perceptions and

attitudes towards children who stutter in Algerian middle schools. Therefore, I have opted for a qualitative approach. Qualitative research is particularly suited to this study as it enables me to interact directly with my participants to gain a deeper understanding of how they interpret and navigate their experiences with stuttering (Sutton and Austin, 2015).

A key advantage of the qualitative approach is that it allows for a nuanced understanding of the thoughts, perspectives about stuttering, and experiences of speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and language teachers with students who stutter (Denzin, 1989). Furthermore, it is particularly suitable for this study as it allows me to delve into participants' perceptions and understand how these perceptions are shaped by the Algerian cultural context (Corbin and Strauss, 2008). By delving deeper into these details, the analysis of the data helped comprehend the reason behind some assumptions and dismissed some judgements (Rahman, 2017). In the context of this study, this allows us to explore how Algerian society, classroom environments and external factors might influence the stakeholders' perceptions and attitudes towards stuttering.

Furthermore, qualitative research empowers participants by giving them a voice to share their unique perspectives and experiences (Creswell and Poth, 2018). That is, each individual of each of the current group samples has a unique perspective, and each one of them constructs their own understandings through their looms. In essence, it allows presenting participants' opinions, experiences, and meaning systems as seen through their eyes (Mohajan, 2017). Unlike quantitative approaches that focus on frequency, qualitative research prioritises understanding the meaning participants make of their experiences (Creswell, 2013). This allows us to delve deeper into the individual narratives and worldviews of speech-language therapists, mothers, and teachers, minimising the authority relationship that generally exists between a researcher and his participants in the research (Creswell, 2013).

Another advantage of qualitative research is the ability to collect rich data directly from participants. Unlike quantitative methods that rely on standardized surveys, qualitative researchers often develop their own instruments, such as open-ended interview questions, tailored to the specific research questions (Creswell and Poth, 2018). For this study, a semi-structured interview guide has been developed to allow for an in-depth exploration of participants' experiences and perspectives on stuttering. This approach, as Creswell and Poth (2018) point out, enables participants to share their stories in their own words and provide detailed accounts that might not be captured by predetermined answer choices. By facilitating open and unrestricted dialogue, semi-structured interviews empower participants to share their unique insights and perspectives (Austin and Sutton, 2014).

Another strength of using a qualitative approach in this study is to uncover participants' lived experiences with children who stutter in Algeria (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Usually, the qualitative enquiry helps to collect data inside the field, at the location in which participants encounter the problems or issues being investigated (Creswell, 2013). This also might help to entail interactive collaboration with participants so that they get the opportunity to construct the topics or concepts as the research progresses (Creswell and Poth 2018). By prioritizing participants' voices and lived experiences, qualitative research aims to elucidate their statements openly and without constraint and clarify the reason behind these beliefs (Austin and Sutton, 2014). (Austin and Sutton, 2014). As Mohajan (2017) stated the goal of qualitative study is to develop new ideas and hypotheses by systematically describing and interpreting problems or phenomena from the viewpoint of the person or group being investigated.

In summary, the qualitative approach allows for the collection of rich, in-depth data on participants' experiences with children who stutter in Algeria and their perspectives on stuttering (Creswell and Poth, 2018). This includes exploring the meanings they attach to stuttering and how their understanding might be shaped by the Algerian context. Secondly, qualitative research facilitates reporting the participants' unique voices and experiences, empowering them to share how their perceptions of stuttering developed (Creswell, 2013; Austin and Sutton, 2014). Finally, by utilising methods like semi-structured interviews, qualitative research allows for direct interaction with participants for a deeper understanding of a specific context, such as the experiences of mothers, speech therapists, and teachers in Algerian middle schools (Creswell, 2013). These strengths make qualitative research well-suited to address the following research questions in this study:

- 1- What is the depth and scope of the Algerian stakeholders' knowledge of stuttering?
- 2- What is the depth and scope of stakeholders' knowledge of the stigma associated with stuttering in Algerian middle schools?
- 3- What are the stakeholders' perspectives on the strategies for mitigating stigma-related stuttering in Algerian middle schools?

Qualitative research is particularly suited to address "what" and "how" questions, which are central to this study (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2015).

5.1.3. Positionality and Reflexivity of the Researcher

Positionality is a term that refers to the beliefs and perspectives of an individual, as well as the stance adopted to conduct a study in politics or a social context (Rowe, 2014). In other words, it is the position

of the researcher that they adopt in a certain study (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013). This section reflects on the researcher's positionality within this study.

The current research aims to investigate the perceptions and attitudes of speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers toward children who stutter in Algeria. The investigated subject, the sample of the study, and the method of the study and its context are usually what identify positionality (Rowe, 2014). The researcher could be an insider if they share similar characteristics with the individual who participated in their research (Bukamal, 2022). On that account, being an Algerian conducting my research within an Algerian community to understand their attitudes towards a phenomenon makes me an insider. Knowing that all my participants are Algerians living in Algeria, my own background as an Algerian has greatly contributed to making sense of the data during the analysis, leading to more accurate and in-depth interpretations.

However, reflexivity is a significant procedure to inform and shape the positionality of the researcher voiced in the study (Holmes, 2020). I consider myself as an insider, because I have knowledge about the topic and the shared cultural perspective between me and my participants (Bukamal, 2022). I have developed substantial knowledge regarding communication disorders during my PhD journey. Additionally, my master's degree is in education, and my PhD is in education and social science, making me familiar with both speech therapy and teaching.

Furthermore, since my ontological position is constructivist, I believe that reality cannot be measured through quantitative tools, but it could be sought through the different experiences of my participants (Mertens, 2020). The researcher should be aware to provide an objective and honest assessment of the individuals' accounts as it could affect the interpretation of the data directly or indirectly (May and Perry, 2017). Nevertheless, being Algerian had a positive impact on my ability to interview or understand these groups as the interaction with her participants will be easier. My broader cultural and educational background facilitated meaningful engagement and understanding, taking into account not to influence my interaction with the participants.

The following discussed the methods used in this research.

5.2. Methods

This section outlines the research methods employed for data collection. It details the participant selection process, sampling strategies, and participant information. Furthermore, it addresses the use of interviews as the primary data collection tool and the ethical considerations addressed throughout the research process. The second section delves into the sampling strategy, the data collection method, and the ethical considerations that were paramount throughout collecting the data for the study.

5.2.1. Case study

The case study method is widely utilised in academia by researchers interested in qualitative research (Baškarada, 2014; Yazan, 2015). It aims to develop a thorough, multi-faceted understanding of a complex issue within its real-life context (Yin, 2018). Researchers can explore specific contexts from various viewpoints (Simons, 2009), employing detailed data collection methods such as observation, interviews, audio-visual material, documents, and reports to describe case details and identify thematic patterns (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Consequently, this study adopts a triangulation approach, using semi-structured interviews to capture diverse perspectives and comprehensively understand stakeholder attitudes towards stuttering.

Yin (2014) argued that evidence should be extracted from different sources, typically three instruments such as interviews, document analysis, and focus groups. Patton (2002) discussed that triangulation can involve different sources of data; therefore, the present study focused on interviewing three different groups to support the evidence with multiple sources (Yin, 2014). Data can be collected from various sources such as different groups of people, places, or even different times (Ammenwerth et al., 2003; Natow, 2020). In this study, the triangulation of data is composed of three different groups of participants: speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter and middle school language teachers. The latter will ensure the validity and credibility of the research. Hence, triangulation will help avoid any biases that might arise when using only one source (Noble and Heale, 2019). Each group will provide data regarding the topic from their own perspectives.

As previously discussed, case studies are particularly suited for addressing how and why questions (Baškarada, 2013), representing a well-established research design extensively used across various disciplines, especially in the social sciences (Crowe et al., 2011), which forms the focus of this study. This provides a strong foundation to critically understand the broader implications of stuttering among children who stutter in Algerian society. According to Gerring (2017), a case study involves ‘an intensive study of a single case or a small number of cases, which draws on observational data and promises to shed light on a larger population of cases’ (p. 28). In this study, the focus is on west of Algeria, with the selection of three groups of participants closely associated with children who stutter. The objective of a case study is twin; to elucidate the specific cases under investigation and to provide insights into a broader set of exemplar cases (Gerring, 2017).

It is crucial to emphasise that case study research involves studying one or more cases within a real-life, contemporary context or setting (Yin, 2014). The primary objective of this study is to uncover current attitudes towards children who stutter in Algeria, highlighting both positive and negative perceptions. Furthermore, the case can manifest as a tangible entity, such as an individual, a small

group, an organisation, or a partnership (Creswell and Poth, 2018). The chosen case study site or sites provide access for researchers to study the group of individuals, the organisation, the processes, or any other aspect that constitutes the selected unit of analysis for the study. In this study, middle school students who stutter have been selected as the case for investigation. Access is therefore a pivotal consideration; the researcher must familiarise themselves with the case study site and collaborate effectively with them (Crowe et al., 2011). As an Algerian who has studied and lived in Algeria throughout my life, I am well acquainted with the protocols and procedures required to access schools and centres selected for conducting this study.

5.2.2. Sample

Sampling is a process that allows researchers to select a manageable subset of a population that would represent a whole population (Naderifar, et al., 2017). Rahi (2017) pointed out that the research design, including its theoretical underpinnings and practical considerations, significantly influences the choice of sampling method. Accordingly, the sample of this study is composed of three different groups, speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle-school language teachers. By recruiting participants with diverse viewpoints on the same topic (Creswell and Poth, 2018), this study gains a richer and more nuanced understanding of the experiences of children who stutter in Algerian middle schools; thus, strengthening the results and credibility of the research. It is also important to note, that the study sample consisted exclusively of Algerian participants employed within Algeria.

In qualitative studies, determining the ideal sample size is an ongoing debate among researchers (Vasileious et al., 2018). Reaching the data saturation could strengthen the possibility of generalising the findings of the study, however, it is somehow difficult to determine the sample size before collecting the data (Boddy, 2016). Taking into account the fact that data should be manageable in terms of collection and analysis (Moser and Korstjens, 2018), I initially set a target for a total of 30 participants. However, the data collection would still proceed, exceeding this initial targeted sample size, if data saturation is not reached.

To recruit participants for this study, I employed a purposive sampling approach, also known as judgment sampling (Etikan and Bala, 2017; Vehovar et al., 2016). This method allowed me to select participants based on specific characteristics or experiences relevant to the research questions. In the next section, I will provide a more detailed explanation of purposive sampling, alongside a discussion of the snowball sampling method, which was utilised during the recruitment process as well.

5.2.2.1. Purposive and Snowball Sampling

Probability and non-probability sampling are the two main approaches to sample selection (Etikan and Bala, 2017). This study adopts a non-probability sampling technique, specifically purposive sampling, which is commonly used in qualitative research (Etikan and Bala, 2017; Cohen et al., 2018). This sampling approach was used to recruit speech therapists and teachers. Furthermore, I have utilised snowball sampling to complement this initial recruitment strategy and reach mothers of children who stutter.

Purposive sampling allows me to select participants with specific knowledge about the research topic, aiming to gather rich and informative data that addresses the research questions (Etikan and Bala, 2017). Participants in this study were selected based on their knowledge and experience with stuttering. Speech-language therapists were selected as their knowledge and experience regarding stuttering and the schooling experiences of children who stutter in Algeria are valuable resources for informing this study. Before contacting the participants, I sought authorisation from the directors of speech-language therapy centres and schools in Algeria. From there, I began visiting the first speech therapy centre, where I was directed to other centres and introduced to additional speech and language therapists who could participate in this study. Furthermore, this research focuses on investigating knowledge and attitudes towards children who stutter within the Algerian middle school environment. Therefore, teachers were a crucial participant group to include in the study. More specifically, language teachers were selected as their subject area directly involves spoken communication which is a potential challenge for children who stutter. Hence, gaining insights into how language teachers address these issues was essential for this research.

In addition to purposive sampling, snowball sampling was utilised to recruit the sample of the mothers for this study. To facilitate the recruitment of mothers, speech-language therapists and teachers who participated in this study helped in contacting parents of children who stutter. Speech-language therapists regularly work with children who stutter, and teachers may have students who stutter, which allows them to contact the mothers directly. The participation of mothers was crucial in this study, as they possess invaluable knowledge about the schooling experience of the children who stutter. Based on these criteria I have chosen my participants, which explains my choices of purposive and snowball sampling.

5.2.2.2. Participants Information Background

In qualitative studies, the sample size is typically determined by reaching data saturation, the point at which no new insights emerge from additional participants (Dhivyadeepa, 2015). I aimed to interview a total of 30 participants in this study; however, two interviews were cancelled at the last minutes by the participants. Nevertheless, the data saturation was reached as expected, hence a total of 28

participants ultimately contributed to the research. It is important to acknowledge that some potential participants were unable to participate due to scheduling conflicts or other commitments. The following tables (Table 1; Table 2; Table 3) provide information about the research participants. The first table includes speech-language therapists' training, work experience, and the number of stuttering cases they encounter monthly. The second table presents details stated by the mother about their children's stuttering severity, age, years of treatment, and personality traits. It is important to note that the participation of mothers only in this study was not the researcher's deliberate choice. However, during the process of contacting parents, fathers often preferred that their wives participate instead of themselves. Hence, this was not a methodological choice, but rather due to cultural reasons; the mothers felt more comfortable speaking with me as I am women. Nevertheless, the research remained flexible in this regard, as the exclusive participation of mothers did not affect the nature or quality of the data collected. Finally, the third table describes the teachers' backgrounds.

Table 1 Background Information of the Sample (Speech-Language Therapists).

Speech-language therapist interviewee	Gender	Private/ public centre	Years of experience	Learners who stutter every year
Hassan	Male	Public and private	14	Around 8
Maya	Female	Private	6	Around 6
Nour	Female	Public	3	Around 10
Ahmad	male	Public	7	Around 4
Leya	Female	Private	6	Around 14
Lama	Female	Public	4	Not defined
Imad	Male	Public	5	8 to 10
Safa	Female	Public	4	8 to 10
Linda	Female	Public	4	2 to 4

Table 2 Background Information of the children who stutter

Mothers Interviewee	Age of the children who stutter	Years of Treatment	The severity of the stutter	The personality of the child
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Oum Reda	12	Seven years (2016-2022)	Severe	Introvert, Short tempered
Oum Yasmine	11	Five years (2016- 2021)	Mild	Ambitious, sensitive
Oum Youcef	11	One year (2012)	Severe	Sociable, short- tempered
Oum Halima	14	Two years (2018-2019)	Mild	/
Oum Ibrahim	14	six years (2015- 2020)	Mild/Severe	Sociable, patient,
Oum Iyad	13	No treatment	Mild/Severe	/
Oum Ritta	13	three years (2018-2020)	Severe	Shy
Oum Djed	16	One year (2014)	Severe	/
Oum Aseel	12	No treatment	Mild	Shy

Table 3 Background Information of the Sample (Middle School Language Teachers)

Teachers Interviewee	Gender	Language Teaching	Years of experience	Learners who stutter in 2022
Malak	Female	English	4	2
Nassima	Female	English	5	0
Samar	Female	French	15	2
Noah	Male	English	37	2
Amal	Female	French	20	3
Imene	Female	Arabic	10	1
Leen	Female	English	4	2
Dania	Female	English	10	2
Samira	Female	French	16	1
Nada	Female	English	15	2

5.2.3. Semi-structured Interviews

According to Redlich-Amirav and Higginbottom, (2014) in qualitative research collecting the data is a very significant task after choosing the methodology and methods. The interpretive paradigm permits the researcher to collect qualitative data using different methods (Al Riyami, 2015). Instead of relying on a single data source, various tools can be used to collect the data such as interviews, observations, and measurements (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Creswell, 2013). Nevertheless, in social sciences and qualitative studies, semi-structured interviews are probably the most common method (Edwards and Holland, 2013; Brinkmann, 2018; Barrett and Twycross 2018). Hence, this study employed semi-structured interviews as the main data collection method.

Many studies highlighted the importance of interviews in qualitative research, emphasizing their role in establishing the credibility of the research findings (Silverman, 2013; Adhabi and Anozie; 2017). This study aimed to understand meanings, therefore, semi-structured interviews allowed participants to express themselves more, allowing me to explore meanings and understand more the participants' perceptions and behaviours towards stuttering (Cohen et al., 2018). Furthermore, interviews in this research study allowed me to investigate aspects beyond observable behaviours (Al Riyami, 2015), facilitating the collection of rich and nuanced data (Barrett and Twycross, 2018). This was achieved through direct communication with the participants, allowing me to ask targeted questions tailored to the specific needs of the data collection (Tripathy and Tripathy, 2015). As a result, the interview responses directly addressed the research questions and yielded purposeful data (Magnusson and Marecek, 2015). This approach allowed for follow-up questions to clarify any ambiguities and gain a richer understanding of their experiences. Consequently, it facilitated an in-depth understanding of their perceptions of stuttering and the associated stigma among middle school students in Algeria.

The interview followed a semi-structured approach, which enabled me to engage in flexible conversation while still being guided by the interview schedule to ensure that the data collected remained relevant to the research questions. Accordingly, the interview schedule was divided into three sections aiming to gather comprehensive data on the participants' knowledge and approaches to stuttering in educational settings. The first section began with general questions to assess the interviewee's background knowledge of stuttering. This initial exploration provided the interviewer with valuable insights into the interviewee's frame of reference. The second section delved deeper into stuttering itself. Here, more specific questions will be used to gauge the interviewee's understanding and experiences related to stuttering. This established a solid foundation for the scenario-based section that follows. The third part of the interview schedule presented imaginary situations that could occur in the classroom. These scenarios were close to reality and reflected issues that students who stutter often face. Some of them were adapted from findings reported in the

literature. The aim of this section was to place teachers in these situations so that their attitudes could be identified and highlighted in case they had no experience of teaching students who stutter. Their responses would reveal whether they demonstrated appropriate or interesting reactions. Furthermore, parents and speech therapists were also presented with the same scenarios; however, they were asked to respond in terms of how they believed teachers should react, based on their personal knowledge of their children and their professional experience working with children who stutter. Finally, the aim of this section was to determine how they perceived Algerian society's attitudes toward stuttering, and the stigma associated with it. Analysing the interviewees' responses to these scenarios provided crucial insights into their attitudes towards stuttering and highlighted potential approaches to managing the stigma in the classroom.

To provide comprehensive and rigorous data, I have used audio recording. I recorded the data using a digital audio recorder. After every interview, I save the recording in a safe file in a UWS drive with a secure password.

5.2.4. Ethical Consideration for Participants' Recruitment and Data Collection

Research ethics are the guidelines that define the ethical practices that researchers must follow to protect the rights and well-being of research participants (Cohen et al., 2018). Therefore, a number of ethical considerations governed this study especially since it requires human participation, and researching sensitive matters (Shaw et al., 2016). In the current study, I have conducted semi-structured interviews with speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers. I have taken research ethics as an integral part of the research following the UWS ethical guidelines. Hence, the University of the West of Scotland's Ethics Committee has approved this study.

Participant recruitment for this study proved to be a lengthy process. While I had secured approval from the UWS ethics committee, obtaining institutional agreements and authorization in Algeria from the Director of the Ministry of Education, school headteachers, the Ministry of Health, and the directors of the speech therapy centres. was necessary to access schools and speech therapy centres. Speech therapists worked in diverse settings, including disability centres, paediatric hospitals, and potentially other locations.

Due to limited online access to these centres, I visited each one and spoke with the directors to gain access to potential participants. Given the key role of speech-language therapists in connecting with mothers of children who stutter, I prioritised recruitment efforts through them. I provided them with my contact information and allowed them time to review the study information sheet and consent

form. Following their consent to participate, we arranged mutually convenient times for in-person interviews.

In addition to the detailed study information sheet and consent form outlining the interview procedures, I provided a comprehensive explanation of the aim of the study and its process to ensure participants were fully informed about their involvement in the research. Before each interview, I clarify any ambiguities that they might have after reading the information sheet and actively encourage them to ask for further information. Furthermore, I have carefully considered the potential consequences of non-disclosure and prioritised transparency whenever possible, as this fostered trust and collaboration with my participants and stakeholders (BERA, 2018).

Throughout the research process, I prioritised my participants' well-being and upheld ethical principles. Hence, I assured them that their participation is confidential and anonymous, and any information that could potentially identify them will be removed from the data. Additionally, I informed them of their rights as participants and that they may withdraw at any time without giving any explanation. I also ensured my participants that the collected data would be analysed and written as a UWS PhD thesis. These measures aim to create a comfortable and open environment, fostering honest and reliable responses that are crucial elements for the validity and trustworthiness of this study.

The collected data was saved and secured in the (UWS) OneDrive protected by a password. The data controller ensures that the only research team is authorised to access the data with the understanding that all the information of the participants will remain protected from unauthorized persons.

5.3. Thematic Analysis Process

The third section describes the data analysis procedures used to analyse the data and present the research findings.

Analysing the data can be challenging for qualitative researchers (Creswell and Poth, 2018) because it reflects the quality of the data (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). It is an ongoing process that should begin as soon as the data collection has started (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Cohen et al. (2018) have described it as a process that starts from the study's procession to its completion. I employed thematic analysis as an analytical approach to generate codes and systematically develop themes to address the research questions. This chapter begins by outlining the analytical approach employed in this study. Following this, a detailed explanation of the analysis process, including its various phases, will be provided. The chapter will describe the procedures used to ensure the accuracy and trustworthiness of the data at the end.

Researchers can divide the analytical phase into different stages to represent the data, identify codes, organise themes, and interpret the data (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Nevertheless, the analysis of the datasets of this study went through six phases suggested by Braun and Clark (2006). It is worth mentioning that within this approach, there are different methods (Clarke and Braun, 2018). To capture the essence of the collected data, I have combined deductive and inductive thematic analysis. The flexibility of this approach allowed this study to initially utilise the stigma framework to guide analysis -deductive- while remaining open to identifying new themes that emerge from the data itself -inductive- (Clarke and Braun, 2017).

Several factors influenced my decision to employ thematic analysis for this study. As a systematic analytical method, thematic analysis allows me to identify key themes within the dataset that reflect its importance and contribute to answering the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This approach facilitates the process of coding and analysing content, ultimately leading to the identification of meaningful patterns in stakeholder perspectives on stuttering stigma among Algerian children (Braun and Clarke, 2017; Roberts et al., 2019). Furthermore, Braun and Clarke (2022) highlight the value of thematic analysis in revealing both similarities and differences in participant perspectives, potentially leading to unexpected insights. This is particularly beneficial for this study which utilizes a triangulation of data sources. Finally, the flexibility of thematic analysis permits its application across various ontological and epistemological stances (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Thematic analysis was particularly suitable for my qualitative data due to its ability to process detailed and complex narratives (Braun and Clarke, 2006). During this process, it is important to highlight that data saturation was assessed by checking the emergence of new codes. After approximately the fifth interview of each group, no new themes or codes were identified, which ensured that saturation had been achieved. By connecting themes and codes derived from the data and literature review, thematic analysis helped me achieve the research objectives. This approach was applied to analyse the perspectives of speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers, regarding stuttering and its associated stigma.

The semi-structured interviews employed in this study allowed participants to share their unique beliefs and interpretations of this phenomenon (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Accordingly, thematic analysis effectively captures these diverse perspectives by identifying themes that represent the most significant elements within the structured data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). While Cohen et al. (2018) warn against introducing contradictory information when connecting data to research topics, I will ensure thematic coherence by grounding my analysis within the established literature framework. It is crucial to maintain clear and rigorous procedures to avoid ambiguity (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Therefore, I have guided my analysis using the specific procedures outlined by Braun and Clarke (2020, 2022). My data analysis followed a six-phase, linear, and progressive approach to ensure clarity and avoid redundancy.

5.3.1. Data Familiarisation and Writing Familiarisation Notes:

The first phase of the analysis was to get familiar with the content of my dataset. It was essential to immerse myself in the knowledge of my data before starting the coding phase. I created an information record from all my interviews. Hence, I have highlighted all critical points during and after the discussion with my participants—these ideas help to save details that help me during transcription.

5.3.1.1. Transcription

Transcribing the audio recordings was significant to gain a deep familiarity with the data of the interviews. I took notes during and after the discussions to ensure that I transcribed the data correctly. The recordings provided more time to examine the data and ensure I had all the information saved to go through it more than once. Then, I transcribed all the interviews manually on a Word document listening to the audio recordings. I focused on transcribing word by word regardless of grammar mistakes or the repetition of words to ensure I included all the information during the interviews.

The data of semi-structured interviews was more significant than the use of the language during the interviews. Standard Arabic is the official language in Algeria, where I conducted my study. However, usually, it is not used in everyday conversation. Instead, they use different dialects that differ according to each region's history (Menacer et al., 2017). Given that my participants were Algerians, who speak the Algerian dialect, I gave them options to choose between standard Arabic, French, English, and the Algerian dialect to express their ideas better. Accordingly, most of them decided to use the Algerian dialect to answer the interview questions, except for three participants who chose to be interviewed in English but switched to dialect during the interview.

The interviews were conducted in Algerian dialect, a mix of Arabic and French. This resulted in code-switching between languages throughout the interview recordings. To address this, I opted for a transliteration method. This method uses the Latin alphabet and numbers. My transliteration choices aimed to maintain the pronunciation of the words by replacing the Arabic alphabet with the Latin alphabet that sounds to represent similar sounds of the spoken Algerian dialect (Mammadzada, 2023; Al Jumaily, 2019). It is typically sought to maintain the phonological structure of words during transliterating (Mammadzada, 2023) While some phonemes in Arabic do not have direct equivalents in Latin, I used numbers to represent these sounds accurately. This is a common practice for me to

communicate with my family, Algerian fellows, and friends, in chatting mainly, to ensure a correct phonetic representation (Al Jumaily, 2019). Transliteration proved to be the most suitable approach because writing the interviews in Arabic and French in the same sections would not be comprehensible due to their differences in structure and in the way, text is written in each language.

5.3.1.2. Reading and revising the transcripts

Once the initial transcripts were complete, I created a second copy for each one and I saved the original ones for future reference, if needed. I redrafted all the transcripts to conduct a thorough review and ensure the participants' confidentiality and anonymity. This review involved removing any unnecessary data, such as pauses and grammatical errors. Furthermore, I have included some notes I took during the interview discussions to highlight grimaces or the nonverbal language of my participants that were relevant to the research questions, such as expressing disappointment or giving a confident smile about a specific question. These observations, captured in brief annotations within the transcripts, helped me gain a deeper understanding of the discussions in relation to the research questions. Finally, after having the detailed transcripts, I listened to the recordings to ensure the correctness of the transcripts' data to start the coding process.

5.3.1.3. Translating

Translating qualitative data requires careful consideration to ensure accuracy and validity. The complexity of this process is due to several factors, such as linguistic competence, cultural background, and the methodology of translation itself (Abalkhail, 2018; Chen and Boore, 2010). Knowing that the Algerian dialect was the first language of my participants, and that most of them felt more comfortable using it to express themselves fully. Translation was, therefore, necessary in the research process, as the study was conducted in English.

Linguistic competence is one of the factors that affect the translation process, as it requires more than literal translation; the interpretation of meaning is of greater importance. According to Abalkhail (2018), the process of translation is not merely a mechanical task but requires interpretation skills, as meaning can be lost during this process. This challenge is often related to the language proficiency of the translator and their positionality within the research. I opted to do the translation myself because I am fluent in Arabic, French, and English, which enabled me to ensure that participants' voices were accurately conveyed in English. The challenge was heightened as the process required reproducing new data that fully reflected the source data and could be ready for interpretation (Santos et al., 2015). Nonetheless, other factors supported the validity of my translation, such as my cultural background, which proved essential for accurate translation.

Since I am an insider, sharing the same cultural background with my participants, language, and knowledge, this gave me the advantage of ensuring a better understanding of the data before starting the translation (Abalkhail, 2018). Furthermore, being the one who conducted the interviews, I also had the advantage of recalling and understanding the nonverbal interactions that occurred during the interview discussions, which could have a strong influence on the meaning of the data (Chen and Boore, 2010). This could be a challenge for many researchers who do not share the same cultural background as their participants, as even minor details can influence the interpretation of the data.

Furthermore, the timing of translation could be an issue for many researchers, and choosing the right method of translation can have a significant effect on the amount of time required to process the data (Santos et al., 2015). During translation, I considered two approaches. The first involved simultaneous translation, directly translating the audio while listening. The second method, which I ultimately chose, involved transcribing and analysing the interviews in their original language first. Although this method was more time-consuming, it allowed me to gain deeper familiarity with the data before translating relevant excerpts for analysis. This approach aligns with the recommendations of Santos et al. (2015), who advocate for early translation in the research process to allow for deeper interpretive engagement with the data.

Back-translation is appropriate, whether the research goals are comparative or operational, once the content of the items has been established (Chen and Boore, 2010). Comparing the back-translated data to the original transcripts allows for a thorough examination of the translation's accuracy, ensuring the data's nuances and intended meanings are preserved. Therefore, I asked two of my colleagues who are fluent in both the Algerian dialect and English to translate the data back from English into the original language. This process helped mitigate errors, minimise the risk of misinterpreting the transcripts, and strengthened the reliability of the findings. Moreover, this method helped preserve the participants' original words and allowed them to verify the quality of the translation.

In conclusion, the process of translation in this study was deliberately designed to ensure the trustworthiness of the data, drawing on my positionality, linguistic competence, and the extended time allocated for this project. Although there are many challenges that occur during the translation phase, I have been diligent in following the recommendations of other scholars. Hence, while there are no standard procedures that evaluate the impact of translation in qualitative research (Chen and Boore, 2010), the transparent strategies used in this study and the reflexivity applied throughout the process enhanced the trustworthiness of this cross-language qualitative study.

The following section discusses the coding process.

5.3.2. Coding

After familiarising myself with the data, I started the coding phase. Codes are labels or tags that describe or infer the collected data (Miles et al., 2020). The data coding process is guided and related to the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2013). In qualitative research, coding is a standard data analysis procedure where the researcher breaks down the datasets to generate new information (Elliott, 2018). This process facilitates the categorisation of the data segments based on shared information (Cohen, et al., 2018). Furthermore, it helps gain insights into both the frequency of codes and how they connect to form patterns (Cohen et al., 2018). Hence, the researchers identify the data sets with codes that illustrate a broader common perspective, experience, topic, or area (Silver and Lewins, 2014). Miles et al. argued that the coding process is not only preparing the data for the analysis but also part of the analysis (2020). It was significant for me to establish a coding system that strengthens the results' reliability and validity. Therefore, the coding process in the current study went through three phases to ensure a profound interpretation of the data and its meaning.

Thematic analysis guided data analysis in this study, utilising both deductive and inductive coding strategies. Deductive coding guided the initial development of codes and themes based on the pre-existing conceptual framework, interview discussions, and research questions (Saldaña, 2021). Moreover, some codes have occurred during the transcription. Inductive coding emerged as I analysed the data, allowing for the identification of new themes not anticipated by the framework (Saldaña, 2021). With inductive coding, the process of analysing data and formulating clear and descriptive codes demands more time for reflection (Saldaña, 2021). It is important to note that I initially began using NVivo for coding. However, due to a cyber incident, I lost all the data. Therefore, I had to restart the coding process entirely using manual coding techniques within Microsoft Word Office. To initiate the coding process, I categorized the interview transcripts based on participant groups: speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle-school language teachers. This involved coding the interviews for each group sequentially, starting with speech-language therapists, followed by mothers, and then middle school language teachers. Hence, the coding process of this study was unfolded in two stages.

Figure 8 Model of the Development of Initial Coding and Sample Analysis, Based on the Concept of Stigma.

Initially, I coded each interview by developing preliminary codes deductively (Saldaña, 2021). I drew on the research questions and theoretical framework to develop initial codes and themes that were expected to appear in the collected data (Saldaña, 2021). As illustrated in Figure 8, I began developing the concepts and codes that could arise from stigma. This helped to shape the process of analysis initially before coding the interview transcripts. The concept of stigma is usually related to labelling, stereotyping, discrimination, and other attitudes; hence, any stigmatising attitudes would probably be highlighted under these codes. These codes might not be explicitly stated; however, they might be exhibited in social attitudes, knowledge, perceptions, and reactions. In this study, however, speech therapists, mothers, and teachers are the ones who report these social attitudes.

In the second stage, instead of working on the coding using printed papers, I used the Microsoft Word comment function to code the extracted datasets and develop initial codes. This phase consisted of coding the data thoroughly to ensure the strength of the analysis, which was done inductively opening the possibility for other code related to the study to appear. This involved a complete coding approach, highlighting all the data that related to the research question with the interview datasets (Braun and

Clarke, 2013). This process helped identify significant aspects across the data set that support the themes of the current study (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Figure 9 An example of the initial phase of coding

The image shows a text document on the left with several segments highlighted in blue. On the right, there is a list of code comments, each enclosed in a rounded rectangle and connected to a specific highlighted segment in the text by a dashed blue line. The text segments and their corresponding comments are as follows:

- Text: "Reda has a stutter, and he has a problem of fear. When he is in a situation where he feels scared, his stutter worsens. However, when he is in a comfortable situation, the severity of his stuttering is less..."
Comment: "Commented [MB]: Stuttering and fear"
- Text: "Okay mm does he know about stuttering? I mean, how do you think he perceive stuttering?"
Comment: "Commented [MB]: Effect of fear on his fluency"
- Text: "He knows, yes, and if someone talks to him or asks him why you speak like that, he explains that he has a stutter..."
Comment: "Commented [MB]: Recognition of stuttering by the child"
- Text: "Okay, and have you done any research about stuttering or read about it to learn more?"
Comment: "Commented [MB]: Struggle of learning about stuttering"
- Text: "I tried researching stuttering online, but the information was confusing with different definitions. I did not get it! However, I followed their advice, such as swimming and I used to help him practise breathing exercises at home... give a balloon to blow up. All day, anything in front of me that help with breathing I ask him to do it. He does not stutter after this; he gets better after doing the activities. But if we stop doing the breathing activities for a while he starts stuttering again. He does not recover 100% the stutter comes and goes. The stutter goes on days when he feels comfortable, during the period of exams starts the stutter comes again."
Comments:
 - "Commented [MB]: Swimming activity"
 - "Commented [MB]: Knowledge learned from internet"
 - "Commented [MB]: Beathing activies"
 - "Commented [MB]: The effect of the breathing activities on the stutter"
 - "Commented [MB]: Reason that lessen the stutter"

In a new document, I developed overarching categories for these codes (Saldaña, 2021). I categorised the coded data based on thematic correspondence, grouping codes that reflected similar underlying concepts. After generating a comprehensive list of codes from the dataset, I embarked on a process of code refinement. This involved systematically reducing and organising the codes into a coloured table for enhanced clarity. To facilitate easy differentiation between categories during analysis, I selected a unique colour for each category within the table. The aim of doing this is to refine the analysis by sorting out the codes into meaningful order and making the coding process transparent. Combining the codes allows for forming a thematic category for this research. This process of organising these categories is to facilitate theme development. In this sense, a category is a code but of a higher order as it identified areas of agreement and disagreement within the research topics. In other words, this analysis process revealed potential similarities and differences across the reported data.

Figure 10 An example of the Categorisation process

Labelling "Aggoun"	Hassan: During adolescence, negative experiences occur when classmates mock stuttering as a joke, which hurts the child who stutters. They can be bullied; classmates joke and laugh at them. This behaviour may also come from; yelling, mocking them in the classroom, and using offensive terms like Aggoun , (expressing disappointment) ... [when the child wants to participate (expresses disappointment and moving his head from side to side to indicate that they will not let them participate)]... These things happen, and when you interview teachers, they will tell you.	Commented [MB8]: Teachers' discrimination Commented [MB9]: Presence of stigma in Algeria Commented [MB10]: Parents as source of stigma Commented [MB11R10]: Unintended stigmatising attitude (comparison)
	Nour: Stigma exists in our society, starting with parents. Mothers often compare their children to siblings who do not stutter. Many mothers have admitted calling their children 'Aggoun' , telling them to speak correctly because it embarrasses them. Comparisons are common; a mother might say, 'When I visit my family, my nephew the same age as my son speaks very well.' [When the child hears this (she paused, her facial expression showing empathy)]... The issue is that his mother is the main link between him and society.	Commented [MB12]: Labelling Commented [MB13]: Negative impact of comparison of Commented [MB14]: Comparison between children who
	Ahmad: The majority of individuals who stutter face bullying due to a lack of understanding about what stuttering actually entails. In our society, the term "Aggoun" is commonly used , particularly in urban areas, to describe those who stutter. This term is often used in a derogatory manner, and even within families, individuals who stutter may be subjected to imitation and ridicule, albeit unintentionally.	Commented [MB15]: Bullying and lack of knowledge Commented [MB16]: Labelling Commented [MB17]: Negative attitudes from family
	Leya: There are some cases who starts to stutter at the school age, and their classmates hurt them by calling them Aggoun, and this term affects him a lot.	Commented [MB18]: Unintentional stigmatising attitudes Commented [MB19]: Stuttering onset
	Lama: Some of these attitudes happen everywhere, not just in the classroom. As long as he is alive, he will encounter many negative experiences. For instance, they may call him 'Aggoun' . The teacher should do their best to educate the students because, at this stage, our schools don't provide enough support. The teacher should educate and help him, giving advice. Do you understand? [There are cases where even the parents say things like 'Aggoun' to him...]	Commented [MB20]: Labelling Commented [MB21]: Existence of stigma Commented [MB22]: Labelling Commented [MB23]: Reaction to stigmatising attitudes
	Safa: the first things I point at are the negative comments, for instance, do not play with him he is Aggoun , this word we hear it a lot in or society...	Commented [MB24]: Labelling Commented [MB25]: Labelling Commented [MB26]: Labelling Commented [MB27]: Bullying from society
	[When it come to school, for teachers and students, they call them Aggoun...]	

5.3.3. Searching for Themes

According to Saldaña, coding and categorisation involve labelling data segments, however, themes represent a higher level of analysis that arises from interpreting and connecting these codes (2016). In this stage, I analysed the codes and categories rather than data to search for themes (Elliott, 2018). Knowing that I have used an inductive approach where I focused more on shaping the analysis based on the reported data (Miles et al., 2020). I remained flexible with analysing the codes and categories, and I avoided imposing previously defined patterns on the data. Accordingly, this stage demanded critical thinking and a reflexive approach to ensure a rigorous and well-considered analysis. As Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest, themes do not emerge from the data, however, it is the role of the researcher to reflect and interpret the participants' responses to construct meaningful patterns. Microsoft Word facilitated this process as I could add columns, move rows in the same tables and organise a codebook. By grouping related themes, I was able to establish clear connections between these emerging themes and the original research questions.

Figure 11 An example of the process of developing themes and subthemes

Themes for speech language therapists		
Categories	Sub-Themes	Theme
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academic Definition of Stuttering - General Definition of Stuttering - Defining Stuttering as a Deficit - Associating Stuttering to Breathing - Physical Description of Stuttering (Secondary Behaviours of Stuttering) - Explaining Stuttering in a Way that Matches Caregivers' Understanding 	Understanding of the Nature of Stuttering	Perceptions and Knowledge about Stuttering
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diagnosis Before Treatment - Relying on Parents to Understand the Child's Environment - Breathing Irregularities - Psychological Issues or Traumas - Parental Mistreatment - Attachment to Parents - Genetic Factors - Acquired/Aggravated Factors 	Perceptions of Stuttering Aetiology	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - François le Huche - Diagnosis Before Treatment - Treatment Program Based on Each Case - Breathing and Relaxation - Breathing Activities - Psychological Support - Chance for Improvement Only - Chance for Recovery - Quran as an Additional Activity - Singing as Additional Treatment - Swimming as Additional Treatment for Breathing - Natural Recovery Approach 	Treatment Approach for Stuttering	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adolescence and Hormonal Changes - Effects of Hormonal Changes Beyond Stuttering - Avoidance (Men Avoid Talking to Women) - Follow-up Disorders - Isolation 	Awareness of the Impact of Stuttering	

5.3.4. Reviewing Themes

By finishing the previous stage, I have developed a clear picture of the themes and the sub-themes that could tell a story using the datasets (Braun and Clarke, 2013). In this phase, I have carefully reviewed and improved these lists of themes. This process is important to improve the quality of the themes and whether they are appropriately fitting with the codes and the collected data (Braun and Clark 2013, p. 233). Hence, I repeatedly reviewed and adjusted the themes to ensure they directly addressed the research questions. To facilitate this process I adopted a visual thematic mapping approach to explore the hierarchical relationships between code categories, themes, and sub-themes, (Braun and Clarke, 2013). I constructed a thematic map using Microsoft Word based on the codes, categories, and themes identified earlier. While other software options exist for thematic mapping, I opted for Microsoft Word due to my familiarity with its editing tools and the ease with which I could manipulate elements within the document. This process yielded three main themes presented and discussed in a separate chapter with several sub-themes associated with each theme.

5.3.5. Defining and Naming Themes

At this stage, I have defined the themes and organised them in a coherent order to start writing the story that the data is reporting.

Figure 12 Final themes for discussion

Final themes for discussion 1
Knowledge about the nature of stuttering and stigma
Knowledge about the cause of stuttering and stigma
Knowledge about the treatment of stuttering and stigma
Knowledge about the impact of stuttering and stigma

Final themes for discussion 2
Social stigma and stuttering
Labelling children who stutter as Aggoun
Negative attitudes towards children who stuttering

Final themes for discussion 3
Education and raising awareness
Ignoring negative attitudes and stigma acceptance
Student and teacher relationship

5.3.6. Presenting and Discussing Themes.

This final phase of the analysis is referred to as the writing-up stage. A thorough analysis and discussion of the data are presented in the following chapters 6,7,8. All the data is written and presented to produce a story that relates to the research questions and theoretical framework using the excerpt from the interviews for further illustration. Hence, I inserted another column for further translating the coded passages of the interview transcript that will be reported in the findings. It is worth mentioning that this process required critical thinking as it was not based only on a description of the data.

5.3.7. Ethical Considerations for Data Analysis

Similar to the ethical considerations that guided the data collection, data analysis in this study followed ethical guidelines that ensured the validity and credibility of research findings. Hence, I had to be proactive in reducing intrusiveness and mitigating bias (Mirza, Mirza and Bellalem, 2023). Mirroring the approach of triangulating data collection methods, this study employed a triangulation of perspectives to enhance the validity and trustworthiness of its findings (Mirza, Mirza and Bellalem, 2023).

Before starting the data analysis, the anonymity of my participants was important, therefore, I refrained from disclosing any identifying details in the research, such as information about the interview's exact locations or participants' workplaces. Additionally, I assigned pseudonyms to all participants that were chosen based on a random selection process and reflected common Algerian names. This approach minimizes the risk of participants being identified.

During the analysis, I was very cautious in the vocabulary I used to avoid causing harm to participants or children who stutter, given the sensitive nature of this research, which explores stigma and stuttering. In some instances, participants used terms that are considered to be negative or offensive such as the word "Aggoun". In similar cases, I explained these terms in English (meaning dumb) within the discussion and presentation of the findings, however, I maintained the original wording in the data to preserve the authenticity and accuracy of the data.

The following chapters 6, 7, and 8 will present the findings of this study.

6. Chapter Six: Presentation of the Findings

Perceptions and Knowledge about Stuttering

6.1. Introduction

Understanding stakeholders' perceptions and knowledge of stuttering is crucial in this research, particularly for informing educational practices and developing targeted interventions for children who stutter in Algeria. Besides, stakeholders' knowledge directly impacts their attitudes towards stuttering and the types of interventions they may utilise. Addressing these attitudes is essential for mitigating the stigma often associated with stuttering and building inclusive learning environments (See Seitz and Choo, 2022). The current chapter addresses the first research question of this study:

What is the depth and scope of the Algerian stakeholders' knowledge of stuttering?

Guided by the detailed methodology and data analysis presented in Chapter 5, the findings from the three participant groups (speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers) developed the following sub-themes related to their knowledge of stuttering: Stakeholders' Understanding of the Nature of Stuttering; Stakeholders' Perceptions of Stuttering Aetiology; Stakeholders' Familiarity with Treatment approach for Stuttering; Stakeholders' Awareness of the Impact of Stuttering. Together, these subthemes represent the depth of stakeholders' knowledge of stuttering. While they are presented separately in this chapter, they will be brought together in Chapter 9 to provide a comprehensive answer to the first research question.

This chapter aims to achieve two primary objectives. The first objective is to present the findings related to stakeholders' knowledge and perceptions of stuttering. This includes presenting participant experiences and how these experiences shaped their understanding of the disorder. The second objective is to provide a comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the findings. Combining qualitative data analysis with direct quotations from participants will offer detailed insights into stakeholder perspectives on stuttering. The quotation of teachers and speech-language therapists is followed by the name of the participant, their gender, and their years of experience (YOE).

The chapter adopts a thematic approach, analysing the findings related to each sub-theme within each participant group (speech-language therapists, mothers, and teachers) separately. This initial analysis will be followed by a comprehensive discussion that explores potential variations in stakeholder knowledge and perceptions across the groups. Furthermore, the participant's responses in all chapters were primarily influenced by their closeness to both individuals who stutter and speech-language

therapists and the research that they have conducted regarding this fluency disorder. The three groups of participants had different experiences and motives that made them read and learn about stuttering. The following section presents the results of the Algerian speech-language therapists.

6.2. Speech-language Therapists

This section delves into the knowledge and understanding of stuttering held by Algerian speech-language therapists. Overall, they have demonstrated a better understanding of stuttering's core nature compared to the other groups, as they have effectively explained it not only in this study but also to parents and caregivers regardless of their level of education. Moreover, they identified psychological factors as a common cause, in addition to some other attributions that vary based on individual cases. Notably, all speech-language therapists primarily utilised the François Le Huche treatment approach for stuttering, they have emphasized controlled breathing as a treatment strategy. Furthermore, their direct work with individuals who stutter provided valuable insights into the disorder's psychological effects, potentially making them more knowledgeable about the broader impact compared to other participant groups.

6.2.1. Understanding of the Nature of Stuttering

Algerian speech-language therapists exhibited a consistent grasp of stuttering's core characteristics. Interestingly, while their understanding of the disorder itself seemed similar, their formal definitions differed slightly. This variation aligns with Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage (2021) observations on potential differences in defining stuttering. This observation suggests a potential disparity between theoretical knowledge acquired during academic training and its real-world implementation. One of the speech therapists provided a detailed definition of stuttering stating the following:

"The academic definition of stuttering is a disorder that can be psychological or organic. One type of stuttering is chronic, where the stutterer does not have specific letters or words that consistently trigger stuttering. While others may speak without stuttering except for certain letters, the stutterer may struggle with particular letters, such as 'A' sounds and 'Q' (ق in Arabic), which involve throat, labial, or alveolar articulation, did you get it? These are the letters that they struggle with the most. Sometimes the stuttering is mild, with slight interruptions, followed by fluent speech. Yet, the complete blocks can occur when trying to articulate certain letters. There are two types of stuttering; one characterised by blocks on any letter or sound, and another where specific letters or words consistently trigger the block during speech. That is it!" (Hassan, Male, 14 YO).

Hassan has provided a long-detailed definition of stuttering, pointing out that it is academic. He explained that this disorder could be either psychological or organismal. While these factors are

relevant, research reported many other theories to understand the causes of stuttering (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021), including the above factors mentioned by Hassan. Hassan further distinguished between types of stuttering. He explained that those with chronic stutter have some difficulties pronouncing certain sounds but cannot identify which sound they struggle with. Therefore, it is difficult for them to anticipate and manage their stutter, which persists. On the other hand, those who achieve fluency are aware of which sounds and words are problematic and actively avoid them. Although many factors have been highlighted to predict stuttering recovery (Sugathan and Maruthy, 2021), however, the quotation above indicates that the possibility of recovery is related to the awareness of stuttering triggers, which was not highlighted by other studies. Hassan highlighted that some letters provoke the block and create issues during the speech, such as labial, alveolar, or throat sounds. Furthermore, the severity of the stutter is from complete blocks to mild stutter that can be hardly noticeable, and this is related to some letters and sounds that trigger stuttering. In some cases, these sounds are known; in other cases, however, the stuttering can occur at any time with no specific sounds that cause it. In the same vein, Mersov and De Nil (2021) referred to the stuttering anticipation types; as general and specific. Unlike the argument of Hassan, these two types are not related to sounds only, as they explained that the general stutter is related to different aspects such as the stutter's situation, setting, and even time. In contrast, the specific stuttering is related to specific sounds or words (Mersov and De Nil, 2021, p. 2). Hassan's perspective highlights the potential influence of specific sounds in stuttering; however, it is crucial to encompass various factors, including motor control and other contributing elements. This broader perspective allows for a more detailed comprehension of stuttering and its underlying mechanisms. While Hassan's definitions focused more on the cause of stuttering, other speech-language therapists shared the same knowledge shown in the above definition but concisely described how the stutter occurs:

"Stuttering is a disorder that affects spoken language. It disrupts the speech rhythm and its units. A child who stutters tends to experience pauses when he starts speaking, for reasons I will discuss later" (Safa, Female, 4 YOE).

"Stuttering occurs as repetitions and pauses in speech fluency. The individual involuntarily repeats sounds or speech units, unable to proceed in speech. We can observe difficulties in breathing processes during exhalation and inhalation, as stuttering is linked to breathing issues. We may also notice other speech behaviours that fluent speakers typically do not exhibit" (Maya, Female, 6 YOE).

Safa and Maya's definition aligns more closely with other scholars' explanations compared to Hassan's. They delved more into the nature of stuttering and how it occurs in spoken language. Safa focuses on the disruption of spoken language fluency and the presence of blocks, which aligns with

the core characteristics of stuttering (See Ramzan *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, Maya provided a similar definition but was more succinct, where she addressed the stutterer's breathing and speech behaviours. She explained that these blocks and repetitions are involuntary and disrupt the speech flow (SheikhBahaei and Maguire, 2020; Busan *et al.*, 2022b) and followed by bodily movement of the stutterers during the speech act as unusual compared to the speech behaviours of individuals who do not stutter (See Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Furthermore, she said that it is noticeable that the stutterer's breathing process is unbalanced during the speech. Accordingly, based on the above quotations, speech-language therapists demonstrated valuable insights and a comprehensive understanding of stuttering.

That being said, as previously mentioned, Speech therapists often opt to simplify the definition of stuttering when explaining it to parents based on their educational level, or even to the children themselves. This is because speech therapists rely on the cooperation of both parents and children who stutter to follow the treatment protocols at home. This demonstrates their understanding of stuttering, which occurs by simplifying their academic knowledge to the caregivers' or the stutterers' level of comprehension. All speech-language therapists agreed to use an alternative explanation of the concept of stuttering that is easy for anyone to understand regardless of age or level of education, thus; One of them stated the following:

"When explaining a child's case to a parent who comes to seek help, I avoid using academic language. Instead, I simplify my language using dialect to be easily understood by everyone, regardless of their educational level" (Nour, Female, 3 YOE).

In the above extract, Nour emphasises the importance of providing caregivers with clear explanations about stuttering. This understanding empowers them to better support their children, recognising the need for accessible language over technical words. Speech-language therapists, like Hassan, prioritise a straightforward approach. Therefore, they tend to explain the stutter by explaining the process of speaking and the issues that affect fluency and cause it. Hassan utilises the following explanation when engaging with caregivers and children:

"To simplify stuttering, it occurs when a person cannot engage in correct abdominal respiration; he primarily breathes with his chest. Stuttering is characterised by a block in speech, especially where he cannot speak aloud, or he is under pressure. When uncomfortable, the individual tends to inhale air through their mouth. Typically, we exhale and breathe out air through our mouths when talking. What is "talking"? Speech involves the movement of air through the speech apparatus, producing sounds. This respiratory issue is what defines stuttering in simpler terms, making it understandable to all, not just academically" (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE).

In his approach, Hassan underlines the significance of understanding the role of breathing in the treatment protocol. He highlights that individuals who stutter often rely on chest breathing rather than the preferred abdominal breathing. Consequently, speech-language therapists prioritise conveying this information succinctly, reserving the academic definition for educational contexts. Their primary objective is not to educate parents extensively on stuttering but rather to equip them with practical insights that are beneficial to treatment. This strategy ensures that caregivers receive appropriate information tailored to facilitate effective therapeutic interventions.

6.2.2. Perceptions of Stuttering Aetiology

The expertise of speech-language therapists affords them an advantage in elucidating the underlying causes of stuttering since they have specialised training and experience in the field. This section aims to report the breadth of knowledge possessed by speech-language therapists regarding the aetiology of stuttering, drawing upon both general understanding and insights constructed from their experiences working with individuals who stutter in Algeria. Crucial to their practice is to identify factors contributing to stuttering, as this builds the basis for adapting effective therapeutic interventions. This section delves into the various factors reported by the participants as causes of stuttering, including psychological aspects, breathing patterns, imitation, and neurological factors. Notably, the data demonstrated an emphasis on the role of psychological trauma in provoking the stutter, which aligns with some studies (E.g. Al-Khaledi, Lincoln, McCabe and Alshatti, 2014).

Before starting the treatment of stuttering speech-language therapists tend to identify the cause of the stuttering. This allows for tailored therapeutic interventions, improving treatment outcomes, and empowering individuals with the knowledge to effectively manage and cope with the condition (Junuzovic-Zunic, Sinanovic and Majic, 2021). In the same vein, Nour argued that the first question we should ask about stuttering is why these individuals stutter, *“The first thing we should know is the cause behind stuttering”*. She explained further, *“When you fix the cause that makes him stutter, he will recover”*. This perception was shared by all participants, indicating their awareness of the importance of developing a solid understanding of the causes of stuttering, as recovery is closely related to identifying the source of the stuttering onset. With this respect, one of the speech-language therapists stated the following:

“When we confirm that individuals who stutter do not have any neurological disorder, we always ask the parents to inform us about any possible incidents that might have caused the disorder so we can tailor our treatment accordingly” (Maya, Female, 6 YOE).

In the above excerpt, Maya explained that the stutterers must be diagnosed first to identify the cause of stuttering. Furthermore, she pointed out that those not diagnosed with neurological issues are asked to share with her any incidents that happened before the stutter. This demonstrates that individuals who stutter will receive their therapeutic programme based on these shared incidents. Furthermore, it emphasises a potential link between stuttering and neurological factors. In the diagnosis, the parents play an essential role in ascertaining the stuttering's cause by providing speech therapists with the necessary information (Unicomb, Hewat and Harrison, 2019). This information could be related to the child's background and possible incidents that happened to the child before the stuttering onset.

To begin with, speech-language therapists in the current study provided some answers about the causes of stuttering. Among these causes, breathing issues were one of the attributing causes of stuttering. The speech-language therapists who participated in this study argued that breathing disturbance during speaking is one of the causes of stuttering. Hence, Safa stated the following:

“One of the reasons for a child’s stuttering could be the inability to balance the exhaling and inhaling process while speaking” (Safa, Female, 4 YOE).

According to Safa's statement, speech-language therapists in the current study explained that individuals who stutter tend to have unbalanced breathing that occurs as shortness of breath while speaking. Eventually, this causes them to stutter. Nevertheless, researchers tend to characterise breathing irregularities as one of the stuttering characteristics rather than a cause of stuttering (Nurnisa and Damanhuri, 2022). Still, in accordance with Safa, Hassan and Maya stated the following:

“Individuals who stutter... often the way they breathe is incorrect, that’s why they stutter. The oxygen will not reach the brain in a sufficient amount, which can lead to visible signs of nervousness, including facial flushing and signs of agitation. You notice his face going red; why is that? This is a result of the lack of oxygen in the brain.” (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE).

“We can notice issues with the exhalation and inhalation process in individuals who stutter during speech, as stuttering is associated with certain breathing difficulties” (Maya, Female, 6 YOE).

Hassan and Maya explained that stutters do not breathe correctly as they tend to have an unbalanced inhaling and exhaling process during speaking. This can be noticeable during the stutter, which occurs as nerves and frustration while speaking, and the face turns pink or red because of the insufficient oxygen that reaches the brain. Hassan described how the physical behaviours of the stutter appear due to the breathing issues, however, Maguire, Nguyen, Simonson and Kurz (2020) stated that the

stutter is accompanied by these motor movements. That is, breathing issues do not directly cause the stutter, yet they are considered a symptom of stuttering that could be followed by these motor movements as well.

Moreover, the participants have stated that breathing disturbance or irregularity is only one of several reasons. However, breathing was not the main reason for stuttering; instead, they stated that it could be a psychological trauma of a negative experience that affected the child. *“Breathing irregularities is not the primary cause; rather, it could be also related to psychological factors”* (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE). Interestingly, they would still use breathing activities to treat stuttering (see section 7.3.1.). It is still significant for speech-language therapists to know about any traumatic event that could be emotional or psychological, as one of the speech-language therapists stated: *“The child can develop stuttering because of psychological pressure”* (Nour, Female, 3 YOE). Nour stated the expression of psychological pressure as the trauma could be developed over time due to repetitive action or at any time due to a specific incident. Therefore, some speech-language therapists supported their arguments by sharing incidents about how some of the children who stutter, whom they used to help, developed stuttering. Nour explained that the parents shared these incidents with her to try to understand the cause of their children’s stutter:

“Breathing is the most common reason for stuttering; however, from a theoretical perspective, the causes of stuttering are more psychological, such as fear, anxiety, shyness, parental divorce, or prolonged separation between parents and children” (Safa, Female, 4 YOE).

“Some of the parents have admitted that they have made a mistake when trying to discipline their children in a way that affected them negatively...Some mothers came to treat their children, and one of them told me that she used to lock her child in a dark room as a form of punishment for misbehaviour” (Nour, Female, 3 YOE)

Safa explained that the main theory that could explain stuttering is breathing irregularities. However, she also stated some psychological issues, such as *“Fear, anxiety, shyness, parental divorce, or prolonged separation between parents and children”* arguing that they could cause the child to stutter. Moreover, Nour stated that the parents claimed that their child’s stutter resulted from their punishment. Childhood moral instruction is crucial for life (Birhan *et al.*, 2021). However, the way of disciplining the child is crucial since the early years are the most formative and have a permanent impact (Birhan *et al.*, 2021). Nour shared this incident that the mother thinks affected her child psychologically. This incident was a repetitive punishment action by isolating her child in a dark room. Consequently, this punishment severely impacted the child to the point that it traumatised them,

therefore, the child developed a stutter. The same speech-language therapist shared another incident saying the following:

"Some mothers have a tendency to leave their child alone at home while they go grocery shopping, which can create a shock for the child upon waking up alone and not finding their mother. This kind of experience may contribute to the development of stuttering in children" (Nour, Female, 3 YOE).

In the above quotation, the mother intended to leave her child home alone, not realising that he would be frightened when he woke up alone. Eventually, the child woke up to find himself alone with nobody with him at home. Furthermore, the distance between the child and his parents is among the reasons mentioned by the speech-language therapists of this study that affects the child psychologically and eventually causes the stutter. This distance could happen because of work duty, divorce, or other reasons.

"I once had a case where a father worked on a rotating schedule; one month close to home and the next month far away. Interestingly, when the father was away, the child experienced speech blocks, but these blocks disappeared when the father returned, almost as if the child transformed into a different person" (Safa, Female, 4 YOE).

Safa has explained that there are other conditions that the parents cannot control which affect the child. For example, working far from home could be challenging for both the child and the parents. This was one of the cases she treated, where the child stutters when the father is working away from home and disappears suddenly once the father is home with him. This can be explained in different ways, such as the child's attachment to the father and his fear of losing him, thinking his father will not return home and he will never see his father again. The majority of speech therapists who participated in this study attributed the causes of stuttering to psychological traumas and provided many incidents to support their argument. However, many researchers have considered that stuttering is not a result of that frightening event or because the individual is shy, as it is a wrong belief (Elrefaie, Ella, Halim and Gobran, 2022; Węsierska and Weidner, 2022; Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021).

Finally, Speech-language therapists have mentioned other factors that cause the stutter. Safa has mentioned that the stutter could be genetic, saying that *"Stuttering could be genetic"* (Safa, Female, 4 YOE). This aligns with some studies suggesting that the stutter could be inherited (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Although, the majority have clearly explained that the stutter is thought to be attributed to genetic factors, some of them demonstrated their disagreement. They have explained the child aggravates it after imitating it from his parents or those who interact with them. Hassan argued that stuttering could not be inherited, saying, *"No, it is not inherited, it is acquired, stuttering*

is acquired.” (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE). Similarly, Maya explained that the child imitates his environment; that is to say, if he has a close one who stutters, he will try to imitate how they speak. “It becomes an entrenched habit” (Maya, Female, 6 YOE). However, Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage (2021) argued that developing stuttering by imitating others is considered a stuttering myth that cannot be true, although there is no data that falsifies it.

The following section discusses the treatment approaches used by speech-language therapists in Algeria to treat stuttering.

6.2.3. Treatment Approach for Stuttering

The previous section reported the underlying causes of stuttering as perceived by speech-language therapists in Algeria. Speech-language therapists who participated in this study emphasise the importance of understanding the causes of stuttering in providing the appropriate therapy for each individual. However, as long as the cause is not neurological, the findings revealed an overreliance on a single treatment method in Algeria. While speech-language therapists reported various activities beneficial for improving children’s fluency, their primary focus appears to be on regulated breathing followed by relaxation techniques. Although knowledge existed regarding helpful fluency-enhancing activities, the speech therapists primarily utilised only one approach based on François Le Huche stuttering treatment approach.

Speech-language therapists focus more on regulated breathing during the treatment period, even if the cause of stuttering is psychological; however, the programme is still developed according to the severity and the age of the stutter. All of the speech-language therapists in this study share the same therapeutic programme to regulate the breathing process of the stutterers. Before starting the treatment, they make a complete diagnosis to confirm that the stutter does not result from other neurological disorders. The second step is to identify the cause of the stutter to address it with the right therapeutic programme. Accordingly, one of the speech therapists stated the following:

“To develop a treatment program for stuttering, we create a comprehensive file that includes a clinical assessment to understand the child’s background and potential causes of the stutter. Here, the parents answer questions about the child’s developmental history, such as whether the child had speech delay, or other experiences during childhood to identify psychological or other contributing factors. Treatment plans are tailored based on the child’s file, because it differs according to the case of each individual. Regarding the activities, we often include relaxation and breathing exercises in our therapy, following the methods of François Le Huche, I do not know if you know him” (Lama, Female, 4 YOE).

“The protocols that we follow... We call them treatment protocols; you cannot apply the treatment protocol 100% on each case. You adapt it according to your understanding of the case, according to their age and educational level. So, when it is something related to children, here, you try to simplify it as much as you can so that the parents can understand and help their children at home”. (Hassan, Male, 14 YO).

Speech-language therapists in Algeria refer to the stuttering treatment programme as “treatment protocols”. The parents of children who stutter help speech-language therapists create a history record for their children to investigate and understand the causes of their stutter. This guides Speech therapists in developing the treatment programme for children who stutter. Although there are several approaches to stuttering therapy (See Gupta, Chandra, Dautenhahn and Loucks, 2022), all Algerian speech therapists follow the treatment approach of “François Le Huche”, and they focus on abdominal breathing treatment. Hassan explained that stuttering cases are different; therefore, not the same treatment protocol is followed for all stutterers. This demonstrates the speech-language therapists’ awareness of the different needs of each individual who stutters (See Gupta, Chandra, Dautenhahn and Loucks, 2022). Hassan stated that the educational level and the age of the stutterer are significant in deciding on therapy. It should be simplified as the parents are also involved in the treatment because they help their children with the activities at home. Similarly, Nour explained that speech therapists work cooperatively with parents when treating their children.

“Positive results from stuttering treatment can typically be achieved within 3 to 6 months, especially with parental cooperation. However, some parents do not want to be involved; some do not care as they do not even know their child’s date of birth. I try to dispel negative expectations by sharing success stories of individuals who have overcome stuttering, as some parents think the stutter has ruined their child’s future. I emphasise that I am just a guide and the therapy is a collaborative effort with parents most of the treatment is done at home. Some parents expect immediate results from the first few sessions, but as a speech therapist I only correct the child’s pronunciation. I avoid using sophisticated language; I use language that suits the parents’ level and ask for simple activities that do not require expensive equipment. Otherwise, they would stop the therapy.” (Nour, Female, 3 YO).

Nour provided a complete picture of the therapy and the struggle that they might face with parents of children who stutter in Algeria. She explained that some of the parents in Algeria do not like to be involved in the treatment, which affects the treatment results. The parent’s role is crucial in stuttering therapy because there will be follow-up exercises for children to do at home for quicker results. Speech therapists in Algeria simplify the activities for parents to ensure that they can help their children. Furthermore, the equipment may not be affordable to all parents; therefore, speech

therapists advise them to work with available and cheap equipment. The above excerpt demonstrated the speech therapist's awareness of the obstacles they face during the treatment process, which explain the speech therapist's use of an easy approach and simple language to facilitate it for the children and caregivers. This could play a crucial role in highlighting potential solutions for a successful therapeutic programme. The activities are mostly related to regulated breathing and psychological support.

"In addition to speech therapy, psychologists provide sessions for individuals who stutter, especially when fear or other emotional issues are identified as the cause. Once a final diagnosis is made and the underlying cause of the stutter is identified, we start the therapy sessions. We often recommend attending Quranic schools, which can be very beneficial. If you notice, stutterers do not stutter while reading the Quran or singing due to the rhythmic nature of these activities, and that is what the stutterer needs to be fluent (rhythm). The Quran gives them the fluency they need, and I incorporate Quran recitation into my therapy sessions. Additionally, I recommend swimming as it helps improve the stutterer's breathing process, with activities that align with our therapeutic breathing exercises. On the other hand, parents play a critical role in nurturing their child's self-confidence as part of the social treatment process." (Safa, Female, 4 YOE)

"Speech-language therapists provide both psychological and physiological treatment for stuttering. We assign general activities and tailor specific activities according to each individual's case. These activities focus on breathing exercises targeting the chest and stomach, rhythm exercises, and voice activities to regulate breathing and voice production. Many stutterers struggle to balance their breathing process with voice production, and these activities help address that challenge" (Ahmad, Male, 7 YOE).

Safa identified several key areas to address in stuttering treatment, including psychological factors, speech rhythm, breathing techniques, and social aspects. Many participants linked stuttering to psychological issues. Therefore, psychological therapy is often considered an integral part of stuttering treatment, ensuring that both the speech and mental well-being of the individual are addressed. This demonstrates that speech therapists in Algeria avoid focusing solely on one aspect of the disorder, knowing that this speech disorder is followed by psychological issues, especially during school-age years and adolescence (See Jones *et al.*, 2021). Ahmad explained that the types of activities that speech-language therapists do to treat the stutter aim to balance breathing and sound production. In addition to the core therapeutic program, the speech therapists recommend supplementary activities that can enhance the therapy. These activities can also have a social element when practised with a group. Nonetheless, most of the activities aim to correct the breathing process. For example, swimming can be beneficial for regulating breathing, which can impact stuttering. Safa

also noted the importance of rhythmic speech flow for stutterers. She suggested activities like joining Quranic schools, as the rhythmic structure of the Quran can help individuals practice speaking with rhythm and potentially improve fluency. Singing can also be a helpful tool. Ultimately, the goal is to train the individual to incorporate rhythmic patterns into their natural speech. Finally, Safa emphasised the importance of building the child's self-esteem, highlighting the crucial role parents play in this process. This indicates that speech therapy is not only limited to the sessions of speech therapy, but it is open to other activities that could help with the fluency of individuals who stutter. However, the focus is on breathing only during the therapeutic session, which demonstrates a potential gap in knowledge of the other approaches of treatment for stuttering.

Speech-language therapists have different perceptions about whether the stutter can be cured. Some of them explained that the stutter comes and goes, and we cannot know if the child has completely recovered from it as it can appear again suddenly. One of the participants explained this by saying, *"We can help improve the child's fluency, but we cannot guarantee complete recovery"* (Safa, Female, 4 YOE). Safa acknowledges the potential for improvement while avoiding an absolute prediction of a cure. Nevertheless, other speech therapists argued, *"I have treated many cases, and they have recovered"* (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE). Drawing on his experience, Hassan suggests a higher chance of recovery with treatment, as he observed successful cases, supporting the potential for significant progress. However, he acknowledges the misconception in Algerian society that stuttering is a temporary childhood issue, emphasising the importance of early treatment to avoid any other complications in the future.

"In our culture (Algeria), there's a common belief that "a child will become fluent when he grows up" until he completes 5 years of primary school and then moves on to middle school, where they face sudden speech blocks due to adjustments to a new schooling system with rotating teachers for each subject. This is where the issues come from, do you understand? This transition and the hormonal changes during adolescence can worsen speech issues. Starting therapy between ages 6 and 10 makes treatment easier for the child, often turning it into an enjoyable activity. This is because most stuttering therapy focuses on abdominal respiration" (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE).

Interestingly, all the speech-language therapists stated that the parents tend to have the perception that the stutter is naturally cured and there is no need for treatment. The expression *"A child will become fluent when he grows up"* was said by all the participants of this study, speech-language therapists, mothers, as well as teachers, which confirms this perception. However, this cannot be taken for granted, as there are severe cases, and there are cases that get worse with time. Research has reported that stuttering can be cured during the first five years, as the chance during this age is

higher than ever without treatment. However, the percentage of recovery chance gets lower after the first 12 months of the stuttering onset (Carey, Onslow and O'Brian, 2021). Hassan explained that children aged 6 to 10 have a higher percentage of the recovery. Furthermore, he pointed out that stuttering treatment is mainly based on abdominal respiration.

6.2.4. Awareness of the Impact of Stuttering

In the previous section, the participants ensured psychological support for individuals who stutter as part of the therapeutic programme. The individuals who stutter share negative experiences that might affect their fluency with speech-language therapists. These experiences can then be addressed during therapy sessions. Accordingly, the Speech-language therapists who participated in this study demonstrated positive awareness of the psychological impact of stuttering compared to the other groups. Thus, they reported that children who stutter in Algeria face many difficulties due to negative reactions from their social environment. This lack of support can begin within the family, extend to the neighbourhood, and persist even in school settings. The speech therapists emphasise that stuttering itself may not be the core issue; rather, it's how others react to it that creates difficulties. They believe these negative behaviours and attitudes have a stronger impact on adolescents compared to younger children. One of the speech therapists has shared two cases he treated, trying to give a picture of what adults who stutter go through, which can happen to any adolescent as well:

"It's not necessarily the stuttering itself, but rather hormonal changes that can lead to psychological issues for many individuals... I have a case of a 29 or 28-year-old who started isolating himself... Due to hormones... He avoids speaking with people and he does not have friends. He used to own a shop but eventually closed it, and now he's unemployed. He couldn't! and it is particularly challenging as he is at the age where marriage is expected. According to his brother and family, you have no idea how he used to avoid interacting with women. Even when he had the shop, he preferred to ask someone else to speak with women on his behalf to avoid stuttering during conversations" (Hassan, Male, 14 YO).

Hassan explained that hormones are the leading cause for developing psychological issues for stutters, as they may prefer to isolate themselves to avoid social interaction. Similarly, some studies reported that adults who stutter tend to have negative feelings because of their stutter in schools, such as isolation (Gerlach-Houck, Kubart and Cage, 2023). Hassan strengthened his argument by sharing a case of one of the individuals who developed a severe psychological response to stuttering. He avoided speaking with women entirely due to embarrassment. However, the excerpt suggests that beyond the stuttering itself, several other factors contribute to the psychological well-being of

children who stutter. Following this, speech therapists emphasised the psychological impact on adolescents who stutter, clarifying that the core issue is not stuttering itself, but the bullying and negative social interactions that follow it.

"Adolescence is the most sensitive period for individuals who stutter, particularly for boys more than girls, as boys are expected to grow up to become a man but often face bullying due to their stuttering... This can have a detrimental impact on his personality that could also be followed by other disorders " (Nour, Female, 3 YOE).

"Low self-esteem is the most common issue resulting from stuttering, often due to direct or indirect bullying" (Linda, Female, 4 YOE).

"Among the psychological effects of stuttering is embarrassment. Stuttering, at home or school, can lead to anxiety, shame, isolation, and fear of society. Confidence plays a crucial role in overcoming these psychological challenges, enabling individuals to transition into adulthood and pursue careers successfully. Conversely, lacking self-esteem can hinder his ability to face with society" (Leya, Female, 6 YOE).

Speech-language therapists in Algeria emphasise that bullying, not stuttering itself, is the primary cause of psychological problems in children who stutter. Nour highlights the vulnerability of adolescents during their psychological development, explaining how stuttering can negatively impact their personality due to bullying. Linda reinforces this point, emphasising that bullying lowers self-esteem. As will be discussed further in Chapter 7, these psychological issues can then create further challenges in a child's education. Based on the above quotation, the participants demonstrated a positive awareness regarding the challenges and the impact of stuttering. However, it is important to highlight that not only bullying can affect children who stutter, as other studies reported the impact of stuttering on individuals, especially during instances of stuttering with others. The speech therapists observed that children who stutter might also face additional challenges beyond stuttering itself. Leya emphasises the importance of confidence in managing stuttering and living a fulfilling life without social and psychological difficulties. The speech therapists believe that children who stutter are more likely to be bullied, leading to stress, embarrassment, social withdrawal, and isolation. These issues often stem from low self-esteem. Consequently, the participants prioritise building self-esteem as a crucial approach to help children overcome these challenges. Stress is identified as a major factor impacting children who stutter.

The following section reports the results of mothers of children who stutter.

6.3. Mothers of Children Who Stutter

This section focuses on the mothers' understanding of stuttering, including its nature, causes, treatment, and effects on their children. The results suggest that mothers' knowledge is significantly influenced by their speech therapists. Since most mothers who participated in this study sought therapy for their children, their understanding is shaped by the speech therapists' expertise and their own observations and experiences. While mothers demonstrate awareness of what stuttering is, their descriptions tend to focus on observable behaviours. Their understanding of causes is often limited to their child's specific case, with some additional knowledge that is socially constructed. Treatment knowledge primarily comes from the speech therapist, focusing on activities that are practised at home. Mothers also reported various impacts of stuttering on their children, which will be reported further in this section.

6.3.1. Understating of the Nature of Stuttering

Based on the results the mothers' knowledge of stuttering was primarily built upon their experiences with their children and the guidance received from speech therapists. However, some mothers did report searching online to understand this speech disorder and help their children. One of the mothers confirmed that she commenced reading about it right after the onset of stuttering, stating, *"The moment I realised that my daughter has a stutter, I started researching and reading about it"* (Oum Yasmine). While the internet is not the primary source of information for most mothers, most of them did report seeking information online during the initial years of their child's stuttering onset. The aim of their research is not to learn mainly about the nature of stuttering, but to learn about its treatment. Some of the mothers said the following:

"Many people ask me about it, I mean, most of them know what stuttering is, but they want to know more if it is another thing. So, I just tell them that it is just stuttering... I never thought of developing my knowledge about it... I don't feel I need to do it, to be honest!" (Oum Ibrahim).

"Stuttering, according to Egyptian speech therapists, is a psychological issue. I encountered cases like my son, who had a severe stutter and introversion... My son's stutter was severe, but they said he will get better by repeated breathing exercises and psychological support, along with constant praise (Oum Reda).

Some mothers, especially those who have a certain level of education, stated that they have done some research about stuttering, yet their aim was to learn about the stuttering treatments. Oum Ibrahim pointed out that she does not consider that learning about stuttering would be beneficial to her, which explains her lack of motivation to improve her knowledge regarding stuttering. Further, she highlighted that people often ask about the type of speech disorder only, rather than seeking

deeper understanding. On the other hand, Oum Reda explained that her knowledge was based on Egyptian researchers, who argued that the stutter is primarily related to psychological issues. Similarly, many researchers reported that the stutter might result from emotional trauma (Maviş, Louis, Özdemir and Toğram, 2013; Singh and Kumar, 2021), as it can also develop some psychological issues (Jones *et al.*, 2021). Oum Reda stated that when she was doing her research, she found similar cases as the stutter of her child in terms of severity and the introverted personality. Therefore, based on those similarities, she followed the research advice regarding psychological support and that the treatment activities should be repeated constantly for faster recovery. However, she showed uncertainty regarding her knowledge as she said the following:

"I tried researching stuttering online, but the information was confusing with different definitions; I did not get it! However, I followed their advice, such as swimming and I used to help him practise breathing exercises at home" (Oum Reda).

"I watched some YouTube videos about stuttering, including stories of individuals who stutter. I just wanted to have an idea about it, but I focused more on how to manage the stutter " (Oum Iyad).

Oum Reda's experience highlights a significant challenge for parents seeking information about stuttering online. This challenge was due to the vast amount of contradictory and misleading information on the internet about stuttering that she encountered. This demonstrated her need for guidance in researching stuttering, for example, she could ask the speech-language therapist of her son for resources about it. Nevertheless, despite the confusion, she still followed the guidance and the pieces of advice she read online that she felt could be helpful to her son. Furthermore, Oum Iyad pointed out that she wanted to see how others overcame their stutter, but her main reason for doing the research was to help her child by following the experiences of others. Yet, it is important to mention that although many YouTube videos can be informative and helpful, still, there might still be some misleading information or fake stories. Therefore, it is very important to note that the parents of children who stutter should be guided and supported with credible resources and professional guidance that could help them develop their knowledge regarding stuttering.

Interestingly, only two mothers did not research stuttering despite the severity of their child's condition. One mother explained:

"I have not done much research about stuttering because I do not have the means that help me with that." (Oum Youcef).

"I don't know how to use the internet and do research like this. I just, aaah, I mean I could ask someone to do it for me but.... Yeah..." (Oum Aseel)

Unfortunately, some of the mothers reported that they had not searched and read about this disorder. Oum Youcef explained that she needed the means to do the research. Similarly, Oum Aseel pointed out that she does not know how to research on the Internet. Knowing that both Oum Youcef and Oum Aseel dropped out from school at a young age indicates that education could affect their research skills and eventually their knowledge. Given that the mothers who participated in this study have children who stutter, they have built more of their knowledge based on their experiences with their children and the speech therapist's advice. The mothers tend to imitate their children's stutter to describe it.

"When he starts speaking, you would think that his soul is getting out of him, aaaaaa, (imitating the stutter), hardly uttering the word" (Oum Reda)

"When she gets anxious or stressed, she stutters, Mmmm mama (imitating the stutter)" (Oum Aseel)

The mothers have described the stutter differently according to the stuttering severity of their children. Oum Reda has imitated her child's stutter to illustrate his stutter. She has explained that you get the feeling that he is dying once he begins to speak, as it is difficult for him to utter a word. Moreover, Oum Aseel pointed out that her child's stuttering severity is related to her comfort and discomfort. She also imitated her child's stutter to illustrate it, explaining that it comes again during a stressful situation. Accordingly, the mothers could describe the stutter according to what they notice in their children rather than give a general description or explanation of it. Furthermore, the majority did not describe stuttering in general, yet they tend to describe the stutter of their children.

"He struggles to utter the word immediately, and you can sense that something is sitting on his chest... His face turns red, very red, and he exerts great effort to respond... He keeps trying to speak, sometimes he cannot speak until he takes a deep breath. This is what I notice when my son stutters" (Oum Youcef).

Oum Youcef explained the stutter in more detail, describing her son's stutter, which shows that the stutter of her child is severe. Although she did not use academic sources, she was able to give a full descriptive picture of stuttering based on her experience. Her descriptions give a full definition of stuttering that covers the type of disfluency in speech and the physical changes during stuttering that are secondary effects of stuttering (See Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Interestingly, she pointed out that her son experiences difficulty breathing when speaking, which temporarily increases his blood pressure, which only could be reduced after taking a deep breath to eventually utter words.

All the mothers gave a detailed description of their children's stutter which made them aware of the nature of stuttering. Accordingly, the mothers demonstrated limited knowledge about the nature of stuttering as their understanding was solely based on their experience with their children.

The following section delves into the mothers' knowledge of the causes of stuttering.

6.3.2. Perceptions of Stuttering Aetiology

Knowing that the mothers of children who stutter have previous knowledge built on their experience with their children and the guidance of the speech-language therapists during the period of the speech therapy. However, they showed uncertainty when asked about the causes of stuttering. This appeared during the interview discussion as expressions such as, *"I am not sure"* (Oum Reda), *"This might be the reason why she stutters."* (Oum Yasmine). *"I don't know exactly"* (Oum Ibrahim). Nevertheless, only one mother was sure that a specific incident had caused the stutter of her child, saying, *"It is only after this incident my child started to stutter; he had never stuttered before"* (Oum Youcef). Overall, the results indicated that the parents have related the cause of stuttering to psychological issues more than any other causes. Some mothers also highlighted that there is a possibility that their children have genetically inherited the stutter by mentioning some of their relatives who have it. *"It could be genetic as they told me that his aunt used to stutter"* (Oum Reda). However, some of them have agreed that, generally, it could be inherited, but this is not the case for their children, saying, *"Yes, the stutter could be inherited"* (Oum Youcef).

The mothers argued that stutter results from psychological factors caused by emotional trauma or stress. In the same vein, many studies have reported that parents assume that stuttering is caused by some psychological issues (Safwat and Sheikhany, 2014; Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat, 2022). The mothers in this study have supported this argument by sharing some incidents that happened to their children and could provoke them to stutter. One of the mothers shared the following:

"I am not sure about the real reason for his stutter; sometimes, I start relating this to many incidents that happened to him in the past because we had a car accident, nothing happened to us, but he was terrified and shocked. Also, he fell once on his lip at my neighbour while playing with her child, but he was frightened; because he saw a lot of blood and did not find me with him. I even sometimes relate his stutter to fear instilled by his aunt who used to warn him about ghosts eating misbehaving children, but I am not sure exactly" (Oum Reda).

Oum Reda stated three different incidents that happened to her child; however, she expressed doubt saying that she is unsure about the cause of her child's stutter. Oum Reda mentioned three similar experiences in the three incidents, all related to the theme of "frightening" as she used the terms 'shocked', 'terrified', 'fearful', and 'frightened'. Nevertheless, all of these reasons could be translated

as psychological trauma. Many studies argued that stuttering could be caused by traumatic events, yet more evidence is needed as not all those who experience a traumatic incident would necessarily develop a stutter (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). In the same vein, one of the mothers also shared the same perspective that frightening is what caused her child's stutter as she was confident about it sharing the following specific incident:

"His father's friend used to play with him, and one day, he wore a ghost mask and scared him. His face turned pale, and he almost lost his breath. After that incident, I didn't immediately realise he was having difficulty speaking because it started gradually. He began having nightmares and complained of feeling like something was sitting on his chest. Over time, he started to stutter" (Oum Youcef).

Oum Youcef shared an incident that happened to her child as his father's friend pranked him. Her child was terrified because of this incident and started developing secondary reactions with time, such as having nightmares, difficulty breathing, and eventually developing stuttering. Despite the fact of being unconfident about the incidents that caused the stutter, still a strong agreement among mothers that there is a link between psychological traumas and stuttering. Following the argument that the stutter is a result of psychological or emotional trauma, some mothers have not specifically stated a terrifying incident, yet they still think that it is psychological. One of the mothers did not share her perspective of the cause of her daughter's stutter stating the following:

"My daughter started to stutter when her younger sister was born. I think it was a reaction because of her jealousy, but other than that, nothing specific has happened to her" (Oum Yasmine).

"When I tell my husband that our daughter has developed stuttering because she started imitating my sister's son (same age and he has stuttering), he makes fun of me, but I do think that sometimes she stutters for attention... but I am not sure" (Oum Aseel).

Oum Yasmine and Oum Aseel stated two different causes that they think are the main reason their children started to stutter, yet both of these reasons are related to seeking attention. Oum Yasmine in the above extract stated that after the birth of her daughter's sister, she started to stutter, guessing that this might explain her daughter's stuttering onset, as she used the expression *"I think"*. Oum Yasmine used the term *"Jealousy"* to describe the psychological state of her daughter, yet the reason was still not obvious and the way she developed stuttering was not described. Similarly, Oum Aseel did not state an incident, but she explained that the stutter was gradually developed because of imitation. The mother did not give a confident answer as she said at the end of her answer *"I am not sure"*, besides the reaction of her husband that demonstrated his disagreement. Nevertheless, her answer aligns with the speech-language therapists who participated in this study, as they argued that

stuttering could be aggravated with time as a result of imitation. Nonetheless, the mothers have also believed that their children tend to stutter, especially when uncomfortable or stressed. Although this could not be the main reason behind the stutter, it is considered as a factor that affects the severity of the children's stutter. This has strengthened their belief that stuttering is psychological.

"Sometimes, when you see my child, you think the stutter has completely disappeared. Once the exam period starts, the stutter reappears" (Oum Reda).

"When my child does something wrong and is scared of my reaction, he stutters a lot. Otherwise, when he's playing outside with his friends, he barely stutters" (Oum Iyad).

Oum Reda noticed her child's stutter occurs especially during stressful periods such as exams, while it completely disappears sometimes. According to Constantino, Campbell and Simpson (2022), individuals who stutter are liable to stutter under stress caused by challenging factors that disable them, which leads to an increase in the disability if the impairment is not taken into consideration. Iverach *et al.* (2017) reported that among 102 teenage stutterers, a greater percentage of stress anticipates a more negative influence on their daily lives. Oum Iyad similarly related the severity of her child's stutter is influenced by his emotional state, as it fluctuates based on the level of stress and comfort in different situations. This latter is considered as one of the factors that provokes stuttering, nevertheless, it is not the main reason that developed the stutter in the first place.

On the other hand, the mothers raised the possibility that stuttering could be inherited when we discussed their general knowledge about the causes of it. However, the mothers explained this differently than the speech-language therapists' arguments, as they believed that the stutter could be genetically inherited. In other words, if one of the family members has a stutter, there is a chance that the child could stutter even if there is no contact between them. According to Chang, Garnett, Etchell and Chow (2019), Stuttering is a genetic illness; heredity is probably a factor in brain abnormalities related to the stutter, nevertheless, this hypothesis is not proven yet. The mothers argued that the stutter could be genetic. *"One of the family members mentioned that his aunt used to stutter; I have not met her before, so I do not know" (Oum Reda).* Oum Reda said that there is a possibility that her child inherited the stutter from his aunt as she was a stutterer. Nevertheless, she mentioned that her child never met his aunt to imitate her, as stated by the speech-language therapists. Furthermore, Oum Iyad showed her agreement that the stutter could be inherited, saying, *"Sometimes you find two or three individuals of the same family who stutter"*. Although the family can indicate a potential genetic connection, still more evidence is needed, especially since not all participants agreed that is

genetics. *"The stutter cannot be genetic. It is an illness, and the cause could be psychological and emotional trauma"* (Oum Youcef). As Oum Youcef believed stuttering is a result of an emotional trauma mainly. The results suggest that while mothers acknowledged the possibility of genetic factors in stuttering, they placed greater emphasis on psychological factors as a cause.

6.3.3. Treatment Approach for Stuttering

The majority of mothers sought the help of speech-language therapists and followed their guidance regarding their children's treatment. Based on the results the treatment consists of breathing activities that must be done during the therapeutic session and followed consistently at home at least once daily, as the role of parents is significant during the treatment of their children's stuttering (Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat, 2022). The data of this study showed that the mothers followed different treatment approaches according to the severity of the stutter of their children, besides having different speech therapists. However, they all reported that they ask their children to take a deep breath every time they struggle with uttering words. The mothers in this study also said that they read about it to learn how they could help their children.

"I came across many YouTube videos of individuals who stutter yet can recite the Quran fluently. When I asked her speech therapist about it, she encouraged me to enrol her in a Quranic school as reciting the Quran could help with her stutter... and I was surprised with the results to be honest, she does not stutter when she reads the Quran " (Oum Halima).

Interestingly, the majority of mothers pointed out the effectiveness of the Quranic recitation in enhancing the fluency of their children who stutter. It is worth mentioning that there is a lack of research that provides scientific evidence regarding the efficacy of Quranic recitation for stuttering. Nevertheless, there are many studies related to the effect of the Quran on individuals' anxiety and stress (See Moulaei et al. 2023). However, some of the speech-language therapists who participated in this study, such as Safa, pointed out that the Quran has a rhythmic flow that improves the fluency of individuals who stutter. Oum Halima did not provide any knowledge regarding the way this approach helped her daughter, and she used the word *"surprised"* demonstrating her doubt of this approach. She eventually argued that her daughter tends to read verses of the Quran without stuttering. Her Speech-language therapists also reported that reading or reciting the Quran could be a practice for children who stutter, which was approved by the majority of mothers as well. The fluency of children who stutter appears during the reciting, yet the stutter still occurs during their daily conversation. However, this is not considered as a therapeutic intervention, as the mothers use it as an additional exercise to the speech therapy sessions. One of the other additional exercises that was also reported by mothers in this study was swimming.

"I've heard a lot about swimming being good for correcting breathing, but I didn't try that with my son. Instead, I helped him with breathing exercises at home to ensure he didn't miss any. Now, I've stopped doing that, but we used to sit and do activities like blowing up balloons or passing a ball back and forth by blowing it on a long-edged rectangle plate. Sometimes, he repeats what he used to do with the speech therapist, putting one hand on his chest and the other on his stomach while practising breathing in and out" (Oum Ibrahim).

Oum Ibrahim has given a general picture of her child's treatment as her child had a mild to severe stutter and this treatment was based on breathing activities only. Swimming was one of the activities that the speech therapist advised as a treatment for stutter, which also tends to improve the breathing process. The mother stated that she used to make sure that her child does the breathing activities and every time she helps him with breathing activities. In addition, Oum Ibrahim explained that her child's speech therapist provides a direct speech therapist session consisting of breathing activities and other games, which are followed and practised at home as well. All the mothers who sought help from speech-language therapists tend to focus on breathing activities which seems to be the same. They also approved that there is a noticeable impact on the fluency of their children (See Sønsterud *et al.*, 2020; Brown, 2020). In addition, the majority of the mothers reported that besides regulated breathing therapy, speech therapists generally provide psychological support to their children. Oum Yasmine emphasised the fact that the speech-language therapist's treatment was effective and helped her child overcome these issues by saying the following:

"Because of the treatment, my daughter became fluent, but there was a possibility that it could get worse without the speech therapy. I think that the cure for stuttering is related to an individual's self-esteem. My daughter lacked confidence; she used to tell me that she does not believe in herself, and this is what she worked on in the treatment, and she succeeded." (Oum Yasmine).

Oum Yasmine's daughter had a mild stutter; therefore, the type of treatment was not as extensive as those who had severe stutter. Oum Yasmine believed that her daughter needed more psychological support to help her build more confidence and overcome her stutter. Although, there is a strong agreement among the majority of participants that confidence directly contributes to the fluency of children who stutter, yet confidence alone might not address issues of fluency. Stuttering is a speech disorder that could occur due to neurological factors as well (Koenraads *et al.*, 2020). Still, working on the child's self-esteem is crucial as it could reduce the stutter and anxiety that provoke the stutter. The mother associated the stutter with self-esteem, assuming the cure for stuttering is by developing

a strong personality. It is helpful for the child to be more confident when interacting with others without hesitation. Yet, it is important to note not all children who stutter have low self-esteem, therefore, using this approach should be based on individual differences, such as therapeutic strategies and psychological elements. In contrast, Oum Youcef was advised to follow a psychological treatment only, knowing that her child's stutter was severe, and he stopped after a year of treatment after seeing no improvement. Interestingly, the treatment was based on drawing activities aiming to understand the child's personality and help him psychologically.

"My child's speech therapist used to give him activities like drawing to understand his way of thinking through painting and colouring. She also talks to him while painting... She told us he would overcome it. I think she used this method to help him forget about the trauma" (Oum Youcef).

"He didn't complete the treatment because his father thought it was useless and saw no improvement... He believed the stutter would disappear naturally. Maybe if my son had completed the stuttering therapy program, he would have recovered" (Oum Youcef).

Oum Youcef explained that the stutter of her child developed because of an emotional trauma, "frighten." Therefore, the mothers tried to treat this trauma to cure their child's stutter. His treatment consisted of painting and talking therapy only. This demonstrates a narrow and potentially inaccurate view of stuttering treatment as they attributed the stutter of their child to psychological factors only. Although the mother stated that she always advises him to take a deep breath before speaking, and she noted that stutter could be related to breathing irregularities, they never sought the speech-language therapist's treatment. Therefore, it is important to seek for the speech-language therapist to identify the real cause behind the stutter of their children, hence deciding on the right treatment which could be a combination of evidence-based speech therapy with an appropriate psychological support. Nevertheless, Oum Youcef pointed out that her child did not finish the treatment as they saw no improvement. Therefore, his father decided that his son should stop the therapeutic programme and wait for him to recover naturally. Similarly, some studies have argued that the child could recover naturally without speech therapy (Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat, 2022; Kefalianos *et al.*, 2017; Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). This will lead them to adopt the approach of waiting for their kids to get fluent with time and ignoring the therapy during the onset of stuttering (Kefalianos *et al.*, 2017). However, Oum Youcef stated that her child had not recovered yet and that there would be a higher chance that he would have recovered if he had completed the speech therapy. Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat (2022) argued that the natural approach to recovery could differ from one person to another; therefore, knowing whether the child needs the treatment is not certain. On the other

hand, most of the mothers stated that they were aware of the natural approach, yet they preferred specialist advice.

“When I told my colleagues that I was taking my daughter to a speech-language therapist, one of them told me that he had a stutter and that my daughter would recover from it with time, but he still stutters from time to time; so, I believe that the stutter can be cured when treated”. (Oum Yasmine)

“It is always good to seek a specialist help, although I heard that some people could become fluent when they get a little older, but I was not sure if she is going to recover naturally or not” (Oum Halima)

Although Oum Yasmine stated that one of her colleagues advised her that her daughter would recover naturally without the treatment, knowing that he followed it still stutters. She believes that the stutter needs treatment despite the possibility of natural recovery. The expression *“could become fluent when they get a little older”* as stated by Oum Halima was stated by all participants of this study, which indicates that is common knowledge among Algerian society that stuttering is a speech disorder that could disappear naturally. Nevertheless, the majority of mothers shared the same perception that is always better to seek specialist help. Accordingly, based on the latter, despite the chance of natural recovery, the mothers are aware that they should seek the help of the speech-language therapist to avoid stuttering aggravation.

The mothers’ understanding of stuttering treatment largely reflected the approaches employed by the speech therapists. Their knowledge primarily focused on the specific treatment their children received, such as breathing exercises. The association between stuttering and psychological factors led many mothers to suggest therapy to address potential trauma and boost self-esteem. While some misconceptions persist, like stuttering disappearing over time, most parents demonstrated a positive awareness of the importance of early intervention through speech therapy.

6.3.4. Awareness of the Impact of Stuttering

The majority of mothers pointed out that their children who stutter developed several psychological issues due to their stutter such as frustration and aggressive attitudes, sadness, isolation, and low self-esteem. Thus, their children tend to self-isolate themselves and limit their interaction with others, as they develop avoidance behaviours. The parental reaction to the stutter is also crucial as it can affect the child socially and psychologically (Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat, 2022). Furthermore, the severity of the children’s stutter appeared to be correlated with the degree of its impact on their psychological well-being. It is significant to highlight that the reaction to stuttering differs based on gender and the individual’s personality. Based on their observation of their children, the parents who participated in this study reported similar reactions and psychological issues that boys experience in Algeria. The

parents' results demonstrate that their children, boys, who stutter tend to have more aggressive behaviours as a reaction to their stutter compared to girls who stutter. Girls tend to avoid social interaction more than boys, besides experiencing feelings of sadness. This also appeared in the teachers' interview discussions, where boys and girls who stutter in Algerian Middle Schools had different reactions to their stutter and negative attitudes towards them (see section 6.4.4.).

Interestingly, one of the mothers stated that her daughter's stutter was not that severe to impact her daughter profoundly.

"Stuttering did not affect my daughter much, but it can affect others with a severe stutter. If you interrupt a child who stutters, they may become quiet, avoid speaking, and become shy. When my daughter started to stutter, she faced this problem. She was embarrassed and afraid of being laughed at, but she got used to it. I explained to her that it wasn't a big deal or a disability that she would be ashamed of, and she overcame it. Now she speaks confidently and now she has become talkative (laughs)... She never stops talking " (Oum Yasmine).

Oum Yasmine described the anxieties of her child due to her stutter at the initial period of her stuttering onset. The anticipation of a negative reaction to her stuttering developed feelings of shame and embarrassment. The mother also pointed out that the same issue could happen to others with a severe stutter and affect them profoundly, yet this was not the case with her daughter. Knowing that the stutter of her daughter was barely noticeable, still she experienced a sort of perceived stigma that internalised negative social perceptions and attitudes towards her. It is important to mention that the mother's reaction in addressing her daughter's feelings to promote self-acceptance, played an important role in overcoming these initial anxieties. Furthermore, the use of the "she got used to it" demonstrates the child's ability to cope with her stutter and her internalised negative feelings, which aligns with Goffman's idea of normalisation (1963) where the child developed a mechanic to manage and minimise the impact of the stigma.

Furthermore, the other mothers of children with severe stutter reported many incidents describing their children's reactions to it. These reactions were mostly avoidance of social interaction or aggressive behaviours. Some of the mothers reported the following:

"He tends to become aggressive when he struggles with speech. When he can't find the words, he reacts with frustration" (Oum Reda).

"He has a short temper, especially with his sisters when it comes to his stuttering. They use his stuttering to mock him" (Oum Youcef).

"I have received comments from family members saying he is aggressive because he yells and gestures with his hands when he speaks. I always tell them that he does this to prevent stuttering; it helps him" (Oum Djed).

The mothers above provided a picture of how stuttering affected their children's behaviours. "Aggressive" behaviours, as described by the mothers were developed as a reaction to the stuttering. Oum Youcef similarly argued that her child could not control his frustration, mainly because of the remarks and bullying associated with his stutter. Oum Reda and Oum Djed explained that their children's inability to respond and defend themselves with words turned into what Oum Reda referred to as "aggressive". They argued that their child tends to navigate the challenges of stuttering by speaking loudly to not stutter, which aligns with the concept of the coping mechanism of the stigma (Goffman, 1963). Labelling this behaviour as "aggressive" may carry a negative connotation as it can reduce the value of their way of communication. With that being said, the mothers demonstrated their resistance to this labelling explaining their children's behaviours. The mothers' role of advocating for their children and challenging the negative perception is crucial, as it indicates the importance of family support in mitigating the stigma associated with stuttering.

Furthermore, the mothers added that the stutter affects the mood of their children, as any negative remark will lower their self-esteem or self-worth. *"I think that the cure for stuttering is related to the individual's self-esteem. My daughter lacked that"* Oum Yasmine. Participants shared the same response relating the psychological impact on their children mostly to their experiences of bullying not necessarily to their stutter. *"They use stuttering to mock him..."* Oum Youcef. The children developed a reaction that is mostly translated as "avoidance" that is sometimes followed by "sadness" as the most common psychological issue. Furthermore, children with severe stutter in Algeria tend to avoid social situations and interaction with others because of stuttering.

"I noticed that she was becoming quiet and started avoiding sitting with us, especially around family or guests, I mean she barely talks with us. So, I related that to her stutter, and I sought the help of a speech therapist." Oum Ritta

Oum Ritta observed her daughter's attitude which was a reaction to stuttering that highlighted a potential impact of stigma. The theory of stigma provides a lens to view how the negative societal perception and reaction to stuttering leads to feelings of shame and social avoidance. The internalisation of stigma appeared in the attitudes of Oum Ritta's daughter. Avoiding mixed contact and communication as she stated *"avoids sitting with us"* which means that she avoids gatherings that require speaking as a way for her to avoid reactions to her stutter. The mother noticed that and sought speech therapy for her daughter realising that her daughter does not only need psychological support but speech therapy sessions as well. This demonstrated the mother's awareness of the importance of both approaches in stuttering treatment.

The following section presents the teachers' results.

6.4. Middle School Language Teachers

Given the significant role teachers play in shaping students' experiences, investigating Algerian teachers' knowledge of stuttering is crucial to understanding the educational environment for students who stutter. The insights from the previous sections on speech-language therapists and mothers provide a foundation for underlying basic knowledge for this research, which likely lies somewhere between specialists' knowledge and experience-based understanding from mothers. The results suggest that teachers may have limited formal knowledge about stuttering. This could be explained by many factors that were mentioned by the participants. It appeared that teachers have not been trained in stuttering management. Nevertheless, some teachers expressed a willingness to learn more about the disorder to better support students in the classroom, as some of them asked speech therapists for guidance to manage stuttering in the classroom.

6.4.1. Understanding of the Nature of Stuttering

The interview process investigated the teachers' knowledge base by addressing two key areas, their formal training in working with students with disabilities and speech disorders, and their independent research efforts regarding fluency disorders. These questions aimed to identify the potential sources of their knowledge and perspectives on stuttering. The results reveal a concerning lack of training among many teachers. Most of them reported no prior training or individual research on stuttering. This suggests a potential knowledge gap and highlights the need for a more systematic approach to equip teachers with the tools to support students who stutter. Overall, the teachers demonstrated limited knowledge about stuttering despite their familiarity with this type of disorder.

Teachers' training programmes differed according to their entry year into the educational field. Hence, their knowledge was not based on similar sources or programmes. Samira who was granted a teaching position at a middle school in 2018, stated the following:

"We received teacher training in 2018, the same year I was granted the position, so we taught and underwent training simultaneously. It was very beneficial. It was a year-long course held on Saturdays and every day during holidays, with weekends off. We covered topics related to pedagogy, such as lesson preparation, knowledge delivery, and teaching students with diverse abilities. We also learned about teaching students with disabilities like autism and physical disabilities because our school focuses on integrating students with disabilities, including those in wheelchairs or with autism. However, we did not cover topics related to fluency disorders or stuttering... I don't consider stuttering or fluency disorders a disability; even my children stutter sometimes, but this doesn't mean they have a disability. It's just a pronunciation issue" (Samira, female, 4 YOE).

Samira explained that she started training and teaching during the same years. She explained that the training was helpful as it covered many modules and topics, such as pedagogy of teaching, including teaching students with disabilities. She added that the government has recently focused on integrating students with disabilities. Similarly, (Boutebel and Yahi, 2018) reported that the Algerian educational system had some changes that consisted of learner integration in public schools regardless of the differences in every learner's needs. Nevertheless, Samira pointed out that the integration that they covered did not include students' disfluencies, as they do not consider speech disorders as a disability but rather as speech difficulty, which conveys the idea that fluency disorder is not a serious issue since it is not classified as a disability such as physical disabilities or those who have autism. However, according to some studies, stuttering is considered an impairment, and it is an individual's identity (Plexico, Erath, Shores and Burrus, 2019). Seitz and Choo argued further that the stuttering nature is uniquely perceived as a disability (2022).

However, a few numbers of teachers lacked formal training and often relied on learning from experience. Children with disabilities in Algeria have the opportunity to attend mainstream schools, provided they possess the academic ability or the school actively implements inclusive practices (Khochen-Bagshaw, 2020). While experience can be valuable, it can also be limited and potentially lead to the development of misconceptions about stuttering. Therefore, teachers face many challenges as they teach students with different abilities and disabilities during their teaching period. This situation might be due, in part, to a historical shift in the Algerian educational system, as it went through different phases after independence. One of the phases consisted of recruiting Algerian educators rather than international educators, mainly from Egypt, turkey, and other countries (Rezig, 2011). One of the teachers who was one of these teachers who recruited during the reforms describes the teacher's training as follows:

"After independence, the Algerian government provided an opportunity for all Algerians with higher education or a baccalaureate degree to enter the educational field and become teachers. Most of us required intensive training and guidance, which was very beneficial. Teachers from Egypt, Turkey, Germany, and Lebanon taught us pedagogy. We also underwent practical training, which is needed now in our system, where we observed teachers in classrooms, learned from them, and then teachers observed and guided us... We studied differences in students' abilities and psychology but did not cover inclusive education" (Noah, male, 37 YOE).

Noah's description of his teacher training highlighted the unique aspect of Algerian education in the post-independence period. The government offered opportunities for recent high school graduates to enter the teaching profession. Therefore, the teachers' training involved an intensive programme that combined theoretical knowledge with practical teaching experience. However, it is important to

note that, at the time, inclusive education was not a core component of teacher training in Algerian middle schools. Therefore, it is significant to note that the majority of teachers in this study tend to share anecdotal knowledge about stuttering rather than relying on scientific evidence or reliable academic sources, as they have not been trained to teach learners with stuttering or speech disorders.

Many teachers, based on past interactions with individuals who stutter, appeared to focus on describing stuttering behaviours rather than providing a clear definition. This reflects a common finding in educational research, as evidenced by Khodair, Bataineh, Al-Khawaldeh and Muhaidat (2022) identifying a significant link between teachers' knowledge of stuttering and their experience. In this study, although two of the teachers have never taught learners with stuttering, they had an idea about stuttering as they have met at least someone who stutters in their environment. Thus, all the teachers were familiar with the term stuttering. Leen, Samar, and Nada have described stuttering as follows:

"Stuttering in speaking refers to the act of stopping while talking for a period, accompanied by unusual body movements. You may notice the person's face turning red and signs of stress. However, I still need to research more about it" (Leen, female, 4 YOE).

*"Stuttering or stammering, known as *شذو* in Arabic, is a deficit characterised by blocks, repetitions of sounds or syllables, or parts of words. Those who stutter have difficulty uttering letters, words, or sentences" (Samar, female, 15 YOE).*

"You notice that the face of a child who stutters turns red, and they start making involuntary movements like bowing their head when they try to speak" (Nada, female, 15 YOE).

Leen and Samar described stuttering as a disruption of speech while talking that is categorised by pauses and physical behaviours, which she referred to as unusual. This description is similar to ASHA's definition of stuttering as the disruption of the flow of verbal speech characterised by unintentional prolongations, blocks, repetitions or sounds or syllables (ASHA, 2023). Although this description indicates a good understanding of the nature of stuttering, a misunderstanding arose regarding the cause. Leen attributed blushing to stress following stuttering, which could have other explanations. She further expressed her doubt demonstrating her limited understanding of stuttering and her need to develop her knowledge regarding this speech disorder. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that, Samar is the only teacher who described stuttering as a defect following the medical model definition of stuttering, which shows that she has researched it not only as a social understanding of it but also medically. The term defect is also used by (Constantino, Campbell and Simpson, 2022; Abutova, 2022) to describe stuttering in relation to biomedical research. Furthermore, Nada stressed more about

describing the stutter's bodily movement than speaking, pointing out that individuals who stutter tend to blush and bow their heads while speaking.

Overall, the study results suggest that teachers possess a foundational awareness of the nature of stuttering. Their descriptions incorporated some primary and secondary behaviours associated with stuttering that were based on their observation and which align with many studies.

6.4.2. Perceptions of Stuttering Aetiology

As mentioned earlier, among the teachers who had the experience of teaching learners who stutter, some had the chance to ask the parents about the stuttering cause. However, most of them showed uncertainty about the cause of the stutter, as all teachers stated that they did not research it. *"No, I have not done any research about stuttering"* (Leen, female, 4 YOE). *"No, I have studied at the university about aphasia and speech disorders, but I have not done any research about stuttering in particular"* (Dania, female, 10 YOE). In addition, during the interview discussions, they used expressions such as *"I think"*, *"in my opinion"*, *"to my humble knowledge"*, and *"I do not exactly know the reason behind stuttering"*, which demonstrates doubts. However, some teachers have studied modules about the brain areas responsible for a speech during their university years and they drew upon this knowledge to explain the cause of stuttering. Overall, the teachers' knowledge was based on societal knowledge, personal experiences with stuttering individuals, academic knowledge from fields like neurolinguistics, and personal assumptions.

Only three teachers out of ten have stated that the causes of stuttering result from some neurological factors. This cause was mentioned only by those teachers who studied neurolinguistics during her university years. Despite her lacking prior research on stuttering, one of the teachers highlighted that there is a possibility that it could be related to a brain disorder.

"I have not conducted any research myself, but I remember studying a module during my master's degree, I think it was psycholinguistics, where we learned about speech disorders, their management, and their neurological basis. Therefore, I am sure that stuttering is related to brain function since it is a type of speech disorder" (Dania, female, 10 YOE).

The teachers drew this conclusion based on what they had already learned about speech disorders in general, yet it was not directly related to stuttering. In other words, since the brain is responsible for language production, stuttering is classified as a speech disorder. Thus, the brain is responsible for this disorder. Hence, Dania's answer was not built upon a proven scientific basis, whereas her conclusion was built on her point of view. Nevertheless, many studies have been conducted to study the brain anatomy of individuals who stutter (See Kronfeld-Duenias *et al.*, 2016; Sowman *et al.*, 2017; Gough *et*

al., 2018; Neef *et al.*, 2021). Thereby, many theories have developed to provide an etiological explanation for stuttering that is related to the anatomy of the brain (See Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Although there might be a link between the brain and the stuttering as pointed out by research, the teachers showed uncertainty that indicated their limited knowledge regarding this disorder.

In contrast to the mothers and speech-language therapists who emphasized emotional or psychological factors, some teachers attributed stuttering to low self-esteem, often seen as a personality characteristic. This highlights a potential disconnect in understanding the causes of stuttering. While emotional factors can play a role in stuttering experiences, low self-esteem is not a root cause. Boyle (2020) has stated that speech-language therapists need to explain that the personality of the individual that is characterised by a negative trait or a low competency does not cause the stutter, whilst also the stutter has a chance to improve his communication performance. One of the teachers stated that the psychological issues the stutters have are part of their personality, making them stutter when feeling uncomfortable.

"In my opinion, stuttering is a psychological issue. I've observed that these students often lack self-confidence compared to their classmates, but I'm not sure of the exact underlying problem" (Leen, female, 4 YO).

"I think one of the reasons behind stuttering is the constant nervousness or pressure felt by those who stutter... If a child or person is reticent, experiences stage fright, or similar issues, they may stutter" (Samar, female, 15 YO).

"I believe stuttering is related to psychological issues. I've noticed one of my students this year is a stutterer; whenever I ask him to speak, he starts shaking and I can notice the stress on him " (Malak, female, 4 YO).

"The problem can stem from family issues. In my experience if parents punish and mistreat a child, it can lead to psychological trauma that manifests as stuttering; the child becomes unable to speak" (Nada, female, 15 YO).

Leen's explanation exemplifies a common misconception as she attributed stuttering to low self-confidence based on her personal perspective. Similarly, Samar linked stuttering to psychological issues like reticence. However, research contradicts Leen's assumption. Studies have shown that the severity of stuttering can significantly impact an individual's self-esteem, affecting their social interactions, friendships, and overall confidence (Adriaenssens, Beyers and Struyf, 2015). This highlights a critical gap in knowledge, as stuttering is not caused by personality traits. Similar to Leen and Samar, Malak attributed the stutter of one of her students to stress based on his outward behaviour. She observed that he started shaking when asked to participate. Nevertheless, emotional

factors can influence stuttering experiences, yet they are not the root cause (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021).

The first year of middle school marks a transitional period from primary school. Throughout this year, children are exposed to different environments, a new educational system, new teachers, and modules. Additionally, they experience changes in their bodies and hormones as they enter adolescence. Along these lines, one teacher pointed out that many students begin to stutter during adolescence due to increased awareness of social issues. Nassima has shared incidents involving her students who developed stuttering because of emotional trauma stemming from experiences with sexual assault and drug consumption.

"During my teaching experience, I observed that some students who had never stuttered before suddenly began exhibiting signs of introversion and aggression. One of my students had witnessed her parents' sexual activity many times, which traumatised her. As a result, she became introverted and started stuttering, which negatively impacted her academic performance. Upon investigation, we found a letter where she detailed everything she had witnessed...In another case, the environment was a factor, particularly due to drug-related issues in the neighbourhood. This area is known for its dangers, and I frequently had to call the police to address gang activity. Unfortunately, the students here were influenced by these surroundings. For instance, one student consistently came to class with orange lips and a nose, showed signs of aggression, and stuttered when speaking. Eventually, I learned that she was using Amila (an Algerian juice powder) as a drug." (Nassima, female, 5 YOE).

Nassima believed these incidents were traumatic for adolescents, potentially affecting their mental health and causing stuttering in some cases. A positive school environment is crucial for adolescents' development, influencing their behaviour and well-being. When exposed to a toxic school environment, children are more likely to be negatively impacted and potentially become involved in negative behaviours themselves. While attributing stuttering solely to psychological trauma reinforces the misconception that it always has a psychological cause, it's important to acknowledge that not everyone exposed to such factors will develop a stutter. Traumatic experiences might trigger stuttering in some individuals, but more research is needed to definitively support this link. Furthermore, this demonstrated limited knowledge regarding the cause of stutter as the teacher based her assumption on personal observations lacking scientific evidence and required reliable sources to validate its accuracy.

While the emphasis was on psychological factors, the teachers acknowledged other potential

contributors to stuttering. Genetics was one such factor they mentioned. Samar argued, *"It can also be genetically inherited. It runs from one person of the family to another"*. In the same vein, there is significant evidence supporting the role of genetic factors in stuttering (Frigerio-Domingues et al., 2019). It is important to note, however, that all the teachers expressed uncertainty about it. Nassima shared the same belief as Samar saying the following:

"I don't know the exact reason behind stuttering, but I think it may be something a person is born with. I am sure that stuttering is related to brain function... I also believe it could be genetic because I know someone who stutters; recently, his daughter started stuttering too, although she is an adult now, so I think it is genetic, I'm not sure" (Nassima, female, 5 YOE).

Nassima acknowledges the uncertainty of her knowledge surrounding the cause of stuttering. Furthermore, her approach of stating hypothetical possibilities alongside established knowledge weakens her argument. Although her personal experience with a family member stutters suggestions of a genetic connection, relying solely on subjective evidence is inadequate. Additionally, labelling stuttering as merely an inborn disorder or a brain condition oversimplifies the issue. That being said, many studies align with genetics and brain activity factors that cause stuttering (Frigerio-Domingues and Drayna, 2017; Packman et al., 2022). However, a more nuanced understanding that recognizes the multifaceted nature of stuttering's causes is essential for effective intervention and support. On the other hand, only two of the teachers stated that the stutter could not be genetics. Malak and Nada stated *"The stutter is not genetically inherited because the parents and siblings of the student I am teaching who have stuttering are not stutterers"* (Malak, female, 4 YOE). *"I do not think that the stutter is genetically inherited from the parents"* (Nada, Female, 15 YOE). While Malak and Nada's assumption that stuttering is not genetic aligns with the speech therapists in the study, it contradicts many established studies that provide evidence supporting the possibility of genetic factors causing stuttering.

6.4.3. Treatment Approach for Stuttering

Many teachers believe stuttering is primarily psychological, leading them to assume treatment should focus on psychological factors mainly. However, a considerable number of teachers believe that there are specialists that can treat this disorder. A few teachers who participated in this study advised some children to seek help from speech-language therapists after noticing they stutter. Nevertheless, the majority of them lack communication with speech therapists therefore they demonstrated a lack of knowledge of the available treatment options for stuttering. *"I don't believe there is a cure for stuttering, I know that there are some treatment options that can be pursued"* (Samar, Female, 15

YOE). Only two teachers were able to describe some activities used in stuttering treatment, suggesting a need for further professional development for teachers on this topic.

"Stuttering is a speech difficulty that speech therapists can address through specific activities and interventions. Some parents are unaware or indifferent to their children's needs, and I always encourage them to seek help from speech-language therapists who offer free therapy. I have seen speech therapists doing speech exercises with gadgets in the mouth to help produce sounds; specialists know about this. When parents neglect their children, it makes me feel responsible for them. They say stutterers don't stutter when they sing, so I give them songs to memorise and sing to me" (Nassima, female, 5 YOE).

The above excerpt demonstrates Nassima's awareness of treatment activities that can assist individuals with stuttering. The teacher shows familiarity with speech therapy techniques by mentioning specific equipment and activities to improve pronunciation. However, it's important to note that these activities were not explicitly endorsed by the speech therapist who participated in this study. Additionally, Nassima actively encourages students to seek treatment, acknowledging that some parents may not be aware of the availability of speech-language therapists for their children who stutter in Algeria. This reflects her proactive approach to addressing stuttering and advocating for the importance of speech therapy. Nassima also recognizes the effectiveness of singing in improving fluency for individuals who stutter and incorporates it into her teaching by encouraging her students to practice singing as an additional therapeutic activity.

Furthermore, one of the teachers had contact with one of the family members of her student who stutters, and she stated the following:

"I asked his sister about the treatment he was receiving just to get an idea. She mentioned that he was seeing a speech therapist, and they were doing breathing activities like shaping paper into a ball and blowing it, but he lost interest in the treatment... I read about stuttering yesterday, not in depth, just to get an idea, and I found that some cases use medication. So, if it's severe, why not... Personally, I encourage them to attend Quranic schools; I think the Quran is beneficial as a treatment. This is just my perspective; I believe it greatly helps" (Imene, Female, 10 YOE).

Imene demonstrated her concern regarding her student's stutter and took the initiative to learn about his treatment. It is important to note that the treatment reported by both groups of participants, the speech-language therapist and mothers, aligns with what his sister, who also attends the same school, communicated to Imene. This highlights the importance of collaboration and communication between various stakeholders to improve the teachers' knowledge regarding stuttering which is

involved in a student's well-being. Interestingly, Imene's knowledge about stuttering appears to extend beyond the information provided by the speech therapist and mothers. She mentioned the use of equipment to help with fluency, which wasn't reported by others in the study. Additionally, Imene seems to be aware that medication can be used in rare cases, demonstrating some independent research on the topic.

On the other hand, the majority of teachers believe that the stutter requires psychological therapy; therefore, they stated the following about the treatment of stuttering,

"Everything has a cure, even stuttering, and I think its treatment should be psychological; they need to understand why they stutter. The cause is psychological...The low self-esteem, hesitation, and fear of answering" (Amal, Female, 20 YOE).

"For me, stuttering is a speech issue, and I believe the main cause is psychological. I have noticed that students lack self-confidence and seem different from their classmates in terms of personality. I'm not sure of the exact problem; I think they need a psychologist to provide the right treatment" (Malak, female, 4 YOE).

Interestingly, Amal and Malak noted that the stutter is not only psychological trauma. However, they consider these psychological issues as personality issues where children who stutter lack self-esteem, which makes them stutter. This misconception leads them to assume that treating their self-esteem will cure their stutter. Therefore, they consider psychological therapy to be the proper treatment for stuttering. This does not only indicate their lack of knowledge regarding the treatment of stuttering, yet the stereotype that children who stutter are shy and anxious (See Boyle, 2017)

Although some teachers were unsure of the types of treatment children who stutter receive, they still believe they can completely recover from stuttering. Many researchers have studied stuttering recovery (Kefalianos *et al.*, 2017; Carey, Onslow and O'Brian, 2021). Carey *et al.* reported that there is no specific way to anticipate the child's stuttering recovery, whilst there are many reasons that could be linked to the persistent stutter (2021). Accordingly, the stuttering recovery and persistence could be debatable even between researchers, nevertheless, all teachers in the current study believe that the stutter can be cured.

"Stuttering can be cured if parents support their child because the psychological state is crucial. However, in this school, I have not seen any children recover from stuttering" (Nada, Female, 15 YOE).

"I believe stuttering can be cured if parents seek help from psychologists" (Leen, female, 4 YOE).

Nada pointed out that it is significant for parents to provide a healthy environment to help their

children who stutter. Both Nada and Leen directly related the psychological state of the child's environment as an essential component of the recovery. However, research reported that there are specific characteristics that determine the degree of stuttering recovery, for instance, the severity of the stutter (Tichenor and Yaruss, 2020). Nevertheless, despite Nada's belief in the possibility of recovery from stuttering, she acknowledges that it's not the case for everyone. She mentions two of her students as examples where stuttering has persisted. While a positive home environment for children who stutter is crucial, the teachers' view that stuttering can be solely cured by addressing psychological issues is a misconception. Furthermore, Malak noted the following regarding the treatment of stuttering:

"I have researched stuttering and found that treatment can be effective if started during childhood. It becomes more challenging as the individual grows older due to its negative impact on wellbeing and mental health"
(Malak, female, 4 YOE).

Interestingly, Malak pointed out the significance of starting the treatment at an early stage. According to (Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat, 2022) the stutter should be treated once it begins so that the treatment would be beneficial for them. She stated that according to research, the child is more likely to reach better results when they seek the speech therapist's help at a younger age. Nevertheless, Carey, Onslow and O'Brian (2021) argued that the recovery rate during the first year and a half of the stuttering onset is lower. Still, Malak explained further that recovery would be difficult for adults due to the impact of stuttering on their psychological health. Researchers highlighted the fact that the anxiety level and the mental health issues that are associated with stutter are serious factors that affect the individuals in the long term, especially if the child is being bullied after the stutter onset (Briley, O'Brien and Ellis, 2019; McAllister, 2016).

Overall, the results highlight a gap in knowledge regarding stuttering treatment options among most teachers. Many teachers appear to hold misconceptions, potentially attributing stuttering to solely psychological causes, leading them to assume that its treatment should be at the psychological level. It's important to note that only two teachers, likely those with experience teaching students who stutter, demonstrated a better understanding of treatment options through personal research. Furthermore, despite these misconceptions and a lack of knowledge about specific treatment approaches, all teachers believed in the possibility of stuttering recovery. However, their uncertainty about effective treatment methods highlights the need for improved training and information sharing.

6.4.4. Awareness of the Impact of Stuttering

Overall, the participants demonstrated some understanding of the impact of stuttering. Nevertheless, this knowledge is mainly based on their observation and interaction with children who stutter. Similar to the speech-language therapists and the mothers of children who stutter results, teachers in Algerian middle schools believe that stuttering affects the child's self-esteem and drives them to avoid interaction with others, eventually isolating themselves.

Adolescence is a period marked by emotional turbulence as it is a phase characterized by both physical and cognitive growth and development, thus, self-confidence can be fragile due to various factors (Adriaensens, Beyers and Struyf, 2015). In the same vein, teachers consider this period as crucial for students to develop their personalities, however, adolescents who stutter may experience a more challenging experience. Research reported that during adolescence, the effects of stuttering are shaped by a multifaceted interaction between speech-related factors and psychological variables (Iverach *et al.*, 2017), for instance, the stuttering severity may increase levels of anxiety and internalizing problems. Accordingly, the teachers reported a number of issues they have noticed in their students who stutter.

"I don't believe it will have long-term effects. We're not just talking about primary school; it's in middle school where adolescence begins, and the student who stutters is trying to develop their personality. If there are supportive teachers and classmates who normalise stuttering, I can assure you that this individual will not experience psychological issues or feel embarrassed to interact with society. However, if this support is lacking, the opposite may occur... The impact varies from one individual to another depending on their circumstances. Parents have limited influence as we're primarily discussing the school environment" (Malak, female, 4 YOE).

"During adolescence, children undergo bodily changes and hormonal shifts, which can lead to issues with their sexual identity and stuttering problems... I once taught a child who excelled in studies but suddenly started stuttering; her classroom performance and grades declined, and she became aggressive and introverted" (Nassima, female, 5 YOE).

Teachers acknowledged the unique challenges of adolescence, highlighting the significant physical and emotional changes young people experience. This demonstrates the teachers' understanding of how stuttering might affect adolescents compared to other age groups. She supported this by stating the impact she noticed on one of her students. thus, based on the quotation, stuttering could potentially hinder this student's academic progress and social interactions, possibly leading to personality changes such as becoming withdrawn or less outgoing. Additionally, the participants reported that students who stutter tend to experience increased levels of nervousness and stress, which consequently leads them to avoid participation in the classroom. This knowledge could

contribute to the improvements of the student's experience in school, as teachers can address these psychological issues as they can influence the student's well-being (Hearne *et al.*, 2021). At the same time, the teachers recognised the different personalities among all students to be able to help them adapt and integrate with the classroom environment. Samar pointed in this regard,

"I believe stuttering can have a negative impact on a person, particularly causing nervousness. Stutterers often feel pressured or stressed and may develop avoidant behaviour, becoming introverted and reluctant to interact with others. For example, a student I taught preferred to speak while seated but refused to answer at the board, indicating fear of facing an audience... Same thing for stuttering; it can lead to introversion and a fear of societal interaction" (Samar, Female, 15 YOE).

The above quotation reflects a common perception of stuttering's impact on individuals, emphasizing its potential negative effects on their psychological well-being and social interactions. Samar identified "nervousness" and "avoidance" as behaviours as major issues associated with stuttering, suggesting a link between stuttering and avoidant personality traits. Similarly, Iverach *et al.* (2016) reported that anxiety is a well-documented consequence of stuttering, as it is one of the most commonly observed and extensively studied characteristics. However, even though stuttering can lead to feelings of nervousness and anxiety in social situations, it is important to critically evaluate whether these feelings are associated with stuttering itself or it is a creation of social attitudes and stigma surrounding speech disorders. Samar addressed other issues regarding the impact of stuttering on school-aged children, such as fear, and self-withdrawal from society. Imene further noted that the impact of stuttering could extend to affecting the student's friendships and relationships with others.

"The impact of stuttering on a child depends on how they perceive the disorder. If they view it as a problem or disease and face ridicule from their environment, they may isolate themselves at home and struggle with friends. Supportive environments are crucial to helping them cope" (Imene, female, 10 YOE).

Similar to other teachers, Imene identified several consequences of stuttering, including social isolation and potential difficulties in relationships with family and friends. She further emphasized the critical role of a child's environment. Imene suggests that the impact of stuttering is likely correlated with the level of support a child receives. According to Adriaensens, Beyers and Struyf (2015), the severity of stuttering adversely affects adolescents' perceptions of social acceptance, school competence, ability to form close friendships, and overall self-esteem. This may explain the child's social avoidance and interaction, therefore, the majority of teachers emphasised the importance of improving the child's self-esteem.

"I think the societal and familial environment of a child who stutters plays a significant role in supporting them and fostering a strong personality. Stuttering itself may not have a severe impact, but if the child has a weak personality, it could easily affect their wellbeing in the long term" (Samira, female, 4 YOE).

Samira pointed out the importance of a positive environment in reducing the negative effect of stuttering and improving the child's self-esteem. Some researchers argued that, in addition to impacting self-esteem, stuttering can contribute to the development of other psychological and physical health problems in individuals who stutter, such as stress and depression, affecting their quality of life (Boyle, 2016a; Boyle and Fearon, 2018). However, it's important to note that findings on the relationship between stuttering and self-esteem are not always consistent. Some studies, such as (Sikandar, Tahir and Shah, 2019), report no significant difference in confidence levels between individuals who stutter and those who do not. This highlights the complexity of stuttering's impact on emotional well-being and the need for further research.

Overall, the teachers demonstrated a positive understanding of the impact of stuttering on children who stutter, acknowledging various factors that could exacerbate its effects, including a child's personality, adolescence, and the supportiveness of their environment. Additionally, the teachers emphasized the importance of creating a supportive environment, which can contribute to a child's self-acceptance.

7. Chapter seven: Presentation of the Findings

Stakeholders' Knowledge of Stigma Towards Children who Stutter in Algeria.

7.1. Introduction

The previous chapter presented the stakeholders' knowledge regarding stuttering. This chapter focuses on stakeholders' knowledge and perceptions of the stigma associated with stuttering. Worthy to mention that the stakeholders' understanding of stuttering influenced their social interactions and attitudes towards children who stutter (See Goffman, 1963). Following the approach of the previous chapter, the results will be presented for each participant group; speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers; separately. This chapter aims to answer the second research question:

What is the depth and scope of stakeholders' knowledge of the stigma associated with stuttering in Algerian middle schools?

The participants' knowledge, represented in this chapter, addresses the above research question and unveils the experiences of children who stutter in this context. The data will be further interpreted and discussed in Chapter 9. The previous chapter provided important insights, linking it with the findings from the previous chapter when relevant to explain some of the negative attitudes directed toward children who stutter.

The negative behaviours towards children who stutter, adverse reactions, and the social stigma influence their self-esteem and their quality of life as a whole, leading them to develop a fear of society, isolate themselves and avoid social interaction (De Nardo, Gabel, Tetnowski and Swartz, 2016; Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Goffman explains that the stigma can be visible as "discredited" while "discreditable" can be known about and visible (1963. p.57). Stuttering can be discreditable as long as the individual does not speak or disclose their stuttering, which explains social avoidance. Accordingly, avoiding social interactions is a way of hiding the stigma, which is stuttering in this study, to make it "discreditable" to prevent adverse reactions towards the individuals' stutter. Once the stutter is revealed and the stutterer becomes discredited, the possibility of stigmatisation occurs. In this study, the stigma appeared in different forms, and negative labelling was the most reported form. This indicates that children who stutter in Algeria experience both social stigma and self-stigma (Abasi, 2022b) . The results indicate that Algerian children who stutter face widespread negative labelling "Aggoun" and negative reactions from parents, peers, and teachers to their stutter.

This, along with bullying, such as laughing, teasing, and mimicking, creates a social environment that discourages social interaction and can lead to self-stigma.

The following section reports the results of the speech-language therapists.

7.2. Speech-Language Therapists

A large body of research investigates the stigma experienced in schools and adverse reactions towards stuttering (Berchiatti *et al.*, 2021; Cobb, Daniels and Panico, 2019; Dean and Medina, 2021). Other studies focused on the teachers' attitudes toward stuttering (Hearne *et al.*, 2021; Elrefaie, Ella, Halim and Gobran, 2022). This section reports and interprets the speech therapist's knowledge regarding the children's experiences in school and how teachers react to the stuttering. The speech therapists work a lot with children who stutter and help them not only with their speech but also with overcoming some psychological issues related to stuttering. Therefore, children share their experiences with speech therapists more than other group participants. The speech-language therapists focused more on developing the children's self-esteem rather than addressing the attitudes of Algerian society. Most of the stigma experiences were reported by the speech-language therapists who participated in this study, as they tend to hear a lot from individuals who stutter, which explains their emphasis on negative attitudes.

7.2.1. Social Stigma and Stuttering

Children who stutter at a particular stage become aware of the reactions of others towards their stutter, which can be misinterpreted sometimes (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). These reactions can also occur as questions about the individual who stutters or the stutter itself due to a lack of knowledge about it. Therefore, many speech therapists emphasise avoiding these types of questions as they can develop a sense of stigma. social reactions to stuttering could appear as Questions such as "Why are you speaking like that?" with a tone that indicates annoyance, order "Speak correctly!" with an angry tone, or comparing the child to their siblings, relatives, or surroundings are reported to be stigmatising. The speech-language therapists reported that these questions are unacceptable and unfair toward the stuttering child.

"It's very tough for a child to live with a stutter. Sometimes people ask their mothers, 'Why don't you take your child to a specialist? They are not normal,' and the child hears, notices, and internalises it, leading to psychological trauma. This is where the negative experiences start. Sometimes they ask, 'Why are you speaking like that?' the questions of why and what's wrong with you; I would prefer not to hear them" (Safa, Female, 4 YOE)

The word "normal" is used by Goffman (1963) in his book "Stigma", as a reference to an individual

who does not have a stigma. As Safa pointed out, the public considers stutters “as not normal”. This word in Algeria refers to a general state of the physical or mental defect, whereas the child disorder is only at the level of speech. This indicates that there is a stereotype that can result from the lack of knowledge and awareness regarding stuttering. Children at a younger age can witness many situations where people ask their caregivers about them and their stutter. As argued by Safa, children remember everything during childhood, especially poor attitudes towards them. She explained that some questions about the child who stutters should not be asked, such as, ‘How’ ‘why’, and ‘What’s wrong with you?’ should not be asked. While asking about stuttering to improve their knowledge about it can be good, the way of asking should be proper. The parents could answer these questions as long as they do not address the child. However, once they are aware and become adolescents, they start facing society by themselves, especially their friends. Most of the speech therapists in this study believe that children in middle schools are stigmatised by their classmates. However, they have also argued that the stigma does not exist in schools only but starts from home.

“Stigma exists in our society, starting with parents. Mothers often compare their children to siblings who do not stutter. Many mothers have admitted calling their children ‘Aggoun’, telling them to speak correctly because it embarrasses them. Comparisons are common; a mother might say, ‘When I visit my family, my nephew the same age as my son speaks very well.’ When the child hears this... (her facial expression showing empathy) The issue is that his mother is the main link between him and society.” (Nour, Female, 3 YO)

“The problem isn’t just with students; it starts at home. When they want to mock a child, they imitate his stutter. That’s the problem. So, what do you expect from the outside environment; the classroom, neighbourhood, or anywhere else?” (Hassan, Male, 14 YO)

Both participants, Hassan and Nour, state that the word “Aggoun” is used even in families between siblings. Nour has pointed out that the parents know that their attitudes towards their children are sometimes negative. Apart from negative labelling, the comparison is considered unhealthy behaviour toward the children. Comparing the fluency of the child who stutters with others who do not stutter affects the child’s personality and self-esteem, although they do not intend to hurt the child’s feelings. This indicates a need to increase awareness among family members, and speech therapists can help with that by organising sessions with parents separately and discussing their relationship with their children. However, the speech therapist has not mentioned any solution to address the families’ attitudes. Hassan identified several negative attitudes family members can hold towards children who stutter, including mockingly mimicking their stutter. This highlights how stigma

can originate within the family, potentially leading the child to internalize negative perceptions and anticipate similar reactions from society. Hassan has highlighted that society could discriminate against children who stutter, saying the following:

“For example, when a child who stutters enters a store to buy something specific that his family requested, and he experiences a block while speaking to the shop owner, the shop owner may start staring or say, ‘Hurry up! You’re not the only one here today.’ (which means there are other people to serve). Regardless of the age or whether someone stutters, this kind of response can be hurtful, it’s just an example.” (Hassan, Male, 14 YO)

Hassan argued that a child who stutters experiences discrimination sometimes during simple everyday interaction needs, such as grocery shopping. This perceived discrimination or the negative attitude towards individuals with a disability affects their self-esteem, contributes to their self-isolation, and negatively affects their social interaction (De Nardo, Gabel, Tetnowski and Swartz, 2016). Children who stutter have no control over their fluency of speech and asking them to speak quickly will not help in any way. Instead, it makes it worse as the level of anxiety will get higher. Therefore, it is essential to highlight that people ought to be mindful of the attitude that could aggravate the stutter and add pressure on children who stutter. Interestingly, most speech therapists, such as Nour and Safa, see it from another perspective, indicating that people’s reactions towards stuttering cannot be controlled. However, the child should be prepared for these reactions and know how to handle them. The speech therapists pointed out that the first thing they work on with children who stutter is developing their self-esteem. This helps them face the stigma with less psychological damage. Hassan demonstrated the effects of attitudes on adults to picture how profound the effect is on children. The experience of stigma in any form leads the children who stutter to anticipate the stigma in the future, eventually developing self-stigma.

“The first thing a child who stutters thinks about before entering the classroom is that classmates will make fun of them. Adolescents are trying to build friendships, so it’s important to understand that they will always be concerned about their speech. Adolescence and stuttering can be challenging to navigate simultaneously.” (Nour, Female, 3 YO)

Interestingly, Nour pointed out that adolescents generally face difficulties, as this stage is characterised by major physical changes, develop new ways of thinking, and navigate changes in their social lives (Maxey and Beckert, 2017). The speech therapists argued that it is a very sensitive stage, and having a disability makes it more difficult. Therefore, they are more likely to be sensitive to being associated with stuttering, hence avoiding social interaction to hide the stutter (Bloodstein, Ratner

and Brundage, 2021). This avoidance could also be interpreted as the anticipation of stigma. Although some individuals overcome the stutter, they still anticipate the adverse reactions. One of the speech therapists argued the latter point, highlighting that they could still be stigmatised even after recovery.

*“Even after recovery, when a child who used to stutter speaks fluently, they may still feel uncomfortable with their environment, classmates, and teachers. It is difficult because others may still expect them to stutter.”
(Hassan, Male, 14 YOE)*

Therefore, Speech therapists try to contribute to strengthening the stutterer’s personality to overcome the effect of the stigma. Hassan explained that since the individual has been known for his stutter for a period and got stigmatised for it, the after-recovery period will still be strange for his surroundings. According to Boyle (2018), past experiences of the stigma of individuals who stutter are more likely to lead them to anticipate future stigma. This stigma anticipation occurs during the stutter or continues even after healing.

7.2.2. Labelling Children Who Stutter as “Aggoun”

The participants reported negative attitudes such as bullying, labelling, social discrimination, and self-stigma. This suggests that stigma is a widespread issue within the Algerian social context. Middle school students share many incidents with speech therapists where they have experienced bullying. Similarly, Zamprogno, Mandrá, Gonçalves and Jorge (2020) reported that school-aged children who stutter consequently suffer from negative traits and stereotyping. This study results indicate that children are more stigmatised by their peer groups within the school settings.

“During adolescence, negative experiences occur when classmates mock stuttering as a joke, which hurts the child who stutters. They can be bullied; their classmates’ joke and laugh at them. This behaviour may also come from; yelling, mocking them in the classroom, and using offensive terms like Aggoun. (expressing disappointment) ... when the child wants to participate (expresses disappointment and moving his head from side to side to indicate that they will not let them participate) ... These things happen, and when you interview teachers, they will tell you.” (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE)

“Aggoun” is a sarcastic term used in reference to those who have difficulty speaking. It can carry offensive connotations and is used in Algerian dialect, or dialects of Maghreb countries. Using it can be translated as mocking, teasing, belittling and stigmatising. This word appeared in all interviews. This confirms that children who stutter are stigmatised, and their surroundings are aware of this stigma. Nevertheless, sometimes people use it to simply refer to others who have a speech disorder, still using it in front of those with speech disorders would be inappropriate and insulting.

Schools can be a challenging experience for children who stutter, especially in adolescence. Evidently, children who stutter face bullying at school by their classmates or even outside by their friends (Boyle, 2014). Berchiatti et al. (2021) reported that students who stutter are victimised and bullied because of their stutter, affecting their social status. Hassan stated more than one example of the stigmatising behaviours towards children who stutter in schools, such as mocking, bullying, labelling, and discrimination, which was also reported by (Andreou, Didaskalou and Vlachou, 2015; Zamprogno, Mandrá, Gonçalves and Jorge, 2020). The speech therapists expressed their disappointment because of the negative experiences of children who stutter. Hassan stated that this stigma could be from peers and some teachers who addressed saying *“teachers who lack professional conscience”* Hassan, Male, 14 YOE. This indicates there is a possibility that teachers can also be part of creating a stigmatising environment. This was also stated in the mothers and teachers’ responses, which confirms that teachers need to be more cautious of their attitudes towards children who stutter.

Based on the results, classmates of children who stutter play a big part in creating a challenging environment for them at school. This indicates a need to raise awareness about stuttering and push their peers to reflect on their attitudes toward students who stutter. Knowledge about disability is significant to a successful inclusive practice (Dar, Paul and Badiger, 2023), and stakeholders should consider working on addressing this gap in schools. This does not apply to teachers only; society should also develop a sense of responsibility towards children who stutter. The speech therapist Linda, also emphasised developing knowledge regarding stuttering.

“Most stutterers here face bullying because we live in a society that doesn’t understand what stuttering means. They are aware, but everyone uses “Aggoun”, especially in the cities Even in families, stutterers may be imitated or teased unintentionally. This psychological impact lessens as they age and understand that stuttering is just a speech disorder; it doesn’t mean they are mentally defective. Overcoming stuttering requires diligence and willingness.” (Linda, Female, 4 YOE)

Labelling continued to occur during all interview discussions, confirming that it is common in Algerian society. The mothers and teachers also confirmed using the word Aggoun to Label children who stutter in Algeria (see section 7.2.1. and section 7.3.1.). Linda addresses an interesting point regarding knowledge and awareness about stuttering. This was addressed to the society as a whole. However, this knowledge should be about stuttering and the correct way of dealing with and treating children who stutter (Junuzovic-Zunic, Mostafa and St. Louis, 2023). As children who stutter are increasingly required to engage and interact with society, the psychological pressure also escalates. Linda pointed out that even families, including parents, can sometimes mistreat their children without intention.

SheikhBahaei and Maguire (2020) argued that public stigma could be reduced by raising awareness about stuttering; therefore, much knowledge and understanding are needed to avoid the stigma. Hassan argued that *“speech therapists are conscientious when working with stutters, as any wrong attitude can cause psychological harm”*. The critical point that could be drawn from this is that helping individuals with their stutter does not necessarily eliminate the adverse social reaction associated with stuttering (De Nardo, Tetnowski and Coalson, 2023b).

7.3. Mothers of children who stutter results

The stigma associated with stuttering significantly impacts both the parents and their children who stutter. Recognising and addressing the stigma by parents is crucial for providing a supportive environment where both the child and the parents manage and cope with stuttering and the stigmatising attitudes towards them. This section reports the mothers’ results regarding their knowledge and awareness of the stigma their children experience because of their stutter. It is significant to highlight that the mothers’ responses align with the responses of the speech therapists. Hence, the mothers have shown awareness of the negative attitudes that their children experience. Although the mothers have disapproved some of the stigmatising attitudes, they have also acknowledged instances where they have reacted negatively to their children who stutter. In addition, they have witnessed some stigmatising attitudes from their siblings. The latter indicates that the stigma must be addressed at home first, as it appeared to be a culturally typical attitude. Many types of stigmas appeared in the data based on the results of mothers of children who stutter, such as stereotypes, labelling, self-stigma, and social isolation (See Goffman, 1963). This stigma occurred in schools and their communities. While the mothers mentioned instances of negative attitudes from certain teachers, they attributed these attitudes to their lack of awareness regarding the children’s stutter. These negative attitudes could lead the child to internalise negative self-perception, and experience heightened self-consciousness, eventually contributing to self-stigma.

7.3.1. Siblings and Family Attitudes towards Children Who Stutter

The mothers have reported many incidents that happened to their children, which demonstrated their awareness of the stigmatising attitudes their children face. Furthermore, the interview results reported some adverse parental reactions toward the stigma, which affected the parent-child relationship. However, it is significant to mention that parents’ attitudes towards their children differ from one family to another (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Furthermore, their reaction to stigma also differed, yet all the mothers aimed to develop their children’s self-esteem and help them accept their stutter. However, the mothers seemed to need more guidance in addressing the child’s attitudes. Some parents act as if their children who stutter have control over their fluency, while this

could be developed with time using strategies such as pull-outs and preparatory sets (De Nardo, Tetnowski and Coalson, 2023b).

Labelling was the most reported during the mothers' interview discussions. Results reported that teachers, classmates, friends, and siblings also used the word "Aggoun" to label individuals who stutter. Even mothers admitted using it when they are mad at their children. It was used to describe children who stutter or mock them either intentionally or unintentionally. Interestingly, during the mothers' interview discussion, there was a chance to discuss the children's reactions to this word. The results indicate that children resisted being labelled by reacting negatively to such categorisation. However, their reaction varied, manifesting either aggression or tears. One of the mothers stated the following:

"His siblings sometimes... They get angry with each other; they tell him, 'Speak well! Aggoun; You can't speak fluently!' Even I, when I get really angry with him, call him Aggoun." (Oum Youcef)

"Sometimes I can't control the kids' behaviour; when they start arguing or get angry with each other, they hurt each other with words. You can hear his brother mocking him and calling him Aggoun. They say random words without thinking about each other's feelings. When I intervene, I can tell that lyad got more hurt because he struggles to reply." (Oum lyad)

"Sometimes I call him Aggoun; 'Stop speaking like that!' He replies, 'Do not call me Aggoun!' But when I criticise him, he does his best not to stutter. When I criticise him, he asks me, 'Why are you criticising me?'" (Oum Reda)

It is important to highlight that sibling relationships profoundly impact children who stutter (Beilby, Byrnes and Young, 2012). The mothers have reported many incidents when their children who stutter get hurt by their siblings because of an argument or a disagreement. The mothers have argued that such labelling attitudes cannot be controlled when their children fight. Like some mothers who participated in this study, Oum Youcef admitted that she uses the word Aggoun sometimes when her child who stutters does something peeved her, indicating the presence of stigma at home. The above results demonstrate that the family may engage in hurtful actions such as verbalising negative judgements toward children who stutter. These actions contribute to the perpetuation of stigma as it affects the child's self-esteem and overall well-being. The reactions of all children who stutter in the excerpts above, "I can tell that lyad got hurt more" "Why are you criticising me?" "Do not call me Aggoun!" demonstrates their intolerance of these behaviours.

7.3.2. Stigmatising Attitudes Towards Children in Schools

In the previous section, the results demonstrated that the children had the chance to defend themselves and show their emotions to their family members. They expressed themselves rejecting these behaviours verbally; however, their reaction was internalised in school. Moreover, the mothers demonstrated their awareness of the negative attitudes their children experience at school, as their children shared it with them, seeking help and emotional support.

“One time, the teacher called him Aggoun, and I think at that moment, he really became aware of the issues related to his stutter. He came home very sad and angry. She said it intentionally, fully aware of his stutter (saying confidently with a sad smile). He started avoiding her; he did not want to go to school after that... It affected him a lot” (Oum Youcef)

Following the previous arguments, labelling can also seriously influence the child’s schooling experience. The use of the word “ Aggoun” by the teacher contributes to the stigmatisation, leading the child who stutters to feelings of sadness and embarrassment, as it can lower their self-esteem. Nevertheless, due to the teacher’s position of authority, the child’s reaction to the stigma manifests as avoidance and internalised feelings of sadness and frustration. Therefore, considering his stutter, the teacher should be aware of the communicative strategies that create an inclusive and supportive environment for the child. Some children can verbally disapprove of the stigmatising behaviour, pointing out the behaviours they dislike. However, teachers should consider the fact that not all students can speak about their feelings. Especially since the teacher’s position sometimes plays a significant role in the way students behave and react in the classroom.

Based on the results, children who stutter in Algeria encounter more than labelling in schools, as stereotypes also appeared in the current study’s data. Most mothers have shared incidents that happened to their children at school, highlighting some stereotypes, bullying and discrimination. Similarly, the mothers have recounted several incidents where their children have encountered stereotyping, bullying, and discrimination.

“The teacher told my husband, ‘He has all this beauty and a good presence, but he stutters’ (imitating the way the teacher said it). So, I told her that stuttering has nothing to do with his beauty and presence. Then she said, ‘No, it is just because I did not expect that. I was shocked, and when I saw him like that, I felt sorry for him.’ (The mother told me this with a sad face; she felt stigmatised by what the teacher said).” (Oum Reda)

“Her teacher thinks that she stutters because she is a shy person, but it is not like that. She likes to participate in the classroom and school activities such as events, ceremonies, singing, and role plays, but she never had the chance to do that...” (Oum Aseel)

Stereotypes also appeared in the teachers' interview discussion when they were asked about their knowledge of the causes of stuttering. They have related stuttering to shyness, anxiety, and low self-esteem (see section 6.3.3). The feeling of pity towards children who stutter can also affect the child and his parents. The teacher holds a negative view of stuttering, which highlights the presence of stigma surrounding stuttering. The use of "I was shocked when I saw him stuttering" implies a sense of disappointment or disapproval associated with the child's stutter, although she recognises his physical attractiveness. This indicates that teachers relate physical appearance and a type of personality with stuttering. This can be related to the teachers' lack of knowledge about stuttering. Oum Aseel confirmed that stating how the teacher correlated her daughter's stutter to her personality, which contributed to stuttering misconceptions and eventually could lead to discrimination or biased treatment. Furthermore, the data reported some incidents where children who stuttered got bullied by their classmates in school. Some of the mothers stated the following:

"My son was kicked out of class once because he started a fight with his peers as they kept commenting on how he speaks and mocking him. He was frustrated... He never told me that until the teacher called me. And... What could I do? Nothing (she said it with a helpless smile). I spoke to him to understand, but... (expressed helplessness)" (Oum Djed)

"I went to speak with the teacher about my daughter because she told me that no one likes to talk to her. I think it's because they get annoyed with her stutter, but the teacher was so helpful... I never told my daughter this, ha-ha. She would not like it..." (Oum Ritta)

Bullying and discrimination against children who stutter, which appeared in the above quotations, have also been reported by speech therapists (section 7.2.1) and teachers (section 7.4.1). The mothers demonstrated their awareness of their children's school experiences. It is important to note that children who stutter might not share everything with their parents, as this occurred when Oum Djed stated that she only heard from the teacher. This indicates that children who stutter might not always openly communicate all their experiences with their parents or caregivers; this includes negative attitudes directed at them. While the mothers recounted several incidents, it is important to note that these experiences may not represent the daily interaction of children in Algeria. Nonetheless, the mothers emphasised that their children faced many negative attitudes at school. Based on the results, these negative attitudes stemmed from the lack of awareness about the child's stutter, insufficient knowledge, and irresponsible peer behaviours. The mothers addressed this as they chose to correct these attitudes against their children, as most of them tend to go to school to understand any issues related to their children. For instance, in the quotation above, Oum Ritta tried to improve her daughter's school experiences, as she went to school seeking the teacher's help, which ended up being positive.

7.3.3. Mothers' and Children's Reactions to Stigmatising Attitudes

The mothers showed sadness and helplessness during these situations, yet they reacted positively. All the mothers reacted to the experience of the stigmatising attitudes immediately as they occurred, or they took action and discussed it with the stigmatised, later aiming at correcting the perception and guiding them to reduce the stigmatising behaviours towards their children.

“His father went to talk to her and understand why she called him Aggoun, and she said she did not mean to address his stutter; she said it spontaneously and that it is a word she uses often, and it is fine. However, my son believes she said it because he stutters.” (Oum Youcef)

Based on the results, mothers show helplessness, sadness, disappointment, and frustration. However, all the mothers reacted immediately after knowing their child was stigmatised. When it is a school-related issue, the parents usually go in person to discuss it with the teacher. This helps parents and teachers understand the problem's core to address any lack of knowledge or misunderstanding. The latter is what the father did when the teacher stigmatised his son. Both parents and children react to the stigma; however, their reactions differ. The parents tend to search for a solution and correct attitudes, while children express their anger and sadness, rejecting these negative attitudes. Some of the mothers have stated the following.

“If she is speaking and someone tells her to shush or stop talking, she does not like it. When she is speaking with my sister, and she tells her ‘Shush, shush,’ she gets mad, starts crying, and says, ‘Let me finish talking.’ I tell them that she has the right to participate in conversations.” (Oum Yasmine)

“My son was kicked out of class once because he started a fight with his peers as they kept commenting on how he speaks and mocking him.” (Oum Djed)

According to the above extracts, the children who stutter do not accept some of the negative behaviours of their family members, such as interrupting them, bullying them, or even criticising how they speak. Their reaction, however, differed according to their personalities, as they could be aggressive or emotional. However, in both ways, their reactions do not tolerate these behaviours. Although both reactions of Djed and Yasmine demonstrate their rejection of these behaviours, they reacted differently. Oum Yasmine stated that their children' reaction was emotional and showed sadness and helplessness, “she started crying.”, while Oum Djed stated that “he started a fight,” demonstrating aggressive behaviour as a reaction to bullying. However, it is important to note that the reactions differ based on their personality.

7.4. Middle School Language Teachers

The results indicate that teachers were aware of the stigma that children who stutter experience. Since students' interaction and communication are important elements of teaching languages, the teacher holds a crucial role in integrating students who stutter. Nevertheless, teachers often face challenges embracing social-emotional learning within inclusive classrooms due to their viewpoints on this education approach (Harper, 2017). Consequently, it becomes crucial to investigate the perspectives of Algerian teachers concerning the stigma associated with stuttering and how they react to it using an inclusive approach.

The interviews with teachers demonstrated their understanding of negative attitudes and the associated constructions of the child who is classified as disabled. Based on the results of this study, it was found that there is a lack of attempts to raise awareness about stuttering and stigma despite teachers' awareness of the presence of stigma in schools. Many studies have reported similar results regarding the negative attitudes children who stutter experience in schools, such as bullying, stereotypes, and discrimination (Dean and Medina, 2021; Berchiatti et al., 2021; Blood and Blood, 2016; Boyle, 2018). This could lead to the understanding that there are insufficient resources and educational policies regarding the protection and inclusion of students who stutter, in addition to limited training (Junuzovic-Zunic, Mostafa and St. Louis, 2023). The teachers may consider stuttering as a minor issue compared to other disabilities to be focusing on, which eventually reflects on their cultural and personal beliefs.

7.4.1. Stigma and Bullying Towards Children Who Stutter in Schools

Teachers asserted that students who stutter are susceptible to bullying in schools, primarily by their peers, acknowledging their responsibility to mitigate or prevent such incidents. It is worth noting that children who face bullying should not be burdened with the expectation to initiate dialogues with their bullies in order to resolve bullying independently, as highlighted by (Hughes, 2014). The teacher explicitly stated that children who stutter in Algeria are bullied and labelled by their surroundings. One of the teachers, for example, argued:

"Being bullied, both by teachers and peers... For instance, when a student has trouble uttering a word, others laugh at him. This laughter becomes a stigma for him, or even when he says 'aaaaaa,' the teacher may get nervous about his delay in uttering a word. The teacher can become impatient with the student... I remember having a classmate who stuttered; she had difficulty with a word, and the teacher said, 'Are we going to keep waiting for you!' He was frustrated and yelled at her." (Samar, Female, 15 YOE)

The teacher argued that children who stutter in Algeria experience bullying. Laughing at them was one example Samar gave to demonstrate her peers' experience of stigmatising behaviour. The children who stutter are bullied by some of their classmates as well as by some teachers. Samar explained that children who stutter need more time to answer than their classmates, which could be frustrating to some teachers, resulting in a negative attitude with an angry tone. It is significant to highlight that despite Samar's role as a teacher, she did not hesitate to call out this attitude among her colleagues. This negative attitude towards students underscores the paradox that while teachers are often seen as the main figures in reducing stigma in the classroom, they can sometimes unintentionally cause the stigma. Nevertheless, the teacher's frustration could result from the pressure on the teacher to achieve the lecture's objective in a limited time. As the teacher stated, "Are we going to keep waiting?" which refers to time pressure, not a reaction to stuttering specifically. However, teachers should be aware of their attitudes towards children who stutter, as this reaction could have the opposite effect. In this vein, one of the teachers as she noted the following:

"Honestly, as a teacher, I am bound by a syllabus that needs to be completed within a specific time. Therefore, I try to give students who stutter shorter passages to read compared to their classmates. I still want to ensure they have their rights, but I also have to consider their classmates who also have the right to participate." (Dania, female, 10 YOE)

Dania justified that students who stutter need more time than their classmates. Based on this analysis, the teacher shows that she gives the students who stutter the opportunity to participate. However, she is selective regarding the amount of speaking given to students who stutter. This demonstrates the teachers' skills in managing time and integrating students who stutter. She argued that giving them more time to participate in the classroom would affect the right of their classmates to participate as well. Eventually, it would affect the flow of the syllabus as well. However, the statement "I still want to give them their rights" suggests that students who stutter are receiving something different from their classmates, potentially leading to the feeling of stigmatisation. Nevertheless, the exclusion criteria are absent as the teacher integrates the students who stutter, giving them shorter passages. This was also suggested by therapists who participated in this study, such as speech therapists Hassan, Amel, and Maya, and some other teachers, such as Malak, Nassima, and Amal. This considers the needs of all students, which is a valid concern, yet it has to be discussed further with the parents, for example, and specialists. As the teacher intends to ensure equity, it might unintentionally create a sense of discrimination.

Furthermore, similar to the other group participants, speech therapists and mothers of children who stutter, the teachers reported that the children are not only stigmatised in schools but also by their families. One of the teachers stated the following:

"I think that bullying is the most common issue for those who stutter. Ahh, bullying starts from their relatives; the family is the source, then there's bullying from society and their friends at school or even outside of school. It's the main factor that makes those who stutter shy or frustrated." (Samar, Female, 15 YOE)

In line with the mothers' responses, teachers argued that the stigma is experienced first in the family. Samar used the expression *"the most common"*, demonstrating that society is familiar with these issues and aware of the negative behaviours children who stutter could face. Furthermore, all the teachers agreed that bullying can exceed the familial confines of societal interaction, including friends and surroundings. This confirms that the stigma is ingrained within society, which calls for a broader reflection on cultural and societal norms and attitudes. This demonstrates that bullying requires a comprehensive societal shift that promotes a culture of respect and empathy towards individuals who stutter. This could help children who stutter grow in a healthy environment without any negative psychological effects from bullying. Nevertheless, the teachers' recognition of the presence of bullying associated with stuttering in the community is a cornerstone of practical education.

Since middle school students are at the age of building their personalities, stuttering could make it more difficult for them to deal with psychological issues because of the changes in hormones during this stage. Along the same lines, teachers highlighted that adolescence contributes to the negative effect of stuttering. One of the teachers stated the following:

"It's obvious that children who stutter are bullied. As adolescents, they don't understand that making fun of them hurts; they see it as a normal thing, just mocking them, and do not realise the impact. So, it's obvious they will go through negative experiences like this." (Nassima, female, 5 YOE)

"In middle school, students are developing their personalities as adolescents. We've witnessed this, especially students in the first and second years being bullied; for example, they are called Aggoun. As teachers, we do our best to prevent this from affecting the students who stutter." (Malak, female, 4 YOE)

Teachers highlighted that children who stutter in middle school are going through a susceptible period, adolescence, and bullying could profoundly affect their personality. Adolescence is a crucial period for the child to develop their personality. The teachers demonstrated their recognition of the impact of stuttering on adolescents, especially when it is followed by bullying. This suggests that the teachers are aware of the complete picture of the student's well-being, which leads to the emphasis on the need for an environment that is supportive, inclusive, and promotes the emotional and social

development of middle school students. According to Blood and Blood (2016), the adverse psychological, social, educational and physical consequences of bullying have been recorded extensively in children and teenagers. Nassima extended on the previous perception of the existence of bullying in middle schools, justifying that their classmates believe that this will not have any negative effect on their peers who stutter. This proves that there is a lack of awareness among middle school students that helps promote an environment that shows empathy and supports children with disabilities. While the teacher showed understanding of the reason behind the students' attitudes, she seemed to have that perspective that offered no solution to bullying among middle school students. Malak demonstrated her understanding of the effect of bullying on adolescents, as she observed that students who stutter are more bullied than others who are not. Accordingly, more attention should be brought to students with disabilities (Andreou, Didaskalou and Vlachou, 2015), including stuttering.

Furthermore, it is essential to highlight that this could appear among students unfamiliar with their classmates' stuttering since it often happens among "First and second years" students, as Malak stated. Accordingly, this could support the argument that emphasis on raising awareness among students at the beginning of the year. However, teachers tend to work with children who stutter to empower them instead and eventually reduce the effect of these negative attitudes. This could give the impression that teachers believe the stigma cannot be erased entirely. Therefore, they should strengthen the personality of the students who stutter to help them deal with the stigma and eventually lessen the psychological effect of these stigmatising attitudes. Although the teachers are against any stigmatising attitude, the children could still bully them or label them as Aggoun.

7.4.2. Peers' Reactions to Stuttering in Educational Settings

While all teachers tend to embrace the inclusion of students who stutter in the classroom, they still draw attention to the possibility of the peers' negative reactions to stuttering, such as laughing. Peer teasing is most recognised at the Elementary and middle school levels (Cobb, Daniels and Panico, 2019). In this study, laughing was one of the most stated peer reactions in the classroom during stuttering incidents. Some of the teachers stated the following:

"We can't ignore situations where classmates make fun of them. If they stutter in front of them, classmates may start laughing. For students who stutter, it is impossible to relax again and speak freely... It is not possible (expressing sadness and helplessness). They might think, 'I will be in a difficult situation if I speak again,' so they stay quiet." (Dania, female, 10 YO)

"Students laugh at how their classmates stutter when speaking... repeating the same... (mimicking). Mainly, they laugh because my students are afraid to say

something in front of me. OK, so they laugh. Students who stutter know they' are being laughed at because of how they speak." (Leen, female, 4 YOE)

"The student I'm teaching had a tough time with classmates; when he started stuttering, they began laughing, provoking him, mistreating him, and mocking him. However, we as educators oppose these attitudes." (Malak, female, 4 YOE)

The teacher demonstrated their awareness of the student's reaction to stuttering, contributing to their strategies to reduce the stigma (See section 8.3.). Unfortunately, the teachers' responses demonstrate that peers' laughter is a typical response to stuttering. However, some teachers find themselves in situations where they cannot help as this could be beyond their control. This could result from the lack of experience and training that encompasses knowledge about stutter and reactions to stigma. Although there were no teachers' guides or policies regarding the stigma associated with stuttering, the teacher did not express their need for it. This may reflect on the cultural side of it, where stuttering is not considered an issue to be addressed in schools. Dania expressed her inability to correct this situation by saying, *"I mean... it's not possible"*, as she showed helplessness while thinking of providing a solution to overcome the effect of laughter on the student who stuttered. The teacher believed this could result in anticipation of future stigma, pushing them to self-isolation and exclusion to avoid experiencing this situation again. These negative experiences can affect their confidence and hinder their academic progress. This is a strong reason for seeking guidance from stakeholders and considering it to be addressed in educational politics and training.

Leen raised the idea that students are aware of the consequences of bullying in the classroom as they avoid exposing negative behaviours or words, eventually reducing the exposure of the stigma. Nevertheless, the teacher showed limited control over these negative attitudes as she pointed out that laughter still occurs sometimes during stuttering situations. Teachers expressed their opposition to such attitudes, acknowledging the challenges students who stutter go through, as Malak described *"tough times"*. However, there is a lack of attention regarding stuttering and conferences that are addressed to teachers and students that aim at reducing the stigmatisation situations. The latter could be explained from a cultural perspective, as stuttering is not considered a disability in Algeria. In addition, teachers do not encounter a significant number of stutterers annually, which could explain why they do not prioritise it as an issue that requires immediate attention or resolution.

7.4.3. Labelling Children who Stuttering as "Aggoun"

Furthermore, the teachers demonstrated their awareness regarding other negative behaviours that students who stutter experience in middle school, such as labelling. This could be known culturally

and not only in schools. One of the teachers said, "Those who have speech disorders usually in Algeria labelled them as "Wethweth, Wegweg, Aggoun" Teacher Noah. Like bullying, it is also significant that teachers know that students who stutter are sometimes labelled or given nicknames by their peers to address it. These labels define that student's identity and can diminish how others will socialise and mix with the labelled person. However, the labelled person may not wish to socialise with the peer group if they perceive the use of damaging labels by their peer group to describe them (Goffman, 1963). Teacher Noah stated that usually, individuals with speech disorders are labelled differently. However, the same teacher later used the word "Aggoun" during the interview discussion to describe a student who stutters.

"I had a student with severe stuttering; as we say Aggoun, when I asked him a question, he struggled to utter a word like 'aaa ddddeedd do' (mimicking the student's stutter). He wanted to say the word, but he could not, even though he knew it." (Noah, male, 37 YO)

In the above statement, the teacher tries to explain the status of his students using the word "Aggoun", saying "as we say," which demonstrates that although it is inappropriate, the Algeria society uses it to describe and identify individuals with a stutter. Furthermore, Teachers and mothers have mimicked the stutter of the individual; however, their intention was not to bully or label the individuals who stutter but to explain a point or describe the stutter. This demonstrates the lack of inclusive language for stuttering that helps reduce the stigma associated with it. The following section will discuss these reactions and the factors contributing to mitigating the stigma according to the teachers who participated in this study.

8. Chapter Eight: Presentation of the Findings

Stakeholders' Knowledge of ways to reduce stigma

8.1. Introduction

The previous chapter reported the participants' knowledge and awareness of the stigma children who stutter experience in schools and in their daily lives. Understanding their experiences of and being knowledgeable about stuttering have a significant contribution to the improvement of social attitudes, helping individuals who stutter be accommodated, assisted, and accepted in the community (Tellis and St Louis, 2015). This chapter reports the participants' perceptions regarding the interventions that help reduce the stigma towards children who stutter in Algerian middle schools based on their knowledge presented in the previous chapter to address the third research question.

What are the stakeholders' perspectives on the strategies for mitigating stigma related stuttering in Algerian middle school?

This question will be further addressed in the third section of the discussion in Chapter 9, while this chapter lays the ground for a better understanding of mitigating stigma within the Algerian culture. It is important to highlight that the knowledge presented in this chapter and its discussion will also be linked with the previous data, as all three sections support each other and provide a meaningful understanding and interpretation of the data.

Some researchers aimed to investigate the stigma associated with stuttering (Boyle, 2018; Dean and Medina, 2021). While others aimed to examine the strategies that help reduce the stigma in individuals who stutter, E.g., (Abdalla and St. Louis, 2014; Boyle, Dioguardi and Pate, 2016). The main approach in all these studies is education and awareness about stuttering to reduce the associated stigma (Louis et al., 2020), which was reported in this study as well. It is significant to mention that developing an anti-stigma approach to improving public attitudes could be a result of having a clear picture of the stigma towards stuttering (Boyle, 2017), in Algeria. Therefore, the previous chapter helped setting up the scenes for the current chapter, where a number of stigmatizing behaviours were highlighted by the participants.

In addition to strategies stated along the interview discussions, the participants were introduced to imaginary situations that could happen to students who stutter in the classroom. This helped the study to determine the teachers' attitudes during these situations and to highlight the strategies they use to reduce the stigma. The triangulation of the perceptions contributed to strengthening the results, as the three groups are close to the children who stutter, yet from different sides. Similar to the

previous chapters, this chapter reports and interprets the participants' results in separate sections starting with reporting and interpreting the results of speech therapists, the mothers, and finally the teachers. At the end of this chapter, these results will be discussed together, aiming to address the final research question.

Three main approaches, which will be discussed further in this chapter, were reported by the participants, education and raising awareness, developing a warm relationship between teacher and students who stutter, and ignorance of stigmatizing attitudes, mainly negative laughter. Based on the results of this study, the strong agreement among stakeholders regarding the three stigma-reducing strategies highlighted in this chapter not only aligns with existing research but also propels a persuasive argument for the implementation of these approaches in educational settings or in research to be evaluated. This would represent a pivotal step toward cultivating an environment of inclusivity and understanding for stuttering in Algerian middle schools.

8.2. Speech Language Therapists

Speech-language therapists suggested many strategies that contribute to the reduction of stigma. Some of these interventions were suggested to be applied before the occurrence of stigma while others after. It is important to mention that some of these strategies might be adequate to Algerian culture but not to all societies. Overall, the speech therapists stressed the importance of raising awareness and knowledge about stuttering and building a warm relationship between the teacher and children who stutter. This was suggested to contribute to the implication of some inclusion criteria to encourage the children who stutter to participate in the classroom.

8.2.1. Raising awareness about stuttering in education

As part of developing peers' and teachers' knowledge about stuttering, speech therapists pointed out the importance of providing a health sheet for the child who has the disability. This sheet can equip teachers with a clearer picture of the child's speech disability and what support might be beneficial in the classroom setting. Furthermore, being aware of the child's fluency could have a positive impact on the teacher's reaction to their stutter. One of the speech therapists said the following:

"Raising awareness...Raising awareness among parents must be the first step. Each student's medical record form should accurately reflect any issues the child faces. Parents should be honest when filling out these forms; if their child has a stutter or hearing difficulties, they should indicate it. This information is crucial, especially for severe cases, as it may lead to referrals to specialised centres if the child is enrolled in public schools. It is important that people understand and recognise these challenges." (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE)

Hassan emphasised on reporting information about the students' disability to the teacher in order to avoid any mistreatment to the student, highlighting that this is the responsibility of the parents. Nevertheless, this has not been highlighted by the other groups. The mothers have stated that they go themselves, or the child's fathers, at the beginning of the schooling year to tell the teacher about their child's condition to avoid any misunderstanding. In cases where this does not occur, the teachers proactively initiate contact with the parents and arranges an in-person meeting upon noticing the disability, facilitating further discussion (see sections 8.3.1. and 8.4.1.). This suggests a lack of awareness about using disability reports to inform teachers. The speech therapist's suggestion aligns with the idea of stuttering disclosure. Nevertheless, research has shown that it could have different reactions, either negative or positive. Still, a study conducted by Boyle (2018) revealed that the positive outcomes of disclosure could be beneficial for personal improvement and confidence, but it could also limit life opportunities and, in this case, affect students' participation in the classroom. Still, Boyle (2018) argued that understanding the disclosure of stuttering will ultimately help in supporting students who stutter to reduce stigma.

Drawing from their knowledge and awareness of the disability, the teachers can make informed decisions to accommodate the students' needs. In addition, this could also reduce any misunderstandings that could lead to stigmatising attitudes. As many incidents occurred in the data (see section 7.3.2) due to the teachers' lack of awareness of the student's stutter. Therefore, the speech therapists emphasized the importance of raising awareness and improving the teacher and students' knowledge about stuttering.

"Teachers should have a detailed understanding of stuttering to effectively interact and support stutterers. I think that, and it is my personal point of view, it is impossible that the teacher can deal with stutterers correctly. If a teacher lacks knowledge about stuttering, their interactions can unintentionally worsen the situation. Even if a teacher thinks that they are doing well, the complexity of stuttering requires careful handling, even as speech therapists we are very careful with them... Similar to handling delicate new clothes, you must be cautious not to inadvertently cause harm to the students who stutter with a simple word or gesture, because this will affect their interaction with the teacher. Therefore, integrating a stuttering child into the classroom environment to assist them is no easy task." (Ahmad, Male, 7 YO)

Ahmad related the negative attitudes of teachers to their lack of knowledge about stuttering. Therefore, he argued that teachers should learn about stuttering to correct their reaction to it and improve their attitude towards children who stutter in the classroom. According to (Hearne et al., 2021) teachers' positive impact is based on possessing accurate knowledge of stuttering and effective approaches to support students who stutter. Although Ahmad highlighted the importance of

addressing the teachers' knowledge regarding stuttering, he still believes that dealing with it in real life is very difficult. This was also stated by other speech therapists who participated in this study such as Safa and Hassan. The speech therapists argued that even them as specialists find it difficult to avoid causing distress to the child who stutters. Ahmad described the children who stutter as the new clothes, arguing that the teacher should be very careful and aware of their attitudes towards them.

Furthermore, the speech therapists argued that some teachers initiate efforts to learn about stuttering and how to deal with students who stutter. Studies argued that teachers could help and improve their attitudes toward students who stutter when they are better equipped with appropriate knowledge regarding stuttering (Thome, 2024), which explains the teachers' motivation for improving their knowledge about stuttering as stated in the above quotation. Despite the difficulty, children who stutter need to be integrated and included in the classroom. Therefore, some teachers tend to go themselves and ask the specialists for advice due to the absence of delivering this knowledge in the teachers training and the study days or conferences. These personal efforts aim to improve their knowledge and correct the teachers' attitudes and reactions towards children who stutter, which will grant them a better school experience.

"One day, a teacher approached me seeking information about stuttering; she wanted to understand how to interact with and support stuttering children better. Some teachers are genuinely interested in learning, especially those with a background in psychology, as they prioritise understanding cases to enhance their skills." (Leya, Female, 6 YOE)

Based on the results, the speech therapists who participated do not organise study days to help teachers improve their knowledge regarding stuttering, still teachers ask their guidance when needed (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE). This demonstrates that teachers in Algeria make personal efforts to improve the students' schooling experiences. Based on this, there is a need for guidance and counselling programs for inclusive education addressed to teachers to help them ensure equal rights for all students (see Indreswari and Ediyanto, 2024). Leya's response demonstrated that teachers are in need to learn about stuttering, and she pointed out that those who studied psychology are more eager to learn the appropriate attitudes towards children who stutter. Nevertheless, only teachers who have children who stutter tend to seek guidance, otherwise they do not.

Despite the emphasis on developing knowledge about stuttering, the results reported by all participants showed that there is a lack of attempts to organise conferences and activities that aim of raising knowledge and awareness about stuttering. *"They should organise seminars in schools, but they have never done (expressing disappointment)"*, (Lama, Female, 4 YOE). The speech therapists

highlighted the fact that our society needs to be aware and cultivated regarding speech disorders. Lama explicitly reported that she supports the idea of organising study days, yet she gave the impression that she is disappointed that there was no attempt to improve the teachers' and students' knowledge about speech disorders or stuttering. One of the speech disorders argued that even colleagues have that perception that the society will not be interested to attend such conferences saying the following:

*"I would be enthusiastic to arrange such a conference. However, when I previously proposed organising a study day on autism, my colleagues were hesitant, they did not welcome the idea. They doubted the interest and participation, suggesting that our society lacks a culture of such events."
(Safa, Female, 4 YOE)*

All the speech therapists who participated in this study supported the idea of organising conferences, none of them have organised a study day in middle schools to improve the students and teachers' knowledge regarding stuttering and its effects. It is evident that collaboration between professionals and teachers is deemed beneficial for inclusive practice in schools, where speech therapists, in this case, can share their expertise and help teachers to better support children who stutter (Jeremy, Spandagou and Hinitt, 2025). However, none of the participants actually organised one that focused mainly on stuttering, as the conference that they presented was related to other disorders such as autism. Some speech-language therapists stated that they have presented at conferences and that they were invited to radio talk shows (Safa, Hassan, Ahmad, and Leya) but the topics were never about stuttering as they do not consider it as a difficult speech disorder to be addressed. This finding highlights Algeria's societal views regarding stuttering, potentially contributing to the understanding of the lack of intervention to reduce stuttering or address its associated stigma. Interesting, this aligns with the neurodiversity perspective of disability (Simpson, Campbell, and Constantino, 2021), where stuttering is perceived as a natural variation rather than a disability. Safa explained that taking the initiative with colleagues to organise study days or conferences is culturally embedded, based on the perception that the majority would not be interested.

That being said, the majority of speech therapists encourage this to be held in middle schools and primary schools to help teachers and students understand stuttering and how to react to it. Based on the results society needs to work more on organising events that focus on stuttering and the stigma associated with it. One of the speech therapists stated the following: *"Speaking about our region, most of our teachers do not know about stuttering; they need training on this disorder"*, (Leya, Female, 6 YOE). It is important to mention that the therapists do not really blame the teachers for not learning about the stutter or not being able to manage the stutter in the classroom.

"We do not blame teachers because they have a considerable number of students to teach; as specialists, sometimes we make mistakes. Imagine a class full of students. You can't cater to each student individually and ensure they all receive their due rights. That's why I was saying that this relies on the teacher's mental presence." (Ahmad, Male, 7 YOE)

"I don't directly work with teachers, and in middle schools in Algeria, each subject is taught by different teachers. With students studying ten subjects with ten different teachers, it's impractical to engage with all the teachers. Hence, it's crucial to establish parents as the communication link between teachers and specialists, particularly for language teachers." (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE)

The issue with secondary school, as stated by Ahmad and Hassan is the number of classes and students that teachers have, thus, it is difficult for them to give all students the attention they need. This echoes a universal concern in the literature regarding the effect of workload on teachers' ability to implement inclusive practices effectively (Agyapong et al., 2022). Besides, the teacher also can have some external issues that affect their performance in the classroom. The speech therapists pointed out that they cannot work privately with teachers, however, the parents are the main figures in providing the teacher with all the information they need to help their children. However, teachers are still required to learn about the child's disability aiming for a successful inclusive classroom.

Although the stigma could still occur, it should be addressed once it appears. The majority of speech therapists believe that stigma is not something that we can control, as the child will be stigmatised and bullied during the absence of the teacher or the caregiver.

"These negative behaviours persist beyond the classroom; they accompany the individual throughout their life. An example of this is when they call him 'Aggoun.' Therefore, teachers should raise awareness among peers about stuttering, especially since physical punishment is prohibited in schools. By making peers aware and holding them aware and embarrassed for their negative behaviours, teachers can help prevent such incidents from recurring, at least in their presence." (Safa, Female, 4 YOE)

Safa, like the other speech therapists, believes that children who stutter could be stigmatised by their peers especially when they are not supervised. This highlights the teachers' role in raising awareness among peers to reduce the stigma and foster a sense of responsibility for their attitudes towards their peers who stutter. Accordingly, developing their knowledge about stuttering, and especially addressing the negative attitudes gives a moral lesson that arises. While knowledge about stuttering is valuable, teachers can still address negative student attitudes by leveraging their existing classroom

management skills. These skills, often acquired through training or experience, can be effectively adapted to create a more supportive environment for students who stutter. However, students are more likely to disclose negative experiences with teachers when they feel a strong sense of trust and support in the relationship. This sense of trust allows students to believe their concerns will be addressed, and that they will receive emotional support.

The following section emphasises the teacher's role in the classroom and the importance of building warm relationships with students to improve their schooling experience and reduce the stigma that is associated with stuttering.

8.2.2. Students who Stutter and Teacher Relationship

Teachers play a crucial social role in shaping students' intellectual and emotional development by fostering a classroom environment that motivates and stimulates learning (Koca, 2016). Research suggests positive teacher-student relationships create a supportive classroom environment, promoting successful school adaptation and boosting student motivation. This aligns with the results of this study, where most participants highlighted the importance of maintaining a warm relationship with students who stutter to reduce the stigma experienced and positively contribute to student interaction in the classroom. Accordingly, some speech-language therapists emphasised the importance of the teacher's role in the classroom by stating the following:

"Teachers should recognise that their role extends beyond delivering lectures, especially when teaching adolescents with disabilities. In such cases, teachers need to establish close relationships with students because adolescence is a vulnerable stage." (Nour, Female, 3 YOE)

Nour, as other speech therapists such as Maya, pointed out teachers should feel the responsibility toward their students, especially those adolescents who have disabilities. The therapist has explained that the teacher should know that the period is difficult for them, needless to mention that the disability makes this experience even more difficult. Therefore, Nour pointed out that their role does not rely on delivering the lecture only but on trying to build a warm relationship which could have a positive impact on the students' study experience in general. This perspective aligns with studies that highlight the importance of teacher and student relationships in promoting inclusion and reducing negative feelings among students with disabilities (Roorda et al., 2011). According to the participants, building a close relationship with the student helps build a comfortable atmosphere in the classroom. Hassan pointed out the following:

"The relationship between the teacher and the student should be positive and nurturing. When students trust their teachers, they are more likely to share

their concerns. Other than that, I don't think it is possible to avoid the stigma." (Hassan, Male, 14 YOE)

Based on the above quotation, having the assurance that the students have the confidence to express themselves without thinking about negative consequences indicates a successful student-teacher relationship. A positive relationship between students and teachers not only enhances engagement and motivation in the classroom but also fosters stronger peer relationships, contributing to a more inclusive environment characterized by acceptance and integration (Hughes and Im, 2016). Furthermore, it helps the teacher to understand the students, manage the classroom, and meet the students' needs. It is significant to mention that the majority of speech therapists believe that children who stutter would still experience negative attitudes. Therefore, most of the participants emphasised helping the child to develop their self-esteem, as they focused on this more during the treatment. Thus, by building that warm relationship teachers will not reduce the stigma, but they can reduce its effect. The speech therapists have highlighted some of the positive behaviours that help build a good teacher and student relationship such as encouraging the student to participate in the classroom and engage with the lecture. One of the speech therapists stated the following:

"Teachers should actively encourage student participation, unlike primary school, recognising the unique challenges that middle school students face due to their age and developmental stage. Adolescents may struggle with shyness and fear, requiring teachers to allocate sufficient time and support." (Lama, Female, 4 YOE)

Lama addressed many interesting points to build a warm relationship with the students taking into account the effect of the transitional phase from primary to middle school and adolescence. Both these factors can have an impact on the students' behaviours and hence on their relationship with their surroundings. Although being 'shy' and 'anxious' could differ from one student to another according to their personality, the students could still face some difficulties, especially during the first year. As the primary school system in Algeria is different from middle schools, where students need more support to adapt to the system, whether they have a disability or not.

Effective communication with the students permits the teacher to listen and understand the students' needs which helps build a supportive environment with the students who stutter (see Duta, Panisoara and Panisoara, 2015). Therefore, Lama also pointed out that the student should be prepared before being asked to participate in the classroom to avoid the stress that can provoke the stutter. This could be addressed after having good communication with the student which could eventually contribute to positive attitudes. The majority of the speech therapists emphasised providing enough time for the

students to answer and preparing them beforehand “Teachers should avoid posing unexpected or surprising questions to students *who stutter*” (Ahmad, Male, 7 YOE) and “They should provide advance notice about discussion topics, giving students time to prepare their responses.” (Maya, Female, 6 YOE). This demonstrates the importance of understanding the students’ needs and engagement methods that should be used in the classroom.

In conclusion, the speech therapists reported two main interventions to reduce stigma in the classroom and create a better environment for students. First, improving knowledge and raising awareness about stuttering. Second, building stronger relationships between students and teachers. Hence, their effectiveness in mitigating stigma is echoed by the literature that aligns with them. The following section presents the results of the mothers of children who stutter regarding their perception of interventions that could reduce the stigma associated with stuttering, drawing on their understanding of their children’s personalities and experiences that led to positive outcomes in mitigating stigma within their schools.

8.3. Mothers of children who stutter

The mothers demonstrated a basic understanding of stuttering, however, there were notable similarities between their reported strategies and speech therapists who tend to be more knowledgeable. Some of these similar strategies are raising awareness and building strong relationships with their children who stutter. This finding suggests that interventions targeting awareness among students and building positive teacher-student relationships are likely to mitigate classroom stigma significantly. It is important to note that the mothers approached these strategies from different perspectives. Speech therapists’ responses were based on their knowledge and experience with many children who stutter, whereas mothers shared insights based on what best suits their own children. Mothers provided valuable insights into their child’s unique experiences and emotional well-being, which can inform and personalise broader intervention strategies. This highlights a potential limitation of parent-focused interventions as their effectiveness may vary depending on individual circumstances and characteristics. Nonetheless, it is important to acknowledge that parental involvement remains crucial.

8.3.1. Raising Awareness about Stuttering

Raising awareness was the most commonly reported strategy by the mothers, as they believe it has greatly helped them with their children. Therefore, this reported strategy is likely to be effective, given that it is supported by mothers who have recognised its efficacy through their experience with their children’s teachers. Additionally, mothers recounted specific incidents where a lack of teacher awareness led to negative consequences for their children. The anecdotes shared by mothers offer

powerful illustrations of the challenges faced by children who stutter in classrooms. Accordingly, this strongly emphasises the need for increased awareness regarding students' disabilities and highlights the urgency of addressing this issue underscoring the need for effective support systems.

The speech therapist advocates for the completion of medical record sheets by parents to equip teachers with essential information about their children's disability. Although it has been argued that it is not always easy to disclose stuttering to other people (Hartman, Klop and Swartz, 2023), mothers appear to be unaware of its benefits, opting to personally report such details to prevent potential stigmatisation or misunderstanding in the classroom. This underscores the importance of a collaborative and nuanced approach between speech-language therapists, mothers and teachers in addressing this knowledge gap. Nevertheless, the mothers' approach to raising teachers' awareness suggests a practical solution to reduce incidents that stuttering children encounter in the classroom. One of the mothers stated the following:

"To be honest, my daughter has excelled in school without issues. However, at the start of each school year, I visit her teachers and explain to them the issue of my daughter. For instance, if she starts speaking, I request that they allow her to finish independently." (Oum Yasmine)

Although Oum Yasmine aims to emphasise the importance of informing teachers about the children's condition at the beginning of the school year, the quotation highlights the proactive role of parental support in navigating educational challenges associated with their children's needs. Indeed research argued that parents, unlike other groups of participants of this study, are not only required to manage interventions that reduce stuttering and the stigma associated with it, but also to address the emotional impact on their children (Hartman, Klop and Swartz, 2023). It also underscores the importance of collaboration between parents and teachers in supporting students by engaging with teachers annually, if not regularly, to explain the child's speech issues. Hence, the participant demonstrates a worthy commitment to ensuring their daughter's educational experience is supportive and accommodating. Furthermore, the efforts of mothers like Oum Yasmine highlight the necessity of individualised attention and effective communication between parents and educators. It is crucial to recognise that each child is unique, and what may be a suitable request for one child, like Oum Yasmine's request for uninterrupted speaking, may not be applicable or beneficial for others. For instance, in the case of the participant's daughter, interrupting her could contribute to a child developing self-stigma, believing she is being treated differently due to her speech issue. With that being said, the above quotation underscores broader systemic challenges in ensuring equitable and accessible education for all students, particularly those with specific needs requiring tailored support

and accommodations. One mother's statement further illustrates how unawareness of a child's condition can lead to stigmatising attitudes.

"One of my child's regular teachers was very supportive, but when she took maternity leave, the substitute teacher was unaware of my son's stutter. After a month, she contacted us requesting documentation to prove his condition because she initially didn't believe him. She told us I thought he was lying" (Oum Reda)

Oum Reda further emphasises the importance of raising teachers' awareness about children's conditions, particularly stuttering in this study, to reduce negative behaviours towards them. It is worth noting that both parents, Oum Reda and Oum Yasmine, highlighted the supportive nature of teachers after discussing their children's issues, which contributed to increased teacher consciousness and understanding of the child's condition. However, Oum Reda raises a critical concern about the potential impact of temporary teacher replacements by substitute teachers, often without parental notification. This situation can lead to substitute teachers lacking essential information about students, including those with speech issues like stuttering. Despite the child explaining his stutter to the teacher, the teacher's need to contact the parent for confirmation may suggest a lack of trust in the child's explanation, potentially affecting their relationship. Moreover, the excerpt indicates that teachers may not receive written reports from the administration regarding student disabilities, exacerbating their unfamiliarity with stuttering as a speech disorder. Oum Reda's observations underscore how a lack of teacher awareness can contribute to stigma, reflecting stereotypical perceptions of stuttering. This highlights the necessity for comprehensive and proactive strategies within educational institutions to foster inclusivity and accommodate diverse learning needs. Placing the burden solely on parents to advocate for their children's rights and educational experiences may be limiting. Therefore, many teachers suggest that raising awareness should be supported but the teachers' ability to manage any situation that could have a negative impact on the child. Accordingly, one of the mothers stated the following:

"At my son's school, they organise conferences but haven't addressed stuttering. I think it is crucial to train teachers on managing stuttering and addressing negative attitudes toward it. The Ministry of Education could help with that!" (Oum Ibrahim)

Oum Ibrahim advocated for a broader understanding of disabilities, the core concern, as expressed by Oum Reda "Our teachers are not trained about stuttering", lies in a lack of specific knowledge about stuttering itself. Consequently, mothers prioritise equipping teachers with knowledge to identify stuttering and develop effective support strategies. Furthermore, the participant's quote

exposes a critical gap in the lack of addressing subjects related to stuttering in schools. Accordingly, it emphasises the need for proactive measures and policy interventions to improve knowledge and support for students who stutter within the educational system by implementing teachers' training to help manage stuttering in the classroom. The suggestion of Ministry of Education involvement emphasises the importance of systemic support in creating inclusive environments for students with speech disorders. However, it is important to acknowledge that the mothers' emphasis may have been more on fostering in-depth knowledge about managing stuttering effectively and its associated stigma, rather than simply learning about the mechanics of stuttering itself.

8.3.2. Addressing Negative Behaviours among Peers

According to Browne (2013), teachers are faced with pressure to achieve positive academic outcomes, especially within inclusive classes. Despite the absence of the teachers' formal training and the teachers' awareness of the student's condition, they still might navigate situations with their peers. Participants acknowledged that some students do not realise the impact of their negative attitudes towards their peers who stutter. Building on this idea, mothers suggested that teachers should actively promote awareness about stuttering among the classmates of students who stutter.

"In cases of stigma, the teacher should explain to students that their classmate has a stutter, not a disability and that they can support him. At the same time, for students who stutter, the teacher should encourage and tell them, 'You can recover, believe in yourself and help yourself not to stutter so that you do not let them laugh at you'." (Oum Yasmine)

Oum Yasmine emphasises the critical role of teachers in raising awareness about stuttering and addressing negative behaviours within the classroom. She suggested that the teacher is responsible for educating the students about stuttering by correcting misconceptions or negative perceptions. This helps the students to foster an understanding regarding stuttering and eventually avoid any negative behaviours in the future. However, a notable aspect is that mothers appear to prioritize addressing stigmatizing behaviours over imparting specific knowledge about stuttering. This shift in emphasis suggests that, from the mother's perspective, creating an inclusive atmosphere is not solely about understanding the technicalities of stuttering but is equally, if not more, focused on eradicating the harmful behaviours and attitudes that contribute to stigma. Kahveci (2023) argued that teachers' attitudes and reactions in the classroom have a significant impact on students in many ways. This highlights the importance of teachers' classroom management skills rather than focusing only on their knowledge of the disability. These findings challenge conventional approaches that primarily concentrate on educational content and suggest a more nuanced strategy that involves cultivating an

empathetic and respectful classroom culture. Oum Yasmine highlighted the significance of teacher support for students who stutter. Her recommendations centred on fostering self-confidence among these students. Nevertheless, this approach may inadvertently put pressure on students to avoid stuttering, potentially resulting in adverse effects as they experience heightened stress about their speech. Stuttering is inherently uncontrollable, with students often unable to predict when they will stutter or speak fluently.

Moreover, teachers can control negative laughter and reactions in the classroom setting which underscore the importance of classroom management skills (see Kaya and Selvitopu, 2019). Some of the mothers added that the teacher could ask the students who were involved in stigmatizing attitudes towards their classmates who stutter to imagine themselves in the place of those who stutter.

"Teachers should raise awareness among students, emphasising the impact of laughing at classmates who stutter or make fun of them. They should encourage empathy by asking students to imagine how they would feel in the same situation." (Oum Youcef)

Mothers emphasised on the importance of actively addressing and mitigating negative attitudes to promote a more positive and inclusive attitude. Oum Youcef highlights a broader societal issue among peers in middle schools which is the lack of empathy, therefore, her suggestion of education focused on raising empathy by addressing and mitigating such behaviours using a psychological approach. This approach involves encouraging students to engage in perspective-taking by imagining themselves in the situation of their peers who stutter and are being made fun of. This approach was suggested by the majority of mothers, hence, according to them this could help these students gain a deeper awareness of the impact of stigmatisation and develop a heightened sensitivity towards their peers. However, promoting empathy alone might not be sufficient. Effective interventions require concrete strategies and consistent reinforcement of positive behaviours within the classroom as well. Still, promoting empathy and mitigating negative behaviours that cause embarrassment or distress to classmates through engaging activities and clearly defined expectations, could also be of a significant impact to building a more inclusive and respectful learning environment.

Most mothers who emphasise raising awareness demonstrate limited skills in addressing these negative attitudes. They lack the proper way to express themselves, which could lead to unintended outcomes. It is important to inform students about the nature of stuttering, as it can develop at any age. However, the way this information is conveyed is crucial. For instance, the expression "this could happen to them at any time" implies that stuttering is a contagious or inherently negative condition that could affect any student. Therefore, even though the approach may have positive intentions, teachers should be careful about how they approach students and how they raise awareness. Teacher

training on communication disorders could greatly assist them in achieving this goal. Additionally, since parents also play a crucial role in supporting their children who stutter, they should be provided with the right support and resources to help improve their communication about stuttering, both with their children and with others around them.

While raising awareness is crucial, the persistence of stigma necessitates proactive measures by teachers even after movements for raising awareness. Addressing instances of stigma through targeted interventions, such as implementing consequences for offenders, becomes imperative to install sensitivity and responsibility among peers. This approach shifts the focus from mere awareness to tangible consequences, fostering a more accountable and respectful classroom environment. By combining preventative education with responsive actions, educators can actively work towards minimizing future occurrences of stigma, creating a holistic strategy for cultivating an inclusive and supportive atmosphere.

“Some of the students do not understand that making fun of their friends who stutter or have any other condition is hurtful and could cause them serious harm. Therefore, I believe it is the responsibility of teachers or parents to educate these children about the impact of their actions on others. If this behaviour persists, there should be consequences such as suspending them from school to ensure they learn to behave respectfully in the future.” (Oum lyad)

Based on the quotation, some students’ behaviours can necessitate measures that require an alternative approach that extends beyond awareness-raising to address these negative attitudes. Oum lyad highlighted that some students consider these negative behaviours humorous and do not recognise their impact on their peers who stutter. In the same vein, as the majority of mothers, she also emphasised the crucial role of teachers in educating students about stuttering and moral issues addressing negative behaviour; however, situations can escalate beyond control, prompting teachers to adopt a different approach, such as school suspension. This approach suggests that if negative attitudes persist despite the awareness of their impact on peers after education and moral guidance, punishment may become necessary as a last resort. Schools should have policies about misbehaving students that do not necessarily focus solely on stuttering. However, it is also important to consider cultural factors when applying disciplinary approaches. In this study, most participants supported these approaches in cases of persistent negative attitudes, advocating for strict consequences after educating and morally guiding students to improve their behaviour. Hence, participants emphasized the importance of prioritising education and empathy-building, while acknowledging the need for punitive actions in some cases to address bullying and discrimination within educational settings.

8.3.3. Students who Stutter and Teacher Relationship

Although this strategy was suggested as an intervention to mitigate stigma, the mothers have acknowledged the support they received from teachers, which helped their children who stutter. The mothers were asked how the teachers helped their children. While some mothers mentioned experiencing stigmatizing attitudes from teachers due to their lack of knowledge and awareness about their stutter of their children, many teachers were very supportive. It is important to note that middle school students in Algeria typically have around 10 different teachers teaching them 10 different subjects each year. Therefore, although the majority of teachers lack knowledge about stuttering and some of them have no experience managing this stigma in the classroom, they were still very supportive when parents asked for help with their children who stutter. Based on that, the mothers emphasized the importance of building positive relationships between teachers and students, which aligns with the speech therapist's suggestion to work on improving the relationship between teachers and students in order to mitigate the stigma associated with stuttering. They have argued its effectiveness acknowledging the teachers' support throughout the interviews, highlighting instances where teachers had directly helped their children. This underscores the mothers' belief in the significance of a strong teacher-student relationship. This also aligns with many studies that report that a supportive classroom environment can contribute to feelings of safety and belonging for students who stutter, potentially reducing the likelihood of negative peer behaviours.

"I am grateful to a particular teacher who has been supportive of my son, especially since my husband passed away. As my son grew older, he developed a tough personality, so he always asks about him and addresses any issues that arise at school " (Oum Djed)

Oum Djed expressed profound appreciation towards a particular teacher who had become a vital source of support for her son. Following the loss of the boy's father, the mother acknowledged growing difficulty in managing his behaviour, possibly due to both age and the emotional impact of the family change. The teacher, however, played a crucial role by demonstrating genuine care for the student, regularly checking in on him, and proactively addressing any issues that arose at school. Zee et al. (2020) importantly argued that the relationship between teachers and students can be strongly influenced by the type of disability. Still, this dedication and support were clearly appreciated by both the mother and the child, highlighting the significant impact teachers can have beyond academics, especially during challenging times. Furthermore, it underscores the importance of the teacher-student relationship. In the same vein, Oum Aseel stated the following.

"I encouraged her teacher to build a closer relationship with my shy daughter. Once she feels comfortable, her fluency improves. I remind my daughter that the teacher is there to help and encourage her to report any issues." (Oum Aseel)

Following the profound impact that a strong teacher-student relationship can have on a student's academic and personal development. By encouraging her shy daughter to forge a closer bond with her teacher, the mother recognizes the transformative power of trust and support within the educational environment. This proactive approach underscores the importance of communication and advocacy, as the mother advises her child to seek help and report any issues directly to the teacher. The observation that the student's fluency improves once she feels comfortable with the teacher highlights how a nurturing relationship can positively influence academic performance. Moreover, the advice to approach the teacher with concerns signifies the role of the teacher-student relationship in empowering students to address challenges and advocate for themselves. Ultimately, the quote underscores the vital role that supportive and communicative relationships between teachers and students play in fostering a positive learning experience and nurturing holistic development.

8.4. Middle School Language Teachers

Following the insights from both speech therapists and mothers, this section delves into teachers' perspectives on mitigating stigma in the classroom. While the responses from therapists and mothers can be highly valuable, as they have close relationships with children who stutter and often hear about their negative experiences in order to seek support, it is important to acknowledge that their knowledge is based on the experiences relayed by the children themselves. However, the teachers' responses provide additional insights based on their own firsthand experiences in the classroom, which cannot be solely based on theoretical perspectives. It is worth noting that some teachers may have encountered situations involving negative attitudes from peers. Therefore, understanding how these teachers managed such situations is crucial for this study. Furthermore, exploring the perspectives of teachers who do not have prior experience with children who stutter would also be interesting.

Overall, the results indicated similar perceptions regarding the techniques of those of the mothers and speech therapists in mitigating stigma in the classroom. However, the teachers also mentioned a number of additional strategies that they particularly use, such as building an inclusive environment and normalizing the stigma. It is important to note that all participants in this section have expressed a acknowledgement that the Algerian educational system supports inclusion; however, their perception for building an inclusive classroom was based on basic pragmatic insight and experience.

8.4.1. Raising Awareness among Peers

One approach the teachers used to reduce stuttering stigma involved raising awareness among peers. This strategy aimed to create a supportive classroom environment. By dispelling misconceptions, promoting empathy and inclusivity, it sought to diminish the negative impact of biases towards stuttering. Ultimately, the goal was to foster a positive atmosphere and encourage respectful attitudes towards classmates who stutter. However, teachers also highlighted the sensitivity of this approach. Most preferred to address stuttering awareness in the absence of the students who stutter themselves. Their concern was to avoid inadvertently causing emotional harm. The teachers worried that drawing undue attention to stuttering or implying something that could be harmful to the student. Nonetheless, they emphasized the importance of raising awareness, particularly if stigmatizing attitudes emerged. This approach demonstrates the teachers' careful consideration when addressing disabilities in the classroom.

"I always try to give them advice and raise awareness. For instance, I tell them, 'Do not make fun of your classmates, as Allah will punish you for that. You never know what might happen to you; you could be a stutterer at any time.' Students tend to behave well after these discussions." (Malak, female, 4 YOE)

The use of an Islamic and ethical perspective by teachers to address negative behaviours among students who stutter is an interesting approach. By highlighting the Islamic principles and values that prevent such behaviours, the teachers tap into the cultural and religious context of Algeria. It highlights the importance of considering local values and beliefs when designing interventions to address stigma and promote positive attitudes towards individuals who stutter. Malak's observation that students respond positively to these reminders suggests that integrating religious and ethical teachings can effectively foster behavioural change. By linking the negative experiences of their classmates who stutter to their own potential consequences, students may develop empathy and become more mindful of their actions. This approach not only addresses the specific issue of stuttering but also promotes a broader sense of compassion and respect for others. It is worth noting that while this approach helps create awareness and mitigate negative behaviours, it primarily focuses on the actions themselves rather than providing detailed knowledge about stuttering. Hence, this approach serves as a general framework for addressing negative attitudes in a broad sense, thus, it applies to any student and any negative attitudes. By instilling moral lessons and encouraging a positive environment, the aim is to foster a supportive and inclusive classroom where students feel accepted and respected. Furthermore, as a means of raising awareness, Leen stated the following:

"When I mention 'punishing,' I don't mean physical punishment. I speak with the student and explain that they are responsible for their actions. I

encourage them to help their classmate and be a supportive friend, or I tell them, 'You are not a good classmate'; this is what I mean by 'punishing.'"
(Leen, female, 4 YOE)

Leen, along with many other teachers, suggested addressing the negative behaviours as it occurs to diminish the stigma. Leen argues that punishment, in this case, entails engaging in conversation with the student who exhibited negative behaviour and conveying the message that they are responsible for their actions. However, the communication between the teacher and the students should be fair and constructive, ensuring that they contribute to the overall growth and well-being of the students involved. Hence, the use of *'You are not a good classmate'* could be interpreted as a harsh way to address a student's behaviour. While the teacher might be aiming to mitigate negative behaviours, the misuse of expressions could potentially lead to advertising results on the student or damage their self-esteem. This observation could underscore the need for guidance on employing constructive conversations that could potentially be more effective. For instance, it may be advantageous to concentrate on specific actions and offer guidance for improvement. However, it is also important to acknowledge that cultural factors may influence how teachers communicate with students. Therefore, it is not evident to assert the effectiveness of a particular type of communication without considering the cultural context, as doing so can be misleading. Ideally, the analysis should be supported by research on effective communication strategies across cultures.

Furthermore, Leen emphasised the importance of students taking an active role in supporting their peers who stutter, fostering empathy and understanding. This approach aims to cultivate a sense of accountability among students through promoting a heightened sense of responsibility among peers. The teachers not only address negative behaviours but also work towards promoting positive actions and attitudes. Leen's quotation demonstrated a combination of verbal warning and fostering a sense of responsibility that serves to create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment. This approach encourages students to actively participate in mitigating the stigma associated with stuttering. It is important to note that while this approach may have benefits in terms of raising awareness and promoting positive behaviours, it is crucial to create a balance between discipline and compassion.

8.4.2. Supporting Self-Esteem and Creating a Comfortable Environment

While the teacher highlighted the importance of addressing negative behaviours, they also acknowledged the challenges of controlling them, particularly during adolescence. The participants believe that such behaviours might be common among peers at this stage. Therefore, the teacher suggested focusing on strategies to improve students' self-esteem and build a more comfortable classroom environment. This, in turn, could potentially lead to a reduction in stress and stuttering

incidents, ultimately minimizing negative reactions from classmates. The teachers believed that classroom interventions might have limited reach, therefore, they tried to robust and cultivate self-esteem among students who stutter. They emphasised the importance of equipping students with the resilience to potentially negative social interactions outside the classroom as well. As one teacher explained:

"First of all, I focus on maintaining their self-confidence because if they lack confidence, they will not progress effectively; so maintaining self-confidence is first " (Samar, Female, 15 YOY)

"The stronger their personality, the more comfortable they will be, which can reduce stuttering. When they feel at ease speaking, they can engage more actively in learning." (Dania, female, 10 YOY)

"We don't always know what they experience outside the classroom, so building strong self-esteem helps them in various aspects of life, both inside and outside the classroom." (Amal, Female, 20 YOY)

Teachers recognise the significant impact of fostering strong self-esteem in students who stutter on their overall learning experience. This emphasis reflects an understanding that self-confidence plays a crucial role in motivating students to engage actively with academic content. Samar's assertion that a reinforced sense of self-worth correlates with increased engagement in lectures highlights the importance of psychological factors in educational settings. However, it is important to critically examine the complexity of this relationship. While self-esteem can indeed enhance a student's willingness to participate, it's essential to consider that other factors, such as the nature of classroom activities, teaching methods, and peer interactions, also influence engagement levels. Dania's observation regarding the link between student confidence and lecture participation further underscores the significance of self-assurance in educational contexts. Yet, it is crucial to delve deeper into the nuanced challenges faced by students who stutter. While increased confidence can promote classroom involvement, the broader societal attitudes towards stuttering may still pose obstacles outside of academic settings. Amal's recognition of the wider impact of self-esteem on a child who stutters, both inside and outside the classroom, invites critical reflection on the limitations of school-based interventions. Moreover, acknowledging the limitations of constant support for students who stutter outside of school highlights the broader societal context within which these individuals navigate their lives. The statement underscores the need for holistic support systems that extend beyond the educational environment. By critically examining the role of self-esteem in the learning journey of students who stutter, educators can better understand the multifaceted challenges faced by these individuals and work towards fostering inclusive learning environments that address both academic and socio-emotional needs.

Additionally, among the strategies teachers employ to mitigate the stigma, creating a comfortable environment for students who stutter which also helps reduce the severity of their stutter. Most teachers tried to reduce the severity of stuttering by asking students who stutter to breathe and take time to speak. Breathing is one of the activities children who stutter do during their treatment. Based on this, the teachers demonstrate a certain level of familiarity with stuttering treatment approaches. Some teachers stated the following:

"They may hesitate to speak, and if pressured, they might stutter. When their classmates laugh at them, it can cause their speech to get blocked. Therefore, as teachers, we should create a comfortable environment for them, providing time and asking classmates to be quiet, then, tell the student 'Take your time, breathe!'. While progress may not be immediate, understanding and patience can encourage them to speak." (Dania, female, 10 YOE)

"During reading activities, if a student stutters on a word like 'learning,' and says 'Lear.... lear..... lear... (imitating stuttering) like this; I prompt them with the complete word, they say learning yes! Then I encourage them to continue reading. Yeah, that's it." (Leen, female, 4 YOE)

Teachers aim to create an environment in which the student who stutter can effectively communicate in the classroom. As they emphasised on the significance of giving enough time to the student to speak and ask them to breathe before speaking to reduce their stress. Eventually, reducing the stress will contribute to the reduction of stuttering. Dania discussed her point in the statement above, arguing that forcing the student who stutter to speak can create a sort of challenge does not stutter. Their peers' reactions such as negative laughter exert a significant impact on their peers who stutter. Therefore, creating a comfortable environment that consist of patience and respect could encourage the student who stutter to speak with confidence. Teachers demonstrated their understanding of the stuttering treatment and what triggers it and based on that they tried to reduce the stutter. Hence, the teacher encourages the student who stutter to breathe before speaking. This empowers students by acknowledging their efforts and providing practical guidance for effective communication. Moreover, Leen statement reflect on the teachers' supportive approach towards students who stutter in the classroom setting. The teacher acknowledged that she provides help to the student who stutters when struggling to utter a word. Although some of the speech therapists and mothers participated in this study stated that the children might not appreciate this kind of help and find it this embracing as they know the word and needs just time to utter it. Yet, as seen with the example of the word "learning" the student responds positively as the aim of the intervention is to overcome the stuttering block. The teacher assisted the student not only with the uttering the word, yet her intervention sought to comfort and encourage the student to proceed with the answer. Hence, the teacher's

statements “*yeah, that’s it*”, “*I usually help him*” conveys a positive and supportive tone that was positive as the student acknowledges the assistance “*learning, yes!*”.

8.4.3. Normalising Stigma

Interestingly, this theme appeared only in the teachers’ group data. While it might be interpreted as accepting negative attitudes, the participants are actually contributing to the neurodiversity perspective (Rosqvist, Chown and Stenning, 2020). One of the techniques teachers use to manage the classroom during stigmatising attitudes such as negative laughter is ignoring them. The teachers tend to reduce the stigma that follows stuttering by building an environment where stuttering is seen as a natural aspect of communication. They believe that this inclusive approach not only help children who stutter in gaining confidence but also encourages their classmates to embrace differences, nurturing a culture of acceptance within the classroom. Most teachers tried to make the situation less stigmatising by making the laughter a normal thing that could happen at any time. Some of the teachers claim that this will make the child who stutters stronger than to be affected by their laughter. Some of the teachers said the following:

“There are times during reading activities when I ask them to read, and I’ll say, ‘Take your time, we are waiting for you.’ Then his classmates laugh, and the student who stutters also laughs and it’s okay! we have to integrate them (Noah, male, 37 YO)

“In situations where classmates laugh at them during reading activities, I ignore the laughter and redirect their attention by asking another question.” (Leen, female, 4 YO)

“As teachers, we must normalise stuttering for his classmates, helping them accept that it is a normal thing...” (Dania, female, 10 YO)

Based on the above statements, teachers either ignore the stigma or normalise it. Noah demonstrated his effort of integrating students who stutter into reading activities for examples. The teacher encourages the student to speak, showing awareness that the students require time to speak and willingness to accommodate their speech patterns. The teacher highlighted the necessity of inclusion and understanding of the classroom environment especially during an embarrassing situation such as laughter. While other teachers tend to ignore it and try to redirect their focus to create an alternative point of discussion. The teachers’ effort to avoid drawing undue attention to potentially embarrassing situations, thereby promoting a more comfortable environment for the student who stutters. Leen demonstrated the teacher’s responsibility in creating an inclusive environment, encouraging familiarity, acceptance, and normalizing stuttering to mitigate the stigma. This aligns with the idea of dilemmas of difference in inclusive education that encourages acceptance (See Norwich, 2008). This

contributes to correcting attitudes and building an environment where diversity is embraced and valued. In the same vein, Dania's perspective emphasizes the importance of destigmatizing stuttering by treating it as a 'normal thing' as she referred to it. This approach challenges misconceptions and encourages students to accept stuttering as part of human variation, thereby promoting a more inclusive and supportive atmosphere.

The following section delves deeper into the previously presented results, providing a detailed discussion and interpretation that integrates the perspectives of all three groups (speech therapists, mothers, and teachers).

9. Chapter nine: Discussion

9.1. Discussion of Findings: Knowledge and Perceptions of Stuttering

Stakeholders' knowledge of stuttering is a significant part of this research, as it reflects their perceptions and interactions with children who stutter. This section delved into the participants' understanding of the nature of stuttering, its causes, treatment and the psychological impact of stuttering on the children who stutter particularly in the Algerian society. Individuals who stutter know well about their stutter as they are the ones experiencing this disorder; nevertheless, stakeholders are considered as their supporters, defenders, and those who collaborate with them for public changes (Dean and Medina, 2021). The changes that could be made are related to the social knowledge about the stutter and the associated stigma, as it eventually affects the level of stigmatisation towards stuttering (Constantino, Campbell and Simpson, 2022). Within this framework, the concept of stigma, as delineated by Goffman (1963), emerges as a lens through which to examine the societal perceptions and experiences associated with stuttering. The concept of stigma appears if a person has an attribute that identifies them while others do not anticipate it to be Goffman (1963). In this research, the stigma is stuttering. The theory of stigma provides a useful framework, offering insights into how stakeholders' knowledge and interactions with children who stutter in Algeria are shaped by prevailing societal attitudes and perceptions of stuttering. Furthermore, the participants have constantly pointed out negative attitudes toward children who stutter face, which links to some concepts related to stigma, such as stereotype, discrimination, labelling and other concepts that intersect with children's experiences of stuttering in Algeria (Goffman, 1963). This discussion section aims to answer the first question:

What is the depth and scope of the Algerian stakeholders' knowledge of stuttering?

Overall, speech-language therapists seemed more knowledgeable compared to mothers and teachers, as they specialized in speech disorders and had experience with individuals who stutter. They were considered as the source of knowledge to mothers of children who stutter and teachers who needed guidance on how to react and manage stuttering in the classroom. Furthermore, mothers demonstrated a general understanding of stuttering, as it was based on their experience with their children who stutter. On the other hand, teachers lack understanding of stuttering, especially those without any experience with students who stutter. Their efforts to develop their knowledge were limited, which was related to factors such as their motivation behind learning about

it, and limited research skills. Nevertheless, most participants who were close to children who stutter tended to learn mainly about stuttering treatment to help them. Based on the results, the majority of the participants held pre-existing stereotypes when discussing the causes of stuttering, which aligns with the concept of “Preliminary conception” introduced by Goffman (1963). These results will be discussed and interpreted further in this section.

9.1.1. Knowledge about the Nature of Stuttering and Stigma

This section underlines the way stakeholders tend to present individuals who stutter and their perception regarding stuttering. Goffman (1963) discusses the concept of “The professional presentation” (p.132-136) which suggests that individuals with stigmatising attributes face paradoxical situations. Society could define them as different, while they do not see themselves as different from others (Goffman, 1963). Nevertheless, in this study, none of the participants considered children who stutter as different from them. Although stuttering has been classified as a disability (WHO, 2016; 2023), the stakeholders avoided labelling stuttering as a disability as they perceive it as a speaking difficulty only. Algerians tend to relate disability to mental or physical disability mainly, which explains their perspective of stuttering.

The majority of the participants argued that stuttering does not primarily affect the students, yet the bullying that follows it is the issue in school, which aligns with other studies (Berchiatti *et al.*, 2021). Thus, children who stutter have the same chance to succeed as their classmates and have a good experience in school, if there were no stigmatising attitudes towards them that could affect them. Nevertheless, focusing only on bullying as the primary issue for children who stutter could present a limited view because stuttering is a fluency disorder that is followed by psychological and emotional impacts on the individual that should not be neglected (See Jones *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, being aware of the nature of stuttering and its impact on the students who stutter could have a significant improvement in the teachers’ ability to provide an effective inclusive environment for students who stutter.

Teachers demonstrated a limited understanding of the nature of stuttering despite their familiarity with stuttering as a fluency disorder. They provided limited or general knowledge about stuttering, which aligns with many studies that have been conducted in the Arab countries (Abdalla and Louis, 2012; Khodair, Bataineh, Al-Khawaldeh and Muhaidat, 2022; Panico *et al.*, 2018). Although they believe that knowledge about stuttering would not affect their attitudes towards students who stutter, many incidents occurred during the interview discussions that demonstrated stigmatising attitudes that resulted from a lack of knowledge and awareness about stuttering (see Chapter 7).

Moreover, most teachers did not support their knowledge with any source, which indicates the need for academic resources that help them improve their knowledge. Similarly, mothers stated that they had researched stuttering; they felt they needed more clarification as they were misled by loads of information on the internet. The mothers were familiar with stuttering but could only describe their children's stutter to explain it. Some imitate how their children stutter instead of explaining it with words. This highlights the importance of providing useful sources for parents and caregivers ensuring more comprehensive and accurate knowledge regarding stuttering. This could also be helpful for schools as well as for teachers and students.

Furthermore, they showed uncertainty multiple times during the interviews as they used expressions such as 'I am not sure'; 'specialist knows more'. The majority of the speech therapists pointed out that teachers tend to seek guidance from them when needed, which demonstrates their personal effort to learn about stuttering aiming to provide a good educational experience to children who stutter avoiding stigmatising attitudes towards them. Moreover, all of them demonstrated their willingness to learn about stuttering from specialists, which calls upon integrating sessions on stuttering awareness and support strategies into broader professional development initiatives for educators can ensure that all teachers receive essential training in this area.

All the teachers who participated know what it is like for an individual to have a stutter as they know at least one of their acquaintances who stutter, if not their students. According to (Abdalla and Louis, 2012) both age and experience have no impact on the teachers' attitudes, yet knowledge about stuttering has a positive impact on their perceptions of students who stutter. Nevertheless, it is important to note that teachers who have already taught students who stutter tend to demonstrate more practical knowledge and strategies supporting them compared to those without prior experience. This indicates that knowledge and experience are two important elements of improving the teacher's attitudes towards students who stutter. It was explicitly stated by most teachers that they need more knowledge when discussing speech disorders and stuttering topics. This confirms that there is a lack of knowledge about stuttering, especially those who have never taught students who stutter. Their responsibility for educating inclusive classes implies the need to improve their awareness to help teachers gain insight into the challenges that children who stutter face in the classroom. Some studies argued that increasing the familiarity between students who stutter and teachers could have potentially an effective means of improving the teachers' perceptions of individuals who stutter (Arnold, Li and Goltl, 2015). This indicates a gap between the teachers' experiences and their understanding of stuttering. Therefore, it could have a significant improvement on the teachers' ability to provide an effective inclusive environment for students who stutter.

While most mothers and teachers consider speech-language therapists as a knowledgeable resource, it is significant to mention that the way speech-language therapists explain stuttering varies depending on the person seeking help. As they aim to provide a good understanding across different ages and educational levels. This demonstrates their profound understanding of stuttering which effectively translated complex concepts into digestible information and level appropriate. While this could be beneficial, especially to those of low educational level, speech-language therapists should give more details to the parents or teachers to avoid any wrong attitudes towards children who stutter.

mothers of children who stutter showed limited understanding of the nature of stuttering, however, most of their knowledge aligns with the speech therapist's knowledge. Speech-language therapists tend to possess more knowledge since they were trained and taught about this topic. Besides, they have worked with individuals who stutter of different ages; thus, they have knowledge and experience. Furthermore, mothers of children who stutter demonstrated some understanding of stuttering. However, this knowledge is based on their experience with their children, some readings, and the guidance of speech-language therapists. Mothers primarily seek treatment options to help their children manage stuttering and improve their fluency. This indicates the mothers' motivation and interest in learning about stuttering.

Most teachers tend to have the perception that individuals who stutter are shy and anxious based on their bodily movements such as avoidance of eye contact or when their face turns red (Maguire, Nguyen, Simonson and Kurz, 2020; Busan et al., 2022a). This aligns with Goffman's concept of "preliminary conception" discussed in his theory of stigma (1963). Teachers tend to develop this stereotype based on their observation of the bodily behaviours of children who stutter. This could be the first impression of the society which does not necessarily match a child's social identity leading to the possibility of stigma, ultimately influencing their attitudes towards children who stutter. Therefore, it is significant to understand and correct wrong perceptions about the nature of stuttering.

9.1.2. Knowledge about the Cause of Stuttering and Stigma

The data revealed varying levels of understanding about stuttering causes among mothers, teachers, and speech-language therapists. Mothers and teachers frequently expressed uncertainty about the causes of stuttering as they tend to use expressions such as "*I am not sure*", "*I don't know*", and "*It might*". Furthermore, they explicitly stated that they need further research and readings on the topic. This aligns with some research that demonstrated limited knowledge about stuttering aetiology (Abdalla and Louis, 2012; Hearne et al., 2021; Nonis, Unicomb and Hewat, 2022). On the other hand, speech-language therapists demonstrated some understanding of the cause of stuttering. While

recent research is placing a greater emphasis on exploring the biological factors associated with stuttering onset (Boyle, 2016b; Boyle, 2020), speech therapists who participated in this study focused more on the psychological factors. Although, different theories have been suggested to explain the cause of stuttering (Türkili, Türkili and Aydın, 2022). However, it is important to note that despite the plethora of research conducted to establish the causes of stuttering, it is still not fully understood (Packman et al., 2022). Overall, the participants stated a number of potential causes of stuttering, such as genetics and biological factors, most of them tend to consider psychological traumas as the main theory for the stuttering onset. This knowledge, however, was based mostly on common sense knowledge or what has been shared by the speech therapists.

The majority of stakeholders believed that due to psychological traumas, stuttering is developed. The word “*fear*” emerged consistently in all the interview discussions as a contributing factor to stuttering. The mothers also expressed uncertainty regarding the exact cause of their children’s stuttering. Nonetheless, there was a consensus among them that traumatic incidents or experiences affecting their children’s psychological well-being could gradually manifest as stuttering. Furthermore, some teachers said that the child might experience psychological trauma during childhood, such as mistreatment, parents’ divorce, or even sexual assaults. Although many studies align with the current findings (Alm, 2014; Al-Ghamdi *et al.*, 2022). However, some researchers have emphasized that there is no scientific basis for it (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). This highlights the complexity of understanding the aetiology of stuttering and the need for further empirical investigation. The teachers and mothers have not based their knowledge on any research, indicating the Algerian cultural perspective regarding the aetiology of stuttering and reflecting a broader societal knowledge framework.

Individuals who do not stutter commonly encounter instances where their speech fluency falters, typically occurring in situations marked by anxiety, tension, or nervousness (Boyle, 2015) which could also explain how teachers have built their perceptions. Furthermore, some of them argued that the severity of stuttering is specifically related to the comfort or discomfort of the child who stutters during his speaking performance. For instance, mothers noted occasions when their children’s stuttering severity heightened during stressful situations such as exam periods or experiencing fear, whereas it decreased when they engaged in activities such as playing with friends. In the same vein, many studies argued that there is a correlation between stuttering and social anxiety for instance (Iverach *et al.*, 2016) which could affect the severity of stuttering as well as their overall speech behaviours (Menzies, Sharpe and Dar-Nimrod, 2019). Therefore, many of the participants associated stuttering with stress and emphasised improving the child’s self-esteem to reduce their stutter. While this provides an explanation of the perceptions held by teachers and mothers, research indicates that

these perceptions could have a serious effect on children who stutter (Boyle, 2016b). Such perceptions tend to impose guilt and pressure on children to speak fluently, assuming that stuttering is their fault due to this stereotype (See Boyle, 2016b).

Expanding on the previous results, teachers related stuttering to psychological issues and specifically to the child's personality. The latter aligns with the concept of "Social information" introduced by Goffman which tends to address some key points that determine the social knowledge about a certain stigma (1963, p. 58-64). Although not all the key points that were discussed align with the participants' understanding of stuttering, their responses are strongly linked to the "sings" as Goffman referred to (1963, p. 59), which could create wrong assumptions and stereotypes. Similar to other research such as (Almudhi, 2022), the majority of teachers and mothers stated that children who stutter have low self-esteem, anxiety, and other issues. Nevertheless, these results indicate a potential stereotype regarding the personality of children who stutter (See Boyle, 2016b). If individuals who stutter consider themselves responsible for their stutter, they will likely experience negative effects on their psychological well-being (Boyle, 2016a).

Furthermore, one of the causes that the mothers and teachers suggested to be a possible cause for stuttering is biological factors that run between family members giving examples of some of their relatives who have stuttering. Although the mothers have not considered this to be the case for their children, thus, they believe that there are some cases where stuttering could be genetically inherited. On the other hand, the speech-language therapists argued that children aggravate the stutter by imitation and cannot be genetically inherited, however, no evidence supported their arguments, which raises questions about its validity. Moreover, the lack of evidence underscores the need for further research into the complex interplay of genetic, environmental, and behavioural factors in stuttering development. Studies tend to relate stuttering to biological issues primarily (Alm and Risberg, 2007; Alm, 2014; Boyle, 2020; Boyle, 2016b; Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Some research reported that there are neuroanatomical differences were found comparing individuals who stutter and those who do not (e.g. Sitek *et al.*, 2016) which determines individuals who have stutter that could be provoked by psychological traumas which eventually cause the stutter (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Studies have found that attributing stuttering aetiology to biological factors tends to have a positive effect on individuals who stutter by reducing their feelings of blame (Boyle, 2016b). According to Boyle (2014), higher biological attributions for stuttering were significantly associated with increased beliefs regarding the uncontrollability of stuttering onset and cessation. However, in this study, the results from mothers and teachers suggest a tendency to attribute stuttering to emotional causes with minimal consideration of genetic factors.

Interestingly, few number teachers who studied neurolinguistics at the university tend to apply their knowledge about Broca's Aphasia to stuttering, arguing that since the brain is responsible for language production, there must be a relation between the speech production areas and stuttering. The teachers have hypothesised this based on prior knowledge related to speech disorders. Although there is a plethora of research that investigated the neurological correlate of stuttering (E.g. Neef *et al.*, 2016; Sowman *et al.*, 2017; Packman *et al.*, 2022; Neef *et al.*, 2021; Chang, Zhu, Choo and Angstadt, 2015), the teachers demonstrated uncertainty, because they have no scientific knowledge regarding the neurological causal of stuttering.

Moreover, according to Conelea, Rice and Woods (2006) stuttering is linked with airflow irregularities. In the same vein, a few number of speech-language therapists argued that stuttering could be a physiological issue where individuals who stutter tend to have breathing difficulties when speaking, such as shortness of breath (Elsherbeny, Baz and Afsah, 2022). Speech-language therapists tend to link the cause of stuttering with the stuturer's ability to balance the inhalation and exhalation process while speaking. Therefore, they work more on correcting the process of breathing as the primary treatment for stuttering (See Conelea, Rice and Woods, 2006). However, it's worth noting that while breathing irregularities are observed in individuals who stutter, some studies did not classify it as a cause of stuttering, but rather one of its symptoms (See Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021, pp. 279-280).

9.1.3. Knowledge about the Treatment of Stuttering and Stigma

Understanding the perspectives and knowledge of stakeholders regarding the cause of stuttering is crucial for informing effective interventions and support strategies. As highlighted in the previous section, there were several factors highlighted by the stakeholders regarding its causes, however, they primarily associate stuttering with psychological factors. Nevertheless, Speech-language therapists played the main role in shaping the treatment approaches adopted for individuals who stutter. In the context of Algeria, where speech-language therapy services may be limited, teachers seemed to have no impact in determining the treatment pathways for children who stutter. However, parents were the main characters in providing information about their children to speech-language therapists, shedding light on their understanding, recommendations, and preferences for addressing this speech disorder, besides helping the children carry the treatment home. This section delves into the insights and perspectives of stakeholders regarding the treatment of stuttering, and the challenges and opportunities in delivering effective stuttering interventions by the speech-language therapists in Algeria.

Before starting the treatment sessions, speech-language therapists request a brain diagnosis to make sure that there are no neurological issues that cause the stuttering. Accordingly, the main treatment approach speech-language therapist provides to children who stutter in Algeria is based on the François Le Huche stuttering therapy program solely, although there are several other effective stuttering therapy programs for all ages that offer various beneficial approaches (See Gupta, Chandra, Dautenhahn and Loucks, 2022; Erdemir *et al.*, 2018). However, there is a lack of research regarding this approach. Speech-language therapists stated that they helped many individuals of different ages who stutter, thus, providing them with the right therapeutic program that works for everyone accordingly. Nevertheless, using only this approach indicates a lack of exposure to the various types of treatment approaches, thus, limiting the chances of recovery from stuttering.

The treatment consists of breathing exercises, such as blowing out candles or balloons and relaxing activities. The speech-language therapists referred to this activity as “Clavicular Breathing”. The practice of clavicular breathing, commonly utilized in stuttering therapy, is aimed at promoting relaxation and reducing tension, thereby facilitating fluent speech (Sønsterud *et al.*, 2020). These reported treatment methods mentioned by speech-language therapists were echoed by mothers and some teachers who have interacted with them. It is important to note that the therapeutic programme is guided by their speech-language therapists and followed at home. Nevertheless, this consistency of data regarding stuttering treatment approaches among the groups highlights the potential for shared knowledge among the Algerian stakeholders which indicates further the limited exposure to stuttering therapy programmes.

On the other hand, most teachers in the current study share the same perspective that children who stutter should receive psychological therapy to recover. Stuttering could impact students who stutter, resulting in some psychological issues (See Boyle, 2016b; Brignell *et al.*, 2020; Carey, Onslow and O’Brian, 2021). Therefore, speech-language therapists who participated in this study argued that addressing the psychological aspects of stuttering could positively impact the self-esteem of individuals who stutter. According to Adriaensens, Beyers and Struyf (2015, p. 44), individuals’ self-confidence represents their response to the question ‘How much do I value, like and accept myself’. This aligns with the concept of self-acceptance discussed by Goffman (1963) within the concept of stigma and social interaction. Accordingly, learning how to accept and cope with stuttering correlates with the children’s self-confidence. Some studies have argued that self-confidence is an essential part of accepting stuttering, and as a result, it can reduce its severity (De Nardo, Tetnowski and Coalson, 2023a). Indeed, most mothers confirmed that the fluency of their children improved when they worked on their self-esteem. In fact, building a high self-esteem is crucial for all participants in order

for children to cope with the stigma as they argued that there will still be chances where children encounter negative attitudes regarding their stutter.

Stuttering typically worsens in stressful situations, and being confident can contribute to the level of stress. Mothers illustrated this by describing the severity of their children's stuttering during exam periods. However, engaging in efforts to improve self-acceptance and self-esteem, as highlighted by Plexico, Erath, Shores and Burrus (2019) may not necessarily lead to satisfaction with life and positive schooling experiences. In fact, this could put a lot of pressure on the child which could have revert results (Boyle, 2016b). Therefore, a comprehensive approach to treating stuttering effectively involves considering various dimensions of the disorder, including speech, psychological and social aspects (Beilby, 2014). Thus, besides speech therapy, teachers can assist students who stutter by encouraging cognitive and emotional shifts, such as building confidence in participating in class discussions or engaging in conversations (Cooke and Millard, 2018).

It is worth mentioning that not all children who stutter receive speech therapy. This study revealed several cases where participants discontinued treatment or never sought help due to parental unawareness of the need for speech therapy. This gap between need and access points to a potential barrier to addressing stuttering effectively. Although the majority of participants acknowledge the possibility of natural recovery however, they still emphasise on early intervention for stuttering therapy. Similarly, Research has reported the possibility of natural recovery of stuttering without assisted treatment (Carey, Onslow and O'Brian, 2021). This demonstrates their awareness of the importance of seeking specialist help for stuttering treatment, although some teachers lack knowledge regarding treatment approaches. Studies have highlighted the importance of early intervention for stuttering therapy, as there is no evidence that the child will recover naturally (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). The expression 'he will get fluent as he grows up' appeared in all interview discussions as many people tend to believe that fluency improves with time. One mother was given the same advice, but she pointed out that the person who advised her still stutters, indicating that there is no guarantee of recovery by opting for the natural approach.

9.1.4. Knowledge about the Impact of Stuttering and Stigma

Although most of the participants do not consider stuttering to be a serious issue, it can hurt the psychology and the social life of the individual who stutters (Chang, Zhu, Choo and Angstadt, 2015). The knowledge and awareness about the stutter and its impact have proven to be effective in reducing the stigma towards individuals who stutter (SheikhBahaei and Maguire, 2020). In this section, participants of this study report their knowledge of the psychosocial consequences of children who stutter in Algeria. Overall, the participants demonstrated a good understanding of the impact of

stuttering. Children who stutter are part of the community as they interact with society daily. This exposes them to different behaviours and attitudes that characterise how they are perceived in society. Most of the participants related the psychological effects of stuttering to the stigma that is associated with stuttering. As a result, participants in this study reported that children who stutter in Algeria tend to experience social and emotional impacts such as isolation, avoidance of social interaction, low self-esteem, aggressiveness and sadness.

Participants of this study reported that children who stutter in Algeria tend to become more isolated, avoid social interaction, and have low self-esteem. Mixed contact could create self-stigma (Goffman, 1963), especially since some parents tend to compare their children to others in terms of fluency. The latter children who stutter build some self-critical judgement for not holding up to fluency standards. The sense of discrepancy with other children who are fluent is painful at all times, especially during being around other children who do not stutter. This could provoke children to isolate themselves which appeared in the data multiple times. Nevertheless, most participants believe the stutter personality is crucial as it helps them overcome the negative psychological consequences.

On the other hand, the other mothers who participated in this study argued that their children stutter severely. They developed anger and aggressive behaviours because of their stutter and the stigmatisation of their surroundings. It is significant to highlight that the reaction to stuttering might differ based on gender or the individual's personality. Based on their observation of their children, the mothers who participated in this study reported similar reactions and psychological issues that boys experience in Algeria. However, the mothers' results reported different results regarding the aggressiveness of their children, comparing boys to girls, as the boys tend to have more aggressive behaviours as a reaction to their stutter. Nevertheless, these results cannot be generalised as the teachers reported similar results among boys and girls who stutter in Algerian Middle Schools. Furthermore, the mothers reported that severe stuttering makes their children frustrated or as they reported "aggressive" especially when they are in an argument. Although the children who stutter are perceived to have a certain way that is seen to be aggressive, the mothers tend to explain this as a coping mechanism, as Goffman (1963) referred to. Teachers have this perception; however, the mothers' data have contributed to the understanding of these attitudes that are labelled as "aggressive" to correct this stereotype.

9.2. Discussion of Findings: Knowledge of Stigma

Overall, the participants reported that children in Algeria are labelled as "Aggoun" by their surroundings, either the parents, siblings, neighbours, classmates, friends or even teachers. The parents do not intend to hurt their children's feelings, yet the way of reacting to the stutter or their

willingness to help overcome it is sometimes incorrect. Furthermore, bullying appeared in all the interview discussions, which appeared in this context as a form of laughing as a reaction to stuttering, teasing, and mimicking the stutter. The participants reported that most bullying was with their classmates or friends. However, speech-language therapists highlighted that bullying could extend beyond schools and include siblings as well. This suggests a broader negative social environment for children who stutter. Most participants reported that children who stutter tend to avoid social interaction due to these negative reactions. Thus, children tend to anticipate negative reactions to stutter and eventually develop self-stigma. This chapter aims to discuss the findings of this research and determine the extent to which the second driving question of this research has been answered.

What is the depth and scope of stakeholders' knowledge of the stigma associated with stuttering in Algerian middle schools?

Based on a triangulation of perspectives, this study mainly used interviews to explore the extent and breadth of stakeholders' comprehension regarding the stigma associated with stuttering in Algerian middles. This is crucial as it helps uncover these stakeholders' understanding of the schooling experiences of children who stutter in depth. Interestingly, the results covered their responses to the stigma that follows stuttering and allowed this study to highlight the gaps that the stakeholders should address to contribute to the children's schooling experience positively.

9.2.1. Social Stigma and Stuttering

There is a strong agreement in the literature that individuals who stutter encounter social stigma (Boyle, Dioguardi and Pate, 2016; Dean and Medina, 2021). The literature demonstrates that individuals who stutter are more likely to be bullied, discriminated against and experience other negative attitudes (Gerlach et al., 2018; St. Louis, 2020; St. Louis et al., 2016), which aligns with the current study. Nevertheless, there is a lack of research investigating the stakeholders' attitudes towards children who stutter in Algerian middle schools. While stuttering has similarities to other speech disorders and disabilities, the stigma experiences of individuals who stutter differ (Seitz and Choo, 2022). These differences could be at the level of cultural environment, while the effect differed from one person to another. Hence, current research showed that gender and personality significantly influence stigma and its effect. The overall results showed that the boys are more exposed to social stigma as the participants shared more stigmatising incidents about boys compared to girls. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that attitudes towards individuals who stutter could differ from one country to another (St. Louis et al., 2016). Therefore, the current study aims to determine Algerian stakeholders' attitudes and understand the cultural perspective regarding stuttering.

The previous chapter discusses the stakeholder's knowledge regarding stuttering. This chapter focuses more on the participants' attitudes towards children who stutter and their knowledge about the stigma children face, mainly in middle school. A plethora of studies have investigated the attitudes towards children who stutter (Adriaensens and Struyf, 2016; Aghaz, Kashani and Shahriyari, 2021; Al-Shdifat, Maayah, Mayo and Louis, 2018; Hearne *et al.*, 2021; Valente *et al.*, 2017) and some other studies were conducted in the Arab world (Ramadan and Soliman, 2022; Meteab Al-Qaisi, Ali and Khudhair, 2020; Junuzovic-Zunic, Mostafa and St. Louis, 2023; Arafa, Senosy, Sheerah and St. Louis, 2021; Abdalla and St. Louis, 2012). Interestingly, these studies investigate the knowledge and attitudes as they interact and shape one another. Therefore, the research tries to relate and connect the participant's knowledge reported in the previous chapter to their attitudes and reactions to the stigma to have a comprehensive understanding of the data.

The current study findings indicate that stakeholders are aware of the stigma that children who stutter encounter within school environments and outside of it. The three groups confirmed this as they could share incidents witnessed at home or school. Stakeholders reported several stigmatising attitudes that align with other studies, such as bullying, teasing, discrimination, Stereotypes and different negative attitudes (Blood *et al.*, 2011; Hughes, 2014; Tellis and St Louis, 2015; Yaruss, Reeves and Herring, 2018; Low and Purwaningrum, 2020). The findings revealed that children who stutter experience stigma at schools, and the stakeholders are aware of this. However, their response to the negative attitudes towards children who stutter seemed limited to the situation or the incidents. Notably, stakeholders tend to show helplessness towards these attitudes, as their reactions do not primarily address the gap towards all children who stutter. The higher authorities also seemed to prioritise other disabilities, as stutter has not been considered a serious issue that must be addressed. Nevertheless, stakeholders have recounted numerous incidents that could profoundly impact stuttering children. Accordingly, this indicates the importance of stakeholders raising this concern for inclusion in teacher training and educational policies to address this issue comprehensively. The stakeholders shared several incidents that helped highlight the main negative attitudes towards children in Algerian middle schools.

9.2.2. Labelling Children who Stutter as Aggoun

Interestingly, negative labelling was among the most common stigmatising attitudes towards children who stutter in Algerian society. However, studies have not brought enough attention regarding negative labelling associated with stuttering; this could be related to cultural aspects. Howard Becker (1963) popularised the theory of labelling in criminology, yet it has been applied in different fields such as social movement, education, and stigmatised Identities. Accordingly, Goffman contributed to the field of labelling theory through his work on stigma and management of spoiled identity (1963).

Goffman's theory of stigma (1963) and his contribution to Howard Becker's theory of labelling (1963) helped reflect on the data and its implications for inclusive education.

Previous research has indicated that teachers' prior perception of disabilities, thus, they label them and assign them less challenging tasks (Arishi, Boyle and Lauchlan, 2017). Stakeholders argued that children who stutter should be given short passages since they need more time compared to their peers, aiming for equity among students. Nevertheless, this could have opposite results, as it could affect the student's self-esteem and lower the teacher's expectation regarding the abilities of the children who stutter. Teachers should be aware that children who stutter have different personalities, and applying the strategy with all students could have negative consequences. That is, some children could cope with stigmatising attitudes, while others might doubt themselves and their abilities (Arishi, Boyle and Lauchlan, 2017).

Labelling could have positive implications for inclusive education, such as determining the disability and seeking suitable inclusion criteria that suit the labelled individual. Indeed, some teachers used "Aggoun" to explain a point of view. However, in the present study it appeared to have a negative effect, as its use is not to categorise or identify individuals who stutter but to bully or tease them. The results indicate that this word is used during instances of disappointment or anger with children who stutter, which appears with mothers and teachers. Furthermore, it appeared more among the children's siblings and friends, who mostly use it to tease them. Accordingly, labelling individuals who stutter in this way can affect their social interaction and the way they socialise with others, as the stigma arises from the negative classification of social differences and attributes (Goffman, 1963).

9.2.3. Negative Attitudes Towards Children who Stuttering

Other key findings demonstrated that children who stutter in Algeria experience bullying and teasing, especially from their friends and peers in school. Unlike labelling, teachers and mothers were very aware of this attitude as they demonstrated their intolerance to it. The participants do realise the effect of bullying on children who stutter. Bullying appeared as a lack of irresponsibility rather than knowledge, as it is more common among adolescents, as the participants argued that they are not aware of the severe effects of their bullying. The participants pointed out that their friends and peers make fun of their way of speaking without considering the negative consequences, masking their mockery as sarcasm, thus expecting the child who stutters not to react negatively. The results, therefore, indicate a need to raise awareness about the stigma associated with stuttering and its consequences. This promotes a sense of sensibility and empathy among students to help contribute to a positive schooling environment. Yet, as mentioned in chapter five, the teacher demonstrated limited knowledge regarding stuttering, which impedes their ability to contribute to the students'

stuttering knowledge. Although speech-language therapists demonstrated their awareness of the negative attitudes and limited knowledge about stuttering, no action has been taken at the level of middle schools that aimed to raise awareness and knowledge about stuttering to help reduce the impact of stigma and improve the children's educational experience (Coleman, 2018). Mothers reported that their children used to avoid social interaction and isolate themselves. This resulted from negative attitudes, such as ignoring, discriminating, teasing or laughing at them (Thome, 2024)

Furthermore, stakeholders reported that negative laughter is one of the most common reactions towards children who stutter in the classroom. As the children tend to laugh during instances of stuttering, nevertheless, this appears to be shared among peers who are not aware of the peers' stutter. This emphasises the importance of raising peer awareness about stuttering to avoid this situation. Especially that not all teachers were able to react accordingly to these stigmatising attitudes, as most of them tried to normalise this situation. Some teachers reported being shocked during instances of stigmatising attitudes, thus, they do not know how to react demonstrating their need for guidance during these situations.

In the previous chapter, stakeholders tend to hold some stereotypes about children who stutter regarding their personality and the reason behind their stutter (Hearne *et al.*, 2021), which explains some of the stakeholders' attitudes. The mothers tend to relate stuttering to stress or fear; thus, they force their children to speak fluently even though stuttering cannot be controlled most of the time. Nevertheless, some mothers argued that this helped for a while, as the children's stutter reduced, yet not for an extended period. These attitudes could make the child feel responsible for their stutter; Thus, they will feel sad, frustrated, and overwhelmed. It is possible that children during adolescence are not supposed to learn all the strategies that reduce their stutter, as there might be other issues that stuttering may cause (Coleman, 2018). Furthermore, some of the other stereotypes teachers held led to the discrimination of children who stutter, as they avoid their participation, assuming that they are shy and asking them to speak in front of their peers will provoke their stutter. The lack of knowledge has created some stereotypes and led to discrimination, hence, what is referred to as public stigma (Boyle and Blood, 2015). The results indicated that some peers may discriminate and isolate children who stutter as a reaction to their stutter. The mothers argued that this happened because their children tend to take longer to utter words, which annoyed their peers. Some mothers confirm that their children do not have a lot of friends.

Unfortunately, the environment has a crucial impact on them, which cannot always be controlled (Tichenor, Herring and Yaruss, 2022). Therefore, most participants emphasised building solid self-esteem for children who stutter to reduce the effect of stigma. Speech-therapists' approaches could

help in coping with negative traits as they have reported that speech therapy involves psychological support and minimises the effect of adverse environmental reactions.

9.3. Discussion of Findings: Ways to Reducing Stigma

Many research that investigated the stigma reduction intervention focused more on mental health and other stigmatising attributes such ADHD and HIV/AIDS (Hartog *et al.*, 2020) . However, research specifically focused on stuttering interventions remains limited, although a plethora of research has been conducted to investigate the stigma associated with stuttering and speech disfluencies in general. Interestingly, a small body of research has begun to explore interventions from the perspective of children who stutter. Accordingly, this section focuses on the strategies used to mitigate the stigma associated with stuttering according to stakeholders.

According to Boyle (2017) stigma can be reduced improving the public attitudes to achieve positive results. However, addressing it can be difficult given that the reason behind it varies according to the country, culture, and people (Abasi, 2022a). In this study the participants highlighted some interventions that could mitigate stigma towards children who stutter in Algerian middle schools. The three groups of participants demonstrated a profound understanding of the essential actions to address the stigma associated with stuttering. This knowledge was shared from an Algerian culturally based perspective, where the participants are aware of how Algerian students and stakeholders will respond. Despite this, there is a lack of attempts that aim to apply these interventions in Algeria, which questions its effectiveness.

A plethora of research that aims at reducing the public stigma (Abdalla and St. Louis, 2014; Tellis and St Louis, 2015; Boyle, Dioguardi and Pate, 2016). It is worth mentioning that this chapter does not compare the strategies used in other studies with the strategies reported by the participants. Therefore, the literature discussed in this study would cover the strategies stated by the participants only. Furthermore, since the strategy has not been applied in Algeria yet, the literature could only provide a basis for the expected results of these interventions. Given that some studies argued that some techniques could not be effective, while others could have an opposite effect (Boyle, Dioguardi and Pate, 2016). Factors, such as cultural aspect, age, personality, could affect the efficacy of the strategies used in studies. Accordingly, this section discusses the strategies that were reported by the stakeholders aiming to answer the third question of this study.

What are the stakeholders' perspectives on the strategies for mitigating stigma related stuttering in Algerian middle schools?

As highlighted previously, the three groups exhibit different levels of relationship and closeness with children who stutter. Nevertheless, some of their responses were quite similar which demonstrated

the emphases on education regarding stuttering, improving teacher and student's relationship, and following some inclusive practices inside the classroom to help enrich an inclusive healthy environment for all students. Although the participants' responses lacked reliable sources, nevertheless, they share similar strategies which reflect on common cultural knowledge. This is also significant as it shows the cultural perspective of mitigating the stigma.

The following section discussed the importance of education and raising awareness to mitigate the stigma associated with stuttering.

9.3.1. Education and Raising Awareness.

There are some interventions or strategies that were approved by a number of studies such as education about stuttering (Abdalla and St. Louis, 2014; Boyle, 2016b; Boyle, Dioguardi and Pate, 2017; Iimura *et al.*, 2018; Louis *et al.*, 2020). According to Williams, Tetnowski and St. Louis (2023) education about stuttering is considered as the one of the most successful strategies to improve the public attitudes toward people who stutter. Boyle conducted many studies related to mitigating stigma associated with stuttering, besides reviewing some studies that used videos or surveys regarding stuttering as a strategy to develop social knowledge and evaluate social attitudes (2013; 2016; 2017; 2018).

In their study (Boyle, Dioguardi and Pate, 2017) evaluated some strategies that address the stigma associated with stuttering stating that these were used in the field of mental disorders and have been proven to be effective. The participants of this study also emphasised on providing solid knowledge to the students and teachers. It is very helpful to understand them and sympathise more with children who stutter. It is interesting to mention that a plethora of research has highlighted that educating the public, not only teachers and peers, about stuttering could have a positive effect on their attitudes (Louis *et al.*, 2020; Flynn and Louis, 2011; Chu *et al.*, 2022; Boyle, Dioguardi and Pate, 2016).

Nonetheless, the results indicate that the lack of knowledge about stuttering causes and stereotypes, fostering misunderstandings and biases (Bloodstein, Ratner and Brundage, 2021). Learning about the biological causes of stuttering, for example, can have a positive impact on the reduction of stigma, besides it helps reduce the self-blame as it provides explanation of stuttering that removes the pressure on individual who stutter (Boyle, 2016b). As it appeared in the previous chapter, that the mothers and teachers sometimes tend to force the children who stutter to speak fluently, which makes the students feel responsible for their stutter. Furthermore, teachers' attitudes have a significant link with their knowledge regarding the disability (Dar, Paul and Badiger, 2023). Therefore, having a negative perspective about stuttering and lacking guidance could create an obstacle for implementing a successful inclusive environment in the classroom (Boyle, Anderson and Allen, 2020).

Based on that, the stakeholders demonstrated the need for improving the students and the teachers' knowledge regarding stuttering (Khodair, Bataineh, Al-Khawaldeh and Muhaidat, 2022; Necir, 2023). Despite their approval of the teachers and mothers lack of knowledge and awareness about stuttering in Algeria (Necir, 2023) and the stigma that follows it, the data indicates there were a lack of attempts to organise study days or conferences related to stuttering. One of the reasons that underestimate the stuttering and its effect on individuals, as this disorder is not considered as a serious issue that needs to be addressed. Furthermore, the ignorance of stuttering and considering it as a minor issue could be traced back to the relatively low number of students in Algerian middle schools reported by the teachers who participated in this study. Moreover, the mothers and teachers focused more on addressing the attitudes of peers and students who stutter as well, which could also explain the lack of attempt at developing the teacher's knowledge regarding stuttering.

As part of education, the stakeholders started raising awareness among peers about the effect of negative attitudes towards stuttering as a method to reduce the stigma associated with stuttering. Nevertheless, this focused mainly on raising sensibility among peers rather than organizing study days that educate them about stuttering (Hearne, Packman, Onslow and Quine, 2008). The teachers do not have enough knowledge about stuttering which calls for the speech therapists to be involved in this process (Necir, 2023). The teachers demonstrated their focus on the students' attitudes rather than stuttering, such as explaining what is permissible and what is not toward their peers, personal correction, because bullying and teasing are generally common among adolescents (Flynn and Louis, 2011).

The methods have not been clearly stated, yet the results demonstrated direct intervention from teachers to students usually after noticing negative attitudes. Many studies have employed methods that raise awareness aiming to improve the public attitudes such as exposing them to the videos (Abdalla and St. Louis, 2014; Aghaz, Kashani and Shahriyari, 2021; Kuhn and St Louis, 2015). The studies have proven to be effective at modifying the participants' behaviours towards the individuals who stutter. In Algeria, however, no studies have been conducted yet that aim at modifying the public or the students' attitudes toward stuttering. Raising awareness among peers aims at raising sympathy and sensibility about stigma associated with stuttering to highlight the peers' responsibility towards their peers who stutter. The stakeholders recognised that it is the teachers' responsibility to react to the stigma by addressing these attitudes in the classroom.

That being said, most teachers in this study tend to react only when needed. It is significant to highlight that the social model does not necessarily focus on the stuttering management, rather on the significance of changing the social attitudes to enhance life experience and well-being of

individuals who stutter (Constantino, Campbell and Simpson, 2022). The teacher aims to reduce future stigma and provide a comfortable environment for the students who stutter for a better schooling experience. Nevertheless, teachers express concern that pre-emptively addressing potential challenges faced by students who stutter may create an uncomfortable atmosphere, especially in their presence.

The stakeholders believe that if the students put themselves in the position of their peers who stutter will feel how their peers feel when stigmatised. However, addressing persistent negative attitudes after raising awareness leads to suspension. This is similar to the Protest strategy as Boyle (2017) argues that it has not been used in many studies and it did not seem to be effective. Nevertheless, this approach seemed to be effective in Algerian classrooms as teachers could notice an improvement in the students' attitudes after addressing their negative behaviours. Based on the results, the teacher follows an educative approach that is based on direct instructions that could be followed by blame and verbal warnings to mitigate unacceptable behaviours. This could also be followed by moral lessons that raise sensibility about stuttering and responsibility towards their peers. Still, inclusive practices that aim at integrating and mitigating the stigma are not evidence-based (Constantino, Campbell and Simpson, 2022) knowing that all cultures differ.

9.3.2. Ignoring Negative Attitudes and Stigma Acceptance

Recent studies have focused on changing people's attitudes towards individuals who stutter (Cozart and Wilson, 2022; Louis *et al.*, 2020; Weidner and Louis, 2023). Although the mothers and speech therapists advise condemning negative attitudes of those who stigmatised their peers, most teachers stated that they cannot control all the students' behaviours all the time. Laughing at students who stutter was one of the most repeated attitudes as mentioned in the previous chapter. The latter indicates the stigma cannot be controlled most of the time therefore teachers believe that the children who stutter should not be affected by these attitudes and ignore them. It is worth noting that the teachers during similar situations appeared to lack confidence, especially those with little experience who clearly stated that they had been "*shocked*" and "*did not know how to react*". This demonstrates their need for guidance and training to successfully control and manage these situations successfully.

That being said, most teachers tend to ignore some negative attitudes, mainly laughter, aiming to make the environment friendly and make the students who stutter feel less awkward. The teachers somehow accepted this attitude and tried to normalise it so that the child would feel less affected by time. This contradicts the concept of acceptance discussed by Goffman (1963). The concept of acceptance of such attitudes is not about endorsing or embracing the students' negative reactions but rather about how individuals navigate and cope with their stigmatized status. This could not be an

effective way as the teachers may believe, as some children tend to hide their feelings especially when they are hurt in the classroom and only express themselves around their close ones. Laughing at someone could be followed by embarrassment and lowering self-esteem.

Acceptance, in this context, should refer to the acknowledgement and integration of the stigmatized identity into one's sense of self, rather than internalizing the negative societal attitudes. However, viewed through a cultural lens, it is important to note that in Algeria, many children, particularly boys, are brought up with a resilience-focused upbringing. This cultural approach tends to associate emotional strength with adulthood, particularly men, who should not have sensitive personalities that could be affected by these negative attitudes.

9.3.3. Student and Teacher Relationship

Although the teachers have not explicitly stated this, both groups, the mothers and speech therapists, argued that working on the student-teacher relationship will have a significant effect on the comfort of the children who stutter, thus on their stuttering severity. Some studies emphasise the teacher-student relationship (Berchiatti *et al.*, 2021; Schwab and Rossmann, 2020; Pérez-Salas, Parra, Sáez-Delgado and Olivares, 2021). The students who stutter should feel more comfortable sharing with the teacher any issues to work on them together. Some research has reported that students with disabilities do not have a good relationship with their teachers compared to their peers (Berchiatti *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, the teacher demonstrated positive attitudes towards children who stutter, while some of the mothers and speech therapists reported some stereotyping and discrimination incidents that affected the relationship between some teachers and their children.

Teachers understand that they are not only responsible for delivering the lecture but for providing a good environment and a successful schooling experience. Hence, the significance of the educational relationship does not mean it should always be academic and focus on the subject of study only as the results of the subject are also related to the quality of their students and teachers' relationship (Longobardi, Prino, Fabris and Settanni, 2019; Berchiatti *et al.*, 2021). Indeed, some of the mothers reported facing some challenges convincing their children to go to school after being stigmatised by their teachers. Therefore, a good relationship between the students and the teacher could help tremendously in early adolescence especially if the student is subjected to bullying (Jungert, Piroddi and Thornberg, 2016).

Furthermore, it allows teacher-student collaborations that permit the teacher to understand what provokes the student's stutter and anxiety to avoid (Berchiatti *et al.*, 2021). The mothers of children who stutter and the speech therapists view the teachers-students' warm relationships as a good strategy to accommodate the students' needs and provide them with a good schooling experience.

Although the teachers have not explicitly articulated this strategy, it should not be interpreted as a lack of concern for the students' well-being beyond academic achievement. The teachers have stated in different parts of the interview discussions strategies and inclusive practices they use to integrate children who stutter, thus, developing a good relationship with students who stutter.

In conclusion the three sections of discussion provide insightful data that contributed to knowledge. The first question explored the knowledge of stakeholders regarding stuttering, thus, the answer to this question revealed not only the depth of their understanding, yet also uncovered the challenges of children who stutter and their close environment including teachers and peers. This contributed to research knowledge about the Algerian need to develop their knowledge regarding stuttering and provide appropriate support to students who stutter by offering training, guidance, and resources to enhance their understanding. In addition, the contribution of the answers to this question was at the level of understanding ultimately the attitudes towards individuals who stutter and uncovering the cultural perspectives related to the perception of stuttering, paving the way to address negative attitudes.

The second question that addressed the stakeholders' knowledge of the stigma associated with stuttering contributed significantly to uncovering the negative attitudes towards stuttering and individuals who stutter, unveiling the experiences and challenges that children who stutter face in Algerian society, particularly in schools. This contributes to the international research that addresses the stigma associated with stuttering by contextualising it within a North African, Arabic-speaking society where limited empirical work has been carried out.

Finally, the last question that addressed the interventions to mitigate stigma significantly contributed by reinforcing the interventions proposed by other scholars, while also being shaped by the Algerian stakeholders, reflecting their understanding of both stigma and stuttering as perceived in Algeria. These interventions are deemed significant as they are built on three nuanced perspectives that combine the clinical expertise of speech therapists, the actual classroom practices of teachers, and the emotional well-being of mothers, which makes this contribution unique and balanced between professional knowledge and personal experience.

10. Chapter Ten: General Conclusion and Discussion

This chapter serves as the general conclusion for this PhD thesis, drawing together the key findings and their significance. I will begin by discussing the main findings from each chapter and then I will address the research questions. Following this, I will address the significance of the research findings highlighting how they contribute to a comprehensive understanding of stuttering and stigma in Algerian middle schools. This will include exploring how the study contributes to the existing body of knowledge and the potential implications for stakeholders such as teachers, speech-language therapists, and policymakers. No research is without limitations, hence, I will acknowledge any limitations of this study, such as sample size or methodological constraints. I will then discuss how these limitations might affect the generalizability of the findings. Finally, I will provide some suggestions for future research that could build upon my work. This will help to guide further exploration of this important topic.

The main part of this PhD research investigates stakeholders' knowledge regarding stuttering, its associated stigma, and potential interventions to mitigate that stigma. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of stakeholders' knowledge, perceptions, and how they affect their practices related to stuttering and its stigma, could contribute to the development of future interventions and strategies to promote inclusivity and support for students who stutter in Algerian middle schools.

10.1. Addressing Research Questions

- **First Research Question:** What is the depth and scope of the Algerian stakeholders' knowledge of stuttering?

The aim of the first research question is to investigate the knowledge and understanding of stuttering held by stakeholders; the speech-language therapists, mothers of children who stutter, and middle school language teachers; in Algeria. The analysis focused on their comprehension of the following aspects of stuttering: The nature of stuttering itself, Potential causes, treatment options, and psychological impact on children who stutter in Algeria. Overall, the three groups demonstrated different levels of understanding of stuttering. This was explained by their closeness, and motivation to learn about this speech disorder.

Algerian speech-language therapists demonstrated a good grasp of stuttering, compared to the other groups. They possessed the ability to provide clear explanations and facilitate learning for individuals of all educational backgrounds. The focus was on raising awareness rather than delving into complex details. This skill is particularly important for caregivers, as understanding stuttering empowers them to support treatment at home. Speech therapists reported that most parents, especially those residing

in rural areas with limited access to education, required simple and concise explanations about stuttering. Although not all of the speech therapists' knowledge aligns with the stuttering studies, especially the latest research, the findings underscore the crucial role of speech-language therapists in the context of stuttering. Their comprehensive understanding of the disorder, as demonstrated in the study, has a remarkable influence on the mothers' and teachers' knowledge who have contact with them. This occurs as similar knowledge shared by the three groups although it was incorrect to some extent. This highlights their pivotal position for speech therapists in educating and empowering caregivers and teachers. However, speech therapist should improve their knowledge regarding stuttering based on recent studies that help equip parents and teachers with clear explanations and treatment strategies.

Furthermore, the mothers who participated in this study exhibited a practical understanding of stuttering based on their observations and experiences with their children. They primarily relied on speech-language therapists to gain a deeper understanding of the disorder and appropriate interventions. However, their reliance on speech-language therapists for a deeper understanding and intervention strategies highlights a potential gap in accessible resources and educational initiatives specifically tailored for parents. While the mothers were unsure about the exact causes of stuttering, their primary concern remained to find effective treatment options for their children. This reliance underscores the necessity for accessible resources and educational initiatives tailored specifically for parents. Enhancing parental awareness and equipping them with comprehensive information can improve their knowledge and enable more informed decision-making regarding treatment options for their children.

Moreover, the study identified significant knowledge gaps among teachers, particularly those without prior experience with students who stutter. This lack of understanding can lead teachers to rely on assumptions, which can impede their ability to support affected students effectively. Even teachers with a general understanding of language production often lacked specific knowledge about stuttering, its causes, and effective intervention strategies. This underscores the urgency for targeted training programs aimed at teachers, providing them with the necessary knowledge and skills to create inclusive classroom environments and provide appropriate support to students who stutter.

It is important to highlight that stuttering is predominantly viewed from a medical model perspective. The following figure illustrates the main characteristics contributing to this viewpoint. However, it is crucial to consider that this model may not encompass the full complexity of stuttering, potentially overlooking social, psychological, and environmental factors that also play a significant role.

Figure 13 Application of the Medical Model of Disability to Stuttering, Based on Participants' Results.

As shown in the figure, the participants focus on the individual symptoms and physiological aspects associated with the disorder. Children who stutter show dysfluency, which manifests as interruptions in the flow of speech, such as blocks, pauses, and repetitions. These speech disruptions are often accompanied by secondary behaviours, including facial grimacing, head movements, and other physical gestures as attempts to overcome the stutter. The participants reported that there is a need to improve knowledge regarding stuttering. However, it is important to note that the participants also rely more on the child to overcome the dysfluency, reporting that they should work more on their self-esteem.

- **Second research question:** What is the depth and scope of stakeholders' knowledge of the stigma associated with stuttering in Algerian middle schools?

The second research question investigated the experiences of children who stutter in Algerian middle schools through the lens of stakeholder knowledge. The absence of prior research on this topic in Algeria excluded the establishment of a formal hypothesis about the existence of stigma towards children who stutter. However, the findings of this research, based on stakeholder knowledge, revealed concerning experiences for children who stutter. Children who stutter reported experiencing various forms of stigma, including discrimination, bullying, and labelling, both at school and at home. It is important to note that the findings suggest a potential link between the negative attitudes

experienced by children who stutter, and the knowledge gaps identified among mothers and teachers. Nonetheless, the results demonstrated that the Algerian society recognises and identifies the stigma as they are aware of the behaviours that could affect the children's feelings and eventually affect their personalities. The participants' perspectives presented a paradox. While they generally minimize the severity of the effect of stuttering, they also reported numerous incidents of students who stutter experiencing stigma in both school and non-school settings. This inconsistency could be due to the low numbers of students who stutter observed in the middle schools might have led teachers to underestimate the impact of the issue and, consequently, not prioritize addressing it with the school administration.

The most common situation reported by all teachers involved students laughing at classmates who stuttered. However, teacher responses to these situations varied, suggesting a reliance on personal knowledge and past experiences. It is interesting to note that teachers with less experience demonstrated a need for guidance on how to control instances of stigmatising attitudes. This indicates that the experience of teaching students who stutter significantly impacts the teacher's skills and attitudes towards stuttering. While the overall results indicated generally positive teacher attitudes towards students who stutter, these incidents highlight a need for more specific training on managing stigma in the classroom. Notably, teachers themselves expressed a desire for professional development opportunities, such as study days, to enhance their knowledge and skills in this area.

Some of the negative attitudes occurred due to the teachers' lack of awareness about the stutter. The mothers acknowledge the teachers' support for their children; however, they have also stated a few incidents that demonstrated stigmatising attitudes from the teachers. The study also revealed instances where teachers exhibited impatience with students who stutter, potentially leading to reactions that accidentally aggravated the situation. This finding highlights the need for targeted training programs to equip teachers with the knowledge and skills necessary to create supportive learning environments for children who stutter. Effective training could encompass understanding the nature of stuttering, appropriate communication strategies, and methods for reducing stigma in the classroom.

- **Third research question:** What are the stakeholders' perspectives on the strategies for mitigating stigma-related stuttering in Algerian middle schools?

The third research question investigated stakeholder perceptions of interventions to mitigate stigma within the Algerian social context. While prior research has identified various factors that can reduce stigma, these strategies are often general or implemented outside of school environments. This question specifically focused on classroom-based interventions that

teachers could utilize to manage stigma and support students who stutter. While the current study did not assess the effectiveness of these strategies, the stakeholder perspectives on classroom-based interventions to reduce stigma provide valuable insights for future research. These insights can inform the development and evaluation of targeted interventions specifically designed to address the needs of students who stutter in Algerian middle schools. This study identified three key strategies to reduce stigma in Algerian classrooms according to the participants: educating teachers and peers about stuttering, fostering positive student-teacher relationships, and addressing negative attitudes.

Participants, especially speech-language therapists and mothers reported numerous incidents due to the teachers' awareness regarding the students' stutter, therefore, they emphasized the importance of promoting education and awareness about stuttering among teachers and peers. This increased understanding and empathy could create a more supportive learning environment for students who stutter. Speech-language therapists suggested using informative materials to educate teachers about stuttering, while mothers highlighted the effectiveness of in-person communication at the beginning of the schooling year. However, the study also identified a gap in support for teachers themselves; there was no mention of initiatives such as study days to improve their knowledge and skills in managing stuttering in the classroom.

Participants also emphasized the importance of building positive relationships between students who stutter and their teachers. A strong relationship can provide a safe space for communication and support. Participants acknowledged that fostering a warm rapport with students, especially those who stutter, can encourage them to feel comfortable sharing experiences or negative attitudes that teachers can address. This, in turn, can contribute to a more relaxed classroom environment for students who stutter, potentially reducing the severity of their stuttering. This was based on the participants' belief that stress can exacerbate stuttering symptoms.

Finally, participants suggested addressing stigma through raising peer awareness, as it can be a valuable tool for reducing negative reactions from classmates and promoting acceptance, ultimately fostering a more inclusive classroom environment. Participants emphasized the importance of directly addressing these negative attitudes by engaging with students who exhibit them, as some peer behaviours may be intentional. This could also involve educational workshops or discussions to raise awareness and promote empathy towards classmates who stutter.

10.2. General Discussion

Stuttering is not generally considered a physical disability. In Algeria, it is often perceived as a speech difficulty rather than a disability. Despite this, only a small number of teachers truly understand the challenges associated with stuttering. A number of them still speak slowly to children who stutter, as if these children have difficulty hearing or understanding words. This reflects Erving Goffman's concept of the generalizability of stigma, where he discusses the tendency to treat people with one disability as if they have others, such as assuming that blind people are also deaf (1963). This situation highlights the lack of knowledge among teachers regarding how to appropriately respond to and manage stuttering in the classroom, inadvertently creating stigma.

Acceptance was a strategy that most participants of this study believed in. However, they also recognised that some negative attitudes could be tolerated and treated as a normal part of life, in an effort not to draw too much attention to stuttering or make it a significant issue. Instead of directly addressing the problem, teachers sometimes advise students to normalise negative reactions, which contradicts Goffman's idea of 'minstrelization' (1963, p. 134). This concept involves reducing the impact of stigma by openly acknowledging negative feelings rather than ignoring them or allowing them to become a source of ridicule. In contrast, parents often advise their children to try to speak fluently to avoid being laughed at, a strategy Goffman refers to as being 'warned against minstrelization' (1963, p. 134).

Nevertheless, in managing stigma, Goffman introduced the idea of educating others to prevent reducing a stigmatized individual to less than human. This perspective was explicitly echoed by the participants. Teachers, however, tend to believe that in the face of unexpected negative reactions to stuttering, strategies such as ignorance, normalisation, and the use of humour to break the ice can protect students who stutter. This approach aligns with Goffman's description of how 'normals' react to stigma (1963, p. 141).

Parents are often the first to seek treatment from speech therapists to address their children's stuttering, akin to those who undergo plastic surgery to compensate for their stigma (Goffman, 1963). Some children who stutter may subsequently isolate themselves and avoid social interaction, a response frequently observed by parents and speech therapists. This behaviour can lead to anxiety or depression (Goffman, 1963). Most of the incidents reported, where children who stutter develop avoidance behaviours, are the result of experiencing stigmatising attitudes.

Furthermore, the results of this study indicate that comparing children is a very common behaviour, especially among mothers and family members. Children who stutter are often compared to their peers who do not stutter, either as a means of comparison or as a way to motivate them to avoid

stuttering. According to Goffman (1963), such comparisons constitute stigmatising attitudes, as they are rooted in social norms. Goffman argued that the issue is largely based on the 'visibility' of the stigmatising attribute, which can lead to communication failures during social interactions. This occurs because the attribute challenges the 'defaulter's acceptability' in social situations (1963, p. 154).

Families are considered 'courtesy members' of children who stutter, and are seen as the 'Wise', as described by Goffman (1963). Although they experience sadness and distress due to their children's struggles with speaking and the negative attitudes directed towards them, they themselves are not stigmatised because of their children's stutter, which does not align with Goffman's concept of stigma by association (1963) based on the results of this study.

Interestingly, Goffman discusses the concept of a 'moral career', which refers to how individuals with a stigma learn from their experiences and adjust to their condition as a coping mechanism (1963). Similarly, based on the results of this study, children who stutter tend to become adaptive to their stutter and develop ways to manage stigmatising attitudes. This was supported by reports from teachers, who observed that children in their final years of middle school cope better with their stutter than those in their first and second years. Consequently, negative reactions, such as mocking laughter, were more frequently reported among first and second year students. Furthermore, some children are able to reduce their stuttering by identifying the specific words and sounds they struggle with and consciously avoiding them. This strategy allows them to manage their stutter more effectively.

The interview data revealed that most participants have developed their knowledge and perceptions regarding stuttering and children who stutter based on their experiences and social interaction. Goffman explained that social information is often conveyed through particular symbols and signs. He refers to these signs as 'fugitive signs', which are not always consistent or reliable and may include misleading 'slips' or helpful 'points' (1963, p. 61). In this study, participants sometimes built inaccurate assumptions, leading to stereotypes about stuttering. For instance, one mother encountered this when a teacher, who associated good appearance with fluency, expressed surprise that her well-presented child stuttered, despite his good looks. Furthermore, Goffman's concept of the 'identity peg' refers to the idea that certain attributes or assumptions can either align with or contradict a person's true identity. In this case, the teacher formed her perception based on a mistaken assumption, largely due to a lack of knowledge.

Stigma can sometimes persist based on an individual's biography or personal history (Goffman, 1963). Similarly, speech and language therapists reported that individuals who have recovered from stuttering may still face negative reactions, as others might continue to expect them to stutter at any moment. This demonstrates how stigma can have long-term effects, leading individuals to engage in

'passing', which depends on the perceptibility of the stigma and the level of knowledge others have about it (Goffman, 1963). This can be particularly challenging when interacting with people who are aware of the individual's history as a person who stutters.

Moreover, individuals who stutter often use various techniques to conceal their stutter. For instance, as speech therapists noted, they may avoid certain sounds or words that trigger their stutter. Seeking speech therapy itself can be seen as a form of 'covering' aimed at reducing or overcoming the stutter. While this effort is partly motivated by a desire to avoid stigmatising attitudes, the primary goal is often recovery, not merely escaping stigma.

Goffman also discusses the concept of stigma visibility, which affects an individual's ability to hide their stigma, especially during mixed contacts where acceptance might not be guaranteed (1963). Some teachers tend to avoid calling on children who stutter to participate in class discussions. While this may not be intended as direct discrimination, it often reflects the teacher's awareness of the stutter. Teachers have explained that they sometimes do this due to time constraints and the pressure to complete the curriculum. However, many teachers have found alternative solutions by providing these students with activities that require less time or verbal participation.

Furthermore, in Goffman's work on stigma, he discusses the concepts of group alignment and ego identification (1963). He suggests that individuals who identify with a stigma may limit their social interactions based on the severity of their stigmatising condition (1963, p. 130). This idea relates to whether individuals with a stigmatised condition prefer to associate with others who share the same stigma or choose to distance themselves. In other words, individuals with a stigmatising attribute tend to associate with others who share the same attribute (1963). However, since stuttering is not perceived as a severe condition compared to other disabilities and participants in this study do not typically consider stuttering to be a disability or see those who stutter as inferior, the concept of group alignment did not prominently appear in the data. The data from the three groups did not indicate that children who stutter prefer the company of other children who stutter nor those who do not. Instead, they are more tending to be around close friends or familiar individuals in their daily surroundings. This suggests that children who stutter are not viewed as fundamentally different by their peers.

10.3. Contribution of this Research Study

The research conducted for this PhD thesis has made significant steps in identifying and addressing critical knowledge gaps surrounding stuttering in Algerian society, particularly, among mothers and teachers. This lack of understanding sheds light on the need for targeted interventions and educational resources to raise awareness and support for stuttering. Hence, the research highlighted

the limitation in improving knowledge about stuttering in Algeria and emphasised fostering understanding among these crucial stakeholder groups.

While this research represents a significant step forward in understanding and addressing knowledge gaps surrounding stuttering, it also underscores the complexities and challenges inherent in effecting meaningful change. It is essential to translate these findings into actionable strategies that prioritize inclusivity, accessibility, and collaboration among stakeholders to create a more supportive environment for individuals who stutter.

The research also paves the way for future research and practical implementation informed by the identified knowledge gaps and diverse needs of stakeholders. By recognising the significance of accessible resources and clear guidance for parents and teachers, this study advocates for a holistic approach to supporting individuals who stutter. However, the effectiveness of these interventions depends on their adaptability, accessibility, and sustained implementation within educational and group settings.

Furthermore, acknowledging the crucial role of teachers in supporting students who stutter is a cornerstone of this research. Therefore, the identification of knowledge gaps among teachers underscores the deficiencies in current teacher training programs and highlights the imperative for comprehensive professional development initiatives. However, the acknowledgement of these gaps is insufficient without concrete steps towards implementing effective training programs tailored to address the specific needs of teachers in supporting students who stutter.

Finally, this research also sheds light on the importance of examining educational policies to ensure they adequately support children who stutter. Current policies may not fully address the specific needs of this student population. Future research can explore the potential benefits of policy changes that promote awareness and understanding of stuttering among educators and classmates. Additionally, policies that protect students who stutter from bullying and discrimination, along with those that provide accommodations and support services such as modified speaking assignments or extended time on tests, could significantly improve the educational experience for students who stutter. By advocating for such policy changes alongside the development of interventions and resources, this research paves the way for a more comprehensive approach to supporting children who stutter in Algerian schools.

10.4. Reflexivity

It is crucial to reflect on the way my positionality and reflexivity shaped the findings during this research journey. My positionality as an insider contributed positively to this research by facilitating interaction and building trust with my participants. Both my cultural and linguistic background enabled

participants to share their knowledge and experiences more openly, which enriched the quality and depth of the data. Indeed, being an insider created more opportunities. Nevertheless, I was very cautious to ensure that my position did not affect the data in any way and to avoid any bias. As Holmes (2020) notes, reflexivity requires awareness of how the researcher's own position may influence what is emphasised or overlooked in the interpretation of data. Moreover, interpreting and translating the data would have been difficult, if not inaccurate, for an outsider researcher, whereas my cultural and linguistic background helped tremendously in understanding the participants' points of view and the expressions they used to explain their experiences.

Finlay (2002) argued that reflexivity is not only about avoiding bias but also about acknowledging the development of the research and the researcher's relationships. Hence, conducting this research has significantly expanded knowledge regarding stuttering and the challenges faced by both stakeholders and children who stutter. This awareness has strengthened my motivation to conduct further research promoting inclusive education in Algeria. My identity as a researcher within education and social sciences has also been positively influenced, as I now consider myself a researcher immersed in the social and educational aspects of stuttering and attitudes towards children who stutter in Algeria.

Recognising the limitations is also important, as being an insider could restrict my viewpoint to a cultural understanding, while there remains the possibility that these data could be interpreted differently by an outsider researcher. Nevertheless, this does not undermine the reliability of the research but recognising that my findings could be interpreted differently should be taken into account, as it reflects my reflexivity as a researcher.

10.5. Recommendations

This study has also highlighted some recommendations for educational policies and practices. The overall findings revealed several gaps and negative attitudes that should be addressed in Algerian society and schools in order to improve the experiences of students who stutter. Accordingly, this section focuses on Policy-Level Recommendations, Educational Practice, Speech-Language Therapy Practice, and Parents and Communities.

First of all, the findings of this study identified a gap in educational policies, where schools urgently need to implement awareness-raising initiatives among all school stakeholders and students regarding stuttering as part of inclusion strategies. This could be addressed through collaboration between the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Health to organise professional development programmes. Speech therapists could be of great help in raising awareness not only about stuttering but also about other communication disorders. Such initiatives would familiarise the school environment with disability, echoing Norwich's (2013) recommendation, which emphasises balancing knowledge with

educational practices. This could also be supported by incorporating teacher training that equips teachers with practical strategies to ensure an inclusive environment and reduce stigma. These steps can contribute to shifting perceptions from viewing stuttering as a defect toward recognising it as a natural variation in communication. Such an approach would be particularly helpful in supporting students' communicative practices and boosting their self-esteem.

In addition to recommendations that should be implemented within school and educational settings, some recommendations extend to the external environment, which can indirectly support schools. One key area is parental support and guidance. The findings revealed that parents often lack guidance during the initial phase of their children's stuttering onset. Providing such support could contribute to several important outcomes, such as improving parents' understanding of stuttering, enabling them to provide appropriate support, and encouraging positive communication practices at home that can also extend into school contexts.

10.6. Suggestion for Future Research

While this research has provided valuable insights into knowledge gaps surrounding stuttering and potential interventions, several avenues for future research could further advance our understanding and support for individuals who stutter in Algeria. This involves investigating the lived experiences of individuals who stutter to gain deeper insights into the challenges they face and the strategies they utilise to manage their stuttering.

Qualitative studies focusing on the experiences of individuals who stutter can offer rich, nuanced perspectives on the psychosocial, academic, and vocational challenges they encounter. By exploring factors such as stigma, self-perception, coping mechanisms, and resilience, researchers can develop a more comprehensive understanding of the diverse experiences within the stuttering community. Moreover, continuing studies addressing individuals who stutter over time can provide valuable insights into stuttering and the factors that influence outcomes such as academic achievement, employment status, and overall well-being.

Additionally, quantitative studies are needed to provide empirical evidence on the prevalence of stuttering in schools and the outcomes of individuals who stutter in educational settings. Large-scale surveys or studies could quantify the prevalence of stuttering among school-age children and adolescents in Algeria, as well as track their academic performance and dropout rates. By identifying patterns of success and challenges among individuals who stutter in schools, researchers can determine areas for targeted intervention and support.

Moreover, investigating the reasons behind dropout rates among individuals who stutter is essential for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies. Mixed methods approaches that

combine quantitative analysis of dropout rates with qualitative interviews or focus groups with individuals who have dropped out could provide valuable insights into the underlying factors contributing to dropout. Factors such as bullying, academic struggles, lack of support, and psychosocial challenges may all play a role in individuals' decisions to leave school prematurely.

Furthermore, future research should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of interventions suggested by stakeholders, including individuals who stutter, parents, and teachers. By implementing and rigorously evaluating interventions such as educational resources, teacher training programs, and support groups, researchers can assess their impact on knowledge, attitudes, and outcomes related to stuttering. Research evaluating strategies that support students who stutter provides valuable insights into the sustained effects of interventions and identifies areas for improvement.

10.7. Limitations of this Research

While this study successfully contributed to the body of research on stuttering in Algeria and its associated stigma in Algerian middle schools, it also encountered challenges that potentially limited its scope. This section addresses some of these limitations and how they were managed.

One significant challenge was the COVID-19 pandemic, which necessitated changes to the research methodology and focus. Initially, I planned to utilise a triangulation of methods, including classroom observations, document analysis, and structured interviews. However, due to limited access to schools during the pandemic and the uncertain duration of these restrictions, I had to adapt the current research design and rely solely on interviews based on a triangulation of perspectives. This methodological shift did not necessarily affect the validity of the research findings; however, it did impact the research process. The decision to adopt an alternative approach to achieve the study objectives required significant time and adaptation.

Furthermore, the limited generalisability of the results is a common challenge for qualitative studies. While qualitative approaches offer valuable insights into individuals' experiences, perceptions, and behaviours, they are not designed to produce statistically representative findings applicable to broader populations. Additionally, the sample size and composition may have influenced the diversity and representativeness of perspectives captured, potentially limiting the breadth and depth of insights gleaned from the data. Notably, the participants were primarily centred in the western region of Algeria. Therefore, while the results could be generalised to the population of the West, it is important to acknowledge that Algeria is a large country with diverse regions. As a result, attitudes and beliefs regarding stuttering in other cities or regions may differ and may not necessarily align with those observed in the Western region. Since PhD research is limited in time as well, it was difficult to travel all around Algeria to collect the data and ensure generalisability. However, future studies should

aim to include a more geographically diverse sample to better capture the range of perspectives and experiences across different areas of Algeria. This broader approach would enhance the applicability and relevance of findings to a larger segment of the Algerian population.

10.8. Limitations of the Research Design

In research studies, some limitations hinder the research process. In the current research, there were some disadvantages of using qualitative research. First, the sample size of this approach is small, making it ungeneralisable. A small sample prompts concerns about generalising the data to the entire research population (Harry and Lipsky, 2014; Thompson, 2011). Rahman (2017) added that a small sample size might make the findings unreliable and ungeneralizable, which makes them less applicable to policymakers. However, the researchers focus on the transferability of their findings so that they can be applied to other contexts by sufficiently covering the topic.

Secondly, qualitative data collection is not statistically representative. Qualitative research focuses on how individuals perceive and create meaning from their experiences to comprehend a person's lived reality (Silverman, 2020). Various methods such as interviews, diaries, journals, classroom observations, and open-ended surveys are used to collect and analyse data from text and image sources, as well as historical documents (Zohrabi, 2013). This allows researchers to give quality to the data rather than relying solely on statistics, as qualitative approaches do not provide statistical and numerical analysis and calculations (Brink, 1993). Thus, the lack of scientific legitimacy and numerical accuracy makes the findings less likely to influence policy (Mohajan, 2017).

Thirdly, researchers can influence qualitative research. Policymakers may view the findings of a qualitative approach with scepticism (Rahman, 2017). Due to various bias issues, both the researcher's and participants' perspectives must be identified and clarified (Mohajan, 2017). Therefore, participants in the research should be carefully chosen to avoid bias. While quantitative researchers rely on statistics to ensure validity and reliability, qualitative researchers achieve this by combining different methodological strategies (Noble and Smith, 2015). In the current research, the collected data is based on interviews with three different groups. These groups have different perspectives that help ensure the reliability and trustworthiness of the results.

Fourthly, collecting qualitative data can be time-consuming. Berg and Lune (2012) commented, 'Qualitative research is a long, hard road, with elusive data on one side and stringent requirements for analysis on the other.' Engaging in the complexity of the research, data analysis is a time-consuming process that involves sorting through large quantities of data and condensing them into a few topics or categories (Creswell, 2013).

In summary, the researcher is aware of the challenges that might be encountered in conducting qualitative research. These challenges include small sample size, data that cannot be generalized, lack of statistical presentation, researcher bias, and time consumption. However, the research ensures that these challenges will be addressed during the study to enhance its reliability, validity, and trustworthiness.

10.9. Concluding statement

In conclusion, this PhD thesis has made significant contributions to understanding stakeholders' knowledge and attitudes towards stuttering and its associated stigma in Algerian middle schools. The findings revealed limited knowledge among participants, potentially impacting their ability to manage stuttering effectively. Additionally, uncertainties regarding managing negative reactions in the classroom, such as laughter during stuttering incidents, were evident. Although this research focuses mainly on stuttering, the findings highlight the critical need for interventions to support not only children who stutter, yet also children with all other types of communication disorder.

This research paves the way for developing targeted strategies, such as providing teachers and parents with resources to address knowledge gaps. It also underscores the importance of advocating for educational policies that protect children who stutter from negative attitudes and promote supportive approaches. Implementing teacher training programs on managing stuttering in the classroom could be a valuable step in this direction. Furthermore, the research opens doors for future investigations into the effectiveness of intervention strategies suggested by participants to mitigate stigma in Algerian middle schools.

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12. Appendices

12.1. A Screenshot of the Email of the Ethical Approval from the UWS Ethics Committee

Ethics Application Approved

donotreply@infonetica.net
To: Meriem Bennedjadi
Cc: Chris Holligan

Letter.pdf
84 KB

The source of this email is EXTERNAL to UWS

Dear Meriem Bennedjadi

Your application 16912: "Middle school teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards learners with speech disorders in Algeria: A case study of stuttering", submission reference 14138, has been approved. Please see attached approval letter.

Dr Iain McPhee

Reply Reply all Forward

- 12.2. A copy of the gatekeeper's approval for data collection in Algeria (the director of social activities and solidarity)

الجمهورية الجزائرية الديمقراطية الشعبية

ولاية [REDACTED]

مديرية النشاط الاجتماعي والتضامن

مصلحة الإدارة العامة والوسائل

رقم 449/م ن ا ت م ا ع و / 2022

في [REDACTED]

17 مارس 2022

إلى المسادة /

مدراء المؤسسات المتخصصة

الموضوع: ب/خ ترخيص لاجراء تريض تطبيقي .

المرفقات: - نسخة من رخصة البحث

يشرفني أن أوجه إليكم الطالبة الأتمة بن نجادي مريم المسجلة في سنة ثالثة دكتوراه بجامعة غرب اسكتلندا شعبة تعليم و علوم اجتماعية لإجراء تريض تطبيقي على مستوى مؤسستكم في تخصص

النطق و اللغة ابتداءا من 2022/03/17 .

و عليه نطلب منكم تقديم يد المساعدة للمعني في حدود ما يسمح به القانون

تقبلوا تحياتنا الخالصة

- 12.3. A copy of the gatekeeper's approval for data collection in Algeria (The director of the paediatric hospital)

الجمهورية الجزائرية الديمقراطية الشعبية
وزارة الصحة

مديرية الصحة لولاية [REDACTED]
المؤسسة الاستشفائية المتخصصة في طب النساء و التوليد
و طب الأطفال و جراحة الأطفال
المديرية الفرعية لإدارة الوسائل
الرقم: 2022/807

مدير المؤسسة الاستشفائية المتخصصة
[REDACTED]
إلى
السيدة: رئيسة مصلحة طب الأطفال

الموضوع: فاي إجراء مقابلة .

نظرا لطلب رخصة بإجراء مقابلات في إطار البحث العلمي، الوارد إلينا تحت رقم 820
المؤرخ في : 2022.03.17 المقدم من طرف السيدة : بن نجادي مريم طالبة الدكتوراه في جامعة
اسكتلندا المملكة المتحدة .

أضع تحت تصرفكم: بن نجادي مريم للقيام بإجراء مقابلات بمصلحة طب
الأطفال لمدة خمسة عشر (15) يوم ابتداء من 2022.05.04 إلى غاية: 2022.05.18.

12.4. A copy of the gatekeeper's approval for data collection in Algeria (The head of the Ministry of Education)

الجمهورية الجزائرية الديمقراطية الشعبية
وزارة التربية الوطنية

2022/05/04

مديرية التربية لولاية
مصلحة التكوين و التفتيش
الرقم : 2022/015/ 447

مدير التربية
إلى
الآنسة : بن نجادي مريم
طالبة دكتوراه بجامعة غرب اسكتلندا
المملكة المتحدة

الموضوع : رخصة لإجراء تربص ميداني.
المرجع : مراسلة جامعة غرب اسكتلندا - المملكة المتحدة - السنة الجامعية 2021/2022

بناء على المراسلة المشار إليها في المرجع أعلاه، يشرفني أن أنهي إلى علمكم أنه
يمكنكم الالتحاق بالمؤسسات الأتية :
، وذلك في إطار إعداد
بحث ميداني لتحضير أطروحة دكتوراه.

- مع الالتزام بالإجراءات الخاصة بالوقاية من فيروس كوفيد 19.

12.5. Speech-Language therapists' semi-structured interview

Date: _____

Male/ female: _____

General questions:

- 1- How many years have you been working in this field?
- 2- How many students do you receive annually?
- 3- What are the average ages of students who register to receive treatment?
- 4- What kind of treatment do you usually provide?
- 5- What are the most common speech disorders to the best of your knowledge?
- 6- Have you received any training or done any personal readings about stuttering specifically?
- 7- How would you rate the parent's awareness of seeking additional support for their children from a language therapist in Algeria?
- 8- How would rate the treatment you provide to the children who stutter in Algeria?

Questions related to the topic:

- 1- Do you know other people with a stutter or any type of speech disorder?
- 4- How would you describe or define stuttering?
- 5- What do think is the cause behind stuttering?
- 6- Do you think that stuttering makes creates psychological problems?
- 7- Do you that negative experiences of stuttering affect them in the long term?
- 8- Do you think that stuttering affects the intelligence of the learner?
- 9- Do think that stuttering may affect the academic progress of the learner?

Questions related to stuttering in the classroom:

- 1- In the classroom, should the teacher avoid the participation of learners with a stutter?
- 2- What can the teacher do if the students who stutter do not participate in the classroom?
- 3- What techniques should the teacher adopt to make the student who stutters comfortable and less stressed while speaking?
- 4- How should the teacher react when facing some of the following imaginary situations with students who stutter:
 - The teacher feels in a rush to finish the lecture and a student with stutter wants to participate in the lecture.
 - Peers repeated the student's stutter.

- The teacher arranges for group work that is based on speaking and s/he saw the student is not comfortable with giving his opinion in the group because of his stutter.
- There was supposed to be a read-out-loud activity, should the teacher give the choice for the student to participate or ask him to read anyway.
- Their Peers started to make comments on their stutter.
- The student asks for advice on how to manage his or her stutter.
- The student is having difficulty to utter a word; should the teacher say it for them?

5- What kind of attitudes do think the stutterer considers as stigmatisation?

6- How should the teacher react if the student who stutters is being stigmatised?

7- Do schools arrange lectures addressed to the student to raise awareness about speech disorders and stuttering? If not, would you recommend that?

8- What do think about the following suggestions:

- The teacher should speak to students about their stutter.
- The teacher should speak with their parents about their stutter.
- Teachers and parents should work cooperatively with speech-language therapists.

12.6. The Parents' Semi-structured interview

Date: _____

Mother / Father: _____

Gender and age of the child who stutters: _____

General questions:

- 1- How old is your child?
- 2- What grade does he/she study?
- 3- Is she aware of his/her stutter?
- 4- Have you received any training or done any personal reading about stuttering?
- 5- Are you familiar with the concept of inclusive education?
- 6- Have you learned or done any personal research about communication disorders?
- 7- What are the most common speech disorders to the best of your knowledge?
- 8- Do have any idea about stuttering?
- 9- Has your child done any reading about this speech disorder?
- 10- Does your child receive any additional support from a Speech therapist?
- 11- How would you describe the severity of the stutter of your child?

Questions related to the topic:

- 1- Do you know other people with a stutter or any type of speech disorder?
- 4- How would you describe or define stuttering?
- 5- What do think is the cause behind stuttering?
- 6- What kind of psychological issues the student with a stutter may develop because of his or her?
- 7- What kind of negative experiences do you think affect stutterers in the long term?
- 8- How does stuttering affect the intelligence of the learner?
- 9- How does stuttering affect the academic progress of the learner?

Questions related to stuttering in the classroom: based on the experiences that your child have been through, how do think teachers should react in the following cases

- 1- In the classroom, should the teacher avoid the participation of learners with a stutter?
- 2- What can the teacher do if the students who stutter do not participate in the classroom?
- 3- What techniques should the teacher adopt to make the student who stutters comfortable and less stressed while speaking?

4- How should the teacher react when facing some of the following imaginary situations with students who stutter:

- The teacher feels in a rush to finish the lecture and a student with stutter wants to participate in the lecture.
- Peers repeated the student's stutter.
- The teacher arranges for group work that is based on speaking and s/he saw the student is not comfortable with giving his opinion in the group because of his stutter.
- There was supposed to be a read-out-loud activity, should the teacher give the choice for the student to participate or ask him to read anyway.
- Their Peers started to make comments on their stutter.
- The student asks for advice on how to manage his or her stutter.
- The student is having difficulty to utter a word; should the teacher say it for them?

5- What kind of attitudes do think the stutterer considers as stigmatization?

6- How should the teacher react if the student who stutters is being stigmatised?

7- Do teachers arrange lectures addressed to all student to raise awareness about speech disorders and stuttering? If not, would you recommend that?

8- What do think about the following suggestions:

- The teacher should speak to students about their stutter.
- The teacher should speak with their parents about their child's stutter.
- Teachers and parents should work cooperatively with speech-language therapists.

12.7. The Teacher's semi-structured interviews

Date: _____

Number of years Teaching Experience: _____

Language: _____

Age: _____

Gender: _____

General questions:

- 1- Could you please tell me about the teacher's training you received?
- 3- What do you know about inclusive education?
- 4- What kind of training you received regarding inclusive education?
- 5- In addition to the training, have you done any research about teaching learners with disabilities?
- 6- What are the disabilities that you focus on in your teachers' training?
- 7- What kind of research have you done to learn about communication disorders?
- 8- What are the most common speech disorders to the best of your knowledge?

Questions related to the topic:

- 1- Do you know someone with a stutter or any type of speech disorder?
- 2- Have you taught anyone with a stutter?
- 3- How would you describe or define stuttering?
- 4- What do think is the cause behind stuttering?
- 5- What kind of psychological issues the student with a stutter may develop because of his or her?
- 6- What kind of negative experiences do you think affect stutterers in the long term?
- 7- How does stuttering affect the intelligence of the learner?
- 8- How does stuttering affect the academic progress of the learner?

Questions related to stuttering in the classroom:

- 1- In the classroom, do you avoid the participation of learners with a stutter?
- 2- What can you do if the students who stutter do not participate in the classroom?
- 3- What techniques do you think you should adopt to make the student who stutters comfortable and less stressed while speaking?
- 4- How would you react if you face some of these imaginary situations with students who stutter:

- You feel in a rush to finish the lecture and a student with stutter wants to participate in the lecture.
- Peers repeated the student's stutter.
- You arrange for group work that is based on speaking and you saw the student is not comfortable with giving his opinion in the group because of his stutter.
- There was supposed to be a read-out-loud activity, would you give the choice for the student to participate or ask him to read anyway.
- Their Peers started to make comments on their stutter.
- The student asks for advice on how to manage the stutter, what would you advise?
- The student is having difficulty to utter a word; would you say it for them?

5- What kind of attitudes do think the stutterer considers as stigmatization?

6- How would you react if your student who stutters is being stigmatised?

7- Do you arrange lectures addressed to the student to raise awareness about speech disorders and stuttering? If not, would you recommend that?

8- What do think about the following suggestions:

- The teacher should speak to students about their stutter.
- The teacher should speak with their parents about their stutter.
- Teachers and parents should work cooperatively with speech-language therapists.

12.8. Semi-structured interview schedule of parents of children who stutter translated in Arabic

مقابلة الأولياء

قبل بداية المقابلة:

- سوف أبلغ من المشاركين أنني أرغب في إجراء مقابلات معهم لأنهم مختصين في علاج النطق و اللغة في الجزائر.
- سوف أذكرهم أيضًا أن هذه المقابلة تهدف إلى فهم تصورات الأولياء و المختصين ومواقفهم تجاه الأطفال الذين يتلعثمون في المدارس المتوسطة في الجزائر.
- سأشرح أهمية وجهة نظر المشاركين فيما يتعلق بتعليم الأطفال الذين يتلعثمون.
- سأخبر المشاركين في هذه الدراسة أنني سأقوم بتسجيل هذه المقابلة وتدوينها؛ و ستكون لديهم الفرصة لمراجعة المقابلات المدونة إذا رغبوا في ذلك.
- سأخبرهم أيضا أنني سوف أقوم بتدوين بعض الملاحظات أثناء المقابلة وأن لديهم الحق في إيقاف التسجيل في أي وقت يشاءون.
- سأؤكد لهم أيضًا أن البيانات ستكون سرية وأن الباحث الرئيسي، والمشرّف فقط إذا لزم الأمر، سيكون لهما حق بالاطلاع على الملفات الصوتية.

ستستغرق هذه المقابلة 40 إلى 60 دقيقة. ستساهم مشاركتك في تحقيق أهداف هذه الدراسة. و التي تتعلق مجال التعليم وخاصة تعليم التلاميذ الذين يعانون من اضطرابات النطق في الجزائر. قد لا يكون هناك أي فوائد شخصية؛ ومع ذلك، فمساعديك في فهم تصورات المعلمين ومواقفهم تجاه التلاميذ الذين يعانون من التأثأة قد تساهم في تحسين التجارب المدرسية للتلاميذ الذين يعانون من التأثأة وذلك بتسليط الضوء على أي تصورات ومواقف خاطئة يجب على المتخصصين إصلاحها.

أسئلة عامة:

1- من فضلك، هل يمكنك أن تحدثني عن طفلك.

أ- عمره

ب- المستوى الدراسي

ج- معرفته بتلعثمه

2- هل قمت بأي أبحاث شخصية عن التلعثم أو اضطراب الكلام بشكل عام؟

أ- هل تعتقد أنه من الضروري إجراء بعض الأبحاث حول التلعثم لمساعدة طفلك؟

ب- ما نوع الأبحاث التي تعتقد أنها مفيدة لطفلك المصاب بالتلعثم؟

ج- هل تعتقد أن الأبحاث التي تتعلق بالمشاكل النفسية التي يسببها التلعثم ستكون مفيدة لك كوالد؟

3-ماذا تعرف عن التعليم الجامع؟

أ- هل تعتقد أن التلعثم إعاقة؟

ب- هل تتصح بتدريب المعلمين على تطوير مهارة المعلمين في تدريس الطلاب الذين يعانون من اضطرابات النطق؟

4-ما هي أكثر اضطرابات النطق شيوعًا على حد علمك؟

5-هل قام طفلك بأي أبحاث حول التلعثم؟

6-هل تعتقد أن طفلك يجب أن يقوم بالقراءة حول التلعثم؟

7-هل يتلقى طفلك أي دعم إضافي من معالج لغة؟

8-كيف تصف شدة تلعثم طفلك؟

أسئلة متعلقة بالموضوع:

1-كيف تصف أو تعرف التلعثم أو التأتأة؟

أ- هل تعرف شخصًا يعاني من تلعثم أو أي نوع آخر من اضطرابات النطق؟

ب- هل تعرف أي أحد يعاني من التأتأة؟

ج- ما أهم أعراض التأتأة؟

د- حسب علمك هل تعتقد أن هناك علاجًا للتأتأة؟

2-على حد علمك، ما هي الأسباب الرئيسية للتأتأة؟

أ- هل يمكنك تبرير إجابتك من فضلك؟

ب- هل تعتبر التأتأة مشكلة نفسية أم اضطراب على مستوى الدماغ؟

ج- هل سمعت من قبل عن حالات يكون فيها اضطراب الكلام أو التأتأة حالة وراثية؟

3-ما نوع المشكلات النفسية التي قد يصاب بها الأطفال بسبب التأتأة؟

أ- ما نوع التجارب السلبية التي قد تؤثر على المتلعثمين على المدى الطويل؟

ب- على حد علمك، ما هي السلوكيات التي يمكن أن تجعل الطفل الذي يتلعثم قلقاً أو محبطاً أو خجولاً؟

ج- ما هي الاستراتيجيات التي يجب على الأساتذة استخدامها لتجنب هذه السلوكيات؟

4-كيف يؤثر التلعثم على ذكاء المتعلم؟

5-كيف يؤثر التلعثم على التقدم الأكاديمي للتلميذ؟

أسئلة متعلقة بالتأتأة أثناء الدرس: بصفتك معالجًا للنطق واللغة، ما هي الطريقة الأنسب التي يجب على الأساتذة

التعامل بها في الحالات التالية:

1-أثناء الحصة هل ترى أن على الأستاذ تجنب مشاركات الأطفال الذين يعانون من التأتأة؟

2-ماذا يمكن للأستاذ أن يفعل إذا كان الأطفال الذين يعانون من التأتأة لا يشاركون أثناء الحصة؟

3-ما هي الأساليب التي تعتقد أنه يجب على الأساتذة اتباعها لجعل الأطفال الذين يعانون من التأتأة مرتاحين وأقل

توتراً أثناء التحدث؟

4- لتجنب السلوكيات المشينة، كيف يتصرف الاساتذة إذا واجهوا بعض من المواقف التالية مع الأطفال الذين يعانون من التأتأة

• يكون الأستاذ على عجلة من امره لإنهاء الدرس، و يريد تلميذ يعاني من التأتأة المشاركة في الفصل.

• كرر اقران تلميذ يعاني من التأتأة طريقة حديثه.

• لاحظ الأستاذ أن التلميذ الذي يعاني من التأتأة غير مرتاح في إبداء رأيه خلال عمل جماعي يتطلب الكلام.

• أثناء نشاط القراءة بصوت عالٍ، لا يرغب التلميذ الذي يعاني من التأتأة في القراءة.

• بدأ أقران التلاميذ الذين يعانون من التأتأة بالتعليق على تلغتهم.

• يطلب التلميذ النصيحة حول كيفية يتحكم في تلغته.

• تصعب على التلميذ الذي يعاني من التأتأة النطق بكلمة.

5- ما هي المواقف التي يعتبرها المتعلم سلوكيات المشينة ؟

6- كيف يكون رد فعل الاستاذ إذا تعرض الطفل الذي يعاني من التأتأة إلى سلوك مشين ؟

7- هل تنظمون محاضرات موجهة للتلاميذ للتوعية حول اضطرابات النطق والتأتأة؟ هل تنصح بذلك؟

8- ما رأيك في الاقتراحات التالية:

• يجب على الأستاذ التحدث مع التلميذ حول تلغتهم.

• يجب على الأستاذ أن يتحدث مع الاولياء حول تلغتهم أطفالهم.

• يجب على الأستاذة وأولياء الأمور العمل بشكل تعاوني مع مختصين في علاج النطق واللغة.

12.9. Research Informed Consent Form

Title of Project: **Middle school teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards learners with speech disorders in Algeria: A case study of stuttering**

Ethics Approval Number: -

Investigators names: Meriem Bennedjadi

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

This is a consent form for a PhD research project Titled: Secondary school teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards learners with speech disorders in Algeria: A case study of stuttering. It is a research project at the University of the West of Scotland carried out by the principle PHD student (Meriem Bennedjadi). By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and photovoice instruction sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after completing the study without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (<i>age, sex, and contact details</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to have my voice/likeness digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

12.10. Research Informed Consent Form Translated in Arabic

استمارة الموافقة على المشاركة في البحث

عنوان البحث: "تصورات و مواقف الاولياء و المختصين تجاه التلاميذ الذين يعانون من اضطراب النطق في المدارس المتوسطة بالجزائر: دراسة حالة للتأثأة "

رقم الموافقة الأخلاقية: :

اسم الباحث: مريم بن نجادي

البريد الإلكتروني للباحث: [REDACTED]

هذه الاستمارة تمثل طلب خطي للموافقة على المشاركة في بحث الدكتوراه بعنوان "تصورات و مواقف الاولياء و المختصين تجاه التلاميذ الذين يعانون من اضطراب النطق في المدارس المتوسطة بالجزائر: دراسة حالة للتأثأة ". هذا البحث من اعداد طالبة الدكتوراه مريم بن نجادي من جامعة الغرب الاسكتلندي. من خلال ملأ هذه الاستمارة فانك تأكد على موافقتك التامة بالمشاركة في هذا البحث. كما تؤكد أنك قرأت و فهمت ورقة معلومات المشارك و ما هو مطلوب منك في هذه الدراسة.

يُرجى قراءة البيانات التالية ، وفي حالة موافقتك ، قم بوضع العلامة ✓ في المربع المقابل لتأكيد موافقتك:

أؤكد أنني قد قرأت وفهمت ورقة معلومات المشارك وورقة التعليمات الخاصة بالدراسة. و قد أتيت لي الفرصة للنظر في المعلومات وطرح الأسئلة ووصلت على أجاب مقلعة على هذه الأسئلة.	
أفهم أن مشاركتي طوعية وأنني حر في الانسحاب في أي وقت لمدة تصل إلى شهر واحد بعد إكمال الدراسة دون إبداء أي سبب.	
أفهم أن المعلومات التي أقدمها سرية وأن أي منشور ناتج عن هذا العمل لن يحددني شخصياً.	
أوافق على معالجة معلوماتي الشخصية (العمر والجنس وبيانات الاتصال) للأغراض الموضحة لي. أفهم أنه سيتم التعامل مع هذه المعلومات وفقاً لجميع تشريعات حماية البيانات المعمول بها.	
أوافق على تسجيل صوتي / تشابهي رقمياً.	
أوافق بحرية على المشاركة في هذه الدراسة.	

التوقيعات:

اسم و لقب المشارك:

التاريخ:

التوقيع:

اسم و لقب الباحث:

: التاريخ:

التوقيع:

School of education and social sciences

Participant Information Sheet

“Middle school teachers’ perceptions and attitudes towards learners with speech disorders in Algeria: A case study of stuttering”

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Ask questions if anything you read is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The main purpose of this study is to investigate teachers’ perceptions and attitudes in Algeria towards learners who stutter. This study also aims to compare these perceptions and knowledge about stuttering held by teachers, language speech therapists, and parents of children who stutter.

Why have I been chosen?

The sample of the study requires the participant to be a middle school language teacher, a speech-language pathologist or a parent of a child who stutters in Algeria. Therefore, you were selected to participate in the study to share your knowledge and perception, and experience regarding the topic. The teachers will help to provide information about their knowledge and perception regarding stuttering and teaching children with a stutter. The speech-language therapists will help to provide knowledge about stuttering and teaching children with a stutter since they are specialised in the field. The parents will help provide us with knowledge about stuttering the experiences of their children who stutter in schools.

Do I have to take part?

No, your participation in this study is voluntary. You have the right to accept or refuse to take part in the study. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. You can withdraw your participation at any time, even after finishing the interview. Your withdrawal does not need to be justified. During the interview, you will have time to ask questions and resolve any issues. Finally, if these issues affect your emotional health or cause any mental or physical harm, you will be asked to withdraw at any time during the interview.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to participate, you will be asked to answer the questions in the online interview, which will take 40 to 60 minutes via zoom. Your participation will be strictly confidential and no one can access the data you will share except for the principal research and the supervisor if necessary. The

data that will be used in the study will be anonymous and all the information that leads to your identifications will be deleted. Your participation will help gain knowledge about the topic and reach the research objectives mentioned above.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There will be no obvious disadvantages and risks of taking part in this study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Your participation will help to achieve the objective of the current study. It will contribute to the field of education and especially teaching learners with speech disorders in Algeria. There might not be any personal benefits; however, you might help understand the teachers' perception and attitudes towards learners with a stutter. Eventually, this could improve the school experiences of learners who stutter and highlight any wrong perceptions and attitudes to be fixed by the teachers.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. Alternatively, we will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide by the first week of the study and all data will be anonymised when analysed. If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The physical, social and psychological well-being of research subjects and researchers will be protected at all stages of the research process. If you agree to participate in this project, once the data will be collected, it will be analysed and written as a UWS PhD thesis. The researcher will Share research findings with the participants at the end of a study which will proves feedback to participants on the outcome of the research to which they have contributed. Furthermore, the thesis version will be published online to facilitate its use for future research. All data will remain anonymous

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Name: Meriem Bennedjadi

University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
PA1 2BE
UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Name: Christopher Holligan

University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
PA1 2BE
UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

كلية التربية والعلوم الاجتماعية

وثيقة معلومات المشارك

عنوان البحث: "تصورات و مواقف الاولياء و المختصين تجاه التلاميذ الذين يعانون من اضطراب النطق في المدارس المتوسطة بالجزائر: دراسة حالة للتأتأة "

يسعدني دعوتكم للمشاركة في هذه الدراسة . قبل ان تقرر ما ان كنت ستوافق على المشاركة في هذا البحث من الضروري ان تفهم الهدف من اجراء هذا البحث و ما سيتضمنه. يرجى أخذ الوقت الكافي لقراءة المعلومات التالية بعناية. يمكنك طرح اي أسؤال في حال ما إذا كان هناك اي غموض حول البحث أو إذا كنت ترغب في مزيد من المعلومات. يمكنك اخذ وقت الكافي لتقرر ما إذا كنت ستشارك أم لا.

ما هو الهدف من هذه الدراسة؟

الهدف الرئيسي من هذه الدراسة هو التحقيق في تصورات و موقف الاولياء و المختصين تجاه الاطفال الذين يعانون من مشاكل في النطق في المدارس المتوسطة في الجزائر، و بالالخص الاطفال الذين يعانون من التأتأة. بالإضافة الى ذلك، تهدف هذه الدراسة أيضًا إلى مقارنة هذه التصورات و المعرفة حول التأتأة لدى كل من الأساتذة، أخصائي علم أمراض النطق واللغة و كذا أولياء أمور الأطفال الذين يتلعثمون.

لماذا تم اختياري للمشاركة في هذه الدراسة؟

لقد تم اختيارك للمشاركة في هذه الدراسة لأنك والد لطفل يعاني من التأتأة. قد تساعد في تزويد الباحث بالمعرفة حول التلعثم وتجربة طفلك في المدارس.

هل يجب علي المشاركة؟

لا ، مشاركتك في هذه الدراسة طوعية. لديك الحق في القبول أو الرفض على المشاركة في الدراسة. إذا قررت المشاركة ، فسيتم إعطاؤك وثيقة المعلومات هذه للاحتفاظ بها وسيطلب منك التوقيع على وثيقة الموافقة على المشاركة في الدراسة. يمكنك سحب مشاركتك في أي وقت ، حتى بعد الانتهاء من المقابلة. لا يحتاج انسحابك إلى تبرير. أثناء المقابلة ، سيكون لديك الوقت لطرح الأسئلة وحل أي مشكل. يمكنك الانسحاب في أي وقت أثناء المقابلة في حال ما اذا كنت غير مرتاح لانهاء هذه المقابلة.

ماذا سيحدث لي إذا شاركت؟

إذا قررت المشاركة ، فسيطلب منك الإجابة على أسئلة المقابلة. ستستغرق المقابلة 40 إلى 60 دقيقة. ستكون مقابلة وجهًا لوجه يتم إجراؤها في مكان هادئ وآمن يناسبك أنت والباحث ، أو ستكون مقابلة عبر الإنترنت، عبر تطبيق "زوم" على سبيل المثال. بعد إذن منك ، سيتم ترتيب الاجتماع. ستكون مشاركتك سرية تمامًا ولن يتمكن أي شخص من الوصول إلى البيانات التي ستشاركها باستثناء

الباحث الرئيسي والمشرف إذا لزم الأمر. ستكون البيانات التي سيتم استخدامها في الدراسة مجهولة المصدر وسيتم حذف جميع المعلومات التي تؤدي إلى هويتك. ستساعد مشاركتك في اكتساب المعرفة حول الموضوع والوصول إلى أهداف البحث المذكورة أعلاه.

ما هي العيوب والمخاطر المحتملة للمشاركة؟

لن تكون هناك عيوب ومخاطر بمشاركة في هذه الدراسة.

ما هي فوائد ممكنة من المشاركة؟

ستساهم مشاركتك في تحقيق أهداف هذه الدراسة. و التي تتعلق مجال التعليم وخاصة تعليم التلاميذ الذين يعانون من اضطرابات النطق في الجزائر. قد لا يكون هناك أي فوائد شخصية؛ ومع ذلك، فمساعدة في فهم تصورات المعلمين ومواقفهم تجاه التلاميذ الذين يعانون من التأخر قد تساهم في تحسين التجارب المدرسية للتلاميذ الذين يعانون من التأخر وذلك بتسليط الضوء على أي تصورات ومواقف خاطئة يجب على المتخصصين إصلاحها.

إشعار حول خصوصية البيانات وحمايتها

ستكون جامعة غرب اسكتلندا (UWS) متحكمة في بيانات هذا المشروع. يوفر مكتب حماية البيانات في UWS الإشراف على أنشطة الجامعة التي تتضمن معالجة البيانات الشخصية ويمكن الاتصال بهم على dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. مسؤولة حماية البيانات في الجامعة هي "إيما كوكرو" ويمكن الاتصال بها على dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. ستتم معالجة بياناتك الشخصية إذا كانت مطلوبة لمشروع البحث. إذا تمكنا من إخفاء الهوية أو إخفاء اسم مستعار للبيانات الشخصية التي تقدمها ، فسنعوم بذلك ، وسنسعى لتقليل معالجة البيانات الشخصية قدر الإمكان. سنقوم إخفاء البيانات الشخصية التي تقدمها بحلول الأسبوع الأول من الدراسة وسيتم إخفاء هوية جميع البيانات عند تحليلها. إذا كنت قلقاً بشأن كيفية معالجة بياناتك الشخصية ، فيرجى الاتصال بـ UWS في المقام الأول على dataprotection@uws.ac.uk إذا كنت لا تزال غير راضٍ ، فقد ترغب في الاتصال بمكتب مفوض المعلومات (ICO). تتوفر تفاصيل الاتصال وتفاصيل حقوق موضوع البيانات على موقع ICO الإلكتروني على:

<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights>

ماذا سيحدث لنتائج الدراسة البحثية؟

ستتم حماية الأشخاص الخاضعين للبحث والباحثين في جميع مراحل عملية البحث. إذا وافقت على المشاركة في هذا المشروع ، فبمجرد جمع البيانات ، سيتم تحليلها وكتابتها كأطروحة دكتوراه في جامعة الغرب الاسكتلندي (UWS) . سيقوم الباحث بمشاركة نتائج البحث مع المشاركين في نهاية الدراسة والتي ستساعد المشاركين في مراجعة نتائج البحث الذي ساهموا فيه. علاوة على ذلك، سيتم نشر نسخة الأطروحة عبر الإنترنت لتسهيل استخدامها في الأبحاث المستقبلية. ستبقى جميع بيانات المشاركين مجهولة.

من قيم هذه الدراسة؟

لجنة الأخلاق ESS

للحصول على مزيد من المعلومات يرجى الاتصال بـ:

الباحث الرئيسي:

الاسم و اللقب: مريم بن نجادي

جامعة الغرب الاسكتلندي

شارع رئيسي (هاي ستريت)،

بيزلي،

المملكة المتحدة

الهاتف

البريد الإلكتروني

مشرف البحث:

الاسم و اللقب: كريستوفر هوليجان

جامعة الغرب الاسكتلندي

شارع رئيسي (هاي ستريت)،

بيزلي،

المملكة المتحدة

هاتف:

شكرا على مشاركتك في هذه الدراسة.